

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education and training

D2.2 - PM training toolkit

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Author name(s):	Georgios Ntanis (UPRC), Maria Boile (UPRC), Vassilis Tsoulis (YET), Nasos Panagiotidis (YET), Attila Akac (CERTH), Afroditi Anagnostopoulou (CERTH), Ioanna Pappa (CERTH), Xenofon Kitsios (CERTH), Michael Mathioulakis (CERTH), Vassilis Kappatos (CERTH), Emilia Binchiciu (HELIX), Gabriela-Victoria Mnerie (ISIM), Emilia Dobrin (ISIM), Rosina Preis (EITM), Nemanja Zdravković (MUB), Emilija Kisić (MUB), Miroslava Raspopović Milić (MUB), Karolina Bielak (LCC), Daria Zawalska (LCC), Marta Walczak (LCC), Erica Vannucci (DB), Ioannis Ergas (WEG), Zoe Agiasophiti (WEG), Rea Levantnou (ACC), Pantelis Velanas (ACC), Aris Zompras (ACC), Ioanna Matouli (ATC)
Reviewer(s):	Adrian Solomon (HELIX), Daria Zawalska (LCC), Aleksandra Wiaderkiewicz (LCC)
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PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

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BOOKLET

Module WN1: Holistic PM competences

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A. Introduction

a. Abstract

Maintenance of machinery systems, electrical devices and equipment, in general, is playing a key role in minimization of operational expenses (OPEX) and keeping smooth and safe operations for many industrial companies. Many of them are seeking ways to improve their maintenance methodologies in order to achieve cost minimization, avoid unexpected losses, increase systems reliability and achieve multi-objective optimization (Ran et al., 2019). Currently, most companies are following more traditional ways of maintenance. These incorporate a range of reactive and proactive methodologies, which in essence, rely on either prevention via a periodic time-based schedule or merely addressing issues and faults whenever they arise. Following the times, with the advent of smart manufacturing and the development of cutting-edge technologies such as Edge and Cloud Computing, Internet of Things and Artificial Intelligence, an advanced form of maintenance has been made possible. Predictive Maintenance (PDM) is a novel way to record the condition of machines and, subsequently, to use additional data in order to make predictions for maintenance.

On top of this, the synergy among Reporting Models, Structural Assessment Methods, Forecasting Systems, and Remote Infrastructure Management (RIM) forms a robust framework essential for predictive maintenance strategies. Reporting Models encapsulate the methodologies for data-driven insights, offering descriptive, diagnostic, predictive, and prescriptive reporting. These models aid in understanding equipment performance, failure patterns, and KPI-based evaluations, thereby influencing informed decision-making. Structural Assessment Methods encompass various techniques, including non-destructive testing, vibration analysis, and finite element analysis, to proactively evaluate structural integrity. This allows for early defect detection, predictive analysis, and real-time structural health monitoring, ensuring the safety and reliability of infrastructure. Forecasting Systems, leveraging predictive analytics and data-driven insights, predict maintenance needs, enabling proactive planning and resource allocation. Integrating these components within Remote Infrastructure Management optimizes predictive maintenance, providing a comprehensive approach towards anticipating, diagnosing, and mitigating risks while ensuring continuous improvement in infrastructure reliability and operational efficiency.

b. Summary/Introduction to Holistic Predictive Maintenance

The WN1 Module will cover the subject of Holistic PDM competences, which will be divided in seven sectors, each dedicated to a particular aspect of Predictive Maintenance, thus providing a multi-faceted foundation view of the topic.

The present Module (Holistic PDM competences) is referred to students, VET apprentices and PDM workforce which are interested in expanding their knowledge on Predictive Maintenance. This Module offers a basic and integrated outline of the main aspects of PDM. A more theoretical background is provided by the first Chapters of this booklet, which are referred to Maintenance Methodologies, Sensor Technologies and Time Management Systems. In addition, a more technical knowledge is gained by the other sections, which are referred to Reporting Models, Structural Assessment Methods, Forecasting Systems, and Remote Infrastructure Management (RIM). These items comprise a multi-faceted framework fundamental to the success of predictive maintenance strategies in various industries.

1. Chapter B provides a general description of Maintenance Methodologies comparing PDM with some traditional and commonly used ways. Some assets from traditional maintenance methodologies are used in PDM, too. Conventional ways that will be presented in this section are: Run-to-Failure Management (Reactive Maintenance), Preventive Maintenance, Total Productive Maintenance, Reliability – Centered Maintenance (Mobley, 2002). In this section, a more detailed description of Predictive Maintenance is made, in order to further understand its notion.

Chapter C is focused to provide adequate knowledge for sensing technologies and their importance in PDM. Sensors are necessary for data acquisition and their role is to transmit them accurately to a data-processing unit (Ran et al., 2019). Furthermore, in combination with a data analysis process, which is also based on historical data, a representative simulation model can be generated. Data analysis relies on both statistical methods and physics-based models, such as Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) or Fine Element Method (FEM) or Thermodynamics. Different types of sensing technologies are described in this section based on different principals and the variety of their applications.

Chapter D provides a brief description of the Time Management System. A necessary factor for time management is the calculation of Remaining Useful Life (RUL) of the equipment/system. This is also calculated based on the available data, both historical data and data received from Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM) and a theoretical background, which varies according to each application (Ran et al., 2019). RUL is an essential calculation because it affects the decision-make process in the PDM.

Chapter E is linked with Reporting Models, which serve as the linchpin, displaying a range of reporting approaches —descriptive, diagnostic, predictive, and prescriptive—, while utilizing historical and real-time data to derive actionable insights and guide strategic decision-making. These models play a pivotal role in

summarizing equipment performance, failure patterns, and key performance indicators (KPIs), allowing for comprehensive evaluations of maintenance effectiveness.

Chapter F provides a general description of Structural Assessment Methods, which encompass an array of techniques, including non-destructive testing, vibration analysis, finite element analysis, and visual inspections. These methods enable proactive evaluations of structural health and integrity, facilitating early defect detection, assessing risks, and ensuring structural reliability. By leveraging these methods, industries can anticipate and address potential vulnerabilities in infrastructure, ensuring safety and minimizing downtime.

Forecasting Systems are presented in Chapter G. They are powered by predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms and play a crucial role in Predicting Maintenance needs and foreseeing potential equipment failures. These systems enable proactive planning and resource allocation, optimizing maintenance schedules and resource utilization. With the ability to forecast trends and predict potential issues, organizations can implement preventive measures, thus reducing operational disruptions and maintenance costs.

Remote Infrastructure Management acts as the integrative force, harmonizing Reporting Models, Structural Assessment Methods and Forecasting Systems into a unified approach. RIM facilitates real-time monitoring, data-driven decision-making, and the seamless coordination of maintenance activities. By integrating these components, RIM ensures optimized infrastructure health, predictive maintenance excellence, and continuous improvements in reliability and operational efficiency. An approach of RIM is described in Chapter H, which is the last one of the Module.

This comprehensive approach, amalgamating diverse methodologies and systems, empowers industries to anticipate, diagnose, and mitigate risks effectively. By prioritizing predictive maintenance strategies facilitated by these integrated frameworks, industries can enhance infrastructure reliability, ensure safety, minimize unplanned downtime, and drive operational efficiencies, thus achieving sustainable and optimized asset performance.

Defining Predictive Maintenance in the Context of Holistic Project Management

Predictive Maintenance (PM) stands as a strategic approach aiming to predict equipment failures before they occur, leveraging data analytics, machine learning, and sensor technologies. In the realm of holistic project management, PM extends beyond mere reactive and preventive maintenance, focusing on proactive measures driven by data insights to optimize asset performance and minimize downtime.

At its core, PM harnesses historical and real-time data collected through various sensor technologies to forecast potential breakdowns or failures in machinery or infrastructure. This anticipatory approach empowers project managers to schedule maintenance activities efficiently, preventing unexpected disruptions and fostering smoother project execution.

Importance and Benefits of Incorporating Predictive Maintenance Competences in Projects

Integrating predictive maintenance competences within project management practices yields multifaceted advantages. Firstly, it augments operational efficiency by allowing for predictive analysis of equipment health, reducing unplanned downtime and associated costs. Moreover, by identifying potential issues in advance, PM facilitates a proactive rather than reactive response, ensuring optimal utilization of resources and manpower.

The proactive nature of PM also enhances safety measures within projects, mitigating risks associated with unexpected equipment failures, thereby safeguarding both assets and personnel. Additionally, predictive maintenance empowers informed decision-making by providing insights into asset performance trends and guiding strategic planning for maintenance schedules and resource allocation.

Predictive Maintenance not only anticipates equipment failures but also optimizes maintenance schedules. By analysing historical data and performance patterns, PM allows for the precise timing of maintenance activities, ensuring that resources are utilized efficiently without causing unnecessary downtime. This approach minimizes disruptions to project timelines and production schedules, maximizing operational output.

Incorporating Predictive Maintenance competences translates into significant cost savings. By identifying potential issues early on, organizations can perform targeted maintenance, replacing or repairing specific components before they fail catastrophically. This prevents costly emergency repairs and reduces the need for replacing entire equipment units, resulting in substantial savings in both maintenance and operational costs.

The reliance on data-driven insights in Predictive Maintenance empowers project managers to make informed decisions. Data collected from sensors and analytical tools provide valuable information about equipment health, enabling accurate forecasting and planning. This not only streamlines maintenance but also aids in strategic decision-making regarding resource allocation and budgeting within projects.

By reducing unexpected downtimes and equipment failures, Predictive Maintenance contributes to enhanced employee productivity. Workers can focus

on their tasks without interruptions, fostering a more efficient working environment. Moreover, by identifying potential safety hazards in advance, PM plays a crucial role in preventing accidents and ensuring a safe working environment for project teams.

Predictive Maintenance extends the lifespan of assets by enabling proactive upkeep. Regular monitoring and timely intervention based on data-driven insights help in preserving the longevity and reliability of equipment. This, in turn, maximizes the return on investment for assets, reducing the frequency of premature replacements and contributing to sustainable resource management.

B. Maintenance Methodologies

Maintenance is crucial for several reasons, and its importance extends across various industries. Maintenance has always been a severe cost driver in the production industry. Studies show that depending on the industry between 15 and 70 percent of total production costs originate from maintenance activities. Maintenance ensures that equipment will operate reliably, and a proper maintenance contributes to a safe working environment. Well-maintained equipment is less likely to malfunction, reducing the risk of accidents and injuries in the workplace. Regular maintenance helps equipment perform at its best and it can lead to significant cost savings by avoiding unplanned downtime and minimising repair costs. In addition, Proper maintenance can extend the lifespan of equipment. Many industries, like shipping (Mobley, 2002) are subject to regulations and standards regarding equipment maintenance, particularly in sectors with safety or environmental considerations. Regular maintenance ensures compliance with these regulations, avoiding legal issues and potential fines. Therefore, maintenance is essential for ensuring the reliability, safety, efficiency, and longevity of equipment and systems. It is a proactive investment that not only prevents costly breakdowns but also contributes to overall operational excellence and a positive organisational reputation (Perera, 2017; Krupitzer et al., 2020).

Therefore, various maintenance approaches have been developed/observed through the years. According to literature, the different maintenance methodologies are divided into two main categories: corrective maintenance, which is performed after a fault has been detected and preventive maintenance, which is performed before a fault is detected in order to avoid it. Each of these two categories will be discussed in more detail below.

The scope of this section is to provide a brief description of applied maintenance methodologies in the industry. In addition, a short comparison between Reactive, Preventive and Predictive Maintenance is made.

a. Reactive Maintenance

Corrective or Run-to-Failure or Reactive Maintenance (hereinafter referred to as Reactive Maintenance or RM) follows an easy-to-understand logic: When a machine breaks down, fix it (You et al., 2010). This approach to plant maintenance has been a major aspect of plant management since the first manufacturing plant was constructed, which appears fair on the surface. A facility that employs Reactive management does not spend money on maintenance until an equipment or system fails to operate.

Reactive management style waits for machine or equipment failure before taking any maintenance action; yet, however, it is a "no-maintenance" management approach. It is also the most expensive approach to managing maintenance. Few plants practise true Reactive management. Even in a Reactive scenario, factories virtually always undertake fundamental preventative actions (such as lubrication, machine adjustments, and other adjustments). Machines and other plant equipment, on the other hand, are not rebuilt, nor are major repairs undertaken until the equipment fails to function. High spare parts inventory costs, high overtime labour costs, high machine downtime, and low production availability are the principal charges associated with this form of maintenance management.

Because no attempt is made to anticipate maintenance requirements, a plant that applies true reactive management must be able to respond to all potential plant problems. This reactive management style requires the maintenance department to keep vast spare parts inventories, which include spare machines or, at the very least, all significant components for every important equipment in the plant. The alternative is to rely on equipment vendors that can deliver all essential spare parts immediately.

Even if the latter alternative is feasible, apart from the downtime necessary to fix machine breakdowns, the costs of repair parts are significantly increased by premiums for faster delivery. To reduce the impact of unexpected machine failures on production, maintenance workers must also be able to respond to any machine malfunctions immediately. The net outcome of this reactive maintenance management is higher maintenance costs and lower process machinery availability. According to maintenance cost analysis, a repair conducted in the reactive or run-to-failure style will cost approximately three times as much as the identical repair performed in the scheduled or preventative method (will be discussed later). Repair time and labour expenses are reduced when the repair is scheduled. It also mitigates the negative consequences of hastened shipping and lost output.

b. Preventive Maintenance

Preventive Maintenance (PM), often known as planned maintenance, is the scheduling of routine maintenance procedures on specific equipment to reduce the probability of failure. The maintenance is performed even when the equipment is still operational and in normal operation to avoid unexpected malfunctions and the associated downtime and expenses (Deloitte, 2017).

Almost all Preventive Maintenance management programs are time-bound. In other words, maintenance operations are time-based. It is assumed that the failure behaviour (characteristic) of the equipment is predictable, which is known as

bathtub curves (will be described in Section 3 “Time Management System”). The bathtub curve characterises the operational life of a component into three phases: break-in period (first weeks), normal life span, wear-out period (close to its deterioration). The general process of Preventive Maintenance can be divided into two steps:

1) The first step is to statistically evaluate the failure characteristics of the equipment using the time series data set that has been gathered.

2) In the following step, the best maintenance practices are determined to improve system reliability, availability, and safety while keeping maintenance costs low (Ran et al., 2019).

While Preventive Maintenance can decrease repair costs and unscheduled downtime, it may also lead to unneeded repairs and still not prevent catastrophic failure. In order to determine when a piece of equipment will enter its wear out phase, the theoretical rate of failure is used, rather than real statistics on the equipment's state. This frequently results in costly and entirely unnecessary maintenance being performed before there is an issue or after a possibly catastrophic damage has occurred. This will also result in far more planned downtime and complicated inventory management. If the equipment fails before the expected "wear out" period, it must be fixed using RM approaches. Reactive repairs are often three times more expensive than scheduled ones, according to another study.

c. [Predictive Maintenance](#)

Predictive maintenance (PDM), also known as condition-based maintenance (CBM), being performed before a fault is detected, can be placed in the second category of methodologies together with Preventive maintenance. Predictive maintenance involves monitoring the vibration of spinning machinery to identify potential problems and prevent catastrophic failures. There is a misconception many believe, that PDM is monitoring the infrared image of electrical switchgear, motors, and other electrical equipment, in order to detect emerging problems, which is actually not the case. Predictive maintenance involves regularly monitoring machine-trains and process systems to ensure maximum intervals between repairs and minimise unscheduled outages caused by failures. However, predictive maintenance encompasses far more than that. It is a method of increasing productivity, product quality, and the overall efficacy of manufacturing and production facilities (Ran et al., 2019).

Predictive maintenance optimises plant operations by utilising current equipment and system conditions. A predictive maintenance management program uses cost-effective tools (e.g., vibration monitoring, thermography, tribology) to monitor critical plant systems and schedule maintenance activities accordingly. Including

predictive maintenance in a comprehensive maintenance management program improves the availability of process gear, while significantly lowering maintenance costs. It enhances product quality, productivity, and profitability at manufacturing and production facilities (You et al., 2010).

Predictive maintenance is a condition-driven preventive maintenance program. It involves monitoring the mechanical condition, system efficiency, and other indicators to determine the actual mean-time-to-failure or efficiency loss for each machine-train and system in the plant, rather than relying on average-life statistics (mean-time-to-failure) to schedule maintenance activities. Traditional time-driven methodologies offer guidelines for "normal" machine-train life durations. In preventative or run-to-failure programs, maintenance managers should rely on their intuition and personal knowledge to determine repair or rebuild timetables (Daley, 2023).

Implementing a predictive maintenance program one can extract accurate data on machine condition and process efficiency. This data provides the maintenance manager with accurate information for scheduling maintenance actions. Predictive maintenance reduces unscheduled breakdowns and ensures restored equipment is in good mechanical condition. This approach is applied to detect machine-train issues before they become severe. Early detection and correction of mechanical faults can significantly reduce their severity. Mechanical failure types typically decrease in proportion to their severity. Early detection of a problem can often save the plant from costly repairs.

Vibration signature analysis is used for predictive maintenance based on two assumptions: (1) all common failure modes have identifiable vibration frequency components, and (2) the amplitude of each component remains constant unless the machine-train's operating dynamics change (You et al., 2010).

Predictive maintenance can measure the effectiveness of non-mechanical plant equipment or systems through non-destructive approaches such as process efficiency and heat loss. Combining these techniques with vibration analysis can help maintenance managers and engineers optimise plant dependability and availability.

Predictive maintenance management typically involves five non-destructive techniques: vibration monitoring, process parameter monitoring, thermography, tribology, and visual inspection. Each technique offers a distinct data set that helps the maintenance manager determine the actual requirement for maintenance.

According to ISO 13381-1, the standard predictive procedure consists of the following steps (Schmidt & Wang, 2018):

- Pre-processing to diagnose all present failure mechanisms and determine probable future failure modes.
- Prognosis of present failure modes to estimate the severity of all measured failure modes.
- Prognosis of future failure modes to assess the future failure modes.
- Complete post-action prognosis to identify steps that will halt or remove present failure modes and prevent the commencement of future failure modes; complete the prognosis process while taking into consideration the impact of any maintenance operations.

Summarising, Predictive maintenance of machinery allows you to assure product quality, perform just-in-time maintenance, reduce equipment downtime, and avoid catastrophic failure.

d. [Other Maintenance Improvement Methods](#)

Over the last decade, management strategies like total productive maintenance (TPM) and reliability-centred maintenance (RCM) have been promoted as solutions to poor maintenance practices. Domestic plants have partially adopted quick-fix solutions to address perceived care limitations.

Total Productive Maintenance

Deming established the TPM concept by dubbing the Japanese approach to effective maintenance management in the late 1950s. His views, as adopted by the Japanese, emphasise strict devotion to the fundamentals, such as lubrication, visual inspections, and the universal application of best practices in all phases of maintenance.

TPM isn't a maintenance management program. Most of the operations connected with the Japanese management method are focused on the production function, assuming that maintenance will do the basic duties required to maintain vital production assets. All quantifiable benefits of TPM are expressed in terms of capacity, product quality, and overall production cost. Unfortunately, domestic advocates of TPM have attempted to adopt its ideals as maintenance-only tasks. As a result, few of these attempts were effective.

TPM aims to increase overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) through collaboration amongst manufacturing, maintenance, engineering, and technical services. The zero breakdown and zero-defect program aims to reduce or eliminate six major shop-floor losses:

- Equipment breakdowns

- Setup and adjustment slowdowns
- Idling and short-term stoppages
- Reduced capacity
- Quality-related losses
- Startup/restart losses

TPM is difficult to define briefly, but the term “improving equipment effectiveness” comes close. The collaboration concept is what makes it work. The Japanese model for TPM includes five pillars that help define how individuals work together in this collaboration. Total productive maintenance emphasises the importance of good business procedures in the maintenance function. The five fundamentals of this method are as follows:

1. Improving equipment effectiveness. To enhance your equipment, identify the six major losses, determine the root cause of inefficiency, and make necessary modifications.
2. Involving operators in everyday maintenance. This does not necessarily include conducting maintenance. Many successful TPM schemes do not require operators to actively perform maintenance. They are active in the maintenance procedure—the plan, the program, and the partnership—but not always in the practical act of maintaining equipment.
3. Improving maintenance efficiency and effectiveness. Most TPM programs need the operator to perform some amount of maintenance. The maintenance department and technologies work together to improve preventive and predictive maintenance, reliability-centred maintenance, spare parts storage, and tool locations.
4. Educating and training workers. The TPM strategy relies heavily on this task. The company teaches both operators and maintenance personnel how to properly use and maintain its machines. Operators are responsible for executing inspections, routine machine adjustments, and preventive duties. Training teaches them how to do so and collaborate with the maintenance department. Supervisors are trained to oversee a TPM-type team environment.
5. Designing and managing equipment for preventive maintenance. While equipment can be expensive, it should be considered as a long-term productive asset. TPM focuses on making equipment easier to run and maintain compared to previous designs. Feedback from operators and maintenance technicians assists engineers in designing, specifying, and procuring more efficient equipment. Evaluating the expenses of operating and maintaining new equipment throughout their life cycle can reduce

long-term costs. Low purchase prices do not necessarily imply low life-cycle expenses.

Overall equipment effectiveness (OEE) is the criterion for TPM initiatives (You et al., 2010). The OEE benchmark is determined by testing equipment performance. Measuring equipment effectiveness must go beyond availability and machine uptime. It must consider all issues concerning equipment performance. Equipment effectiveness formula considers availability, performance rate, and quality. This allows all departments to evaluate equipment effectiveness. The formula can be represented as follows:

$$\textit{Availability} \times \textit{Performance Rate} \times \textit{Quality Rate} = \textit{OEE}$$

Where:

- The availability is the required availability minus the downtime, divided by the required availability. The formula is shown below:

$$\frac{\textit{Required Availability} - \textit{Downtime}}{\textit{Required Availability}} \times 100 = \textit{Availability}$$

Where:

Required Availability: the production time to operate the equipment.

Downtime: the actual time the equipment is down for repairs or changeover (such as breaks, scheduled lapses, meetings). This is also sometimes called breakdown downtime.

- The performance rate is the ideal or design cycle time to finish a product multiplied by the output and divided by the operating time. This will give a performance rate percentage. The formula is:

$$\frac{\textit{Design Cycle Time} \times \textit{Output}}{\textit{Operating Time}} \times 100 = \textit{Performance Rate}$$

Where:

Design Cycle Time: the production output, such as parts per hour.

Output: the total output for the given time.

Operating time: the availability value.

- The quality rate is the production input of the process or equipment, minus the volume or number of quality defects divided by the production input. The formula is illustrated below:

$$\frac{\textit{Production Input} - \textit{Quality Defects}}{\textit{Production Input}} \times 100 = \textit{Quality Rate}$$

Where:

Production input: the unit of product being fed into the process or production cycle.

Quality Defects: the amount of product that is below quality standards after the process or production cycle is finished.

Reliability-Centred Maintenance

RCM assumes that all machines fail and have a finite useful life, although this is not true (You et al., 2010). If machinery and plant systems are properly planned, installed, operated, and maintained, they will not fail and have a nearly unlimited useful life. Few, if any, catastrophic failures occur at random, and all failures are caused by an external influence, such as operator error or incorrect repair. Operating dynamics analysis can detect, isolate, and avoid system problems, except for those caused by operator mistakes or other external factors (Gillespie, 2015).

Since the foundation of RCM is the idea that all machines will eventually deteriorate and fail, Weibull distribution analysis and failure modes and effects analysis (FMEA) are used to predict when these failures will happen. Both theoretical methods rely on probability tables, assuming good plant machinery design, installation, operation, and maintenance. Neither can account for abnormal deviations in any of these areas.

It wasn't until the early 1980s that predictive maintenance technology, like microprocessor-based vibration analysis, provided an accurate technique of detecting emerging problems. New technology has eliminated many of RCM's foundational beliefs. Detecting even small deviations from optimal operating conditions in important plant systems can avoid degradation and eventual collapse.

E-maintenance

Predictive maintenance is a significant improvement over traditional maintenance methods. However, a predictive maintenance plan implemented in isolation from other key processes has room for improvement. As a result, efficiency can be greatly increased by linking several machines across manufacturing locations of a production plant and remotely monitoring them with wireless sensors. A web application and cloud-based monitoring infrastructure enable synchronisation of the maintenance process with the overall operation, even across production sites.

This system can also include linked activities like maintenance resources and even automatic spare-part ordering.

A precondition for such an e-maintenance system is the ability to collect and process important data in real time. Therefore, e-maintenance can be viewed as a fully integrated system, since it encompasses monitoring, diagnostic, prognosis, and control processes. Thus, e-maintenance extends beyond just predictive maintenance. The integrated approach to e-maintenance aligns with the concept and ideas of Industry 4.0 (You et al., 2010).

e. [Maintenance issues](#)

Problems related to maintenance can be divided into two fundamental aspects: financial and technical. The first consideration is the financial reason for maintenance activities. It considers costs, advantages, and investment issues. Maintenance is traditionally viewed as a cost-related activity. However, when considering its impact on output and quality, it can be viewed as an investment and evaluated accordingly. Economic justifications have a role in determining what actions should be taken. Moreover, there are technical aspects to consider, such as what can be done and how.

One issue with existing maintenance practices is the lack of a comprehensive perspective of assets and the existence of "islands of knowledge." Asset data is collected by several functional units within a corporation, such as maintenance, production and quality assurance. Distributing the same machines/subsystems across lines, units, and factories results in independent data collection and analysis. Lessons learned in one area are not applicable in another. Existing data can be used, but it is only analysed in specific circumstances or not at all. This type of data is commonly seen in machine tool controller systems and comprises various events and parameters. Often, there is a lack of understanding regarding the significance of the data. Despite having the necessary technical resources, crucial data for diagnosis and prognosis are not being collected (Schmidt & Wang, 2018).

Another issue is the difficulty to forecast future performance when adding new working conditions, such as new materials for manufacturing. This also applies to optimising process parameters for production.

f. [Comparison of the main methodologies](#)

This section compares the main three types of maintenance techniques based on cost, benefits, problems, and suitability for specific applications. Below, the

maintenance plans for Reactive Maintenance, Preventive Maintenance, and Predictive Maintenance are presented in Fig. 1., while in Fig. 2, a comparison of the costs of these three methodologies is depicted.

Figure 1

Maintenance plans of Reactive, Preventive and Predictive Maintenances

Note. From A survey of predictive maintenance: Systems, purposes and approaches, by Ran et al., (2019)

It has been found that Reactive Maintenance has the lowest prevention cost owing to run-to-failure management, while Preventive Maintenance has the lowest repair cost due to well-planned downtime. Among these, Predictive Maintenance achieves the optimum trade-off between repair and prevention costs. Ideally, Predictive Maintenance provides for the lowest possible maintenance frequency to prevent unforeseen Reactive Maintenance while avoiding the costs associated with excessive Preventive Maintenance. It is important to highlight that the prevention cost primarily includes inspection costs, preventive replacement costs, and so on, whereas the repair cost represents the corrected replacement cost after a failure has occurred.

Figure 2

Comparison of Reactive Maintenance, Predictive Maintenance and Preventive Maintenance on the cost

Note. From A survey of predictive maintenance: Systems, purposes and approaches, by (Ran et al., 2019)

Specifically, the advantages of Reactive Maintenance are maximum utilisation and production value and lower prevention cost, but the disadvantages include unplanned downtime, high spare parts inventory cost, potential further damage to the equipment and definitely a higher repair cost (Deloitte, 2017). Regarding Preventive Maintenance, although the benefits are lower repair cost, less equipment malfunction and unplanned downtime, some challenges occur, like the need for inventory, the increased planned downtime, and the maintenance on seemingly perfect equipment. Concerning Predictive Maintenance, it is used mainly for maintenance management. In most circumstances, this is only used to prevent unscheduled downtime and/or catastrophic failures. Although this function is crucial, predictive maintenance can bring significant additional benefits by broadening the program's scope or mission. Predictive maintenance is a useful tool for both maintenance management and optimization. The program should prioritise avoiding scheduled and unscheduled downtime, reducing preventive and corrective maintenance chores, prolonging essential system life, and lowering total life-cycle costs (Mobley, 2002).

C. Sensing Technologies

Sensing technologies are central to the evolution of predictive maintenance, providing critical insights into equipment health and performance. These sensors act similarly to human nerves, converting external stimuli into electrical signals for processing. They gather and analyse data from production processes in real-time, enhancing the autonomy of machines and devices. Common wireless sensor technologies include RFID, ZigBee, and Bluetooth, which are pivotal in monitoring and evaluating production resources (Pech et al., 2021). These technologies also enable real-time monitoring of various parameters, such as vibration, temperature, and pressure. This continuous data collection is key to identifying potential issues before they lead to equipment failure. Advances in sensor technology, combined with developments in data analytics, machine learning, and IoT, have significantly enhanced predictive maintenance capabilities. They allow for more accurate forecasting of equipment failure, leading to optimized maintenance schedules, reduced downtime, and prolonged equipment life.

The role of sensing technologies in predictive maintenance is transformative, extending beyond mere data collection. They are crucial in providing real-time insights into the operational health of machinery, detecting anomalies and potential faults before they escalate into major issues. This enables a shift from traditional, schedule-based maintenance to a more efficient, condition-based approach. The data collected from sensors are fed into predictive algorithms, enhancing the decision-making process and leading to more effective maintenance strategies. By proactively identifying maintenance needs, sensing technologies significantly reduce downtime and extend equipment lifespan, making them indispensable in modern maintenance practices.

a. Basic Principles

The basic principles of sensing technologies in predictive maintenance integrate data acquisition, analysis, model generation, and simulation. Initially, sensors gather vital data from machinery, tracking parameters like vibration and temperature. This data is then analysed to identify trends and anomalies, a process enhanced by advanced statistical and machine learning techniques. Predictive models are generated from this analysed data, designed to forecast potential equipment failures. Lastly, data simulation uses these models to predict various scenarios, aiding in maintenance planning and decision-making. This systematic approach is essential for an effective predictive maintenance strategy, ensuring equipment reliability and operational efficiency.

The main steps for fault diagnosis using sensors in predictive maintenance typically include:

- **Data Acquisition:** This involves collecting data from various sensors installed on the machinery. These sensors can measure a range of parameters like vibration, temperature, pressure, and acoustic emissions, which are indicative of the machine's health.
- **Data Transmission:** The collected data are transmitted from the sensors to a central processing system. This can be done through wired connections or wireless networks, depending on the setup and requirements of the predictive maintenance system.
- **Data Processing and Analysis:** At this stage, the raw data are processed and analysed. This involves filtering, normalizing, and analysing the data to identify patterns or anomalies. Advanced techniques like statistical analysis, machine learning algorithms, and artificial intelligence can be employed to interpret the sensor data more effectively.
- **Fault Detection and Diagnosis:** Based on the analysis, potential faults or failures in the machinery are detected. Diagnostic algorithms are used to determine the specific type and location of the fault. This step often involves comparing current data with historical trends and known failure modes.
- **Decision Making and Maintenance Planning:** Once a potential issue is identified, the system aids in decision-making regarding the maintenance actions needed. This could involve scheduling repairs, ordering parts, or planning for a machine shutdown, if necessary.
- **Feedback and Optimization:** After maintenance is performed, feedback is collected to refine and optimize the predictive maintenance system. This continuous improvement cycle ensures the system becomes more accurate and reliable over time.

Figure 1

Main steps for fault diagnosis in rotating machinery through vibration analysis

Note. From A Review on Vibration Monitoring Techniques for Predictive Maintenance of Rotating Machinery, by Romanssini et al., (2023)

[b. Key Sensor Types and Their Roles in Predictive Maintenance](#)

Following, a selection of key sensor types is presented, which are utilized in predictive maintenance. This section aims to provide a clear understanding of each sensor's function and its significance in maintaining operational efficiency in industrial settings.

Vibration Sensors

Vibration sensors play a pivotal role in predictive maintenance, especially in the context of rotating machinery used across various industries, including motors, pumps, fans, generators, and compressors. These components are crucial for maintaining productivity and safety in industrial facilities. Research indicates that machine failures, often due to continuous operation and cyclic loading, lead to gradual component wear, increasing failure risks. This wear is a normal consequence of machine operation, but critical conditions can compromise the integrity of components, leading to potential total failure.

Advanced IoT vibration monitoring systems can measure multiple points simultaneously on the same machine, enhancing the effectiveness of predictive maintenance strategies.

Figure 2

Example of vibration monitoring system installed in an electrical rotating machine for predictive maintenance

Note. From A Review on Vibration Monitoring Techniques for Predictive Maintenance of Rotating Machinery, by Romanssini et al., (2023)

The fault diagnosis process in vibration analysis for machine monitoring involves four key steps: data acquisition, data transmission, signal processing, and fault detection. It starts with data acquisition using vibration measurement devices, commonly accelerometers, to capture signals. These signals are then transmitted for processing, where they are filtered, digitized, and analysed to extract actionable insights. The final step, fault detection, involves interpreting these processed signals to identify the type and location of faults in the machinery. This methodical approach is essential for effective and timely maintenance in industrial settings (Romanssini et al., 2023).

Humidity sensors

Humidity sensors, commonly known as hygrometers, are integral tools in predictive maintenance, tasked with monitoring moisture levels across various settings. These sensors work by measuring either relative humidity, which is the amount of moisture air contains compared to its maximum capacity at a specific temperature, or absolute humidity, the total water content in the air irrespective of temperature.

The most prevalent types of humidity sensors include capacitive, resistive, and thermal hygrometers. Capacitive sensors detect humidity through the electrical changes in a polymer or metal oxide film, while resistive sensors measure changes in the electrical resistance of a material caused by humidity. Thermal sensors, on

the other hand, gauge humidity by comparing temperatures between a dry bulb thermometer and a wet bulb thermometer.

In the realm of predictive maintenance, humidity sensors serve various critical functions. They are essential for corrosion prevention, particularly in environments where excess moisture could corrode metal parts. Regular monitoring of humidity levels helps in scheduling maintenance activities before significant corrosive damage occurs. In sectors like food processing or pharmaceuticals, where moisture could lead to mold growth or contamination, humidity sensors are employed to ensure conditions remain within safe parameters (Prihatno et al., 2021).

Moreover, these sensors are pivotal in maintaining the efficiency of equipment. Machinery such as air compressors might operate less efficiently or even fail in conditions of high humidity. Humidity sensors alert maintenance teams to take necessary actions, like adjusting environmental conditions or servicing equipment, to avoid such issues. In building maintenance, particularly within HVAC systems, these sensors help in sustaining optimal indoor air quality and prevent moisture-induced deterioration of building materials.

Another critical application of humidity sensors is in data centres and electronic equipment, where they play a vital role in mitigating risks associated with varying humidity levels. High humidity can cause condensation, while low humidity might lead to static electricity, both posing threats to sensitive electronic components. By maintaining the environment within safe humidity thresholds, these sensors help in protecting this equipment (Prihatno et al., 2021).

Ultrasonic Sensors

Ultrasonic technology has become a crucial component in predictive maintenance due to its ease of use, versatility, and low implementation cost. This technology operates on the principle of emitting high-frequency sound waves and detecting their echoes to gather information about equipment conditions. Modern ultrasonic instruments are sophisticated and customizable, allowing for precise monitoring and fault detection in various industrial applications. These instruments are particularly adept at transforming high-frequency ultrasound into audible sounds, which are analyzed to extract valuable diagnostic data. Their ability to integrate with other predictive technologies, like infrared scanning, further enhances their utility in predictive maintenance programs.

In predictive maintenance, ultrasonic technology is widely applied for tasks such as compressed air leak detection, monitoring bearing conditions, and inspecting steam systems. It is exceptionally effective in detecting leaks in pressurized systems, as the high-frequency sounds produced by leaks are easily identifiable amidst factory noise. For bearing condition monitoring, ultrasonic detectors measure the intensity of frictional forces, providing early warning signs of potential failures. This technology is also crucial in steam system maintenance, where it can

identify issues like blockages or failed steam traps, enabling timely interventions to prevent system inefficiencies and breakdowns.

Ultrasonic technology also plays a vital role in electrical maintenance and the monitoring of reciprocating compressors and valves. It aids in identifying early signs of electrical faults, such as arcing or insulation breakdowns, which are critical for preventing safety hazards like arc flash incidents. In reciprocating compressors, ultrasonic detectors help monitor valve conditions, pinpointing issues that could lead to inefficiencies or failures. The non-invasive nature of ultrasonic monitoring, combined with its ability to detect issues early in the fault cycle, makes it a valuable tool in predictive maintenance strategies, helping to reduce downtime, extend equipment life, and optimize maintenance scheduling (Galarza-Urigoitia et al., 2019).

Pressure sensors

In the context of predictive maintenance for centrifugal pumps, as detailed in the research paper provided, pressure sensors are employed in a technical and sophisticated manner. These sensors are strategically positioned to continuously monitor the pressure and flow within the pump systems. By doing so, they gather essential data which is crucial for detecting variances from normal operational parameters. These variances could indicate potential issues like leaks, obstructions, or mechanical degradation.

The technical application of these sensors involves their integration into the pump system's key points - typically at the inlet and outlet. This placement allows for the accurate measurement of differential pressure, a key indicator of the pump's health. The data collected from these sensors are then analyzed, often with the help of advanced algorithms and IoT-based systems, to predict potential failures and schedule maintenance activities. This methodical use of pressure sensors in predictive maintenance not only enhances the reliability of the centrifugal pumps but also optimizes their operational efficiency and lifespan.

Figure 3

Principal components of a conventional pressure transmitter

Note. From Predictive maintenance of pumps based on signal analysis of pressure and differential pressure (flow) measurements, by Higham & Perovic, (2001)

Humidity sensors, essential in predictive maintenance, operate primarily on the principle of detecting moisture levels in the air. Two common types are capacitive and resistive humidity sensors. Capacitive sensors measure humidity by detecting changes in electrical capacitance caused by moisture absorption in a polymer or dielectric material. Resistive sensors, on the other hand, rely on changes in electrical resistance of materials due to humidity. These variations in electrical properties are indicative of the moisture content in the environment.

In predictive maintenance, humidity sensors are crucial for environments where moisture levels can impact equipment performance and longevity. They are used in a wide range of industrial applications, including preventing corrosion in metal parts, avoiding condensation in electrical systems, and maintaining the integrity of moisture-sensitive materials. By continuously monitoring and analyzing humidity levels, these sensors enable early detection of potential issues caused by excessive moisture, facilitating proactive maintenance actions to prevent equipment failure and extend its operational life.

In summarizing the various sensor technologies in predictive maintenance, it's evident that advancements in sensor systems like vibration, temperature, pressure, and humidity sensors play a pivotal role in the modern industrial landscape. These sensors, with their real-time data acquisition and analysis capabilities, are integral to ensuring operational efficiency and equipment longevity. However, it's important to note that these are not the only sensors in play. Other sensor technologies, such as acoustic sensors for leak detection and optical sensors for visual inspections, also contribute significantly to predictive maintenance frameworks. The integration of these diverse sensor technologies is crucial in shaping the future of predictive maintenance, especially as we move further into the era of Industry 4.0. This evolution brings challenges and opportunities, with future trends likely focusing on further miniaturization, enhanced data integration, and the increasing use of artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms to interpret vast amounts of sensor data.

[c. Industry 4.0: Revolutionizing Predictive Maintenance with Smart sensors](#)

The Fourth Industrial Revolution, or Industry 4.0, marks a paradigm shift in manufacturing and industrial practices, underpinned by the integration of the Internet of Things (IoT) and predictive maintenance, facilitated by advanced smart sensor technologies. This integration heralds a new era of efficiency and intelligence in industrial operations.

Figure 6 illustrates the development of the total number of publications related to Industry 4.0 and predictive maintenance, as indexed by Scopus (denoted by circles on the bold line) and Web of Science (indicated by squares on the line), showcasing the growing academic and research interest in these fields over time."

Figure 4

Development of total number of science publications

Note. From *Predictive Maintenance and Intelligent Sensors in Smart Factory: Review*, by Pech et al., (2021)

A key aspect of this integration is the shift from centralized control systems to decentralized and distributed architectures. In the context of Industry 4.0, decentralized smart industry systems offer enhanced scalability and resistance to failures, crucial for the robust implementation of predictive maintenance strategies. The distributed nature of these systems allows for more efficient coordination and management of the complex digital ecosystems characteristic of modern production factories.

Advancements in sensor technology, particularly the development of virtual and nano-sensors, play a pivotal role in this evolution. These sensors, known for their reliability, are integral to control, measuring, and automation systems. The trend towards integrating these sensors into compact designs, where they coexist with signal processing and analysis circuits, optimizes the entire system.

However, this technological advancement is not without challenges. The integration of older sensors with new systems can lead to increased manufacturing and maintenance costs, signal interference issues, and consequently, production interruptions. Addressing these challenges necessitates a focus on real-time preventive maintenance and the continuous upgrading of sensor technology to ensure compatibility and efficiency.

In the realm of predictive maintenance, the industry is witnessing a surge in the application of deep machine learning, IoT, and big data analytics. Intelligent sensors in smart factories are increasingly leveraging edge, fog, and deep learning methods to control and optimize manufacturing processes. The concept of Smart and Intelligent Predictive Maintenance (SIPM) has emerged, encompassing production, monitoring, planning, and maintenance subsystems that interact through IoT and cloud-based technologies. This system not only enhances real-time management but also significantly reduces economic costs due to production downtime.

Moreover, predictive maintenance is gaining prominence due to the increasing integration of robots, digitization, and artificial intelligence in production lines. This trend necessitates the development of advanced machine learning methods and the exploration of new paradigms such as "Machine as a Service" (MaaS), which focus on performance model evaluation and cost-benefit analysis in the context of sustainability.

In conclusion, the synergy of IoT and predictive maintenance in Industry 4.0, powered by smart sensors, is pivotal in driving the transition towards more automated, efficient, and intelligent manufacturing processes. This paradigm shift emphasizes a data-driven approach to operational decision-making, where the role of advanced sensor technology and machine learning algorithms is central. The ongoing evolution in this field points to a future where smart factories become the norm, characterized by heightened efficiency, reduced downtimes, and enhanced operational intelligence. (Pech et al., 2021) (Coandă et al., 2020)

Figure 5

A visualization of the system with data being collected from an industrial sensor network (based on IoT)

Note. From Review—Deep Learning Methods for Sensor Based Predictive Maintenance and Future Perspectives for Electrochemical Sensors, by Namuduri et al., (2020)

d. Challenges and Future Trends in Sensors for Predictive Maintenance

The integration of sensors in predictive maintenance within Industry 4.0 faces several challenges and is poised for significant future trends. A primary challenge is the need for seamless integration of advanced sensor technologies, such as nano-sensors and virtual sensors, with existing industrial systems. This integration often requires overcoming compatibility issues, particularly when incorporating new sensors into older equipment, which can lead to increased costs and complexity. Another critical challenge is ensuring the reliability and accuracy of sensor data amidst potential interference and signal degradation, which are vital for effective predictive analytics. Moreover, the security and safety of sensor data in increasingly interconnected networks presents a growing concern, necessitating robust cybersecurity measures to protect against data breaches and unauthorized access. Future trends point towards the development of more sophisticated sensor technologies that are not only highly sensitive and reliable but also self-calibrating and capable of real-time data processing. The use of artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms is expected to enhance the predictive capabilities of maintenance systems, enabling more precise fault detection and prognosis. Additionally, the evolution of IoT and cloud technologies will likely lead to more decentralized and autonomous sensor networks, offering greater scalability and flexibility in predictive maintenance strategies. As these technologies advance, addressing these challenges and embracing these trends will be crucial in realizing the full potential of sensors in predictive maintenance in Industry 4.0.

D. Time Management System

The scope of this section is to provide the general picture of the integrated Time Management System of Predictive Maintenance approach. Students will gain a brief knowledge of the assets of Time Management System and how useful parameters are evaluated.

A common misconception about PDM is that it is a maintenance management tool. Instead, PDM is mostly a maintenance scheduling tool. It is a part of integrated total plant-based performance management program, providing the means to improve production capacity, product quality and overall performance of the production plant. PDM is a management technique that uses regular evaluation of the actual operating conditions of plant equipment, production systems and plant management functions to optimize total plant operation. A model is structured in a way to run some calculations, which are based on various principles. The outcome of this model is data, which constitute the PDM output. Enhancing plant performance requires addressing issues identified by this outcome. Improvements will be achieved as soon as a proper plant management philosophy exists. This is the reason why the whole PDM concept relies on an effective and dynamic Time Management System (TMS). TMS is a cornerstone in the evolution from reactive to proactive maintenance involving the strategic integration of time-related data and predictive analytics.

Time Management System (TMS) in Predictive Maintenance is the systematic utilization of time-related data and predictive analytics to refine maintenance schedules. Unlike traditional methods which are based on fixed and specified intervals, TMS in PDM empowers engineers to strategically allocate these intervals based on the components' condition. Predictive models are responsible to provide the necessary data to assist decision-making procedure with the proper allocation of time intervals. In this case, TMS is a dynamic approach as reporting models run continuously (monitoring, forecasting and optimizing), while considering unpredicted factors. This robust process ensures targeted maintenance, optimized resource allocation, and a reduction in operational disruptions.

The significance of TMS surfaces when contrasting it with reactive maintenance concepts. TMS mitigates challenges like unplanned downtime and emergency repairs by introducing a data-driven methodology to maintenance scheduling based on components' condition.

Quotes like "A dollar today is not a dollar tomorrow" and "time is money" are a suitable reminder about the correlation between time and money, especially in the corporate world. This is particularly true when it comes to predictive and preventive maintenance. The following describes some of the time and cost related elements for the further understanding of the main drawbacks of preventive maintenance:

- When preventive maintenance is scheduled to occur too early, some portion of the usable life of a component will be wasted.
- When maintenance is scheduled to be conducted on a continuous basis and fixed intervals, some amount of work will be done when there is little or no risk of failure and therefore, of little value.

In both preventive and predictive maintenance concepts, it is possible to not have all the necessary information needed to evaluate timing issues. The same applies when the construction of the maintenance schedule is requested from the very beginning. According to Preventive Maintenance philosophy, a component is changed based on maker's recommendation, following some safety margins imposed by the Original Equipment Manufacturer (OEM). However, due to some unpredicted factors, it happens quite regularly for a component to suffer deterioration prior to the maintenance interval. While one may know that a component is subject to deterioration resulting from a specific Failure Mechanism, one may not know specifically when this deterioration starts or when it reaches a point of impending failure. This is crucial in order to identify the root causes and in position to re-design the initially created maintenance plan.

Ultimately, it might be necessary to use the results collected during early maintenance activities to adjust the timing of future plans. For instance, if an anti-friction bearing is changed at a specific time, based on the manufacturers B-10 rating, it is possible to inspect the removed bearing and make the following recommendations for the future:

- Roll the inner race against the outer race of the bearing to determine if the bearing is running roughly or smoothly or if there is any unexpected sound. Also, determine if the two races have loosened relative to each other. First assume the bearing shows no deterioration whatsoever. In this case, the time between preventive maintenance tasks will gradually be increased to maximise the bearing's usable life.
- Now assume that the bearing has been found to show some amount of deterioration, but no other element in the equipment has been damaged. In this case, preventive maintenance has been scheduled at the appropriate interval (or a little later), meaning that the initial planning should remain.
- Finally, assume that the bearing shows marked deterioration and the bearing failure has caused damage to some other components (like the shaft). In this case, the preventive maintenance interval should be shortened to the point when only the bearing has failed.

This example is used to demonstrate how preventive maintenance intervals are chosen and how costly this method can be. By carrying out vibration or ultrasonic analysis, it is possible to identify early stages of bearing deterioration. This knowledge provides the proper information in order to schedule the maintenance

at an optimum interval, which is important in order to harvest all the usable life from the bearing and avoid collateral damage to other components. And here it is where the term of “Remaining Useful Life” (RUL) comes up, though a detailed analysis will follow later in this section (Daley, 2023).

All the above explain some of TMS multifaceted advantages. Evaluating the remaining useful life of components allows engineers to avoid unnecessary replacements and repairs, leading to minimized downtime. Imagine the cost saving that can be achieved by avoiding frequent replacements. Purchasing a new spare part includes its transportation cost too. In any case, such expenses can be avoided by limiting the replacements. In addition, use of the predictive approach extends equipment lifespans. The idea is to exploit as much as possible a component’s useful lifetime (also mentioned in literature as “normal life”). Equipment’s operational life is divided in three different phases (Fig 8): the break-in or start-up, the normal/useful life, the wear out/deterioration. Figure 8 illustrates the failure behaviour of a component based on its age, which is called bathtub curve. The bathtub curve, as already presented in Section 1, indicates that new equipment would experience a high probability of failure due to installation problems during the first few weeks of operation. After this break-in period, the failure rate becomes relatively low for an extended period of time. After this normal life period, the probability of failure increases dramatically with elapsed time (Ran et al., 2019). The ideal time of change would be just before the wear out phase, and this can be achieved when the condition of the equipment is known (Ran et al., 2019).

Figure 6

Statistical bathtub curve of a piece of equipment, including different phases of equipment's operating life

Note. From A survey of predictive maintenance: Systems, purposes and approaches, by Ran et al., (2019)

Moreover, with PDM a reduction in operational disruptions can be achieved, considering that changing of spare parts will not take place so frequently. This means that it is not necessary to stop the machinery in order to change components (i.e., overhauling). Hence, the reliability of components will be increased, making the whole operational profile safer and more desirable. Therefore, the spectrum of benefits of a well-developed TMS can be summarized to the following categories below:

- Avoidance of unnecessary replacements
- Cost savings
- Extended equipment lifespan
- Reduced unplanned downtime
- Optimized Maintenance schedules
- Maximization of reliability
- Operational efficiency

Understanding these gains is crucial for demonstrating the value of TMS to stakeholders and decision-makers and further assists in improving predictive models, in order to optimize the whole maintenance system.

While a dynamic TMS offers important benefits, there exist some potential challenges too. The models are dynamic, thus, comprehensive data collection, integration of advanced analytics, and continuous monitoring for model refinement are factors that require frequent monitoring. These challenges, however, require further improvement and this is where Machine Learning steps forward, in order to provide valuable assistance. However, ML integration will be covered in another section.

Calculating RUL

As already mentioned, the integrated TMS is relied on the calculation of Remaining Useful Life (Werner et al., 2019). Evaluation of this factor as accurately as possible is an essential part for optimizing TMS. This complicated process involves usage of various methodologies, tools, and data sources to predict when a specific component is likely to reach the end of its functional lifespan. By estimating RUL, engineers schedule maintenance jobs, optimize operating efficiency and avoid unplanned downtime. For this reason, RUL evaluation is considered top priority in predictive maintenance approach.

The journey into calculating RUL begins with harnessing data from sensors, which are strategically placed on machinery systems. The sensors are responsible to continuously collect information about the health and performance of components. As soon as data is received, Machine Learning algorithms are

employed for analysis, identifying patterns and trends, which lead to potential future failures. Incorporating historical performance data and any statistical data available, predictive models are further refined, enhancing the accuracy of RUL calculations.

Sensors act as the frontline data collectors, providing real-time information about the condition of components. Whether it's vibration sensors, which monitor rotating equipment, or temperature sensors, which assess thermal stress, the integration of diverse sensor data is critical for a comprehensive understanding of machinery health. Therefore, it is essential to place sensors strategically, in order to receive relevant performance metrics, based on the best expected outcome. Sensors provide data, which, in our case, become the input to the model, which is responsible to calculate RUL. However, the outcome also acts as feedback to the model, since crucial results can be extracted, related to input data. These data are fed into the model and also explain why proper selection of sensors is important. More sensors than needed will provide a cornucopia of data, which will make the calculation of RUL more difficult and in addition, more computational power will be required. On the other hand, less sensors than necessary will provide less data and hence, a miscalculation of RUL could take place, which in turn may lead to unexpected component failure.

The backbone of RUL calculations lies in the application of machine learning algorithms. These algorithms, trained on historical data and similar statistical data, learn to identify patterns associated with the deterioration of components.

The culmination of sensor data integration and machine learning application results in the creation of predictive models. These models become powerful tools for Predictive Maintenance Engineers, allowing them to foresee potential failures and schedule interventions pre-emptively. The whole TMS is structured, based on these models. However, the method selection for calculating RUL, largely depends on the available data. There are three common models used to estimate RUL: survival, degradation, and similarity (Mathworks, 2019).

- Survival model: When data is available only from the time of failure, rather than complete run-to-failure histories.
- Degradation model: When some data are available between a healthy state and failure and a safety threshold value is known too.
- Similarity model: When data is gathered during the full degradation cycle of a system from a healthy state to failure.

Figure 7

RUL Estimator models

Note. From Predictive Maintenance: Estimating Remaining Useful Life with MATLAB, by Mathworks, (2019)

Constructing and using such models is not an easy thing and requires good software development skills, in addition to mathematical and science knowledge. Deeper analysis of such models is not included in this booklet, but, if one is interested, there are plenty of academic papers introducing ways to build them (Mathworks, 2019; Gebraeel et al., 2005).

Although, the field of PDM is dynamic, predictive models require continuous refinement. RUL can easily change due to unpredicted factors and this requires high adaptability of predictive models on any modification in operational conditions. Model refinement involves updated algorithms based on new data and incorporating insights gained from practical experiences in the field.

Developing and following TMS

As the necessary terms have been explained, the implementation of an effective TMS in PDM requires a systematic approach.

The first step in developing a TMS involves selecting and installing the appropriate sensors to collect relevant data. This requires a comprehensive understanding of the machinery and its critical components. Subsequently, data collection protocols are established by engineers, ensuring that the information gathered is accurate, timely, and representative of the actual operating conditions.

Once data collection infrastructure is in place, the next crucial step is integration of predictive analytics. This involves usage of appropriate machine learning algorithms to analyse the collected data and create predictive models. Their role is to pinpoint which components are close to their wear out phase (calculation of RUL). This integration demands a deep understanding of data science principles and data analysis, which is based on various statistical methods, mathematics and physics.

The evaluation of how effective TMS is, relies on its adaptability. This explains the dynamic nature of PDM concept. Continuous monitoring of predictive models is a pre-requisite, in order to achieve an accurate calculation of RUL. The following figure provides an overview of an effective TMS. Data acquisition process from sensing technologies always needs to be monitored, forecasted and optimized, in order to provide the output (in our case is the calculation of RUL), which is where the whole decision-making procedure is based on (in other words, the scheduling). This involves both tracking model performance against real-world data and adjusting as needed. However, data acquired from unpredicted situations (i.e., unpredicted damage of a component due to exogenous factors) shall be incorporated into the system, too (Tiddens et al., 2022; Sang et al., 2020).

Figure 8

Description of effective TMS

Note. From A survey of predictive maintenance: Systems, purposes and approaches, by Ran et al., (2019)

Nowadays, development of proper TMS can be achieved by incorporating the use of Digital Twin concept, which relies on the mutual data exchange between physical and virtual environment. Digital Twins provide a real-time representation of the physical machine and generate data, such as asset degradation, which the predictive maintenance algorithm can use. Similar research work may assist on such development and it can be found in the relevant literature (van Dinter et al., 2022).

Precautions, Validation and Case studies

Predictive Maintenance Engineers should be prepared to face challenges during the implementation of TMS. These challenges may include data security concerns, necessity for workforce training on new technologies, and the integration of predictive maintenance into existing organizational structures. Of course, the deployment of condition monitoring devices (i.e., sensors) requires a high installation cost (increases CAPital EXpenditure - CAPEX), as well as additional costs due to malfunctions (relevant to OPERational EXpenditure – OPEX). Moreover, the complexity of a Predictive Maintenance system is increased due to data collection, data analysis and decision making, which leads to higher computational power requirements. This is also translated into higher costs. Therefore, a financial assessment is necessary, in order to compare expenditures with cost savings.

Common concerns that may arise during PDM is the validity of received data. For this reason, it is often requested that a proper calibration of sensing technologies takes place upon installation by a competent technician. Additionally, regular validation of data received is necessary too. Validation is a critical step in ensuring the reliability of predictive models. Generated predictions by the model should be compared to actual outcomes to assess accuracy. Continuous validation, using new data and adjusting models accordingly is essential to maintain the precision of TMS over time.

Predictive models should also be adaptable and part of their role is to exclude specific data received; the well-known “filtering”. There are certain parameters and constraints that can be implemented into the model to eliminate certain data and make the algorithm more accurate. The notion behind this is that some environmental factors or some other exogenous factors may influence the accuracy of sensor data. Nowadays, cyber security is at its finest, ensuring the security and integrity of every data acquisition process. This is another significant technological advancement to be taken into account in PDM implementations. The transmission of data requires protection, in order to avoid unexpected interference by any third party. This will also increase the total expenditures of the PDM system deployment.

By implementing PDM does not mean that one has to invent the wheel. This is a common technique that many companies follow and develop consistently. The aviation industry seems to be few steps forward in the implementation of TMS.

In conclusion, the implementation of a Time Management System in Predictive Maintenance is a dynamic and multifaceted process. Predictive Maintenance Engineers play a main role in developing, refining, and implementing TMS to optimize maintenance schedules, extend equipment lifespans, and achieve cost savings. Overcoming challenges, exercising precautions, and continuously

validating predictive models are essential elements of a successful TMS implementation.

E. Reporting Models

Reporting models are instrumental in collecting, organizing, and presenting data related to equipment health, maintenance activities, and operational efficiency. They serve as a foundation for informed decision-making, facilitating the implementation of proactive maintenance strategies and continuous improvement initiatives within organizations. These models are crucial elements in ensuring a holistic approach to preventive maintenance.

Reporting Models in Holistic Preventive Maintenance

1. Diagnostic Reports

Diagnostic reports focus on identifying equipment health issues, root causes of failures, and recommended corrective actions.

Figure 9

Predictive Maintenance Toolbox from MATLAB

Note. From Predictive Maintenance Toolbox: Design and test condition monitoring and predictive maintenance algorithms, by Mathworks, (2024)

Diagnostic reports should include the following information:

- Equipment Information: Identification and details of the equipment or asset being diagnosed.

- Current Condition: Assessment of the current health status, including any abnormalities or deviations from normal operation.
- Fault Analysis: Identification of specific faults or issues detected during diagnostic procedures.
- Root Cause Analysis: Analysis and identification of the underlying reasons causing the observed faults.
- Recommended Actions: Clear and concise recommendations for corrective actions or maintenance interventions.

Significance: Offers insights into current equipment conditions, aiding in timely maintenance interventions.

2. Prognostic Reports

Prognostic reports predict future equipment failures, estimate remaining useful life, and recommend proactive maintenance actions.

Figure 10

Prognostic model for Predictive Maintenance

Note. From Estimating remaining useful life in machines using artificial intelligence: A scoping review, by Sayyad, (2021)

Prognostic reports should include the following information:

- Remaining Useful Life (RUL): Prediction or estimation of the remaining operational life expectancy of equipment.
- Failure Projections: Forecasts or predictions of potential failures and their likelihood within a specified timeframe.
- Recommended Preventive Actions: Suggestions for proactive maintenance or interventions to prevent anticipated failures.
- Risk Assessment: Evaluation of risks associated with potential failures and their impact on operations.

Significance: Enables anticipation of potential failures, allowing for preventive actions.

3. Performance Reports

Performance reports evaluate the effectiveness of predictive maintenance programs, measuring key performance indicators (KPIs) and assessing overall maintenance efficiency.

Figure 11

Predictive maintenance 2024 performance report by IoT Analytics

Note. From *Predictive maintenance market: 5 highlights for 2024 and beyond*, by IoT Analytics, (2024)

Performance reports should include the following information:

- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): Metrics used to measure the effectiveness and efficiency of the maintenance program.
- Maintenance Metrics: Data on maintenance activities, such as mean time between failures (MTBF), mean time to repair (MTTR), etc.

- Equipment Reliability Trends: Analysis of equipment reliability over time, highlighting improvements or deteriorations.
- Cost Analysis: Evaluation of maintenance costs and their relationship to equipment reliability and downtime.

Significance: Offers insights into the effectiveness of maintenance strategies, aiding in continuous improvement.

4. Standardized Reporting Models

Description: Industry-standard reporting models promote consistency and structure in maintenance reporting practices.

Figure 12

Digital Twin Implementation Schematic

Note. From *Building a digital twin powered intelligent predictive maintenance system for industrial AC machines*, by Singh et al., (2023)

Standardization reports should include the following information:

- **Data Standardization:** Guidelines or frameworks for consistent data collection, formatting, and reporting practices.
- **Unified Metrics:** Standardized metrics and KPIs used for assessing maintenance performance across different systems or organizations.
- **Comparative Analysis:** Methods for comparing maintenance performance against industry benchmarks or established norms.
- **Best Practices:** Recommendations or guidelines based on industry best practices for maintenance reporting.

Significance: Streamlines maintenance evaluations and comparisons across industries.

Reporting models stand as the cornerstone of holistic preventive maintenance, offering structured frameworks that capture, analyse, and disseminate vital information crucial to maintaining operational efficiency, enhancing reliability, and optimizing resources. The significance of these reporting models lies in their ability to translate complex data into actionable insights, guiding informed decision-making and fostering continuous improvement within maintenance strategies.

Diagnostic Reports meticulously detail the current state of equipment health, enabling swift identification of issues and facilitating targeted corrective actions. These reports act as the initial diagnostic tool, guiding maintenance interventions to address imminent concerns.

Prognostic Reports extend the horizon, foreseeing potential failures and estimating remaining useful life. By providing a proactive outlook, they empower organizations to plan and execute maintenance tasks in advance, mitigating risks and minimizing downtime.

Performance Reports serve as the compass, offering a comprehensive evaluation of maintenance operations. They measure the effectiveness of maintenance strategies, quantify performance through key metrics, and uncover areas for optimization and enhancement.

Standardized Reporting Models serve as the foundation, ensuring uniformity and consistency in maintenance reporting practices. By establishing industry-standard frameworks, they facilitate comparisons, benchmarking, and the adoption of best practices across diverse sectors.

The amalgamation of these reporting models transcends mere documentation; it encapsulates a culture of data-driven decision-making, continual assessment, and adaptive strategies within preventive maintenance frameworks. Their impact resonates in the reduction of unplanned downtime, optimization of resources,

enhancement of equipment reliability, and ultimately, the fortification of operational resilience.

In essence, reporting models within holistic preventive maintenance herald an era of informed, proactive, and strategic maintenance approaches. Their utilization not only augments equipment performance but also fosters an environment of perpetual improvement, driving organizations toward operational excellence and sustained competitiveness.

F. Structural Assessment Methods

Structural assessment methods within holistic preventive maintenance encompass various techniques and tools used to evaluate the condition, integrity, and reliability of assets and infrastructure. These methods play a crucial role in proactive maintenance strategies by enabling the identification of potential issues or failures before they occur, ensuring operational safety, and optimizing maintenance schedules. In the following we present some commonly utilized structural assessment methods:

Non-Destructive Testing (NDT)

Non-Destructive Testing (NDT) is a cornerstone in structural assessment, allowing for comprehensive evaluations without damaging the equipment. NDT techniques, such as ultrasonic testing, magnetic particle inspection, liquid penetrant testing, radiographic testing, and eddy current testing, allow for thorough inspections without causing damage to the equipment or infrastructure. These methods detect surface and subsurface flaws, cracks, and material inconsistencies, aiding in the early detection of potential failures.

- Ultrasonic Testing (UT): uses high-frequency sound waves to detect internal flaws, cracks, or defects in materials.

Figure 13

Ultrasonic Inspection

Note. From *Ultrasonic Testing*, by MaterialsScience2000, (2014c) (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UM6XKvXWVFA>)

- Magnetic Particle Inspection (MPI): identifies surface and near-surface flaws in ferromagnetic materials by applying a magnetic field and observing particle accumulation.

Figure 14

Magnetic Particle Inspection

Note. From *Magnetic Particle Inspection*, by MaterialsScience2000, (2014a) (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qpgcD5k1494>)

- Liquid Penetrant Testing (PT): utilizes capillary action to reveal surface defects in non-porous materials by applying a liquid penetrant and developer.

Figure 15

Liquid Penetrant Testing

Note. From *Dye Penetrant Inspection*, by MaterialsScience2000, (2014b) (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xEK-c1pkTUI>)

- Radiographic Testing (RT): uses X-rays or gamma rays to inspect the internal structure of components, revealing defects or inconsistencies.

Figure 16

Radiographic Testing (RT)

Note. From *X-ray Inspection and Industrial Computed Tomography*, by MaterialsScience2000, (2015) (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=IcWjZbXiFkM>)

- Eddy Current Testing (ET): detects surface and subsurface flaws by inducing electrical currents in conductive materials and analysing resulting electromagnetic fields.

Figure 17

Eddy Current Testing (ET)

Note. From *Eddy Current Testing*, by MaterialsScience2000, (2016) (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oriFJByl6Hs>)

Vibration Analysis

By analysing vibration patterns in machinery and equipment, this method helps assess the health of rotating components. Irregularities in vibration patterns can signal potential faults or wear and tear, enabling proactive maintenance interventions. It plays a crucial role in detecting faults and anomalies in machinery. It allows for the analysis of vibration patterns to assess equipment health, aiding in the early identification of potential failures and facilitating timely maintenance.

- Accelerometers: devices used to measure vibration by converting mechanical motion into electrical signals.

Figure 18

Different designs and elements of an accelerometer

Note. From *Accelerometer Sensors*, by Brüel & Kjær, (2024)

(<https://www.bksv.com/en/transducers/vibration/accelerometers>)

- Frequency Analysis: identifies specific vibration frequencies related to machinery faults or component wear.

Figure 19

Data Identifying the Natural Frequency of a Structure

Note. From *Predictive Maintenance Case Study*, by Fore, (n.d.)

- Time Waveform Analysis: evaluates vibration patterns over time to identify irregularities or changes in equipment behaviour.

Figure 20

Time waveform analysis of the spindle with bearing damage in the inner race

Note. From *Vibration analysis of machine tool spindle units*, by Rastegari, (2017)

Thermographic Inspection

Thermographic Inspection utilizes thermal imaging to identify temperature variations in equipment, highlighting potential issues such as overheating or abnormalities that could lead to failures. Utilizing thermal imaging cameras, thermographic inspection detects temperature variations in equipment or

structures. Anomalies in temperature can indicate issues like overheating or insulation problems, helping identify potential failures.

- Infrared Thermography: captures thermal images to detect variations in temperature across equipment or structures.

Figure 21

Thermography for faulty terminations in high power electrical circuits

Note. From *Thermography for Predictive Maintenance*, by Engineering World, (n.d.)

- Temperature Measurement: identifies anomalies, overheating, or insulation problems by analysing temperature distribution.

Figure 22

Condition monitoring and Predictive Maintenance (PdM)

Note. From *The Importance of Bluetooth for Condition Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance in IIoT*, by Cassia Networks, (2019)

Finite Element Analysis (FEA)

Finite Element Analysis (FEA), a simulation-based approach, enables predictive modelling of structural behaviour and stress analysis. It aids in identifying potential weak points and optimizing maintenance schedules. FEA is a computational method used to simulate and analyse the structural behaviour of components or

systems under different conditions. It aids in predicting stress concentrations, potential failure points, and overall structural integrity, enabling optimized maintenance planning.

Figure 23

FEA used to predict shapes of a 24" x 24" x 0.125" flat plate. Animation of Seventh Natural Frequency Mode Shape Deflection

Note. From Complete Solutions for Demanding Environmental Test Requirements, by Sentek Dynamics, (2024)

- **Mesh Generation:** Divides a complex structure into smaller elements for analysis.

Mesh generation involves dividing the entire structure into a mesh or grid of elements, ensuring an adequate representation of its geometry and complexity. Engineers choose the type of elements based on the structure's geometry, complexity, and the type of analysis required (e.g., linear or quadratic elements). The density of the mesh or the number of elements used determines the accuracy of the analysis. Finer meshes provide more detailed results but require more computational resources. A good mesh maintains element shapes, avoids distorted elements, and minimizes abrupt changes in element size, ensuring accurate analysis results.

Advantages of Mesh Generation in FEA

Accuracy- Proper meshing ensures accurate representation of structural behaviour and stress distribution.

Efficiency- A well-designed mesh balances computational resources with accuracy, optimizing analysis time and resources.

Adaptability- Different parts of the structure can have varying mesh densities based on the criticality of analysis areas.

Challenges

Mesh Quality- Generating a high-quality mesh requires expertise to avoid issues like element distortion or inadequate representation of the structure.

Computational Cost- Finer meshes demand more computational resources, increasing analysis time and complexity.

Figure 24

Finite element model and mesh generation

Note. From Temperature-based optimization of friction stir welding of AA 6061 using GRA synchronous with Taguchi method, by Sefene & Tsegaw, (2022)

- **Stress Analysis:** Predicts stress concentrations, deformations, and potential failure points under varying loads or conditions.

Stress analysis determines the distribution of internal forces, deformations, and stresses within a structure or component under various loading conditions.

Types of Stresses

Normal Stress- acts perpendicular to the surface and induces tension or compression.

Shear Stress- occurs parallel to the surface and causes deformation by sliding or tearing.

Von Mises Stress- a combined stress measure representing a simplified criterion for material failure.

Process of Stress Analysis in FEA

Modelling & Boundary Conditions- the structure or component is modelled, and boundary conditions (loads, constraints, and material properties) are defined.

Mesh Generation- the structure is divided into smaller elements, creating a mesh.

Material Properties & Loads- material properties, such as modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio, are assigned to elements. External loads or forces are applied.

Solver & Analysis- the FEA solver solves mathematical equations for each element, determining stress distribution, strain, and displacement throughout the structure.

Results & Interpretation- engineers analyse stress maps, identify critical areas prone to failure, and assess whether stress levels exceed material limits.

Types of Stress Analysis

- Static Stress Analysis: Evaluates stress distribution and deformation in structures subjected to constant loads or forces.
- Dynamic Stress Analysis: Considers time-dependent loading conditions, such as vibrations or impact, to predict structural responses.

Applications and Significance

Structural Integrity- Determines whether a structure can withstand applied loads without failure or excessive deformation.

Failure Prediction- Identifies critical areas prone to fatigue, yielding, or fracture, enabling preventive maintenance or design modifications.

Optimization- Helps optimize designs by minimizing material usage while ensuring structural safety.

Safety Assurance- Ensures compliance with safety standards and regulations.

Challenges

Complexity- Analysing complex structures with various material properties and loading conditions can be challenging.

Accuracy vs. Computational Cost- Achieving accurate results often requires finer meshes and increased computational resources, impacting analysis time.

Figure 25

Example of FEM model geometry/stiffness modification: adjustment of the flexible shaft structure and stiffness allowed to improve model fidelity, left plot- amplitude FRF comparison prior to modifications (top) and after the proposed adjustments (bottom).

Note. From Employing finite element analysis and robust control concepts in mechatronic system design-flexible manipulator case study, by Goubej et al., (2021)

- **Material Property Analysis:** Evaluates material properties, aiding in predicting structural responses and behaviour.

Material Property Analysis involves assigning material characteristics (such as elasticity, density, strength) to elements within a model to simulate the behaviour of materials under different loading conditions.

Key Material Properties

- **Elastic Modulus (Young's Modulus):** Defines the material's stiffness or resistance to deformation under stress.
- **Poisson's Ratio:** Indicates material's tendency to contract laterally when stretched longitudinally.
- **Density:** Represents the mass per unit volume of the material.
- **Yield Strength & Ultimate Strength:** Measure material's ability to withstand deformation and failure under stress.
- **Thermal Conductivity & Expansion Coefficient:** Reflects material's response to temperature changes.

Role in Finite Element Analysis (FEA)

Material Assignment- Accurately assigning material properties to each element based on the material being simulated.

Material Nonlinearity- Some materials exhibit nonlinear behaviours like plasticity or elasticity, requiring appropriate property definitions.

Temperature Effects- Materials may behave differently at varying temperatures; thus, temperature-dependent properties are crucial for accurate analysis.

Process of Material Property Analysis in FEA

Material Selection- Choosing appropriate material models based on the behaviour and properties of the real-world material.

Material Assignment- Assigning material properties (Elastic Modulus, Poisson's Ratio, etc.) to each element in the FEA model.

Validation- Ensuring the selected material properties accurately represent the real-world material's behaviour through calibration or testing data.

Sensitivity Analysis- Assessing the impact of variations in material properties on analysis results.

Significance

- Proper material property analysis ensures the FEA model closely mimics the real-world behaviour of materials.
- Ensures reliability in predicting stress distribution, deformation, and structural responses under different loading conditions.

- Facilitates the evaluation of various material options to optimize designs for performance and cost-effectiveness.

Challenges

Material Variability- Materials can exhibit variability, requiring consideration of different material states (e.g., anisotropic, or non-homogeneous materials).

Limited Data- Obtaining accurate material properties, especially for novel materials, can be challenging.

Figure 26

Mechanical properties of materials used for finite element analysis

Material	Young Modulus (MPa)	Poisson Ratio (ν)	Reference
Mini and conventional implants/ball attachment/housing (Ti 6Al 4V)	103 400	0.35	Liu et al. ⁴⁰
Overdentures	8.3	0.28	Daas et al. ³³
O-ring nylon conventional implant	2400	0.39	Barão et al. ²⁸
O-ring rubber mini implant	5	0.45	Chun et al. ³⁰
Mini implant housing (stainless steel)	19 000	0.31	Lanhoti et al. ³⁹
Cortical bone	13 700	0.35	Liu et al. ⁴⁰
Cancellous bone	1370	0.30	Liu et al. ⁴⁰
Mucosa	340	0.45	Barão et al. ²⁹

Note. From *Biomechanical behaviour of 2-implant–and single-implant–retained mandibular overdentures with conventional or mini implants*, by Pisani et al., (2018)

Early Identification of Potential Failures

- Structural assessment methods, such as NDT and analytical techniques, allow for the early detection of flaws, defects, or wear in assets. This early identification enables organizations to schedule proactive maintenance interventions before minor issues escalate into critical failures.
- Early detection minimizes risks associated with unexpected equipment failures. By addressing potential issues at their nascent stages, organizations significantly reduce the likelihood of sudden breakdowns or catastrophic failures, thereby mitigating safety risks and avoiding operational disruptions.
- Proactive maintenance interventions based on early identification of structural issues contribute to reduced downtime. By addressing problems before they escalate, organizations minimize unplanned shutdowns, maximizing operational uptime and productivity.

- Identifying and addressing issues early on prevents the need for extensive repairs or replacements. This proactive approach reduces overall maintenance costs, as small, manageable repairs are more cost-effective than dealing with larger, critical failures.

Ensuring Safe and Reliable Operation

Regular evaluations of structural integrity ensure that assets meet safety standards. By implementing assessment methods, organizations uphold safety protocols, preventing potential hazards that could compromise operational safety and risk the well-being of personnel.

Identifying structural weaknesses or potential failures in advance helps prevent accidents. By addressing these issues proactively, organizations create a safer work environment, reducing the risk of equipment-related accidents or malfunctions.

Structural assessment methods contribute to maintaining asset efficiency and longevity. Regular evaluations and timely interventions prolong asset life by addressing wear and tear, ensuring optimal performance, and reducing the likelihood of sudden failures.

In conclusion we would like to emphasize that these assessment methods not only ensure the structural soundness of equipment but also contribute significantly to proactive maintenance strategies, enabling organizations to forecast, plan, and execute maintenance tasks before issues escalate. The implementation of structural assessment methods in predictive maintenance is imperative for ensuring the longevity, reliability, and safety of critical assets. These methods, ranging from non-destructive testing to advanced analytical techniques, offer a proactive approach to identifying potential failures and addressing structural issues before they escalate. Real-world case studies underscore the effectiveness of these methods in various industries, emphasizing their role in minimizing downtime, optimizing maintenance resources, and upholding operational safety standards. As technology evolves, ongoing advancements in structural assessment methods will continue to shape a more resilient and efficient approach to asset management.

G. Forecasting Systems

Statistical Models and Predictive Analytics

Forecasting systems utilize statistical models and predictive analytics to anticipate potential equipment failures. These systems analyse historical data, patterns, and trends to forecast the probability of future failures or deviations from normal operational conditions.

- **Data Analysis Techniques:** Forecasting systems employ various statistical models and advanced analytics techniques, such as regression analysis, time series forecasting, machine learning algorithms, and artificial intelligence, to analyse historical maintenance data, equipment performance, and failure patterns.

Figure 27

Experience- and data-driven predictive maintenance

Note. From Predictive Maintenance and Intelligent Sensors in Smart Factory: Review, by Pech et al., (2021)

- **Pattern Recognition:** These systems identify patterns, correlations, and anomalies within the data. By recognizing trends and deviations, they create

predictive models that estimate the likelihood and timing of equipment failures or degradation.

Figure 28

Types of pattern recognition models

Note. From *Pattern Recognition in Machine Learning [Basics & Examples]*, by Baheti, (2022)

- **Continuous Learning:** Machine learning-based forecasting systems continuously learn from new data, improving prediction accuracy over time. They adapt to changing conditions, enabling more accurate forecasts as they accumulate additional information.

Figure 29

Four modules continual learning solution

Note. From *Continual learning for predictive maintenance: Overview and challenges*, by Hurtado et al., (2023)

Proactive Maintenance Planning

Accurate forecasts generated by these systems empower organizations to plan and schedule proactive maintenance activities. By predicting when equipment is likely to fail or require maintenance, maintenance tasks can be strategically scheduled, optimizing resources, and minimizing disruptions to operations.

- **Predictive Insights for Maintenance Scheduling:** Accurate forecasts derived from forecasting systems enable maintenance teams to proactively schedule maintenance tasks. These systems provide insights into when specific components or equipment are likely to require maintenance, allowing for timely interventions.

Figure 30

Combining the Power of Machine Learning & Decision Optimization for Maintenance Scheduling

Maintenance Scheduling: ML and DO Work Best Together

Note. From Predictive Maintenance Scheduling with AI and Decision Optimization, by Ageeva, (2018)

- **Resource Optimization:** Proactive planning optimizes the allocation of resources, such as manpower, spare parts, and equipment, by ensuring they are available when needed. This prevents underutilization or overextension of resources, improving overall operational efficiency.

Figure 31

Architecture of proposed predictive maintenance planning model

Note. From *Predictive maintenance planning for industry 4.0 using machine learning for sustainable manufacturing*, by Abidi et al., (2022)

Reduction of Unplanned Downtime

Forecasting systems play a critical role in minimizing unplanned downtime. By identifying potential failures in advance, organizations can take preventive measures, such as replacing worn components or performing maintenance during scheduled downtimes, thus avoiding unexpected equipment failures that disrupt operations.

- **Early Warning System:** Forecasting systems act as an early warning system, allowing maintenance teams to address potential failures before they occur. This proactive approach minimizes unexpected breakdowns, reducing unplanned downtime and associated production losses.

Figure 32

Predictive maintenance in a P-F curve

Note. From *Preventive Maintenance vs. Predictive Maintenance*, by HanAra Software, (n.d.)

- **Prescriptive Maintenance:** Some advanced forecasting systems not only predict failures but also provide recommendations on the most effective maintenance actions to take, optimizing the decision-making process for maintenance teams.

Figure 33

P-F Curve of Different Types of Maintenance

Note. From *Differences Between Condition-Based, Predictive, and Prescriptive Maintenance*, by Hanly, (n.d.)

Enhancement of Asset Reliability

The implementation of accurate forecasting systems enhances asset reliability. Anticipating and addressing potential issues before they escalate into failures ensures that assets remain in optimal working condition, contributing to improved overall reliability and performance.

- **Improved Asset Health Management:** By predicting and preventing failures, forecasting systems contribute to improved asset health management. Regular maintenance based on accurate forecasts ensures that assets remain in optimal working condition, thereby enhancing their reliability and longevity.

Figure 34

Asset maturity journey

Note. From *Asset Performance Management*, by Znapz, (n.d.)

- **Increased Operational Availability:** Reliable assets mean increased operational availability. Assets are available for production or operation when needed, contributing to higher overall productivity and reducing disruptions.

Figure 35

Inherent availability, Achievable availability & Operational availability

Note. Inherent availability (A_i): The expected level of availability for the performance of corrective maintenance only. Inherent availability is determined purely by the design of the equipment. It assumes that spare parts and manpower are 100 percent available with no delays. Achievable availability (A_a): The expected level of availability for the performance of corrective and preventive maintenance. Achievable availability is determined by the hard design of the equipment and the facility. A_a also assumes that spare parts and manpower are 100 percent available with no delays. Operational availability (A_o): The bottom line of availability. It is the actual level of availability realized in the day-to-day operation of the facility. It reflects plant maintenance resource levels and organizational effectiveness. From *Managing Availability for Improved Bottom-Line Results*, by Efficient Plant, (2003)

Cost Reduction and Resource Optimization

Proactive maintenance planning driven by forecasting systems helps in reducing operational costs. By strategically allocating resources, prioritizing maintenance tasks, and avoiding emergency repairs, organizations optimize their maintenance efforts and maximize the efficiency of their assets.

- **Cost-Effective Maintenance:** Proactive maintenance planning leads to cost savings by avoiding expensive emergency repairs and minimizing downtime. Planned maintenance tasks are often more cost-effective than reactive interventions.

Figure 36

Cost-Failure/Time chart

Note. Some assets probably call for earlier detection methods that come with higher prevention costs like condition monitoring and analytics systems due to the high cost to repair (see the Prevention-1 and Repair-1 curves in the Cost-Failure/Time chart). And some assets may be better suited for more cost-efficient but delayed detection or even a “run-to-failure” model due to lower cost to repair (the Prevention-2 and Repair-2 curves in the Cost-Failure/Time chart). From *Condition Monitoring & Predictive Maintenance: Cost-Benefit Tradeoffs*, by Knauer, (2022)

- **Efficient Resource Allocation:** These systems enable the efficient allocation of resources by directing them to the most critical areas. Resources are focused on tasks that directly impact asset performance, optimizing their utilization.

Figure 37

Efficient resource allocation

Note. From Capacity utilization: Optimizing Resources in Goods in Process, by Faster Capital, (2024)

Overall, forecasting systems in preventive maintenance leverage advanced analytics and predictive models to optimize maintenance planning, enhance asset reliability, reduce downtime, and streamline resource utilization, thereby significantly contributing to efficient and cost-effective maintenance strategies. Leveraging statistical models and predictive analytics, these systems enable proactive maintenance planning, reducing unplanned downtime and enhancing asset reliability. The cost-effectiveness of maintenance operations is improved through optimized resource allocation and efficient management of maintenance tasks. As organizations continue to embrace digital transformation, the integration of advanced forecasting systems will be integral in maintaining a competitive edge, fostering innovation, and ensuring the long-term sustainability of assets.

H. Remote Infrastructure Management

1. IoT, Cloud Solutions, and Remote Diagnostic Tools in Predictive Maintenance

Facilitating Monitoring from a Distance (IoT)

Internet of Things (IoT) devices are embedded within equipment, collecting real-time data on various parameters such as temperature, vibration, and performance metrics. These devices enable continuous monitoring, and the data they generate is transmitted to a centralized system. Imagine a manufacturing plant where each piece of machinery is equipped with IoT sensors. These sensors continuously monitor parameters such as temperature, pressure, and vibration. The data is then transmitted to a cloud-based platform where it is stored and analysed in real-time.

Pros:

- **Real-time Insights:** IoT sensors provide real-time data, allowing for immediate insights into equipment performance.
- **Data Centralization:** cloud solutions centralize data storage, making it easily accessible and analysable from anywhere with an internet connection.

Cons:

- **Initial Implementation Cost:** implementing IoT devices and setting up cloud infrastructure may have initial costs.
- **Data Security Concerns:** cloud storage raises concerns about data security, and organizations need robust measures to address potential risks.

IoT Integration steps:

- **Identify Critical Parameters:** determine which parameters are crucial for predictive maintenance in your specific industry or application.
- **Select Reliable IoT Sensors:** choose sensors that provide accurate and reliable data. Consider factors such as sensor accuracy, durability, and compatibility with existing equipment.
- **Implement Connectivity:** ensure that IoT sensors are connected to a secure network for data transmission. Utilize protocols such as MQTT or HTTP/HTTPS.

Cloud Solutions

Cloud-based platforms store and process the massive amounts of data generated by IoT devices. This centralized storage allows for efficient data analysis, predictive modelling, and easy access to information from anywhere with an internet connection. The data collected by IoT sensors is stored on a cloud platform, such as Amazon Web Services (AWS) or Microsoft Azure. This cloud-based storage allows maintenance teams to access and analyse the data from anywhere in the world, using a secure internet connection.

Cloud Solutions integration steps:

- **Choose a Cloud Platform:** select a cloud platform that aligns with your organization's requirements and preferences. Popular choices include AWS, Azure, Google Cloud, or industry-specific platforms.
- **Set Up Data Storage:** design a structured data storage architecture that accommodates the volume and variety of data generated by IoT sensors.
- **Implement Security Measures:** prioritize data security by implementing encryption, access controls, and compliance with relevant data protection standards.

Remote Diagnostic Tools

Advanced diagnostic tools utilize the data collected by IoT devices to assess the health and condition of equipment remotely. These tools can identify anomalies, patterns, or trends that may indicate potential issues or the need for maintenance. Utilizing the data from IoT sensors, remote diagnostic tools can analyse equipment health. For example, a predictive maintenance software could identify a gradual increase in vibration levels in a rotating machine, indicating potential bearing wear. Maintenance teams can receive alerts and diagnostic reports remotely.

Remote Diagnostic Tools integration steps

- **Select Appropriate Tools:** choose diagnostic tools that align with the types of equipment and sensors used in your predictive maintenance setup.

- Integrate with Cloud Data: ensure that diagnostic tools seamlessly integrate with the cloud platform to access real-time data for analysis.
- Train Maintenance Teams: provide training to maintenance teams on using diagnostic tools effectively to interpret results and make informed decisions.

2. Remote Access and Assistance for Timely Intervention

Real-time Monitoring

Through IoT and cloud solutions, maintenance teams gain real-time visibility into equipment status and performance. This information allows for proactive decision-making based on actual conditions rather than relying solely on scheduled maintenance. Maintenance teams receive real-time alerts and notifications regarding equipment status. For instance, if a critical temperature threshold is exceeded in an industrial oven, the team can be alerted immediately, allowing them to investigate and address the issue promptly.

Pros:

- Reduced Downtime: remote access enables quick troubleshooting and intervention, minimizing downtime.
- Expert Assistance: remote assistance allows experts to provide guidance without being physically present, improving problem-solving efficiency.

Cons:

- Dependence on Connectivity: reliance on network connectivity may pose challenges in remote or low-connectivity areas.
- Security Risks: remote access introduces security risks, requiring strong authentication and encryption measures.

Real-time Monitoring implementation steps:

- Implement Alert Systems: set up alert systems that notify maintenance teams in real-time when critical thresholds are breached.
- Utilize Visualization Tools: implement dashboards and visualization tools that provide a clear overview of equipment status, facilitating quick decision-making.

Remote Access

Maintenance professionals can remotely access equipment interfaces and control systems through secure connections. This access enables them to troubleshoot, diagnose issues, and perform adjustments without being physically present at the site. Engineers can remotely access the control systems of equipment. For instance, a HVAC system in a commercial building can be adjusted and optimized

remotely based on real-time data, ensuring energy efficiency and occupant comfort.

Remote Access implementation steps

- **Establish Secure Connections:** ensure that remote access is established through secure and encrypted channels to protect against unauthorized access.
- **Implement Two-Factor Authentication:** add an extra layer of security by implementing two-factor authentication for remote access.

Assistance through Augmented Reality (AR)

Using AR glasses or devices, on-site technicians can receive visual guidance from remote experts. For example, an AR overlay could guide a technician through the steps of replacing a faulty component in a complex machinery setup. Assistance through Augmented Reality (AR): AR technologies allow experts to provide remote assistance by overlaying digital information onto the physical environment. Maintenance personnel on-site can receive guidance, instructions, and annotations, enhancing their ability to address complex issues.

Augmented Reality (AR) implementation steps:

- **Invest in AR Technologies:** explore and invest in AR technologies such as smart glasses or AR-enabled devices suitable for your industry.
- **Develop Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs):** create SOPs for using AR tools during maintenance interventions. Train on-site personnel on proper usage.

3. Enhancing Operational Efficiency and Reducing On-site Resource Requirements

Timely Intervention

Remote monitoring and diagnostics enable timely intervention, addressing potential problems before they lead to equipment failures. This proactive approach minimizes downtime and disruption to operations. With remote monitoring and diagnostics, a maintenance team can identify a potential issue with a pump's performance. Instead of waiting for a scheduled maintenance visit, the team can plan a targeted intervention, minimizing downtime.

Pros:

- **Resource Optimization:** remote monitoring optimizes resource allocation by focusing efforts on critical areas.

- **Cost Savings:** proactive interventions and reduced on-site visits lead to cost savings in the long run.

Cons:

- **Technology Dependence:** heavy reliance on technology may create vulnerabilities in the event of system failures.
- **Skillset Requirements:** maintenance teams need the skills to utilize remote tools effectively, requiring training and development.

Timely Intervention implementation steps:

- **Establish Predictive Models:** develop predictive models based on historical data to anticipate when maintenance interventions are likely required.
- **Automate Alert Responses:** implement automated responses to alerts, such as initiating work orders or scheduling maintenance tasks.

Optimized Resource Allocation

With the ability to monitor and diagnose remotely, maintenance resources can be allocated more efficiently. Critical issues can be prioritized, and on-site visits can be scheduled based on actual equipment conditions, reducing unnecessary visits and associated costs. Maintenance schedules can be optimized based on actual equipment conditions. For instance, if a set of valves in a chemical processing plant requires attention, resources can be allocated specifically to address that issue, avoiding unnecessary visits to other well-functioning equipment.

Optimized Resource Allocation implementation steps:

- **Prioritize Maintenance Tasks:** use data-driven insights to prioritize maintenance tasks based on criticality and urgency.
- **Integrate with Maintenance Management Systems:** ensure seamless integration with maintenance management systems to facilitate resource allocation based on real-time needs.

Cost Reduction

By reducing the need for on-site visits and optimizing maintenance schedules, organizations can achieve cost savings. Remote monitoring and intervention contribute to overall operational efficiency, translating into financial benefits. By addressing issues proactively and optimizing on-site visits, organizations can achieve cost savings. For example, a wind farm may reduce the frequency of physical inspections on each turbine by using remote monitoring, resulting in reduced travel costs and increased overall operational efficiency.

Cost Reduction steps:

- Conduct Cost-Benefit Analysis: evaluate the cost savings associated with reduced on-site visits and improved operational efficiency.
- Monitor Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): track KPIs related to maintenance costs, downtime reduction, and resource optimization to measure the success of the implementation.

Remote infrastructure management stands as a linchpin in the era of predictive maintenance, revolutionizing the way organizations oversee and maintain their critical assets. The seamless integration of IoT, cloud solutions, and remote diagnostic tools facilitates real-time monitoring, timely interventions, and efficient troubleshooting from a distance. This not only enhances operational efficiency but also reduces the need for on-site resource requirements. As industries embrace the concept of Industry 4.0, the continued evolution of remote infrastructure management promises to drive smarter, more agile maintenance practices, ensuring organizations remain at the forefront of reliability, cost-effectiveness, and sustainable asset management.

I. Conclusions

In closing, this comprehensive exploration of predictive maintenance competences has delved into the intricacies of reporting models, structural assessment methods, forecasting systems, and remote infrastructure management. These elements collectively form a dynamic framework that empowers organizations to navigate the challenges of maintaining critical assets in an ever-evolving landscape.

Robust reporting models have emerged as the bedrock of informed decision-making, providing organizations with actionable insights and predictive analytics. The continuous integration of these models with cutting-edge technologies promises to elevate maintenance strategies, fostering optimized asset performance and minimizing downtime.

Structural assessment methods have proven indispensable in ensuring the reliability and safety of critical assets. From non-destructive testing to advanced analytical techniques, these methods offer a proactive stance against potential failures, contributing to operational efficiency and safety standards. As technology advances, the evolution of these methods will undoubtedly shape a resilient and efficient approach to asset management.

Forecasting systems have heralded a new era in predictive maintenance, enabling organizations to anticipate and mitigate potential equipment failures. Leveraging statistical models and predictive analytics optimizes resource allocation, reduces unplanned downtime, and enhances asset reliability. Embracing these systems is crucial for organizations aspiring to maintain a competitive edge and ensure the long-term sustainability of their assets.

Remote infrastructure management, exemplified by the seamless integration of IoT, cloud solutions, and remote diagnostic tools, stands as a transformative force. This approach revolutionizes real-time monitoring, timely interventions, and troubleshooting from a distance, ultimately enhancing operational efficiency, and reducing on-site resource requirements. As we embrace the era of Industry 4.0, the continued evolution of remote infrastructure management promises to drive smarter, more agile maintenance practices.

In the ever-evolving landscape of predictive maintenance, the journey doesn't end here. As organizations continue to embrace technological advancements, innovation, and sustainability, the competences outlined in this booklet will serve as a guiding compass. Let this handbook serve as a guiding beacon, empowering you to harness the transformative capabilities of predictive maintenance for a future of operational excellence.

May your path forward be marked by optimized efficiency, reliability and commitment to the future of maintenance excellence.

Thank you for embarking on this journey through the intricate yet fascinating world of Predictive Maintenance.

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PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education and training

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PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

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BOOKLET

Module WN2: Digital Skills competences for PM

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

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A. Introduction

In the era of Industry 4.0, digitalization has emerged as a transformative force, reshaping traditional paradigms of maintenance by ushering in a new era of efficiency, cost-effectiveness, and unprecedented insights. At the forefront of this revolution is the integration of digital technologies into predictive maintenance strategies. Predictive maintenance, a proactive approach to equipment upkeep, aims to anticipate machinery failures before they occur, thereby minimising downtime and optimising operational performance (KSB, 2023).

Digitalization in predictive maintenance encapsulates the convergence of advanced technologies, data analytics, and connectivity to propel maintenance practices into the future. Central to this shift is the proliferation of sensors, Internet of Things (IoT) devices, and smart monitoring systems embedded in machinery, generating a wealth of real-time data. This data, once harnessed and analysed, becomes a powerful tool for predicting equipment health, detecting anomalies, and ultimately, preventing costly breakdowns.

This trend can be observed in various sectors where predictive maintenance has already been established, such as multiple transportation modes (UITP, 2020), infrastructure for power generation (Ervin, 2022), industrial and chemical processes, light/heavy manufacturing operations and many more. As an example, the digitalisation of PM in the transportation industry can provide vehicle and vessel operators with a variety of data science that can prioritise a vessel's maintenance schedule, increase fuel efficiency, reduce crew time and costs, meet regulatory compliance goals and analyse the data generated from a vessel's various digital maintenance records. (SATAIR, 2023)

During the last few years, digital skills are important to work, learn, entertain and generally live in a modern environment. In Europe, 1 in 4 people (aged 16-74) had low level of digital skills and 1 in 6 people (aged 16-74) had no skills at all¹. On the other hand, digital skills are necessary for 90% of jobs and in Europe, the open vacancies for ICT specialist are more than 400,000². More specifically, digital skills are essential for jobs in Predictive Maintenance as data, analytical approaches and technological equipment are utilised to predict when maintenance is needed to mitigate risks and avoid failures. Towards the purpose, improved and functional digital skills of employees and labour force answer to the industry demand that involves several aspects such as the understanding of large data sets and IoT, the knowledge of sensor equipment for collecting real-time data, the development of predictive models using machine learning and AI techniques, and cybersecurity to protect sensitive data and ensure the integrity of PM systems.

¹ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/digital-skills-and-jobs-coalition-nutshell>

² <https://ec.europa.eu/social/BlobServlet?docId=21163&langId=en>

The PreMETS initiative plays a pivotal role in shaping the future of Predictive Maintenance by addressing crucial gaps in innovation, expertise, and training. This documentation provides an extensive list of digital skills which are identified as key topics in which future employees in predictive maintenance should have a solid knowledge background and be aware of. The modules described in this report cover a wide range of digital competences, from technical proficiency to data analysis, cloud computing, and beyond. These skills form the foundation for leveraging technology effectively. As the Fourth Industrial Revolution unfolds, proficiency in signal processing, machine learning, and emerging technologies like IoT and blockchain become indispensable.

B. Types of Maintenance & Role of Digitalisation

Condition-Based Maintenance

Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM) is a maintenance strategy that relies on real-time monitoring and assessment of the condition of equipment to determine when maintenance activities should be performed. Instead of adhering to fixed schedules or running equipment until failure (preventive maintenance), CBM leverages continuous monitoring and data analysis to identify signs of potential issues and triggers maintenance actions when necessary. The goal is to perform maintenance tasks only when there is evidence that the equipment's condition is deviating from its normal or healthy state (Reliasol, 2021).

Figure 1

Types of Maintenance

Note. From *Why is Condition Monitoring not always enough and why is Predictive Maintenance worth implementing?*, by Reliasol, 2021 (<https://reliasol.ai/condition-monitoring-vs-predictive-maintenance/>)

Condition-Based Maintenance vs. Predictive Maintenance

Predictive and condition-based maintenance (PM / CbM) are both maintenance types that occur before breakdowns happen. As such, they are both forms of proactive maintenance and are designed to increase reliability and decrease downtime.

The primary difference between them is the way in which maintenance is measured. Predictive maintenance relies on precise formulas in addition to sensor measurements (temperature, vibration, noise), and maintenance work is performed based on the analysis of these parameters. In this way, predictive maintenance is a very exact form of maintenance because it predicts future maintenance events.

On the other hand, condition-based maintenance relies only on real-time sensor measurements. Once a parameter reaches an unacceptable level, maintenance workers are dispatched. This means that condition-based maintenance systems perform work only in the moment it is needed (UpKeep, 2022).

Table 1

Difference between state-of-the-art types of maintenance.

	Preventive Maintenance (PM)	Condition-based Maintenance (CBM)
Definition	Combines data from sensor devices with precise formulas to predict when condition-based maintenance is needed.	Perform maintenance tasks at the exact moment when needed.
Workflow ³	<p>The Predictive Maintenance Workflow diagram shows a sequence of steps: 1. Connect Sensors to Assets, 2. Collect Data from Sensors, 3. Identify Baselines and Set Parameters, 4. Run Asset as Usual, 5. Sensor Detects Performance Anomaly, 6. Create Work Order and Perform Maintenance. The flow is indicated by arrows connecting these steps in a loop.</p>	<p>The Condition-Based Maintenance Workflow diagram shows a sequence of steps: 1. Determine Baseline Standards, 2. Install Sensors to Monitor Conditions, 3. Collect & Monitor Data, 4. Identify Conditional Data Anomalies, 5. Create Corrective Action Work Order, 6. Perform Corrective Maintenance. The flow is indicated by arrows connecting these steps in a loop.</p>
Trigger	Predicted failure modes	Exact condition of an asset
Cost	Medium/High	Medium/High (capital cost)
Cost Savings	25% to 30%	Depends on the number of assets

³ <https://www.getmaintainx.com/learning-center/condition-based-vs-predictive-maintenance/>

Resources Needed	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance software for scheduling • Maintenance scheduler (for larger organisations) • Condition monitoring software • Condition monitoring tools and sensors • PM training 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance software for dispatching technicians and creating work orders • Condition monitoring software • Condition monitoring tools and sensors • CbM training
Advantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance need is predicted in advance • Reduces maximum amount of downtime • Improved automation of maintenance tasks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Maintenance work is performed only as needed • Fewer unplanned downtime events • Improved prioritization of maintenance time
Disadvantages	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Expensive to implement and maintain • Time-intensive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • High cost of installation, training, and maintenance • Difficult to choose proper sensor equipment

Note. From Why is Condition Monitoring not always enough and why is Predictive Maintenance worth implementing? by Upkeep, 2022 (<https://upkeep.com/learning/predictive-condition-based/>)

Summary of Predictive Maintenance Technologies

CBM employs a variety of condition monitoring technologies, depending on the type of equipment and the industry. In Table 2 a summary of several key PM techniques that will be further explained during this module is shown.

Table 2

Summary table of different methodologies of predictive maintenance

Type	Methodology
Vibration (Signal)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fast Fourier transform • Support vector machine and k-nearest neighbour • IoT-enabled sensors • Backpropagation neural network models • Convolutional neural network
Thermography	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Thermographic images with thermographic camera • Thermography for detecting the failure states of photovoltaic modules • Active thermographic inspection

Tribology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Random forests, feed-forward neural networks and logistic regression model • Deep convolutional learning methods and residual neural networks • Infrared spectroscopy • Degradation model • Wiener and Ornstein-Uhlenbeck • Statistical analysis
Visual Inspection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Peripheral vision (luminance) • Pictorial examples for visual comparison • Pan-tilt-zoom cameras • Wearable augmented reality devices • Image processing methodologies
Ultrasonic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pattern recognition algorithm • Ultrasonic transducer • Root cause analysis • Finite element analysis

Note. From *Digitalization of Predictive Maintenance*, by PowerMI (2018) (<https://power-mi.com/content/digitalization-predictive-maintenance>)

Figure 2
Benefits of Predictive Maintenance

Note. From *What is Predictive Maintenance in the Manufacturing Sector and What Are the Benefits?* by Tesseract Academy (n.d.), (<https://tesseract.academy/what-is-predictive-maintenance-in-the-manufacturing-sector-and-what-are-the-benefits/>)

C. Data utilisation in Predictive Maintenance

Quality of the used data can influence how successful predictive maintenance will be. Data used for predictive maintenance can come from different heterogeneous sources such as equipment (machine and process data), product (product quality data), customer (customer features, feedback data, suggestions), and environment (weather information, indoor temperature, humidity, noises). This data is collected, transmitted and stored, and later, it is processed and analysed. This collected data is typically time-series or spatial data. Time-series data is recorded in some time intervals, and may include recording variables such as temperature, pressure, chemical concentrations, etc. On the other hand, spatial data may include details on the physical location or a layout in a given space. An example of spatial data is images from optical sensors (Namuduri et al., 2020).

Collected data can be stored in different formats - structured, semi-structured and unstructured data. Structured data is highly organized quantitative data and are typically stored in databases or spreadsheets. Structured data may include numerical values, sensor readings, operational parameters, etc. Structured data are easily processed and analysed using traditional methods and tools. On the other hand, semi-structured data is not completely raw or unstructured and it does contain some structural elements. Semi-structured data does not follow a strict format or schema and its structural elements such as tags and metadata make this type of data easier for analysis. An example of semi-structured data are XML documents (eXtensible Markup Language). In intelligent manufacturing systems, semantic web technology is often employed for handling semi-structured data. This involves tagging or annotating data with ontology concepts, which provides a standardized way of interpreting and understanding the information. By doing so, the data becomes more accessible and can be integrated into the overall knowledge framework of the system. Unstructured data poses a unique challenge as it does not have a predefined data model and is typically not organized in a tabular format. Unstructured data can include information such as voice signals, video surveillance footage, and other non-standardized sources. Because of different sources, formats, dimensions and other factors, in order to be able to extract useful information, data should be transferred to structured data. Structuring data in industrial environments requires feature extraction and expert knowledge in related application areas. For example, in manufacturing videos the goal might be to analyse an operator's efficiency and environmental safety. This involves building models for target (operator) detection and tracking through noise elimination, information rehabilitation, and enhancement (Yan et al., 2017).

Even though data can be collected from various sources, there are three commonly used methods to collect data about machine and equipment health and performance: Internet of Things (IoT) sensors, condition monitoring, and equipment history logs. When these three sources are integrated, predictive maintenance strategies can produce useful information that can help enhance equipment reliability, prevent failures, and optimize maintenance practices. Using IoT sensors to collect real-time data from equipment and machinery is one of the primary methods for data acquisition in predictive maintenance. IoT sensors are strategically placed on the equipment and their environment to monitor specific parameters such as temperature, vibration, pressure, humidity, and energy consumption. Sensor data is collected and transmitted to a data storage location, which is typically a cloud-based platform or an edge system, where data is stored and analysed. The obtained information from this data helps to detect deviations from normal operating conditions, recognize anomalies and predict possible device failures.

Condition monitoring uses specialized equipment and techniques to assess the condition of equipment and detect early signs of failure or degradation. Various techniques are used for condition monitoring: (i) measurement of vibration levels and frequencies to detect anomalies that indicate bearing wear, misalignment or imbalance; (ii) use of infrared cameras to detect temperature variations and identify hotspots that indicate potential electrical or mechanical issues; (iii) examination of samples to detect contaminants, lubrication breakdown, or wear particles that provide information about the condition of the equipment; (iv) use of ultrasonic testing to detect high frequency sound waves emitted by the equipment to detect leaks, friction and other anomalies; (v) use of thermal imaging cameras to capture temperature patterns and identify abnormal heat signatures that indicate possible equipment failures.

Another important method of data collection is using equipment history logs. These logs provide a comprehensive record of maintenance activities, repairs, replacements and performance metrics for each asset. Maintenance teams document details such as maintenance dates, tasks performed, parts replaced and any reported issues or failures. Equipment history logs provide a historical perspective on equipment maintenance by showing recurring issues, failure patterns and overall equipment performance over time. Analysing these logs helps identify maintenance trends, evaluate the effectiveness of past maintenance strategies and make informed decisions about future maintenance actions.

Once the data is collected, it needs to be transformed into a meaningful and usable format for model training. The data associated with each predictive maintenance problem has specific characteristics. For example, data related to fault detection is usually very unbalanced, as the information about faulty situations is much less frequent than the one about fault-free situations. In general, the properties of the data should be taken into account when choosing a preprocessing strategy. Data

transformation involves several steps, which all lead to allowing the enhancement of modelling capabilities (Cernuda, 2019):

1. Data cleaning - it is used to handle incomplete, redundant and noisy data. Collected data often contains noise, outliers, and redundant or irrelevant features. In order to prepare the data for further processing, e.g., by ML algorithms, it is necessary to remove noise, outliers and irrelevant features.
2. Data normalization - data collected from heterogeneous sources can have different scales and ranges. Data normalization, also known as homogenization, ensures that the algorithms are not affected by these variations.
3. Data transformation - data transformation involves the application of functions to the data. These functions are selected based on the system from which the data originates and the predictive maintenance actions required. For example, in predictive maintenance of industrial machinery, understanding the relationship between chemical composition and spectroscopic data can lead to beneficial transformations for subsequent monitoring techniques.
4. Missing values handling – collected data may contain missing values for various reasons, however it may not be appropriate to simply ignore missing values. The approach to handling missing values may include deleting records with missing values (deletion), replacing missing values with estimated values (imputation), using the values of other variables to estimate the missing values (interpolation), a statistical method that involves using the values of other variables to predict the missing values (regression), etc. The choice of an approach for handling missing values depends on factors such as sample size and data characteristics.
5. Feature engineering – this step includes feature selection (determining important features based on quality criteria), feature extraction (creating new features from the original ones), and discretization (transforming continuous features into discrete features using bins).
6. Dealing with imbalanced data - if certain sample types are extremely rare compared to others (minority class), then one faces a problem of imbalanced learning. Some of the possible approaches to solve the imbalanced data are to give more importance to the samples from the minority class or to balance the data somehow.

Each of these preprocessing steps contributes to the overall improvement of modelling capabilities, with goals such as increased accuracy, improved robustness, reduced computation time, reduced memory and computational power requirements, and minimized financial costs. The specific preprocessing strategy that is chosen depends on the characteristics of the data and the requirements of the predictive maintenance task. The goal is to create robust and accurate models that can adapt to the dynamic nature of the systems involved in predictive maintenance.

In a predictive maintenance setting, it is useful to have a cloud-based platform where data is stored, processed and analysed. Various algorithms can be run on this platform in order to obtain useful information on equipment and machinery, including historical and real-time data. Even though a cloud-based platform has its benefits in regard to reducing cost, allowing easier data access, providing remote access, easier and faster software upgrades, it still poses some challenges that can improve processing data in real-time and improve on-site performance of data processing. Edge computing tries to mitigate these issues by bringing data processing closer to sensors and where data is generated and collected, however, edge devices do not always have the compute and storage resources required for advanced analytics. This is the reason why the hybrid solutions are taken into consideration, where cloud solutions are used to handle data-intensive and time-critical processes, edge computing is used more on premise to handle real-time data processing. Furthermore, edge computing can be used to reduce latency and increase data processing on-site, while long-term storage, cost effectiveness and demanding high computing power can be provided by cloud. Decisions about which data will be analysed on premise in real time, which data requires long-term storage and analysis on cloud, and which does not need to be analysed at all is of great importance. Dynamic development of devices, technologies and requirements of predictive maintenance calls for careful consideration about different technology integration.

D. Emerging technologies in Predictive Maintenance

Predictive Maintenance (PM) continues to evolve with advancements in technology. Several emerging technologies are shaping the future of PM, enhancing its capabilities and enabling more accurate predictions of equipment failures. Here are some notable emerging technologies in Predictive Maintenance:

Digital Twins

Digital twin is a key enabling technology, and it is the virtual representation of physical objects, processes and real-time data involved in the entire product life cycle (Wu et al., 2020). Its concept first appeared in Greives's speech on the concept of Product Lifecycle Management (PLM) in 2002. The digital twin has the characteristics of interactive feedback between cyberspace and physical space, data fusion and analysis, and decision-making iteration optimization. It can be applied to a variety of scenarios. In industrial manufacturing enterprises, digital twins are used to optimize the manufacturing life cycle and promote intelligent manufacturing upgrade (Wu et al., 2020), which has become a research hotspot in the area of intelligent manufacturing (Tao et al., 2017). Driven by the needs of various industries, the latest application areas of digital twin have been extended to electric power, automobiles, medical care, ships, etc. (Tao et al., 2019).

Figure 3

Predictive maintenance workflow

Note. From *Predictive Maintenance Using a Digital Twin*, by Miller, (2019)

In the context of predictive maintenance, digital twins are used to create a virtual model of an asset or piece of equipment. This virtual model is continuously updated with real-time data from sensors and other sources, providing a dynamic and accurate reflection of the physical asset's condition. The use of digital twins in predictive maintenance offers several benefits, including improved monitoring, analysis, and decision-making. Here are some key aspects of the use of digital twins in predictive maintenance, along with examples from different industries:

1. Continuous Monitoring.

Digital twins enable continuous monitoring of equipment and systems in real-time, capturing data on various parameters.

Example: In manufacturing, a digital twin of a production line can monitor the performance of individual machines, tracking parameters such as temperature, vibration, and energy consumption.

2. Performance Analysis:

Digital twins allow for in-depth performance analysis by comparing real-time data against the expected behaviour defined in the virtual model.

Example: In the energy sector, a digital twin of a wind turbine can analyse actual power output, wind conditions, and mechanical stresses to assess the turbine's performance and predict potential faults.

3. Predictive Maintenance Planning:

By combining real-time data with historical performance information, digital twins facilitate predictive maintenance planning by forecasting when maintenance activities should be performed.

Example: In aviation, a digital twin of an aircraft engine can predict component wear and recommend maintenance actions, optimizing the scheduling of inspections and repairs.

4. Scenario Simulation:

Digital twins enable the simulation of various scenarios, allowing organizations to assess the impact of different operating conditions on equipment health.

Example: In the transportation industry, a digital twin of a fleet of vehicles can simulate the effects of different driving conditions, helping optimize maintenance schedules and fuel efficiency.

5. Proactive Fault Detection:

Digital twins can detect anomalies and deviations from normal operating conditions, providing early warnings of potential faults.

Example: In healthcare, a digital twin of a medical imaging device can monitor factors like temperature and calibration, alerting technicians to deviations that may indicate impending malfunctions.

6. Remote Monitoring and Diagnostics:

Digital twins facilitate remote monitoring and diagnostics, allowing experts to assess equipment health from a distance and guide on-site personnel.

Example: In the mining industry, a digital twin of a drilling rig can be monitored remotely, with experts using the virtual model to diagnose issues and recommend maintenance actions.

7. Lifecycle Management:

Digital twins support the entire lifecycle of an asset, from design and construction to operation and maintenance, providing a comprehensive view of the asset's history.

Example: In the construction industry, a digital twin of a building can be used to track structural health, energy usage, and maintenance needs throughout its lifespan.

8. Resource Optimization:

Digital twins aid in optimizing resources by providing insights into equipment health, allowing organizations to allocate maintenance resources more efficiently.

Example. In the manufacturing sector, a digital twin of a production facility can optimize the maintenance schedule of machines, minimizing downtime and maximizing productivity.

The use of digital twins in predictive maintenance enhances the ability of organizations to make informed decisions, reduce downtime, and optimize maintenance strategies across diverse industries. The examples provided demonstrate the versatility of digital twins in improving asset management and operational efficiency. Indicative predictive maintenance workflows, including tests with all possible fault combinations and faults of varying severity as illustrated in Figure 4 below.

Figure 4

Digital twin implementation framework in Predictive Maintenance in manufacturing industry

Note. From *Overview of predictive maintenance based on digital twin technology*, by Zhong et al. (2023)

Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR)

Augmented reality (AR)

Augmented reality (AR) is technology that adds information to the existing real-world environment in which a technician is present. Augmented reality is enabled through tools such as connected goggles or glasses. In most cases, AR will overlay details about what the technician is viewing. Augmented reality draws information from data sources in order to provide an effective “heads-up” view of the manufacturing environment, helping the technician to make fast, accurate decisions using the full scope of information at hand. In augmented reality, the technician can use hand gestures and other methods to interact with the information being presented.

Figure 5

Digital twin implementation framework in Predictive Maintenance in manufacturing industry

Note. From *How AR & VR are Transforming Maintenance in Manufacturing*, by ATS (2023), (<https://www.advancedtech.com/blog/ar-vr-and-mixed-reality-in-manufacturing-maintenance/>)

The key differentiator of augmented reality is that it focuses exclusively on the environment in which the technician is located — including the machines, processes, products and people — and adds (or augments) information to facilitate more effective operations (ATS, 2023).

Virtual reality (VR)

Virtual reality presents a view of an environment different from that in which the technician or viewer is located — and can even present an environment that does not exist at all. Virtual reality is typically facilitated through a headset and enables full interaction with the “virtual” environment being presented.

Virtual reality is most frequently used to facilitate a close analogue of interaction with a real-world element such as a part, component or machine. The key differentiator of virtual reality is that it places the user in an environment completely separate from that in which they are currently located (ATS, 2023).

Mixed reality

Mixed reality combines elements of augmented reality and virtual reality to varying degrees. A mixed reality implementation will almost always lean further toward one type of technology or the other while incorporating elements of both. In mixed reality, the technician might see and interact with elements of the environment in which they are present, with augmented reality and virtual reality elements present as well (ATS, 2023).

Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR) are immersive technologies that overlay or create virtual elements in the real world. In the context of predictive maintenance, VR and AR have valuable applications in enhancing training, troubleshooting, and remote assistance. Maintenance technicians can use AR glasses to access real-time information about equipment, visualize potential issues, and receive step-by-step guidance for repairs. Here's an overview of their use in predictive maintenance, along with examples from different industries:

Benefits & uses of augmented reality (AR) in maintenance

AR in maintenance offers a number of benefits, including:

- Generally unobtrusive, hands-free technology such as goggles or glasses
- A lower barrier to entry, since the tools overlay information on top of the existing work environment
- Real-time, easy access to data, including machine health, troubleshooting, training and more
- Quick access to historical maintenance data on the plant floor
- Transmits institutional knowledge from experienced to new technicians
- Real-time, interactive training and upskilling
- More accessible maintenance tasks for technicians who may not be as familiar with certain types of equipment

Uses of AR include:

- Real-time, at a glance performance data for equipment, presented through a heads-up display
- Information about personnel on the floor, including availability, specialization, training and more
- Step-by-step maintenance instructions

- Facilitation of fast, effective decision making when maintenance needs are identified
- Easy insight into potential failure conditions for equipment, enabling more proactive and predictive maintenance processes
- More effective training processes, providing a more interactive environment for technicians
- Facilitation of maintenance processes for personnel who may not be as familiar with equipment

Benefits & uses of virtual reality (VR) in maintenance

Benefits of VR in maintenance include:

- Virtual access to parts, components, equipment and machinery from anywhere in the world, with full interaction capabilities
- Reduced costs for travel and on-site visits
- The ability to virtually represent parts, products and components that may not actually exist yet, based on technical drawings and data
- More effective communication among manufacturers and customers, with the ability to discuss and look at components in a “real world” setting rather than a technical drawing or CAD model
- Fully immersive training with risk-free, “hands-on” processes where neither the employee nor equipment is at risk of errors

Virtual reality can be used for a number of applications in manufacturing, including:

- The vetting and inspection of processes from anywhere, without the need to be on-site
- Interaction with parts that may be too large or heavy to efficiently transport
- Interaction with parts that have not yet been built
- Planning for floor footprint layouts and facility redesigns
- Part and component design
- Training of new hires and upskilling of technicians on staff, enabling more effective learning processes

Benefits & uses of mixed reality in maintenance

Mixed reality, in many ways, offers the best of both worlds from virtual reality and augmented reality. Mixed reality benefits include:

- Full interactivity with on-site equipment, as well as virtual equipment representations
- Access to a more geographically diverse workforce, without the need to seek technicians in the local area
- Real-time communication among staff located anywhere in the world, where everyone is looking at the same thing
- Error reduction
- More efficient maintenance

Mixed reality uses include:

- Building a technical workforce located nearly anywhere in the world, with the ability to communicate as if they were in the same room together
- Step-by-step maintenance training and facilitation of maintenance processes
- More effective and efficient work tracking
- More efficient guidance in personnel and process management
- Real-time communication among technicians, management and other stakeholders

Drones and Robotics:

Drones equipped with sensors and cameras are increasingly used for inspecting and monitoring equipment in hard-to-reach or hazardous locations. Similarly, robotics can be employed for routine maintenance tasks, reducing the need for human intervention in high-risk environments. Exoskeleton technology is being explored to assist maintenance technicians by reducing physical strain during equipment inspections and repairs. These wearable devices can enhance worker safety and productivity.

As technology continues to advance, the integration of these emerging technologies into Predictive Maintenance systems holds the promise of more proactive, efficient, and cost-effective maintenance strategies for industries across the spectrum. The synergy of these technologies aims to transform maintenance practices from reactive to predictive, minimising downtime and optimising resource utilisation.

Real-world cases highlighting the benefits of emerging technologies usage in Predictive Maintenance

- Rolls-Royce turns to digital twins to improve jet engine efficiency: <https://www.cio.com/article/188765/rolls-royce-turns-to-digital-twins-to-improve-jet-engine-efficiency.html>
- ABB predictive maintenance on electric motors - low power motors; https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cFIY6L1igKY&ab_channel=ABBMotorsandGenerators
- GE Digital Twin for Local/District Power Grid Optimization & Utilization: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5Ji8dZqkECM&ab_channel=GEPower
- Digital Twin of a Wind Turbine Power Train: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lp2yML_tyUA&ab_channel=TECNALIA
- BMW Group Celebrates Opening the World's First Virtual Factory: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=g78YHYXXils&ab_channel=NVIDIA
- Augmented Reality for aircraft maintenance, remote support and training: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=O7dXn9u2WEc&ab_channel=OVA
- US Air Force Aircraft Maintenance Training with Augmented Reality: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=CxoczR8-mwU&ab_channel=Taqtile
- Augmented & Virtual Reality(AR/VR) Based Interactive Engineering Training: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mwrHkbLCHP0&ab_channel=Learningby3dinVET
- Rolls-Royce's Virtual Reality Jet Engine Familiarization Class: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Y8qJ3eps-xs&ab_channel=AviationInternationalNews
- Vasile Pleșca and Cristian Purece's study (Pleșca & Purece, 2020), where the Predictive maintenance operations of photovoltaic plants using multirotor drones are examined in Romania: https://www.e3s-conferences.org/articles/e3sconf/abs/2020/40/e3sconf_te-re-rd2020_02007/e3sconf_te-re-rd2020_02007.html
- EYES IN THE SKY AND SEA: NEW OPPORTUNITIES FOR DRONE USE IN INSPECTION: <https://marine-offshore.bureauveritas.com/insight/business-insights/new-opportunities-drone-use-inspection>

E. Cybersecurity & Ethical Considerations

1. Importance of cybersecurity in protecting predictive maintenance systems

In the context of Industry 4.0, IoT and other intelligent devices play a crucial role in predictive maintenance systems which enlist internet-based services including cloud computing and advanced data analytics (Kanawaday & Sane, 2017). These arrangements continuously observe equipment conditions with sensors that accumulate vast quantities of data to predict possible failures before they come about—favourably improving operational efficiency but at once exposing industrial constituents to new risks. With such reliance on digital technologies alongside profound assimilation of sensitive information, cybersecurity stands not as an elective measure but rather emerges as an indispensable prerequisite for these systems. Cybersecurity in this context serves as the barricade against potential cyber-attacks that can lead to data breaches, operational disruptions, and even catastrophic failures (Compare et al., 2019; Achouch et al., 2022).

The importance of cybersecurity in predictive maintenance systems cannot be overstated. With the increasing sophistication and integration of these systems into industrial operations, safeguarding them against cyber threats has become imperative. Robust cybersecurity measures are necessary to uphold data confidentiality, integrity and availability - all critical components that ensure successful execution of predictive maintenance processes. Effective implementation of such measures mitigates financial losses as well as operational disruptions while enhancing overall safety and resilience within industrial ecosystems.

The significance of cybersecurity in safeguarding predictive maintenance systems is manifold. Primarily, the preservation of data integrity assumes paramount importance (Achouch et al., 2022). A cyber intrusion compromising the same could result in wrong predictions that may precipitate unprecedented equipment failures, ineffective upkeep schedules and hazardous circumstances. For instance, any modifications made to temperature-related information can hinder identification of a critically high-temperature problem thereby resulting in potential breakdowns or worse still workplace mishaps (Khan & Madnick, 2021).

Moreover, the importance of cybersecurity cannot be overstated as it is imperative for maintaining uninterrupted operation. Industrial systems, particularly those utilized in critical infrastructure such as power plants and water treatment facilities are progressively incorporating predictive maintenance (Fausing Olesen & Shaker,

2020). A cyber intrusion within these settings carries not only the potential to disrupt normal maintenance functions but also has far-reaching implications on public safety and economy by causing breakdowns in essential services (Elmaghraby & Losavio, 2014).

In addition, it is important to note that predictive maintenance systems frequently operate as components within expansive interconnected networks. These networks often involve the exchange of information between various departments and may even extend to external entities such as equipment manufacturers and maintenance contractors. While this interconnectivity can enhance operational effectiveness, it simultaneously enlarges a system's attack surface; thus compelling the implementation of thorough cybersecurity measures not only for safeguarding prediction systems but also for fortifying overall network security (Lee et al., 2019).

The secure incorporation of cybersecurity into predictive maintenance systems extends beyond safeguarding data and technological assets, as its overarching objective is to secure the operational ecosystem at large (Karampidis et al., 2019). As sophisticated predictive maintenance technologies continue expanding in prevalence and sophistication, addressing cyber threats proactively takes on an increasingly pivotal role in guaranteeing safe and effective system functionality. Organizations that prioritize proactivity regarding their cybersecurity challenges can derive both asset-protection benefits while simultaneously establishing confidence with stakeholders - thereby contributing towards a more dependable industrial future overall (Alqudhaibi et al., 2023).

2. Data Ethics Principles and Best Practices in Maintenance: A Guiding Framework

The principal dependence on data-driven decision-making in diverse industries for maintenance processes emphasizes the significance of data ethics. These encompassing sets of principles and practices enable responsible handling, collection, and use of information. In pursuing adherence to these tenets within maintenance operations guarantees trustworthiness, compliance with regulations as well as safeguarding stakeholder interests (Hand, 2018; Mühlhoff, 2021; Chang, 2021).

In maintenance operations, transparency regarding data collection and utilization is crucial. It is imperative to keep all stakeholders, inclusive of employees, customers, and partners apprised on the details pertaining to what information is being amassed along with how it will be employed as well as for which purposes. Such an approach characterized by open communication inspires confidence among stakeholder groups while also facilitating compliance with regulatory standards. Simultaneously paramount are accountability measures whereby

entities must undertake ethical management of collected data whilst remaining poised to handle any issues precipitated through its misuse proactively.

Acquiring unequivocal authorization from individuals whose data is gathered constitutes a fundamental principle of ethical conduct regarding data. In the context of maintenance, such information may encompass personal details pertinent to equipment users or records obtained through devices situated in private locales. Safeguarding privacy entails not only protecting against unauthorized entry but also upholding confidentiality standards and utilizing said material exclusively for its intended purpose.

Maintaining high standards of data quality and integrity is crucial for efficient maintenance. This necessitates the assurance of accurate, comprehensive, and dependable data. Inadequate data quality can result in erroneous decisions regarding upkeep measures that may lead to equipment malfunctions or safety hazards. To preserve the reliability of information, systematic assessments and validation procedures must be established through regular audits.

In order to adhere to ethical data practices, it is imperative that all data sources and subjects are treated fairly and devoid of any partiality. This pertains specifically to maintenance which requires the creation of algorithms and processed-data designs free from biases capable of leading towards unequal treatment or discriminatory outcomes. It becomes necessary then, for these systems to undergo regular reviews in ensuring their continued upholding as impartial with a complete absence of bias influence.

The management of data in maintenance should encompass a holistic perspective that takes into account the wider social and environmental implications. Such considerations involve utilizing data not solely to enhance efficacy and mitigate expenditures, but also to curtail negative ecological effects while fostering positive societal contributions. Predictive maintenance data serves as an illustrative example since it can be employed towards energy optimization which reduces carbon emissions stemming from operations.

The incorporation of data ethics principles into maintenance can foster a sustainable, reliable and socially responsible approach. Embracing these optimal techniques ensures that organizations' maintenance procedures are not only productive and proficient but also adhere to ethical standards while upholding broader societal values.

3. Navigating Regulatory Compliance and Data Protection Standards in the Digital Age

Compliance with regulatory and data protection standards has never been more essential in today's increasingly interconnected world where information traverses freely across geographical borders and industries (Phillips, 2018). For companies, especially those that handle sensitive customer data or work within regulated domains, observing and comprehending these regulations is not merely a legal duty but also an integral aspect of building trustworthiness and maintaining integrity.

Understanding the Regulatory Landscape:

Data protection regulations are intricate and differ noticeably based on geographical areas and fields. Regulations such as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) in European Union, California Consumer Privacy Act (CCPA) in United States, etc., have established strict ethical values for data security (Goddard, 2017; Williams, 2020; Barrett, 2019). These guidelines require businesses to adhere to specific stipulations when gathering, preserving, handling or disseminating private data of individuals. In order to prevent significant fines or legal issues due to noncompliance with regulations particularized for their kind of enterprise operation must be marked precisely by companies while ensuring that they authentically meet compliance requirements without infringement challenges.

Data Protection and Privacy Standards:

In order to comply with regulations, it is imperative that data privacy be safeguarded and security measures implemented. These must include robust cybersecurity protocols in place to prevent unauthorized access, breaches or theft of sensitive information through encryption, controlled access methods such as password protection while maintaining regular audits on the system. Furthermore, businesses need adhere ethical practices involving transparent use of collected data for specific purposes so customers' confidentiality can remain intact.

Compliance as an Ongoing Process:

Maintaining regulatory compliance requires ongoing effort rather than a once-and-done task. As legal and standard requirements keep changing, along with evolving cyber risks, organizations must consistently evaluate and upgrade their adherence strategies. To achieve this end, they should provide regular employee training sessions while revising policies regularly besides keeping track of the latest data protection best practices and regulatory changes to stay informed.

The Role of Compliance Officers and Team:

Organizations often designate compliance officers or teams who are responsible for supervising regulatory compliance and safeguarding data. These experts have a crucial function of monitoring adherence, performing internal audits, and

guaranteeing that all business practices align with applicable legal requirements and benchmarks.

Balancing Compliance with Business Objectives:

Although compliance is crucial, it needs to be weighed against the business goals. Excessively strict regulations might hinder creativity and operational productivity. The main idea is to strike a balance between satisfying data protection norms while also supporting the development and flexibility of a company's operations.

4. Real-world cases highlighting the consequences of data breaches

Cybersecurity vulnerabilities can lead to various data breaches which can have a significant impact on business. Lister below are just a few examples of the consequences of data breaches

- During the Pwn2Own hacking contest, researchers demonstrated how to hack the Iconics Genesis64, a human-machine interface tool. This software is used in critical infrastructure, and a successful breach could allow hackers to take control of critical systems while misleading human operators into thinking everything is normal. This type of hack poses a significant threat because it could lead to machine malfunctions in critical infrastructure like power plants or water treatment facilities (O'Neill, 2022).
- This attack on the largest petroleum pipeline in the United States involved hackers using credentials found on the dark web to access Colonial Pipeline's system through a VPN. The ransomware attack led to a temporary shutdown of the pipeline, cutting off gas supply across the East Coast. This case highlights the potential for cyberattacks to disrupt critical utilities and cause physical consequences, such as the malfunction of energy distribution systems (Dashlane, 2022).
- Hackers remotely accessed a water treatment plant's supervisory control and data acquisition system (SCADA) in Florida. They attempted to manipulate the system, potentially to poison the water supply. The plant ran on an unsecured version of Windows, and employees used a shared password for remote access, making the system vulnerable. This breach could have led to severe consequences, including malfunctioning of the water treatment process (Dashlane, 2022).
- Cyber attackers compromised the credentials of two Marriott employees to access a third-party application. The breach wasn't detected for two months, allowing hackers to access client data. The incident illustrates the importance of monitoring third-party vendor access and user behaviour analytics to detect breaches early (Pryimenko, 2024).

- A former employee downloaded private patient data onto a USB drive. While the medical centre's security software alerted the cybersecurity staff, this case emphasizes the importance of efficient access management tools and the need for privileged access management solutions to prevent unauthorized access (Doherty, 2023).
- The Brighton and Sussex University hospital was fined £325,000 after the theft of thousands of patients' data from stolen hard drives. This incident shows the risks associated with physical data storage and points towards the benefits of secure cloud services for data protection (Vanwell, J., 2021).
- Hackers accessed live feeds from Ring security cameras by exploiting weak, recycled, and default credentials. This breach affected more than 30 people in 15 families, highlighting the importance of changing default admin credentials and implementing strong, unique passwords and two-factor authentication for IoT devices (Howard & Howard, 1994).
- Vulnerabilities in Nortek Linear eMerge E3 devices allowed hackers to hijack credentials and control building access systems. This case illustrates the importance of securing IoT devices and systems, which are increasingly integrated into business operations (Howard & Howard, 1994).

F. Predictive Maintenance Techniques

In the rapidly advancing landscape of maintenance strategies, predictive maintenance (PM) has emerged as a pivotal approach to enhance the reliability and efficiency of different systems in multiple domains. Predictive maintenance leverages a suite of sophisticated techniques to foresee potential issues before they escalate into costly breakdowns. This introduction explores the diverse realm of predictive maintenance techniques, categorizing them into five main pillars: Vibration Monitoring, Thermography, Tribology, Visual Inspection, and Ultrasonic. Each category plays a distinctive role in proactively monitoring and assessing the health of critical components within transportation systems.

Vibration Monitoring stands at the forefront of predictive maintenance, employing sensors to detect irregularities in mechanical vibrations. By analysing vibration patterns, professionals gain insights into the condition of rotating machinery, pinpointing potential faults such as misalignments or imbalances. This technique enables timely interventions, preventing catastrophic failures and optimizing the lifespan of equipment.

Thermography, another indispensable category, utilizes infrared technology to capture temperature variations across surfaces. Anomalies in temperature

patterns serve as indicators of potential malfunctions or overheating, aiding in the identification of faulty components. Thermographic inspections offer a non-intrusive means of assessing electrical systems, mechanical structures, and other critical elements, allowing for targeted maintenance efforts.

Tribology, the science of friction, wear, and lubrication, plays a crucial role in predictive maintenance. By monitoring lubricant conditions and analysing wear patterns, maintenance professionals gain valuable insights into the health of machinery components. Tribological techniques help optimize lubrication strategies, mitigate friction-related issues, and extend the operational life of equipment in the transportation sector.

Visual Inspection remains a fundamental pillar, encompassing manual assessments and inspections by trained personnel. While other techniques delve into the realms of data analytics, visual inspections provide a tangible and immediate way to identify visible signs of wear, corrosion, or damage. This hands-on approach remains essential for comprehensive maintenance strategies, complementing the data-driven insights provided by other categories.

Ultrasonic techniques round out the spectrum, utilizing high-frequency sound waves to detect anomalies and assess the integrity of structures. Ultrasonic sensors are particularly adept at identifying issues such as leaks, bearing problems, or electrical faults that may not be visible to the naked eye. This category offers a versatile and non-invasive method for detecting a wide range of potential maintenance concerns.

In this exploration of predictive maintenance categories, we delve into the distinctive features of each technique, underscoring their collective role in fostering a proactive and efficient maintenance paradigm within the transportation sector.

Signal - Vibration monitoring & analysis

Obtaining information through signal processing is one of the main elements for the analysis of vibration in machines. At the same time, signal processing can be considered demanding, since it aims at highlighting the features of the collected vibration signals, which are generally noisy and complex. Therefore, the data must be processed in such a way that the features of interest can be extracted.

There are several vibration signal processing methods that can be applied in monitoring rotating machinery to identify and diagnose defects or characteristic variations in the measured signal that indicate possible failures. These techniques can be divided into *time domain analysis, frequency domain analysis, and time-frequency analysis*. The choice of technique depends heavily on the signal to be analysed and the characteristics of the signal to be evaluated to identify possible

defects. Here are various signal processing techniques commonly used in predictive maintenance:

- ***Filtering:***

Description: Filtering techniques, such as low-pass, high-pass, or band-pass filters, are applied to remove noise and isolate specific frequency components in the signal.

Use: Filtering helps enhance the clarity of signals and focuses on the frequencies associated with potential faults or abnormalities.

- ***Fourier Transform:***

Description: Fourier Transform converts a time-domain signal into its frequency-domain representation, revealing the frequency content of the signal.

Use: Useful for identifying dominant frequencies related to specific machinery components, aiding in fault diagnosis.

- ***Wavelet Transform:***

Description: Wavelet Transform is a time-frequency analysis technique that captures both high and low-frequency components in a signal.

Use: Effective for analysing non-stationary signals and detecting transient events in the data.

- ***Hilbert Transform:***

Description: Hilbert Transform is used to compute the analytic signal, providing information about the amplitude and phase of the original signal.

Use: Useful for envelope analysis and detecting amplitude modulation in vibration signals.

- ***Envelope Analysis:***

Description: Envelope analysis focuses on extracting the envelope of a signal, highlighting changes in amplitude over time.

Use: Particularly effective in detecting faults in rolling element bearings and gearboxes.

- ***Cepstrum Analysis:***

Description: Cepstrum analysis helps identify recurring patterns within the signal by analysing the log spectrum of the signal.

Use: Useful for diagnosing faults in rotating machinery, such as gear faults or bearing defects.

- ***Time-Frequency Analysis:***

Description: Time-frequency analysis methods, such as Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) or spectrograms, provide insights into how the frequency content of a signal changes over time.

Use: Useful for analysing signals with non-stationary characteristics.

- ***Spectral Kurtosis.***

Description: Spectral kurtosis is a measure of the "peakedness" of a signal's frequency spectrum.

Use: It helps identify transient events and impulsive signals associated with faults, enhancing fault detection capabilities.

- ***Order Tracking.***

Description: Order tracking correlates vibration data with the rotational speed of the machinery.

Use: Useful for identifying faults that are speed-dependent, such as unbalance or misalignment.

- ***Principal Component Analysis (PCA).***

Description: PCA is a dimensionality reduction technique that identifies the principal components of a signal.

Use: Useful for extracting the most relevant features from high-dimensional data and reducing computational complexity.

- ***Time-Domain Analysis.***

Description: Time-domain analysis involves examining the signal in its raw, time-based form.

Use: Useful for identifying trends, peaks, and irregularities in the signal that may indicate potential issues.

These signal processing techniques are often applied in combination to analyse and interpret data from various sensors and monitoring systems. The choice of technique depends on the characteristics of the data and the specific requirements of the predictive maintenance application.

Thermography

There are numerous ways of collecting and measuring asset data that can provide insight into asset health and performance. Trending asset health data over time reveals patterns and makes it easier for teams to spot potential issues early on. Thermography is a key technology for identifying thermal degradation or changes in operating temperature of an asset. Another benefit of thermography is that it is non-contact, meaning that temperature data can be collected from safe distances. With moving or hard-to-reach parts, this increases worker safety. Contactless infrared cameras are also particularly beneficial in industries such as food and beverage, where monitoring processing equipment at a distance can be useful.

Thermography is a common and effective method of gathering useful data about an asset's condition. Many teams already use thermography in their maintenance

operations, making it a natural choice for teams looking to move into predictive maintenance. With thermography, they can use a familiar modality while applying a new maintenance approach. Thermography is best suited for finding electrical hotspots, mechanical faults and process issues. It is a modality that can be useful across many industries, asset types and concerns. It can identify a wide range of issues with many types of assets and components (Romanssini et al., 2023).

When an asset or component experiences a temperature change, that can be a key indicator that it is beginning to fail. That insight into asset health and potential failure gives teams time to plan their response so that assets or components can be serviced or replaced without interrupting production.

Some of the electrical components or issues thermography can be used for include faulty connections in panels, fuses, motors and switchgears. Some common electrical reasons behind temperature deviations or hotspots include (Romanssini et al., 2023):

- Unbalanced loads
- Harmonics
- Overloaded systems/excessive current
- Loose or corroded connections
- Insulation failure
- Wiring mistakes

Some of the mechanical components or issues thermography can be used for include motors, shafts, bearings, couplings, hydraulic pumps and misaligned belts. Some common mechanical reasons behind temperature deviations or hotspots include (Romanssini et al., 2023):

- Reduced airflow
- Power quality problems, such as unbalance, overload, or harmonics
- Insulation resistance
- Undersized components

Some of the process components or issues thermography can be used for include tank levels, pipe integrity, steam traps, boilers and reactors, heaters and furnaces, chiller operation, faulty insulation and weld cooling observation. Some common process reasons behind temperature deviations or hotspots include (Romanssini et al., 2023):

- Damaged structures
- Abnormal heat flow
- Gas or steam leakage
- Failed components
- Corrosion

Thermography can be a crucial part of a predictive maintenance program. Heat is a common symptom of equipment damage or malfunction — but do not forget that cooler-than-normal temperatures could also be an indication of a problem. Thermography and thermal imaging tools can help maintenance teams quickly and safely identify and diagnose issues with equipment. Infrared cameras and thermal imaging sensors, paired with software, can take reliability programs further by helping teams harness asset data to trend it and gain actionable insights. With those insights, teams can plan and prioritize their responses to maximize asset availability and lifespan (Farias et al., 2016). Here are various thermography techniques commonly used in predictive maintenance (Huda & Taib, 2013):

- Infrared Thermography:

Description: Infrared thermography captures the infrared radiation emitted by an object's surface to create a thermal image.

Use: Detects temperature variations, identifies hotspots, and provides a non-contact method for monitoring the thermal condition of equipment.

- Transient Thermography:

Description: Transient thermography involves heating a surface briefly and then capturing the thermal response as it cools down.

Use: Detects subsurface defects and provides information about the thermal properties of materials, aiding in the identification of hidden issues.

- Pulsed Thermography:

Description: Pulsed thermography uses short bursts of energy (pulses) to heat the surface, and the resulting thermal response is captured.

Use: Useful for detecting subsurface defects and differentiating between materials with varying thermal conductivities.

- Lock-In Thermography:

Description: Lock-in thermography involves modulating the thermal excitation source, and the thermal response is analysed at a specific frequency.

Use: Enhances the detection of subsurface defects and provides better signal-to-noise ratio in certain applications.

- Line Scanning Thermography:

Description: In line scanning thermography, an infrared camera scans along a line or path on the object's surface.

Use: Useful for inspecting large surfaces or components with a continuous scanning motion.

- Area Scanning Thermography:

Description: In area scanning thermography, the entire surface of the object is scanned by the infrared camera.

Use: Suitable for detailed inspection of smaller components or surfaces where a comprehensive thermal image is required.

- Rapid Infrared Imaging:

Description: Rapid infrared imaging involves capturing thermal images at a high frame rate to monitor dynamic processes or transient events.

Use: Useful for applications where fast temperature changes occur, such as during equipment startups or shutdowns.

- High-Speed Infrared Imaging:

Description: High-speed infrared imaging captures thermal images at exceptionally fast frame rates.

Use: Applied in scenarios where extremely rapid temperature changes need to be observed, such as in combustion processes or high-speed machinery.

- Quantitative Infrared Thermography:

Description: Quantitative infrared thermography involves calibrating thermal images to obtain accurate temperature measurements.

Use: Provides quantitative temperature data, enabling precise assessment of thermal conditions and identification of temperature gradients.

- Thermal Trend Analysis:

Description: Thermal trend analysis involves monitoring temperature variations over time to identify patterns and trends.

Use: Helps predict potential issues by observing changes in temperature patterns during normal operation.

- Infrared Video Thermography:

Description: Infrared video thermography captures thermal videos, allowing dynamic monitoring of temperature changes.

Use: Useful for real-time observation of temperature variations in components or systems during operation.

These thermography techniques are valuable tools in predictive maintenance, enabling early detection of thermal abnormalities, preventing equipment failures, and optimizing maintenance strategies across various industries. The choice of technique depends on the specific requirements of the application and the characteristics of the equipment being inspected.

Tribology

Tribology refers to the science and engineering of interacting surfaces in relative motion, and it plays a crucial role in predictive maintenance, especially for machinery with moving parts. Tribology techniques help monitor and analyse the friction, wear, and lubrication conditions of components, aiding in the early detection of potential issues. Here are various tribology techniques commonly used in predictive maintenance (Marinescu et al., 2021; Bhat et al., 2022; Desai et al., 2021):

- **Wear Particle Analysis:**

Description: Collecting and analyzing wear particles from lubricating fluids, such as oil or grease.

Use: Identifies the type and quantity of wear particles to assess the condition of components like gears, bearings, and other moving parts.

- **Ferrography:**

Description: Ferrography involves separating ferrous and non-ferrous wear particles from lubricating oil for microscopic analysis.

Use: Provides detailed information about the size, shape, and composition of wear particles, aiding in the identification of specific wear mechanisms.

- **Oil Analysis:**

Description: Analysing the chemical and physical properties of lubricating oil to assess its condition.

Use: Detects contaminants, measures viscosity, and evaluates the overall health of the lubricating oil, helping to identify potential issues with components.

- **Viscosity Measurement:**

Description: Measuring the viscosity of lubricating fluids to assess their ability to provide effective lubrication.

Use: Changes in viscosity can indicate issues such as fluid degradation, contamination, or inadequate lubrication.

- **Friction Coefficient Measurement:**

Description: Measuring the coefficient of friction between interacting surfaces.

Use: Identifies variations in friction levels, which can be indicative of changes in lubrication conditions or the onset of wear.

- **Surface Profilometry:**

Description: Examining the surface topography and roughness of components.

Use: Reveals changes in surface condition due to wear, abrasion, or other factors that may affect the performance of moving parts.

- **Wear Debris Monitoring:**

Description: Continuously monitoring wear debris in real-time during equipment operation.

Use: Provides immediate feedback on wear conditions, allowing for proactive maintenance and reducing the risk of unexpected failures.

- **Lubricant Film Thickness Measurement:**

Description: Measuring the thickness of the lubricant film between interacting surfaces.

Use: Helps ensure proper lubrication and prevents issues like boundary lubrication, where surfaces may come into direct contact.

- **Tribochemical Analysis:**

Description: Studying the chemical reactions occurring at the surfaces of interacting components.

Use: Provides insights into the formation of protective films or surface coatings and helps evaluate the effectiveness of lubrication additives.

- **Acoustic Emission Monitoring:**

Description: Detecting acoustic emissions produced by friction and wear processes.

Use: Enables the identification of specific wear mechanisms and the onset of abnormal friction conditions.

- **Rolling Element Bearing Analysis:**

Description: Analysing the condition of rolling element bearings, including vibration analysis and temperature monitoring.

Use: Detects abnormalities in bearing condition, such as defects, misalignment, or insufficient lubrication.

- **Triboelectric Sensor Technology:**

Description: Using triboelectric sensors to monitor friction and wear conditions.

Use: Provides real-time data on the triboelectric charge generated by sliding or rubbing surfaces, helping identify changes in friction levels.

These tribology techniques are integral to predictive maintenance strategies, allowing maintenance professionals to monitor and assess the condition of critical components, optimize lubrication practices, and minimize the risk of unplanned downtime. The choice of technique depends on the specific requirements of the equipment and the nature of the potential issues being addressed.

Image Processing - Visual Inspection

Image processing contributes to predictive maintenance by enabling the analysis of visual data from equipment, machinery, or infrastructure to detect anomalies,

defects, or signs of potential failure. Here's a brief overview of how image processing plays a role:

- **Detection of Anomalies:** Image processing techniques, such as computer vision and pattern recognition, are used to analyse images captured by cameras or sensors installed in industrial environments. These techniques can identify abnormalities, such as cracks, corrosion, leaks, or wear and tear, on equipment surfaces or structural components.
- **Condition Monitoring:** By regularly capturing and analysing images of machinery or infrastructure, image processing allows for continuous condition monitoring. Changes in appearance or texture can be detected over time, indicating deterioration or degradation that may require maintenance or repair.
- **Fault Diagnosis:** Image processing algorithms can categorize and classify visual data to diagnose specific faults or issues. For example, machine learning models trained on labeled images can identify different types of defects or failures and provide insights into their root causes.
- **Predictive Analysis:** By combining image data with other sensor data and historical maintenance records, predictive models can be developed to anticipate equipment failures before they occur. Image processing helps extract relevant features and patterns from visual data to improve the accuracy of predictive maintenance algorithms.
- **Asset Management:** Image processing contributes to asset management by providing visual documentation of equipment condition and maintenance history. Images captured during inspections or maintenance activities serve as valuable records for tracking asset health and performance over time.

Overall, image processing enhances predictive maintenance by leveraging visual data to assess equipment condition, identify potential issues, and inform proactive maintenance strategies. It complements other predictive maintenance techniques, such as vibration analysis, thermography, and acoustic monitoring, to provide a comprehensive understanding of asset health and optimize maintenance practices.

Visual inspection was the first method used for predictive maintenance. Almost from the beginning of the Industrial Revolution, maintenance technicians performed daily "walkdowns" of critical production and manufacturing systems in an attempt to identify potential failures or maintenance-related problems that could impact reliability, product quality, and production costs. A visual inspection is still a viable predictive maintenance tool and should be included in all total-plant maintenance management programs (Technomax, 2024). Table 3 presents various visual inspection techniques commonly used in predictive maintenance:

Table 3

Summary table of Visual Inspection techniques

Technique	Description	Use
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Direct Visual Inspection	Direct observation of equipment components and surfaces using the naked eye.	Identifies visible signs of wear, corrosion, damage, or other issues.
Borescopic Inspection	Using a borescope or endoscope to visually inspect the interior of hard-to-reach components or machinery.	Enables inspection of internal parts of engines, pipes, or other enclosed structures without disassembly.
Remote Visual Inspection (RVI)	Using cameras or remote visual inspection tools to inspect areas that are difficult to access.	Suitable for inspecting components inside machinery, pipelines, or other confined spaces without physical entry.
Close-Up Photography	Taking close-up photographs of equipment surfaces for detailed visual analysis.	Captures high-resolution images for documentation and analysis of surface conditions.
Video Inspection	Recording video footage during inspections for continuous monitoring and later analysis.	Provides a dynamic view of equipment conditions and aids in identifying changes over time.
UV Inspection (Ultraviolet Inspection)	Using ultraviolet (UV) light to reveal fluorescent indications of issues such as leaks or contamination.	Using ultraviolet (UV) light to reveal fluorescent indications of issues such as leaks or contamination.
Infrared Inspection	Using infrared cameras to detect temperature variations on the surface of equipment.	Identifies hotspots or temperature anomalies that may indicate issues with electrical components, machinery, or insulation.

Stereo Microscopy	Using a stereo microscope to inspect small components or intricate details.	Allows for detailed examination of the surface condition of small parts.
Visual Comparison (Before and After)	Comparing current visual observations with baseline or historical images.	Helps identify changes, deterioration, or abnormalities in the equipment's appearance over time.
Surface Roughness Inspection	Assessing the texture and roughness of surfaces using tactile or visual methods.	Aids in identifying wear patterns, corrosion, or surface damage that may affect performance.
Magnetic Particle Inspection	Applying magnetic particles to a surface and visually inspecting for indications of cracks or defects.	Effective for detecting surface and near-surface defects in ferrous materials.
Liquid Penetrant Inspection (Dye Penetrant Inspection)	Applying a liquid penetrant to the surface, which seeps into defects and is then visible under UV light or through color contrast.	Detects surface-breaking defects, cracks, or porosity in materials.
Eddy Current Inspection	Using eddy current technology to inspect conductive materials for surface and near-surface defects.	Effective for detecting cracks, corrosion, and variations in material properties.
Corrosion Mapping	Mapping and visually inspecting the extent of corrosion on surfaces.	Aids in assessing the severity of corrosion and planning maintenance actions.

These visual inspection techniques are essential for maintaining a comprehensive understanding of the condition of equipment and structures, allowing for timely identification of issues and informed decision-making in the realm of predictive maintenance.

Ultrasonic

Ultrasonics, like vibration analysis, is a subset of noise analysis. The only difference in the two techniques is the frequency band they monitor. In the case of vibration analysis, the monitored range is between 1 Hertz (Hz) and 30,000 Hz; ultrasonics monitors noise frequencies above 30,000 Hz. These higher frequencies are useful for select applications, such as detecting leaks that generally create high-frequency noise caused by the expansion or compression of air, gases, or liquids as they flow through the orifice, or a leak in either pressure or vacuum vessels. These higher frequencies are also useful in measuring the ambient noise levels in various areas of the plant. As it is being applied as part of a predictive maintenance program, many companies are attempting to replace what is perceived as an expensive tool (i.e., vibration analysis) with ultrasonics. For example, many plants are using ultrasonic meters to monitor the health of rolling-element bearings in the belief that this technology will provide accurate results. Unfortunately, this perception is invalid. Because this technology is limited to a broadband (i.e., 30 kHz to 1 MHz), ultrasonics does not provide the ability to diagnosis incipient bearing or machine problems. It certainly cannot define the root cause of abnormal noise levels generated by either bearings or other machine-train components. As part of a comprehensive predictive maintenance program, ultrasonics should be limited to the detection of abnormally high ambient noise levels and leaks. Attempting to replace vibration monitoring with ultrasonics simply will not work (Technomax, 2022, Rienstra, 2014).

Fault prediction approaches for predictive maintenance techniques

Fault is basically a state of deviation within a system, and failure is an event, usually permanent disruption, caused by a fault. With fault detection, evidently, one can predict the failures that might otherwise disrupt the operation of a machine or component. The prediction of a fault or failure depends on the data acquired from the process or the system. This data is processed and fed to the different analysis models. Different modelling techniques are available for processing the data from real-time networks, which are raw and abstract in nature. These techniques are quite similar in the process. With feature construction, the missing or abstract data is initially constructed to reduce the input dimensionality and enhance prediction capability to effectively manage a large set of inputs by transforming them into a completely new feature. This goal is achieved by performing feature extraction, which is yet another process whose aim is to reduce the redundancy of the features.

This method ensures that the data relevant to the prediction are considered and other less important features are removed (Sondhi, 2009).

Knowledge-based models

Heuristic knowledge from the process and subject matter knowledge can play a vital role in predicting faults. Mathematical or physics-based modelling is not available for this method, and it solely depends on the domain knowledge of the experts. Fuzzy logic and logical condition/rule based (IF, THEN or ELSE) are the most common methods for deriving this model. Owing to the high complexity in transforming the expert knowledge into logical conditions, this method cannot be used alone. Typically, with the help of data from a physics-based approach, this complexity can be reduced considerably (Isermann, 2011; Zhou et al., 2013).

In 2017, the researchers developed a fault detection method that relies on an ontology-based integration outline for the computerised knowledge-based fault diagnostics of a conveyor system in an industrial application (Steinegger et al., 2017). Delgoshaei and Austin (2017) developed a scalable and comprehensive knowledge-based framework for a heating ventilation and air conditioning system over a reasoning based on inference to derive information on the anomalies in the process. In 2020 (Karakose & Yaman, 2020), for an electric railway system, a fuzzy-based complex approach with thermography was posited for prognostic maintenance activities.

Data-based models

Data-driven approaches have been well used, considering the different statistical and machine learning methods achieved via the vast pool of historical trend data from various sensors. With past information and states from this trending data, it is possible to predict failures in the current state. Since it is quite possible to have machine learning libraries and real-time sensor data, data-driven methods and the algorithms derived from them have gained more popularity than other methods for predictive maintenance. However, since this method does not integrate knowledge or the actual physical implementation of the process, the accuracy achieved with this model cannot be fully determined in the best possible way. Furthermore, the actual failure mode at its root cannot be fully recognised with just a black box approach. Most of the research has been performed with open-source data, and very little has been taken directly from the mechanical or electrical equipment in actual usage. This aspect makes it challenging to determine the reliability of reusing these models for other equipment in the instance of manufacturers providing custom-made machines. This leads to immense fine-

tuning and parameterisation of the model when used for other customised equipment (Zhang et al., 2019).

In aircraft maintenance, the components which are in the out-of-service zone of operation are at times not discarded, thus leading to potential failure. In 2018, a framework with data-driven approaches involving an autoregressive moving average model (ARMA) was proposed (Baptista et al., 2018). The predominant health indicators of a battery, the remaining useful life (RUL) and state-of-health (SOH) of a lithium-ion battery are widely monitored. In 2019, using a data-driven approach with the Deep Neural Networks (DNN) method, a predictive model (e SoH and the RUL of the lithium-ion battery) was developed (Khumprom & Yodo, 2019). Using advanced big data and the random forest algorithm. In 2017, researchers developed a platform with a dashboard which shows the predicted failures in a wind turbine (Canizo et al., 2017). With the usage of a Gaussian hidden Markov model and the Wavelet Packet Decomposition technique, the remaining useful life of a wind turbine bearing has been discussed in (Tobon-Mejia et al., 2012). Different machine learning methods, such as supervised, unsupervised, reinforcement and deep neural network-based algorithms, are widely employed to predict failures using the vast pool of data from machines or systems.

Physics-based models

Mathematical models of pieces of equipment or a process that involve numerous differential equations are realised to form physics-based models from first principles. With accurate models, predictive models can be designed to provide reliable predictions. These models are implemented using various experimental and empirical data, and they require a thorough knowledge of a system and the associated failure modes. Degradation models are designed to forecast the remaining useful life of the machine. Different statistical methods are used to update the constraints of the model. Having a rigorous knowledge of the system, and building an accurate model from them is a tedious task that is not, in any case, always achievable. Parameter identification also requires exhaustive experimentation. Not all failure modes can be considered while building such models, making it a not-so-obvious method for complex system architecture (Liao & Köttig, 2014). In 2012, the degradation model of a rolling element bearing that relies on physics-based modelling was simulated, and a health-monitoring system was discussed (Stringer et al., 2012). The remaining useful life of a component in a multiple operational mode that depends on a physics-based prognostic method was suggested in Luo et al. (2003). Using advanced physics-based predictive maintenance with digital-twin implementation, the digital image of an industrial robot and its methodology were discussed in Aivaliotis et al. (2019). Reliability is a factor which is more important in the tidal power sector than in conventional wind power systems. For tidal stream turbines, to forecast the remaining useful life of the bearing of a pitch system, a reliability-focussed physics-based model was employed. (Ewing et al., 2019)

Hybrid models

Today, to overcome the complexities of other models and to achieve a certain betterment, hybrid models are extensively used. Such models combine knowledge, data, and physics-based models to achieve a better trade-off between these models, offering more reliable and accurate predictive and degradation models. The usage of hybrid models in the remaining life estimation of a lithium-ion battery while incorporating a particle filter and other techniques was discussed in (Liao & Köttig, 2016). In 2009, the summary of a hybrid system using both physics- and data-based approaches to condition-based monitoring was discussed. A hybrid technique based on adaptive mode with regression-based predictive models for health monitoring of a rolling element bearing was discussed in Zhang et al. (2009) and Ahmad et al. (2017). A digital-twin powered hybrid model for a CNC machine tool was implemented and discussed in Luo et al. (2020).

Figure 6

Fault Prediction methods in manufacturing industry

IoT Devices in Predictive Maintenance

Internet of things (IoT) is a technology that connects the physical world to the Internet. It represents devices that are connected either directly to the Internet or are built in networks and are communicating with each other in a mesh. IoT devices use sensors to gather data or actuators to send feedback. Sensor is a device that senses the physical properties of the real world such as measuring speed, temperature, humidity, air pressure, vibration, sound, etc. IoT devices can give feedback using actuators which are devices that do something such as turn on the switch, make a noise, etc. In other words, one can think of IoT as an ecosystem that

gathers data using sensors, interacts with the physical world using actuators and connects with peer devices and the Internet.

IoT also includes edge devices which do not have or do not need Internet connection. Typically, these devices can process data themselves, based on the AI trained model.

IoT devices communicate with each other and send sensor data using different communication technologies such as WiFi, Bluetooth, cellular networks, low power specialized communication protocols, etc. Having in mind the sensitive nature of the collected data and typically wireless transmission of data, security and privacy are important features that IoT-based systems should have. This includes putting in place systems and protocols that will ensure resilience towards cyber threats and data breaches. Commonly adopted security frameworks or protocols for IoT devices include:

- Transport Layer Security (TLS): TLS is a cryptographic protocol that ensures secure communication between IoT devices and servers by encrypting data and authenticating the identities of communicating parties.
- Message Queuing Telemetry Transport (MQTT): MQTT is a lightweight messaging protocol commonly used in IoT environments. It supports authentication, encryption, and message integrity to secure communication between devices and brokers.
- Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure (HTTPS): HTTPS provides secure communication over the internet by encrypting data transmitted between IoT devices and web servers. It ensures confidentiality and integrity of data exchanged between devices and cloud services.
- OAuth (Open Authorization): OAuth is an authentication protocol used to grant access to IoT devices or applications without sharing credentials. It enables secure and controlled access to resources by providing access tokens that expire after a specified period.
- OAuth 2.0 Device Authorization Grant: This OAuth 2.0 extension is designed for IoT and devices with limited input capabilities. It allows devices to obtain authorization from users via a secondary device, such as a smartphone or computer.
- JSON Web Tokens (JWT): JWT is a compact, URL-safe token format commonly used for authentication and authorization in IoT systems. It securely transmits claims between parties, enabling stateless authentication and authorization.
- Device Identity and Access Management (IAM): IAM solutions manage device identities, permissions, and access control policies in IoT ecosystems. They ensure that only authorized devices can access resources and perform specific actions within the system.
- Secure Boot and Firmware Verification: Secure boot mechanisms verify the integrity of device firmware during startup to prevent unauthorized or

malicious code execution. Firmware verification ensures that only authenticated and unaltered firmware is loaded onto the device.

- Network Segmentation and Access Controls: Network segmentation divides IoT networks into separate subnetworks to contain security risks and limit the impact of breaches. Access controls restrict unauthorized access to critical resources and services within the IoT network.
- Security by Design Principles: Security by design principles advocate for incorporating security measures into IoT device design and development processes from the outset. It emphasizes proactive risk assessment, threat modeling, and security testing throughout the product lifecycle.

Implementing these security frameworks and protocols helps mitigate common IoT security risks, such as unauthorized access, data breaches, and device tampering, and ensures the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of IoT systems and data.

Even though there are different implementations of IoT architecture, based on the context implementation, one of the fundamental IoT architectures is an architecture with four layers:

1. Sensing layer – this layer is the first layer in IoT architecture, and it consists of sensors and actuators. These devices are connected to the network layer either through wired or wireless communication channels, although wireless communications channels are widely used.
2. Network layer – responsible for establishing and maintaining communication and connectivity between devices, and between devices and the Internet. Examples of network technologies that are commonly used in IoT include WiFi, Bluetooth, Zigbee, and cellular networks such as 4G and 5G. Security features and protocols are also implemented in this layer.
3. Data processing layer – this layer is responsible, with its hardware and software, to collect, analyse, and interpret data from IoT devices. In this layer various technologies are used such as data management systems, analytics platforms, and machine learning algorithms.
4. Application layer – responsible for the user-friendly interface that allows users to access and control IoT devices, to use data visualization tools and/or advanced analytics by using different applications such as mobile apps, web portals, and other user interfaces that are designed to interact with the underlying IoT infrastructure.

IoT as a technology has found its applications in various industries and applications, and hence, their implementation influenced the usage of different types of IoT devices. Depending on the applications, IoT devices also use different networking and commutation protocols, which are tailored to meet requirements of the application domain. Even though there are many different IoT devices, they can be categorized in following groups:

- Consumer IoT devices – refers to IoT usage for consumer applications and devices, typically in homes or offices, for products such as smart watches, home appliances, wearables, etc.
- Commercial IoT devices – refers to IoT usage for large commercial venues such as hotels, hospitals, office buildings, supermarkets, or other environments outside of the home. Examples of commercial IoT would be monitoring environmental conditions or managing access to facilities.
- Industrial IoT devices – refers to the usage of IoT devices in the industrial sectors and its applications. While in its core it is using the same technology as other IoT devices, industrial IoT focuses more on automation and efficiency across the entire ecosystem, and not just the individual consumer. Industrial IoT has been implemented in different industry sectors, and with its integration with AI it can be found in smart manufacturing, predictive maintenance, smart agriculture, etc.
- Infrastructure IoT devices – represents a subset of industrial IoT, but due to the significance of its application, it is considered separately. Infrastructure IoT devices commonly referred to as IoT devices in smart cities.
- Military IoT devices – refers to usage of IoT devices in military operations. Examples of military IoT are surveillance robots, wearable military gear, coordination of military units, etc.

Even though predictive maintenance can use various IoT devices, it is predominately considered as implementation of an industrial IoT. In predictive maintenance, components of IoT devices are used to collect data from different equipment and machinery and to send that data to centralized systems, cloud-based or edge platforms. IoT sensors are used to collect different environmental conditions such as temperature, vibration, pressure, etc, allowing to implement advanced analytics on the collected data. Once processed, this data provides a real-time input about the production process, allowing to have timely and informed decisions to manage, prevent or indicate different equipment issues, outages and downtimes. Continuous monitoring of equipment allows not only to detect major issues, but also to track subtle deviations, which can contribute to identifying potential issues and equipment failures. Even though IoT devices and their sensors collect raw data, this data is transformed into meaningful insights that can be acted upon. Predictive algorithms and data analytics are used together to combine historical data with sensor data in order to identify patterns and anomalies that can be used to predict equipment failure.

IoT-based predictive maintenance consists of following components:

- Sensors – strategically placed on the machinery, equipment or on assets and are used to collect data
- Data communication – represents a system that allows collected data to be sent to central data storage
- Central data storage – centralized location for storing all collected data

- Predictive maintenance platform – streams all of data to maintenance/repair team and signals when the machine operates out of the defined range
- Predictive analytics – generates actionable insights using AI/ML algorithms on the existing data.

Both predictive maintenance and IoT are used in many different industries, therefore, almost all kinds of sensors are used in predictive maintenance, some of which are:

- Pressure sensors - commonly deployed in industries dealing with water, oil, and gas, are strategically fitted in pipes and tanks to detect leaks or blockages. These sensors promptly indicate value changes, triggering warning messages to the relevant authorities
- Gas sensors - employed to detect toxic gasses and also find applications in monitoring indoor air quality. The comprehensive range of sensors caters to diverse industrial needs and even extends to home applications.
- Temperature sensors - play a crucial role in measuring equipment temperatures like motors, gears, and piping. Offering proactive warnings against potential overheating issues, these sensors contribute to damage prevention.
- Humidity sensors – implemented in industries requiring low moisture levels, such as smartphone manufacturing and HVAC systems.
- Vibration sensors – used to monitor intense vibrations in heavy machinery, issuing warnings when vibrations exceed predetermined thresholds.
- Proximity sensors – used to detect the presence of nearby objects without contact, are extensively used in retail, malls, and stadiums for various applications, including targeted marketing
- Security sensors – including motion detectors, alarms, GPS trackers, infrared sensors, and photoelectric beams, are integral for ensuring robust security measures across diverse settings.

Predictive maintenance assesses equipment condition, allowing for the early identification of potential failures before they disrupt production. Breakdowns and replacing broken equipment can cause significant financial losses. For instance, unplanned stop of production lines or field operations stalling, may cause missing on service level agreements and the loss of risk revenues. The role of IoT in predictive maintenance is to continuously monitor health and performance of machines and equipment, so that data can be used to infer their current status in order to detect any issues in current time. Knowing when equipment needs attention helps planning maintenance work, keep the right inventory of spare parts and plan to avoid unplanned outages. Predictive maintenance analytics helps equipment last longer, worker safety increases and supply chain is optimized. Asset condition monitoring captures the state of the machine and equipment so it can be understood how the asset is performing in the field or on

the factory floor. Typically, data such as temperature, vibration and error codes indicate whether the equipment usage is optimal, however, this is hard to capture manually since technicians need to physically examine machines and equipment. Capturing health and performance indicators with IoT and sending them to a predictive maintenance platform lets operations staff know whether the capacity is under or overused without sending people to use physical inspections. With increased visibility into assets, asset utilization can be optimized and investment in machines and equipment can be exploited.

Within the predictive maintenance context, usage of IoT to capture conditions of machines and equipment, and sending it to a predictive maintenance platform, allows to take intelligent actions by using machine learning. In order to do so, IoT data is collected and later it is cleaned and transformed before being stored. It is necessary to pre-process collected data before this data is used for further analysis. When using cloud-based platforms, machine learning models can be trained on the cloud on the historical data, and later trained models can be deployed in industrial environments locally. Cloud based IoT predictive maintenance platforms can ideally help to quickly integrate large numbers of different types of devices. By doing so, inventory of devices can be maintained with static and dynamic information such as serial numbers, manufacturing date, current temperature, etc. Merging both static and dynamic data, allows users to be able to provide current device status any time. Not only does this help with diagnosis and troubleshooting and managing different issues in time and remotely, but it also allows to do so across many locations. Equally important is to keep in mind that devices and collected, transmitted and stored data should be secure. This is typically done with built in authentication and authorization, which includes data encryption, access control and security policies associated with devices.

Some examples of how businesses can use IoT predictive maintenance are:

1. Optimizing fleet management in the transportation industry – logistics companies that experience financial losses due to the increased costs of vehicles' maintenance and their downtime. Implementing an IoT predictive maintenance system that in real time tracks performance and health of their vehicles can help with reduced maintenance costs, reduced downtime, improved utilization of their fleet, increase the driver safety, and hence improve the satisfaction of their customers.
2. Enhancing production efficiency in a manufacturing plant - A manufacturing plant faced recurring equipment breakdowns, leading to significant production downtime. The company introduced an IoT predictive maintenance system for continuous monitoring of machine conditions and performance. This led to increased equipment lifespan, reduced maintenance costs, improved production efficiency, minimized downtime, and enhanced decision-making with optimized resource allocation.

3. IoT-based predictive maintenance in management of medical equipment – while medical devices such as MRI systems can be monitored and repaired by experts, a limited number of MRI experts cannot monitor all MRI systems around the world. One of the approaches to decrease the downtime and expansive repair costs, is to use sensor data to train the model on the typical reasons for the malfunctioning of the MRI system, which can allow healthcare organizations using this MRI system to have an early detection of potential issues and schedule maintenance before the system breaks down.
4. Predictive maintenance of elevators with IoT – traditional predictive maintenance of the elevators is based on the statistical models that take into consideration the number of hours of elevator usage and estimates on fault detection and useful life. This approach however does not monitor health and performance of the elevator in real time, which can lead to long downtimes, increased travel costs for the repair technicians, and hence, decreased client satisfaction. Introducing IoT predictive maintenance to gather and analyse sensor data, allows to predict issues before the downtime happens. This allows companies to reduce their maintenance costs and it also increases the customer satisfaction.
5. IoT predictive maintenance for supply chain management – companies use IoT based predictive maintenance to scan the efficiency of the full operations as well to cut down the expanses. For the supply chain management IoT based predictive maintenance can be used to track the state of the equipment, prevent supply chain interruptions, detect inefficiencies, as well as predict and address the risks in the supply chain.

G. Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning in Predictive Maintenance

1. Introduction to Artificial Intelligence

Artificial intelligence (AI) is an area of computer science that aims to make machines do intelligent things, that is, learn and solve problems, similar to the natural intelligence of humans and animals. In AI, an intelligent agent receives information from the environment, performs computations to decide what action to take in order to achieve the goal, and takes actions autonomously. AI can improve its performance with learning (Russell & Norvig, 2016).

According to many resources, AI can be divided into three categories.

- **Narrow AI**, also called weak AI or artificial narrow intelligence (ANI), refers to the AI that is used to solve a specific problem. Almost all AI applications we have today are narrow AI. For example, image classification, object detection, speech recognition (such as Amazon's Alexa, iPhone's Siri, Microsoft's Cortana, and Google Assistant), translation, natural language

processing, weather forecasting, targeted advertisements, sales predictions, email spam detection, fraud detection, face recognition, and computer vision are all narrow AI.

- **General AI**, also called strong AI or artificial general intelligence (AGI), refers to the AI that is for solving general problems. It is more like a human being, which is able to learn, think, invent, and solve more complicated problems. Narrow AI is what we have achieved so far, and general AI is what we expect in the future.
- **Super AI**, also called superintelligence, refers to the AI after the singularity point. The singularity, also called technological singularity, is when AI overtakes human intelligence. Nobody knows what will happen with super AI. One vision is human and machine integration through a brain chip interface. We cannot predict the future, but we can prepare for it.

We can say that main goals of AI are: replication of human intelligence, solving the knowledge-intensive tasks, an intelligent connection of perception and action, building a machine which can perform tasks that requires human intelligence such as: proving a theorem, playing chess, plan and perform some surgical operation, driving a car in traffic, etc. and creating some system which can exhibit intelligent behaviour, learn new things by itself, demonstrate, explain, and can advise to its user (Javapoint, 2019).

The main subfields of AI are: Machine Learning, Deep Learning, Natural Language processing, Expert System, Robotics, Computer Vision and Speech Recognition (Cardoso & Ferreira, 2020). This is presented on Figure 7.

Figure 7
Subfields of AI

Note. From Application of predictive maintenance concepts using artificial intelligence tools, by Cardoso & Ferreira, (2020).

Machine learning is a subfield of AI which provides intelligence to machines with the ability to automatically learn with experiences without being explicitly programmed. It is primarily concerned with the design and development of algorithms that allow the system to learn from historical data. Machine Learning is based on the idea that machines can learn from past data, identify patterns, and make decisions using algorithms. Machine learning algorithms are designed in such a way that they can learn and improve their performance automatically. Machine learning helps in discovering patterns in data.

Natural language processing is a subfield of computer science and artificial intelligence. Natural language processing (NLP) enables a computer system to understand and process human language such as English. NLP plays an important role in AI as without NLP, AI agent cannot work on human instructions, but with the help of NLP, we can instruct an AI system on our language. Today we are all around AI, and as well as NLP, we can easily ask Siri, Google or Cortana to help us in our language. Natural language processing applications enable a user to communicate with the system in their own words directly. The Input and output of NLP applications can be in two forms: speech and text.

Deep learning is a subset of machine learning which provides the ability for machines to perform human-like tasks without human involvement. It provides the ability for an AI agent to mimic the human brain. Deep learning is implemented through neural networks architecture hence also called a deep neural network. Deep learning is the primary technology behind self-driving cars, speech recognition, image recognition, automatic machine translation, etc. The main challenge for deep learning is that it requires lots of data with lots of computational power.

Expert system is an application of artificial intelligence. In artificial intelligence, expert systems are the computer programs that rely on obtaining the knowledge of human experts and programming that knowledge into a system. Expert systems emulate the decision-making ability of human experts. These systems are designed to solve the complex problem through bodies of knowledge rather than conventional procedural code. Expert systems have high performance, they are reliable, highly responsive and understandable.

Robotics is a branch of AI and engineering which is used for designing and manufacturing of robots. Robots are programmed machines which can perform a series of actions automatically or semi-automatically. AI can be applied to robots to make intelligent robots which can perform the task with their intelligence. AI algorithms are necessary to allow a robot to perform more complex tasks. Nowadays, AI and machine learning are being applied on robots to manufacture intelligent robots which can also interact socially like humans.

Computer vision encompasses a wide range of tasks, including image recognition, object detection, image segmentation, and more. It is a subset of (AI) and is concerned with teaching computers how to gain high-level understanding from

digital images or videos. Machine vision is often used in the context of industrial applications and refers to the use of computer vision technology in manufacturing or industrial processes. It captures and analyses visual information using one or more video cameras, analogue-to-digital conversions, and digital signal processing. Machine vision systems are programmed to perform narrowly defined tasks such as counting objects, reading the serial number, etc.

Speech recognition is a technology which enables a machine to understand the spoken language and translate into a machine-readable format. It can also be said as automatic Speech recognition and computer speech recognition. It is a way to talk with a computer, and on the basis of that command, a computer can perform a specific task. Today there are various software or devices which contain speech recognition technology such as Cortana, Google virtual assistant, Apple Siri, etc.

2. Artificial intelligence in Predictive Maintenance

Artificial Intelligence tools, in particular machine learning, exhibit enormous potential in the analysis of large amounts of data, now readily available, thus aiming to improve the availability of systems, reducing maintenance costs, and increasing operational performance and support in decision making (Cao, Q., 2020). The most common and most successful application of AI in predictive maintenance is the use of machine learning as a subfield of AI, thus next chapters will be dedicated to introduction to machine learning and its applications in predictive maintenance. Predictive maintenance is often associated with machine learning due to its ability to analyse patterns and predict equipment failures, but AI in the context of predictive maintenance can encompass a broader range of techniques beyond traditional machine learning. We will go through each of these techniques briefly:

- **Rule-Based Systems:** Rule-based systems are a form of AI that utilises predefined rules and logic to make decisions. In predictive maintenance, these rules can be derived from expert knowledge about the equipment and its failure modes. Engineers can create rule-based systems that trigger maintenance actions based on specific conditions or thresholds, such as temperature exceeding a certain limit or vibration patterns indicating potential issues (Wang, X., 2023).
- **Knowledge Representation:** AI systems can represent and store knowledge about equipment, maintenance procedures, and historical failure data in a structured format. This knowledge representation allows for efficient retrieval and analysis of relevant information, aiding in decision-making processes related to maintenance scheduling and resource allocation (Butler, K. L., 1996).
- **Expert Systems:** Expert systems are AI programs designed to mimic the decision-making abilities of a human expert in a specific domain. In predictive maintenance, expert systems can incorporate domain-specific

knowledge to diagnose equipment issues and recommend appropriate maintenance actions (Akhbardeh, F., 2020).

- **Natural Language Processing:** NLP can be applied to analyse unstructured textual data, such as maintenance reports, equipment manuals, and sensor notes. By extracting insights from textual information, AI systems can enhance the understanding of historical maintenance activities, contributing to more informed decision-making (Cao Q., 2022).
- **Knowledge-Based Reasoning:** Knowledge-based reasoning involves using logical rules and inferences to derive new information from existing knowledge. In predictive maintenance, knowledge-based reasoning can be employed to deduce potential future issues based on the observed patterns and historical data (Wei, Y., 2020).
- **Data Fusion:** AI techniques, including data fusion, can integrate information from multiple sources, such as sensor data, maintenance records, and external environmental factors. The integrated data can provide a holistic view of the equipment's health and help in identifying potential failure risks (Borissova, D., 2012).
- **Decision Support Systems:** AI-driven decision support systems assist maintenance professionals in making informed decisions by presenting relevant information, trends, and recommendations. These systems can enhance the effectiveness of maintenance planning and resource allocation (VanderPlas, J., 2016).

3. Introduction to Machine Learning

Machine learning (ML) is a subfield of artificial intelligence that deals with the study and application of algorithms and techniques that allow computers to learn from data without explicit instructions. It's a process of learning from examples, where a model receives data about a problem and uses them to learn patterns and relationships in data and calculate rules that are used to predict future outcomes. The model is continuously improved based on new data and results, which allows it to generalise and make more accurate predictions. The difference between machine learning and classical programming techniques is that classical programming requires detailed instructions from programmers to manually define each step in the problem-solving process, while on the other hand, ML uses algorithms that learn from data and calculate the best solution. The benefits and applications of machine learning in various industries enable the automation and optimization of many tasks, such as prediction, classification and segmentation, leading to greater efficiency and accuracy. Its applications are wide ranging and include industries such as the financial sector, healthcare, the marketing industry, manufacturing industry and many others.

We can say that ML is a branch of the broader field of artificial intelligence that uses statistical models to develop predictions. It is often described as a form of predictive modelling or analytics and is traditionally defined as the ability of a

computer to learn without explicit programming. According to Mitchell, 1997, definition of ML is: *A computer program is said to learn from experience E with respect to some task T and some performance measure P, if its performance on T, as measured by P, improves with experience E.* In basic technical terms, machine learning uses algorithms that take in historical data, analyse them, and generate output based on that analysis. In general, the algorithms do the so-called "training with data" which is a learning process where they learn hidden patterns and relationships in data, then they perform predictions on new data and look for ways to improve their performance over time.

Machine learning is particularly useful for the following types of problems:

- For tasks that people solve very easily, but they are not able to accurately (algorithmically) describe how they do it. Example: recognition of images, sound, speech.
- For tasks where solving algorithms can be defined, but these algorithms are very complex and/or require large knowledge bases. Example: automatic translation.
- In many areas where data is continuously collected with the aim of "getting something out of them". Example: in medicine (data of patients and used therapies), sports (matches played and individual players' play), marketing (about users/customers and what they bought, what they were interested in, how they rated the products, etc.)

There are three types of machine learning: Supervised learning, Unsupervised learning and Reinforcement learning.

Supervised learning: The algorithm is fed with data and the desired outputs from which it learns input/output relationships. The algorithm should learn to provide appropriate outputs for appropriate data. A program that learns receives a set of the desired/correct values (often called labels), so that for each input we have the correct/desired output. We say that the program learns from labelled data. The main goal is that the program learns on training dataset underlying patterns and input/output relationships, so that for new data that were not in the set on which the system was trained on, it is capable of assigning the correct output value. The types of supervised learning are: **classification** (output value is categorical) and **regression** (output value is continuous).

Classification is a type of task where the goal is to categorise input data into predefined classes or labels. The algorithm learns from a set of labelled training data and then predicts the class of new, unseen instances. Essentially, classification is about assigning categories to input data based on patterns and features learned during the training phase. Some of the most popular classifiers are: Bayesian classifier, KNN (K nearest-neighbours), SVM (Support-vector machine), Decision Tree Classifier, Linear Discriminant Analysis, Neural Networks, Logistic Regression, etc. (Tao et al., 2019) Classification is widely used in diverse applications, such as spam email detection, image recognition, medical diagnosis, sentiment analysis, and fraud detection. It is a crucial component in building intelligent systems that can automate decision-making processes based on learned patterns. In

classification, output is categorical value such as: spam or not spam, sport article or cultural article or news article, scart or not scart. In classification, the algorithm learns **decision boundaries** in the feature space that separate different classes. These boundaries are determined during the training phase and guide the classification of new instances. On Figure 8 an example of classification is presented.

Figure 8

Example of classification

Note. From Subsets of Artificial Intelligence, by Javapoint (2019), (<https://www.javatpoint.com/subsets-of-ai>)

Regression is used to model the relationship between a dependent variable (target) and one or more independent variables (features or predictors). The goal is to learn a mapping function that can predict a continuous output based on input features. Regression is widely used in fields such as finance, economics, healthcare, and many others for making quantitative predictions and informed decisions based on data. There are several types of regression. Regression can be: Linear, Polynomial, Stepwise Regression, Ridge Regression, Lasso Regression, ElasticNet Regression (Géron, 2022). Linear regression assumes a linear relationship between the input features and the output variable. It aims to find the best-fitting line that minimises the difference between predicted and actual values. Polynomial Regression extends linear regression by allowing for polynomial relationships

between features and the target variable. Ridge Regression (L2 regularisation) and Lasso Regression (L1 regularisation) introduce regularisation terms to prevent overfitting by penalising large coefficients in the model. Regression deals with predicting continuous values or numerical outcomes. On Figure 3 is presented example of linear regression where the goal is to predict house price which depends on house size in square feet.

Figure 9

Example of regression

Note. From Application of predictive maintenance concepts using artificial intelligence tools, by Cardoso & Ferreira, (2020)

Unsupervised learning: The algorithm is fed with unlabelled data. e.g., data do not have output. A learning program is given a set of input data, but there is no information about the desired output value. The task of the program is to find out hidden structures/regularities and patterns in the data. Unsupervised learning is also called clustering. Clustering can be: k-means, mountain clustering, subtractive clustering, neural network, etc. On Figure 10 is presented an example of clustering.

Figure 10

Example of clustering

Note. From Hands-on machine learning with Scikit-Learn, Keras, and TensorFlow, by Géron, (2022)

Reinforcement learning: Reinforcement learning (RL) is a distinct type of machine learning that is neither purely supervised nor purely unsupervised. Instead, it represents a unique paradigm of learning where an agent learns to make sequential decisions by interacting with an environment to maximise cumulative rewards, because the system still receives feedback from the environment, but feedback is more often criticism than instruction. In other words, a "behaviour critic" will say whether the agent's behaviour is good or not, but it won't say what it should be. The learning system, called an agent in this context, can observe the environment, select and perform actions, and get rewards in return (or penalties in the form of negative rewards). It must then learn by itself what is the best strategy, called a policy, to get the most reward over time. A policy defines what action the agent should choose when it is in a given situation (Burkov, 2019). Popular reinforcement learning algorithms are: Q-learning, temporal-difference learning, deep reinforcement learning, etc.

There are also hybrid approaches, including semi-supervised learning, which can be tailored to the problem the researcher wants to solve. Each approach has its specific strengths and weaknesses, and some techniques are better suited to certain types of problems than others.

In general, below are basic steps for implementing ML algorithms:

1. **Data Collection and Preprocessing:** Gather the relevant data for a problem that needs to be solved and clean it by handling missing values, removing outliers, and encoding categorical variables if necessary. This step ensures that the data is in a suitable format for training a model, enhancing its predictive performance.

2. **Splitting Data:** Divide the dataset into training and testing subsets (and optionally, validation set) to assess the model's performance on unseen data. This prevents overfitting by evaluating the model's generalisation ability on data it hasn't seen during training.

3. **Model selection:** Select an appropriate ML algorithm based on the problem type (e.g., classification, regression) and the characteristics of the data. The choice of model impacts the model's ability to capture patterns and make accurate predictions.

4. **Model training:** Fit the chosen model on the training data to learn the underlying patterns and relationships. Through this process, the model adjusts its parameters to minimise the difference between predicted and actual outcomes.

5. **Model Evaluation:** Assess the model's performance using appropriate evaluation metrics (e.g., accuracy, precision, recall, F1-score for classification; MSE, RMSE for regression). This step helps in understanding how well the model generalises to unseen data and identifies areas for improvement.

6. **Hyperparameter Tuning:** Fine-tune the model's hyperparameters to optimise its performance further. Adjusting hyperparameters such as learning rate, regularisation strength, or tree depth can significantly impact the model's performance.

7. **Model Deployment:** Deploy the trained model into production, making it accessible for making predictions on new data. This step involves integrating the model into existing systems or applications for real-world use.

8. **Monitoring and Maintenance:** Continuously monitor the model's performance in production and update it as needed to adapt to changing data patterns or requirements. Regular maintenance ensures that the model remains effective and relevant over time.

Further explanation of specific steps for ML algorithms implementation can be found in Bobbitt (2021), Ziganto (2018) and Tran et al. (2021). Also, a complete ML roadmap for learning machine learning from beginner level to more advanced topics can be found in Sainath (2021).

4. Machine learning in predictive maintenance

In the manufacturing environment, maintenance is one of the most important success factors. Poorly maintained equipment often leads to unplanned downtime and low performance. Different corporations have different maintenance strategies depending on several factors, such as maintenance goals, equipment's nature, operational process design, and work environment (Nowakowski et al., 2019). Commonly used maintenance approaches are categorised into a) corrective maintenance, b) preventive maintenance, c) predictive maintenance (PM), and d)

proactive maintenance (Mohan et al., 2021). Amongst these approaches, the PM aims to make timely maintenance decisions by focusing on fault detection, component diagnosis, degradation monitoring, and failure prediction in real-time, therefore reducing the uncertainty of maintenance activities.

With the rise of Industry 4.0, IT infrastructure has been continuously improved to support smart sensing, Internet of Things (IoT), big data collection, and analytics tools, so companies now can get the most out of their data. Data-driven decisions can be made by analysing historical events and trends in the past. Artificial intelligence and its subfield ML are an element of Industry 4.0, showing its application in the manufacturing industry as a powerful tool for machine health diagnosis. By utilising ML in processing, continuously monitoring, and analysing equipment's health, corporations can achieve greater operational and maintenance efficiency and effective growth management by improving equipment performance. A case study (BigData Republic, 2017) shows an 84% reduction of breakdown time and 88% reduction of breakdown occurrences when applying an intelligent ML-based PM approach compared to the conventional Industry 3.0 setup. This will also increase the availability and reliability of equipment and reduce operational risks, therefore improving corporates' competitive advantages.

The biggest challenge when we use ML in PM applications is to choose the most suitable, simple, and effective algorithm for each specific problem. ML algorithms often require large data acquisition about failure situations and different operating states of the system or device to train the model. When we apply ML algorithms to predictive maintenance, we follow the same steps as described before, but in this case, we have to adapt the whole process to the specific PM problem we are trying to solve. The challenge of proper maintenance grows with the complexity of machines: in a system with many components working together and influencing each other's lifetime, how can we find the right moment when maintenance should be performed so that components are not prematurely replaced but the whole system still stays functioning reliably? Providing an answer to this question is the aim of predictive maintenance, where we seek to build models that quantify the risk of failure for a machine at any moment in time and use this information to improve scheduling of maintenance. The success of predictive maintenance models depends on three main components: having the right data available, framing the problem appropriately and evaluating the predictions properly (Si et al., 2011).

To build a failure model, we require enough historical data that allows us to capture information about events leading to failure. In addition to that, general "static" features of the system can also provide valuable information, such as mechanical properties, average usage and operating conditions. However, more data is not always better. When collecting data to support a failure model, it is important to make an inventory of the following: What are the types of failure that can occur?

Which ones will we try to predict? How does the “failure process” look like? Is it a slow degradation process or an acute one? Which parts of the machine/system could be related to each type of failure? What can be measured about each of them that reflect their state? How often and with which accuracy do these measurements need to be performed? Data acquisition is a prerequisite from which raw data can be processed and analysed later to solve a PM problem. Data acquisition involves designing and sizing the appropriate system architecture to be installed on the equipment to capture and store different sensing data. A data acquisition system consists of sensors, data transmission, and data storage devices. Depending on equipment types, different combinations of sensors are used so that the captured data can fully reflect the degradation process of machinery. Some commonly used sensors are accelerometers, acoustic emission sensors, infrared thermometers, current, temperature, and pressure sensors, etc. The captured data are transmitted into a PC or portable devices through a data transmission device and stored in a memory location or historian system for further analysis. With a rapid development of sensor and communication technologies, more advanced data acquisition devices have been designed and applied to modern industries. After data collection the next step is data pre-processing. Commonly used techniques for data pre-processing include data normalisation and noise removal, feature extraction, and feature selection (Nowakowski et al., 2019).

The life span of machines is usually in the order of years, which means that data has to be collected for an extended period of time in order to observe the system throughout its degradation process. An ideal scenario would be that both data scientists and domain experts are involved in the data collection plan to ensure that the data gathered are suitable for the model to be built. However, what mostly happens in real life is that the data has already been collected before the data scientist arrives and they must try to make the best of what is available.

Depending on the characteristics of the system and on the data available, a proper framing of the model to be built is essential: which question do we want the model to answer and is it possible with the data we have at hand?

When thinking about how to frame a predictive maintenance model, it is important to keep a couple of questions in mind:

- What kind of output should the model give?
- Is enough historical data available or just static data?
- Is every recorded event labelled, i.e. which measurements correspond to good functioning and which ones correspond to failure? Or at least, is it known when each machine failed (if at all)?
- When labelled events are available, what is the proportion of the number of events of each type of failure and events of well-functioning?
- How long in advance should the model be able to indicate that a failure will occur?

- What are the performance targets that the model should be optimised for? High precision, high sensitivity/recall, high accuracy? What is the consequence of not predicting a failure or predicting a failure that will not happen?

With all this information at hand, we can now decide which modelling strategy fits best to the available data and the desired output, or at least which one is the best candidate to start with. There are multiple modelling strategies for predictive maintenance and we will describe four of them in relation to the question they aim to answer and which kind of data they require:

1. Regression models to predict remaining useful lifetime (RUL)
2. Classification models to predict failure within a given time window
3. Anomaly detection
4. Survival models for the prediction of failure probability over time

4.1 Regression models to predict remaining useful lifetime (RUL)

Prediction of the **remaining useful life** (RUL) of machinery is the most critical problem in the field of PM. The RUL of machinery is defined as “the length from the current time to the end of the useful life” (Katser, 2023). So, the main question that we have is: How many days/cycles are left before the system fails? For this kind of problem, we need static and historical data available, and also every event must be labelled. Several events of each type of failure are presented in the collected dataset. Based on static characteristics of the system and on how it behaves now, the remaining useful time can be predicted, which implies that both static and historical data are required, and that the degradation process is smooth. Just one type of “path to failure” is being modelled: if many types of failure are possible and the system’s behaviour preceding each one of them differs, one dedicated model should be made for each of them. We must have labelled data available and measurements that were taken at different moments during the system’s lifetime. There are several types of regression that we can use depending which kind of problem we are trying to solve. We can use: Linear regression which is simple and interpretable and assumes a linear relationship between input features and remaining useful life, Polynomial Regression as extension of linear regression by introducing polynomial terms which can capture more complex relationships between features and RUL, Support Vector Regression based on support vector machines which is effective for high-dimensional data and can handle non-linear relationships, Random Forest Regression (ensemble learning method) which is robust and can capture complex relationships in the data, Gradient Boosting Regression which builds a series of weak learners to create a strong predictive model (XGBoost and LightGBM are the most popular implementations), Deep learning models which can capture intricate patterns in the data, Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) networks which are commonly used for time-series data, Time-

series Models (ARIMA and SARIMA) which are suitable for time-dependent data, capturing trends and seasonality and Prognostics Models which are designed specifically for predicting the remaining useful life. Common evaluation metrics for regression models include Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and R-squared. These metrics quantify the accuracy and goodness of fit between predicted and actual values. Regression comprises understanding of relationships between variables, selecting appropriate features, and evaluating the model's performance using various metrics. Practical example of predicting RUL with regression can be found in (Ouda et al., 2021).

4.2 Classification models to predict failure within a given time window

Creating a model which can predict lifetimes accurately can be very challenging. In practice however, one usually does not need to predict the lifetime very accurate far in the future. Often the maintenance team only needs to know if the machine will fail 'soon'. So, the main question that we now have is: Will a machine fail in the next N days/cycles? For this kind of problem, we also need static and historical data available, and also every event must be labelled. The assumptions of a classification model are very similar to those of regression models. They mostly differ on: Since we are defining a failure in a time window instead of an exact time, the requirement of smoothness of the degradation process is relaxed.

In classification, during the training phase, the ML algorithm is provided with a labelled dataset. This dataset consists of input examples along with their corresponding correct labels. The algorithm analyses the input data, identifies patterns, and learns the relationships between features and labels. The goal is for the model to generalise from the training data so that it can accurately classify new, unseen instances. Once the model is trained, it can be used to predict the labels of new, unseen data. The input features of the new data are fed into the trained model, and the algorithm uses the learned patterns to assign a predicted label or category. The accuracy of the model's predictions is often evaluated using metrics such as precision, recall, and F1 score. Types of classification are: binary classification and multiclass classification. In binary classification, the algorithm categorises data into two distinct classes or labels, such as spam or not spam, positive or negative. In multiclass classification, the task involves assigning data points to more than two classes. Each instance is assigned to one of several possible classes.

Classification models can deal with multiple types of failure, as long as they are framed as a multi-class problem, e.g.: class = 0 corresponding to no failure in the

next n days, class = 1 for failure type 1 in the next n days, class = 2 for failure type 2 in the next n days and so forth. For this type of problem, it is expected that labelled data are available and there are “enough” cases of each type of failure to train and evaluate the model.

In general, what regression and classification models are doing is modelling the relationship between features and the degradation path of the system. That means that if the model is applied to a system that will exhibit a different type of failure not present in the training data, the model will fail to predict it. There are several types of classifiers that we can use depending which kind of problem we are trying to solve. We can use: Logistic regression, Decision Trees, Random Forest, Support Vector Machines, K-Nearest Neighbors, Neural Networks, Naïve Bayes, Ensemble methods (GitHub, 2020). The choice of algorithm depends on the nature of the data, the complexity of the relationships between features and labels, and the specific requirements of the classification task. Practical example of classification with XGBoost can be found in (Choi et al., 2022).

4.3 Anomaly detection

Both previous strategies require a lot of examples of both normal behaviour (of which we often have a lot of) and examples of failures. However, in some cases we do not have all this information. If we have mission critical systems, in which acute repairs are difficult, there are often only limited, or no examples of failures at all. In this case, a different strategy is necessary. We now have a different question: Is the shown behaviour normal? We need static and historical data available, but either labels are unknown or too few failure events were observed or there are too many types of failure. For this kind of problem, it must be possible to define what normal behaviour is and the difference between current and “normal” behaviour is related to degradation leading to failure. The generality of an anomaly detection model is both its biggest advantage and pitfall: the model should be able to flag every type of failure, despite not having any previous knowledge about them. Anomalous behaviour, however, does not necessarily lead to failure. And if it does, the model does not give information about the time span it should occur. The evaluation of an anomaly detection model is also challenging due to the lack of labelled data. If at least some labelled data of failure events is available, it can and should be used for evaluating the algorithm. When no labelled data is available, the model is usually made available and domain experts provide feedback on the quality of its anomaly flagging ability.

More generally speaking, anomaly detection in predictive maintenance involves identifying unusual patterns or outliers in data that may indicate potential equipment failures or abnormalities. This is crucial for proactive maintenance to prevent unexpected breakdowns and reduce downtime. Several machine learning techniques can be applied for anomaly detection in predictive maintenance (GitHub, 2022):

- **Supervised Learning:** Using labelled data, where the model is trained on normal and abnormal instances. This approach requires a dataset with labelled examples of both normal and anomalous behaviour.
- **Unsupervised Learning:** Anomaly detection can be performed without labelled data. Algorithms like Isolation Forests, One-Class SVM, and Autoencoders are commonly used for unsupervised anomaly detection.
- **Time-Series Analysis:** In predictive maintenance, time-series data is common. Techniques such as Seasonal-Trend decomposition using LOESS (STL), Exponential Smoothing State Space Models (ETS), and autoregressive integrated moving average (ARIMA) models can be employed.
- **Prognostics Models:** These models not only detect anomalies but also predict the remaining useful life of equipment. They use historical data to estimate how much longer a component is likely to function before failure.
- **Feature Engineering:** Creating relevant features from the available data can enhance the performance of anomaly detection models. Domain knowledge is often crucial in identifying features that may be indicative of equipment health.
- Some popular tools and frameworks for implementing anomaly detection in predictive maintenance include:
 - **Scikit-learn:** A machine learning library in Python that provides various algorithms for anomaly detection.
 - **TensorFlow and PyTorch:** Popular deep learning frameworks that can be used to implement neural network-based anomaly detection models.
 - **Apache Spark MLlib:** A distributed machine learning library that includes tools for anomaly detection on large datasets.

When implementing anomaly detection for predictive maintenance, it's essential to evaluate the model's performance using metrics such as precision, recall, and F1 score, and to continuously update the model as new data becomes available. Practical example of anomaly detection in Python can be found in (Papathanasiou et al., 2023).

4.4 Survival models for the prediction of failure probability over time

The previous three approaches focus on prediction, giving us enough information to apply maintenance before failure. However, if we are interested in the degradation process itself and the resulting failure probability, this last strategy will be the best choice. For this problem, the main question is: Given a set of characteristics, how does the risk of failure change in time? We expect that static data are available, information on the reported failure time of each machine or recorded date of when a given machine became unobservable for failure. A survival model estimates the probability of failure for a given type of machine given static features and is also useful to analyse the impact of certain features on lifetime. It

provides, therefore, estimates for a group of machines of similar characteristics. Therefore, for a specific machine under investigation it does not take its specific current status into account.

Generally speaking, survival analysis is a branch of statistics and machine learning that deals with predicting the time until an event of interest (such as failure) occurs. It takes into account the time-to-event data and censoring, where some observations may not experience the event during the study period. In the context of failure prediction over time, survival models are commonly used (PySurvival, 2019). Below are some commonly used models:

- **Cox Proportional-Hazards Model:** This is a widely used survival model that assumes the hazard (instantaneous failure rate) is proportional across different levels of the predictor variables. It's a semi-parametric model that doesn't make strong assumptions about the shape of the hazard function.
- **Accelerated Failure Time (AFT) Models:** AFT models specify how the survival time is affected by predictor variables. It directly models the logarithm of the survival time as a linear function of covariates.
- **Kaplan-Meier Estimator:** While not a predictive model, this non-parametric statistic is often used to estimate the survival function from time-to-event data, especially when there is censoring.
- **Random Survival Forests:** This is an extension of random forests for survival analysis. It builds an ensemble of decision trees and handles censored data.
- **Deep Learning Models:** Neural networks, especially recurrent neural networks (RNNs) and long short-term memory networks (LSTMs), can be used for survival analysis. They are capable of capturing complex patterns in time-to-event data.

When applying survival models to predict failure probability over time, it's crucial to have a dataset with information about the time until failure or censoring, as well as relevant predictor variables. The choice of model depends on the characteristics of the data and the assumptions we are willing to make. It is crucial to always validate the model performance using appropriate metrics and consider the interpretability of the results for specific applications. The practical example of survival analysis and predictive maintenance in Python can be found in (Deisenroth et al., 2020).

H. Blockchain Applications in Predictive Maintenance

1. Introduction to Blockchain technology and its fundamental principles

Blockchain Technology has surpassed its initial use in cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin (Wood, 2014) and Ethereum (Mattila, 2016), and is widely considered a disruptive technology that may change the method of communications over the Internet (Nofer et al., 2017), (Morkunas et al., 2019). While the key aspects of all blockchain technologies remain mostly the same, such as having one or multiple transactions form blocks that form a chain, different approaches of block formation, levels of access and most importantly, consensus mechanism, heavily differ in various technologies (Zheng et al., 2017).

Blockchain technology imposes fundamental changes to the way personal data are being processed and can improve various data security solutions. A Blockchain can be viewed as a shared, append-only distributed ledger, in which all events (described by transactions) are stored in linked blocks (Lastovetska, 2019). A copy of this chain of blocks is kept by all nodes comprising the blockchain network.

Figure 11
Blockchain Structure

Note. From *Consensus Mechanisms: How Blockchains Stay Secure*, by Ledger Academy, (2023) (<https://www.ledger.com/academy/consensus-protocols-how-are-blockchains-secure>)

Each transaction contains a unique cryptographic signature decoupled with a timestamp, thereby making the ledger resistant to alterations. As the ledger is shared across all member nodes of the network simultaneously, all nodes are updated in real time. A block can be viewed as a data structure consisting of a set of transactions, and a header which connects the new block to the previous one.

All blocks hence form a chain, and can trace back to the first block, called the genesis block. A blockchain relies on peer-to-peer networking, public-key cryptography, and distributed consensus.

Figure 12

Decentralized consensus

Note. From Blockchain beyond bitcoin, by Underwood, (2016)

The combination of these three concepts is what secures blockchain transactions. Unlike a centralized system, no single entity should be able to control the process of adding a block to the chain: each block is managed by all nodes who share equal rights. This is done in order to overcome security issues and is achieved through the process known as distributed consensus. This process establishes an agreement among the nodes in the blockchain network in the validation of each data block to be added to the chain. Depending on the consensus algorithm, nodes can either compete for correct transaction validation, be chosen randomly, or apply a different algorithm altogether. These algorithms can vary in complexity.

Figure 13

Types of consensus mechanisms

Note. From Blockchain beyond bitcoin, by Underwood, (2016)

It is important to note that Blockchains are a class of technology; the term refers to different forms of distributed databases with variations in their technical and governance arrangements and complexity.

Blockchain is often referred as the next disruptive technology. The properties of transparency and immutability that blockchain technologies offer have surpassed its initial use in cryptocurrencies (Mettler, 2016). A variety of Blockchain solutions in healthcare, financial technology, supply chain management, and education are being developed, start-ups are formed and scientific research is being conducted (Grković et al., 2020; Cai, 2018; Saberi et al., 2019; Xu et al., 2018; Sang et al., 2020).

2. How Blockchain can contribute to data integrity and trust in maintenance

There are challenges when implementing a useful predictive maintenance program that must be addressed. The process involves collating and analyzing significant amounts of data from several sources, such as equipment sensors, operation logs, and upkeep records. Maintaining the purity of this data is essential to avoid inaccurate predictions that could lead to unexpected downtime or unnecessary maintenance operations. In multiple industries linked with machinery support systems, related information often connects with various other pipelines making it challenging for generating an integrated view concerning said equipment's status. This fragmentation not only impedes efficient analysis but also brings about risks pertaining to impaired integrity owing unique standards in each storage system utilized for collecting data.

The rise of the Internet of Things (IoT) has increased connectivity within industrial systems, resulting in a heightened concern regarding maintenance-related data security (Alabadi & Habbal, 2023). Cybersecurity breaches pose significant risks to predictive maintenance system reliability as they could result in data tampering or loss. Therefore, managing and securing this valuable information using a trustworthy approach is now more vital than ever before. One promising solution that offers decentralization, immutability, and transparency is blockchain technology. Implementing these technologies can enhance trustworthiness while enabling industries to achieve efficient predictive analytics for their respective equipment performance (Liu et al., 2018).

3. Blockchain's Role in Ensuring Data Integrity

Data integrity is a crucial element in predictive maintenance, and blockchain technology presents an innovative approach to storing, managing and ensuring

trust of data. The utilization of this technology within the context of predictive maintenance can revolutionize conventional practices by providing a highly secure, transparent and dependable means for handling data.

The most significant attribute of blockchain technology is its capacity for ensuring data immutability. Once information has been registered on a blockchain, it cannot be modified without the agreement of the entire network. This quality proves to be exceptionally useful in situations where upholding precision and consistency are critical concerns. For instance, let's consider sensor details that indicate equipment parts' wear and tear—once logged onto a blockchain these specifics become an immutable fact: such unchangeable nature authorizes dependable predictive analyses grounded in authentic facts rather than tampered records- thereby boosting reliability concerning maintenance callouts and operational verdicts based on this precise information stored within blockchains' secure recordkeeping system.

In contrast to conventional data storage methods that depend on centralized databases, blockchain technology operates in a distributed manner by distributing the information across various nodes. This approach guarantees that there is no single point of weakness which could jeopardize the authenticity of the records. Additionally, since new data entries are only appended onto the chain after being approved by multiple nodes via a consensus mechanism feature embedded within it, this collective validation process reinforces security measures and credibility throughout every node's system thus ensuring both consistency and accuracy overall.

Blockchain technologies possess a natural quality of transparency, allowing authorized parties to view all transactions. In an industrial context, this equates to increased clarity in maintenance operations. Network stakeholders have the ability to track complete records of machine maintenance history with precise and unmodified data. This degree of openness promotes responsibility among participants across the maintenance process - from operators up through technicians - assuring that every decision made is grounded on reliable and current information.

The potential of blockchain technology extends beyond data storage as it can facilitate complex operations such as executing smart contracts. These are self-executing agreements whose terms are written in code and, when applied to predictive maintenance, they enable automatic processes based on predetermined conditions. An instance would be a smart contract triggering a maintenance request upon detecting wear and tear exceeding specified limits from the tamper-proof data stored in the blockchain ledger. Apart from optimizing efficient performance during maintenance procedures, this automated approach guarantees that actions taken arise solely from reliable information (FAHM Technology Partners, 2018).

4. Use cases for implementing Blockchain in predictive maintenance, including distributed and immutable record-keeping

While it has been utilized most notably in the finance industry to facilitate cryptocurrencies, international payments, remittances and complex financial products; the potential applications for blockchain technology are numerous (Das, 2021).

Figure 14

The applications of blockchain

Note. From *Future Flight: Boeing Will Use Blockchain Tech to Track Unmanned Air Vehicles*, by Das, (2021) (<https://www.ccn.com/future-flight-boeing-will-use-blockchain-tech-to-track-unmanned-air-vehicles/>)

Predictive maintenance is already utilizing blockchain technology in various fields.

In the aerospace industry, blockchain technology has potential to improve safety and compliance. By using a blockchain ledger, maintenance history of aircraft parts can be tracked and recorded accurately due to their critical nature. Each part is tagged, and its record cannot be altered thereafter providing transparency for airline crews, manufacturers or regulators who may access it as required. Strategies are being pursued by various stakeholders in the aviation sector

including Airbus which explores ways of recording complete lifecycles while Air France-KLM integrates this technology tastefully into tracking manufacturing records ensuring that all components have an auditable lifecycle log with details such as originations, repairs etc enhancing further regulatory requirements (Bellamy, 2017a; Bellamy,2017b; Vujinovic, 2021).

The utilization of blockchain technology in manufacturing can facilitate the monitoring of crucial machinery and equipment maintenance. The integration of IoT and blockchain enables predictive maintenance, leading to a noteworthy reduction in downtime while driving enhanced efficiency. With sensors attached to each machine capturing real-time data streams into the distributed ledger system, advanced algorithms power analytics that predict when an industrial device is prone to malfunction, enabling proactive maintenance actions (Ortmeier, 2019).

Blockchain technology can be employed in the automotive sector to keep tabs on a vehicle's maintenance past. This feature is especially advantageous for pre-owned car sales, where unrestricted visibility of said history proves beneficial. Utilizing blockchain as its basis, this system logs all service and repair procedures conducted on an automobile. The data serves as pivotal information for interested buyers, insurers, and regulatory entities alike by ensuring that proper upkeep was carried out (Graser, 2020).

Blockchain technology can play a vital role in the energy industry, particularly with regards to renewable sources such as wind farms. It has the potential to accurately monitor and authenticate maintenance records of extensive equipment located across large geographical regions. By recording information on every wind turbine's upkeep history, this system guarantees data consistency while streamlining maintenance schedules through efficient organization (Ionita et al., 2021).

By showcasing how the essential traits of blockchain technologies - namely immutability, transparency, and security can be leveraged to enhance maintenance practices across diverse industries or sectors, these examples underscore its practicality. They vividly illustrate the immense gains made possible by integrating this technology in systems devoted to ensuring aerospace part safety as well as regulatory compliance or boosting dependability of automotive secondary markets amongst others.

I. Project management and collaboration tools

Project management tools play a crucial role in organizing, planning, and executing predictive maintenance activities. They help teams collaborate, track progress, manage resources, and ensure that maintenance tasks are completed efficiently. Here are several project management tools commonly used in the context of predictive maintenance:

- [Trello](#):

Description: Trello is a visual project management tool that uses boards, lists, and cards to organize tasks. It allows users to create boards for different maintenance projects and track the status of tasks in a visual and collaborative environment.

- [Asana](#):

Description: Asana is a flexible project management tool that enables teams to create projects, tasks, and timelines. It supports collaboration and communication, making it suitable for planning and tracking predictive maintenance activities.

- [Jira](#):

Description: Jira, developed by Atlassian, is widely used for issue tracking and project management. It can be customized for various workflows, making it suitable for managing maintenance tickets, tracking issues, and monitoring project progress.

- [Microsoft Project](#):

Description: Microsoft Project is a comprehensive project management software that allows users to plan, schedule, and track projects. It's suitable for complex predictive maintenance projects with detailed scheduling and resource management requirements.

- [Monday.com](#):

Description: Monday.com is a visual collaboration platform that offers customizable workspaces. It supports project tracking, task assignment, and communication, making it useful for managing maintenance projects and tracking progress.

- [Smartsheet](#):

Description: Smartsheet is a collaborative work management platform that combines the familiar spreadsheet interface with powerful project management features. It is suitable for creating maintenance schedules, tracking tasks, and managing resources.

- [Fiix](#):

Description: Fiix is a computerized maintenance management system (CMMS) that includes project management features. It helps organizations plan and track maintenance work, schedule tasks, and manage assets.

- [UpKeep](#):

Description: UpKeep is a mobile-first CMMS that simplifies maintenance management. It includes features for work order management, asset tracking, and preventive maintenance scheduling.

- [Maintenance Connection](#):

Description: Maintenance Connection is a CMMS that provides tools for managing work orders, preventive maintenance, and inventory. It aids in planning and scheduling maintenance activities.

- [IBM Maximo](#):

Description: IBM Maximo is an enterprise asset management (EAM) solution that includes features for asset tracking, work order management, and predictive maintenance. It is suitable for large-scale maintenance operations.

The choice of tool depends on the specific needs, size, and complexity of the predictive maintenance initiatives within an organization.

J. Conclusion

In the rapidly evolving landscape of infrastructure and industrial systems, the implementation of Predictive Maintenance (PM) emerges not only as a necessity but as a catalyst for positive change. As we reflect on the comprehensive exploration of Predictive Maintenance Systems (PMS), digital skills, and the ambitious objectives outlined in the PreMETS initiative, it becomes evident that the intersection of innovation, education, and technology holds the key to a resilient, efficient, and sustainable future. The urgency to embrace Predictive Maintenance is underscored by its pivotal role in averting catastrophic failures, ensuring human safety, and optimizing resource utilization. The economic and social advantages it brings, ranging from enhanced safety to substantial energy savings, position PM as a cornerstone in the optimization of infrastructure and industrial processes.

The PreMETS initiative plays a pivotal role in shaping the future of Predictive Maintenance by addressing crucial gaps in innovation, expertise, and training. By fostering innovative teaching methods, promoting entrepreneurship, and creating a digital platform that encompasses the entire PM training process, PreMETS aims

to cultivate a skilled workforce capable of navigating the complexities of modern industrial landscapes.

The extensive list of digital skills outlined in this document serves as a roadmap for professionals venturing into Predictive Maintenance. From technical proficiency to data analysis, cloud computing, and beyond, these skills form the foundation for leveraging technology effectively. As the Fourth Industrial Revolution unfolds, proficiency in signal processing, machine learning, and emerging technologies like IoT and blockchain become indispensable.

The learning modules presented herein offer a structured approach to acquiring the necessary knowledge and skills. From understanding the impact of digitalization to delving into the intricacies of data utilization, structural simulation, and AI applications, each session contributes to a holistic understanding of Predictive Maintenance.

In conclusion, Predictive Maintenance stands as a beacon of progress, and the PreMETS initiative lights the path forward. By investing in education, fostering innovation, and cultivating a workforce with digital dexterity, we propel ourselves towards a future where infrastructure is not merely maintained but optimized with precision and foresight.

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PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education and training

Funded by
the European Union

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BOOKLET

Module WN3: Green skills competences for PM

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

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A. Introduction

This booklet addresses diverse facets of sustainability, environmental responsibility, and energy efficiency across various industrial contexts. The Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) framework is highlighted as a crucial tool for assessing companies' approaches to managing sustainability issues, emphasizing the absence of a universal ESG reporting standard and the pivotal role of quality departments in achieving ESG objectives. Measuring and reporting greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, particularly the challenges associated with Scope 3 emissions in manufacturing, are also discussed in section two. Additionally, the evaluation and reduction of the impact of human activities on the environment are explored, emphasizing the role of environment-oriented software tools, such as life cycle assessment software.

Predictive maintenance is a proactive approach that leverages data analysis and machine learning to predict when equipment and systems will require maintenance, thereby preventing unexpected failures and minimizing downtime. This methodology is gaining traction in industries such as construction and transport, where operational efficiency and safety are paramount. By incorporating predictive maintenance, companies can enhance lifecycle costing, end-of-life management, resource efficiency, and waste management, all while aligning with regulatory frameworks like the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD).

In conclusion, a comprehensive overview of sustainability challenges and solutions, encompassing ESG frameworks, GHG emissions reporting, renewable energy adoption, and the crucial role of energy and resource efficiency in various industrial sectors are going to be explored in this booklet. In particular, the following sections will be discussed: ESG Compliance & ESG reporting in manufacturing, emissions reduction in manufacturing, hybrid lifecycle analysis, resource efficiency strategies in manufacturing, and clean energy in manufacturing.

B. ESG compliance and reporting in manufacturing

In an era dominated by a heightened awareness of environmental issues, ethical considerations, and transparent governance, manufacturers are prioritizing the integration of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) objectives. Yet, this integration surpasses mere compliance with regulations; it entails incorporating sustainability into the very essence of an organization's values and operations. This process necessitates a broader understanding of "green jobs," an acknowledgment of the pivotal role played by quality departments, and committed leadership that is prepared to confront challenges such as the talent gap and diverse reporting requirements.

The Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) framework serves as a tool for investors to assess a company's approach to managing risks and opportunities related to sustainability issues. ESG offers a holistic perspective, encompassing not only environmental considerations but also social and corporate governance aspects.

Figure 1

The Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) framework Farnsworth

Note. From Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) explained: Five important considerations for companies and their lawyers, by Rubic et al., (2022)

Predictive Maintenance in Construction

In the construction industry, machinery and equipment are critical assets. Traditional maintenance strategies, such as reactive or preventive maintenance, often result in either unplanned downtime or unnecessary maintenance activities. Predictive maintenance addresses these issues by utilizing advanced technologies such as IoT sensors, big data analytics, and machine learning algorithms.

1. **Lifecycle Costing:** Predictive maintenance can significantly reduce the total cost of ownership of construction equipment. By accurately predicting when maintenance is needed, companies can avoid the high costs associated with unexpected breakdowns and extend the useful life of their assets.
2. **Resource Efficiency and Waste Management:** Implementing predictive maintenance helps optimize the use of materials and energy, reducing waste and improving resource efficiency. For example, timely maintenance of machinery can ensure that it operates at peak efficiency, consuming less fuel and producing fewer emissions.
3. **End-of-Life Management:** Predictive maintenance also aids in planning for the end-of-life phase of construction equipment. By understanding the wear and tear on machinery, companies can make informed decisions about refurbishment, repurposing, or recycling, contributing to a circular economy.

Predictive Maintenance in Transport

In the transport sector, ensuring the reliability and safety of vehicles is crucial. Predictive maintenance offers a way to monitor the health of transport vehicles continuously, ensuring that they remain operational and safe for use.

1. **Lifecycle Costing:** Similar to construction, predictive maintenance in transport can lower lifecycle costs by reducing unexpected breakdowns and extending the life of vehicles. This approach enables more accurate budgeting for maintenance activities and replacement parts.
2. **Resource Efficiency and Waste Management:** Predictive maintenance ensures that vehicles operate at optimal efficiency. This reduces fuel consumption and emissions, contributing to more sustainable transport operations. Additionally, it minimizes the environmental impact by reducing the need for frequent part replacements and repairs.
3. **End-of-Life Management:** For transport vehicles, predictive maintenance provides insights into the degradation patterns of various components. This information can be used to plan for refurbishing or repurposing parts, thereby reducing waste and supporting sustainable practices.

Regulatory Frameworks and Compliance

Predictive maintenance aligns well with regulatory frameworks like the CSRD, which emphasizes transparency and accountability in sustainability reporting. By implementing predictive maintenance, companies can demonstrate their commitment to sustainability and compliance with regulations that focus on environmental impact, resource efficiency, and corporate responsibility.

1. **Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD):** The CSRD requires companies to report on a range of sustainability metrics, including those related to resource use and environmental impact. Predictive maintenance provides the data needed to report accurately on these metrics, helping companies meet their reporting obligations.
2. **Other Regulations:** Various industry-specific regulations also mandate the maintenance and operational standards for machinery and vehicles. Predictive maintenance ensures compliance with these standards, enhancing safety and reliability.

Manufacturing organizations are placing growing significance on Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) goals, aiming to harmonize business practices with societal expectations. In navigating the diverse landscape of standards, frameworks, and discretionary reporting requirements, quality departments emerge as pivotal contributors, facilitating organizations in achieving their ESG objectives.

Regulatory compliance constitutes the essential standards set by the government, serving as the minimum requirement for organizations. In contrast, Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors encompass non-regulatory elements where organizations surpass the mandated baseline. Unlike regulatory requirements, ESG standards lack uniformity, reflecting a broader and more varied set of considerations that companies voluntarily adopt to address environmental, social, and governance issues (Minutolo, 2023).

ESG reporting involves publicly disclosing Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) data, aiming to illuminate a company's ESG activities and enhance transparency with investors.

An ESG framework provides a structured approach to ESG reporting, generating measurable, actionable, and credible results. ESG standards operationalize ESG framework principles by defining factors such as metrics, methodologies, and reporting formats.

Due to the absence of a universal ESG reporting standard, various standards are utilized, with common ones including the Task Force on Climate-related Financial Disclosures (TCFD) and the United Nations Global Compact (UNGC). ESG

compliance refers to meeting or surpassing the ESG guidelines established by compliance frameworks and regulatory bodies.

Figure 2

ESG reporting and preparation of a sustainability report

Note. From ESG reporting and preparation of a sustainability report, by PricewaterhouseCoopers, (2023)

Figure 3

TCFD Framework, 2017

Recommendations and Supporting Recommended Disclosures			
Governance	Strategy	Risk Management	Metrics and Targets
Disclose the organization's governance around climate-related risks and opportunities.	Disclose the actual and potential impacts of climate-related risks and opportunities on the organization's businesses, strategy, and financial planning where such information is material.	Disclose how the organization identifies, assesses, and manages climate-related risks.	Disclose the metrics and targets used to assess and manage relevant climate-related risks and opportunities where such information is material.
Recommended Disclosures	Recommended Disclosures	Recommended Disclosures	Recommended Disclosures
a) Describe the board's oversight of climate-related risks and opportunities.	a) Describe the climate-related risks and opportunities the organization has identified over the short, medium, and long term.	a) Describe the organization's processes for identifying and assessing climate-related risks.	a) Disclose the metrics used by the organization to assess climate-related risks and opportunities in line with its strategy and risk management process.
b) Describe management's role in assessing and managing climate-related risks and opportunities.	b) Describe the impact of climate-related risks and opportunities on the organization's businesses, strategy, and financial planning.	b) Describe the organization's processes for managing climate-related risks.	b) Disclose Scope 1, Scope 2, and, if appropriate, Scope 3 greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and the related risks.
	c) Describe the resilience of the organization's strategy, taking into consideration different climate-related scenarios, including a 2°C or lower scenario.	c) Describe how processes for identifying, assessing, and managing climate-related risks are integrated into the organization's overall risk management.	c) Describe the targets used by the organization to manage climate-related risks and opportunities and performance against targets.

Note. From *TCFD issues new guidance as its climate reporting framework continues to gain traction*, by Morawetz et al., (2021)

Choosing the appropriate standard from various options like Reuters, Bloomberg, or other ESG measuring agencies poses a common challenge for organizations (Minutolo, 2023). It is crucial that the selected standards align with the organization's objectives.

However, the complexity arises from the absence of a singular ESG standard; different measuring entities, such as Reuters, Bloomberg, and others, each have their distinct criteria. This diversity complicates the decision-making process for companies seeking alignment with a specific standard.

Despite this challenge, selecting a reporting agency that aligns with an organization's goals can yield precise measurements. For instance, Bloomberg focuses on the percentage of disclosure an organization aims to achieve, with higher scores indicating greater transparency to the public. These disclosure scores not only function as targets but also facilitate engagement with stakeholders. By divulging information about governance practices, an organization can initiate a dialogue with its audience. Once stakeholders possess this information, they can provide feedback, enabling the organization to make well-informed decisions based on the input received.

ESG Framework

An ESG rating, also known as an ESG score, serves as a benchmark for investors to assess a company's Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) performance and make comparisons with other companies. Greenwashing is a significant aspect of ESG reporting, representing the practice of misleadingly presenting a company's environmental efforts or sustainability practices to create a more favourable impression than warranted.

ESG metrics refer to non-financial indicators that assess companies' performance in the Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) domains. These metrics include both quantitative measures, such as greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and qualitative assessments, such as Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI). Examples of ESG metrics include: Levels of carbon dioxide, kWh, cubic meters, but also: employee surveys, human rights violations, and amount of tax paid etc.⁴

With the growing awareness of climate change and social inequity, there is an escalating interest among consumers, investors, and regulators in the realm of environmental, social, and governance (ESG) activities. Information plays a crucial role as an input for stakeholders when making decisions. The pressure from investors and stakeholders can incentivize a shift towards activities that align with ESG principles or are financially lucrative, especially when direct regulation of these activities is challenging or impractical. Consequently, governments and industry bodies are actively developing standards for corporate ESG reporting. Greenwashing remains a notable aspect of ESG reporting, emphasizing the need to address misleading presentations of environmental or sustainability efforts (Kaplan et al., 2021).

Multiple stakeholders depend on ESG data reported by companies to evaluate investment prospects, choose suppliers, and make other significant decisions. The increasing dependence on ESG disclosures and the inherent challenges in evaluating them are pushing for greater standardization in reporting. Notably, several third-party entities, such as S&P Global, MSCI, and Refinitiv, are creating their own ESG frameworks and methodologies to enable a more uniform evaluation of ESG performance data.⁵

Many organizations have primarily concentrated on the compliance and reporting aspects of their Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) objectives. While these components are undoubtedly crucial, they form just one part of the more extensive perspective on sustainability. Some organizations find themselves confined to a narrow emphasis on compliance and reporting, potentially overlooking the broader aspects of sustainability.

⁴ Source: <https://quantive.com/resources/articles/esg-metrics>, accessed on 4.12.2023.

⁵ Source: <https://www.pwc.com/ca/en/today-s-issues/environmental-social-and-governance/measure-esg-performance.html>, accessed on 4.12.2023.

Figure 4

NAVEX Global *ESG investing statistics, data & trends*

Companies believing they are performing well on E,S, and G factors

Percentage

Source: NAVEX Global

Note. From *ESG investing statistics, data & trends in 2024*, by Vitali, (2024)

Rather than merely adhering to standards, leaders should envision a transformation in the nature of work, value, products, and processes that genuinely benefits everyone. This entails contemplating resource dependency, reimagining the built environment and infrastructure, and approaching innovation with a focus on resilience and a culture of transparency.

Regarding quality, the objective should not be limited to integrating quality methodologies into Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) initiatives. Instead, quality departments should play a pivotal role by bringing their methodologies to the forefront when shaping the vision for a more sustainable organization. This involves collaboratively defining goals, objectives, and measurable criteria that will be monitored through the ESG program and governance.

The integration of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) goals is a gradual process that doesn't occur overnight. Achieving sustainability involves a

transformative journey, necessitating the reimagining of traditional roles, aligning quality methodologies with sustainability objectives, and emphasizing growth, regeneration, and equity beyond mere compliance.

ESG Risks

Addressing sustainability challenges has evolved into a global imperative for business success. Companies are increasingly recognizing that they cannot afford to ignore or navigate the wave of sustainability issues alone while meeting the broader expectations of stakeholders. To effectively address some of the most pressing Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) concerns—such as climate change, greenhouse gas emissions, access to non-renewable resources, and preventing human rights violations—businesses are forming strategic networks. This collaborative approach emphasizes the necessity for transparent and accountable governance mechanisms (Kiron et al., 2015).

In today's business landscape, transparent measurement and disclosure of ESG performance are considered integral components of effective business management. The growing prevalence of sustainability reporting, coupled with the intricacies of reporting measures, has raised concerns about the reliability of such information among stakeholders (Lokuwaduge et al., 2022). The complexity surrounding these disclosures has created a challenge in developing a comprehensive solution to ensure the credibility of ESG reporting, highlighting the urgent need for a trustworthy framework in this domain.

The escalation of concerns about greenwashing on a global scale can be attributed to the absence of international standards governing ESG-related taxonomy. Within the environmental context, the term 'greenwashing' refers to potentially misleading disclosures and claims. This term encompasses a broad spectrum of actions that involve exaggerating and misrepresenting the 'green' credentials of a company or its products. Greenwashing may manifest as a marketing tactic crafted to create a positive impression, as outlined by Corrs Chambers Westgarth in 2021. At the more deceptive end of the spectrum, it involves actions designed to mislead and deceive investors and customers, often through the use of terms such as "clean energy."

ESG Integration

ESG practitioners employ a variety of acronyms, terms, and methodologies when discussing ESG integration, creating challenges for those outside the ESG field to ascertain whether they are engaging in ESG integration. Phrases like sustainable investing, ESG investing, socially responsible investing (SRI), green investing, ethical investing, and impact investing are often used interchangeably.

Within this context, ESG integration is explicitly defined as "the deliberate and systematic inclusion of ESG factors in investment analysis and decision-making." It represents a comprehensive approach to investment analysis, wherein both material factors—encompassing ESG factors and traditional financial considerations—are identified and evaluated to inform investment decisions.

ESG integration typically involves three main components:

Research:

Information gathering: Practitioners collect financial and ESG data from various sources, including company reports and third-party investment research.

Materiality analysis: Practitioners scrutinise pertinent financial and ESG information to pinpoint significant factors influencing a company, sector, and/or country.

Active ownership assessment: Practitioners engage in discussions with companies/issuers regarding material financial and ESG factors, monitoring the outcomes of such engagements and/or voting activities.

Security and portfolio analysis: Practitioners evaluate the impact of material financial and ESG factors on the corporate and investment performance of entities such as companies, sectors, countries, and portfolios. This evaluation may result in adjustments to forecasted financials, valuation-model variables, valuation multiples, forecasted financial ratios, internal credit assessments, and/or portfolio weightings.

Investment decision: The material traditional financial factors and ESG factors that have been identified and assessed play a crucial role in influencing the decision to buy/increase weighting, hold/maintain weighting, sell/decrease weighting, or take no action/not invest.

However, ESG integration does not imply a prohibition on investing in specific sectors, countries, or companies. It does not necessitate sacrificing portfolio returns to implement ESG integration techniques, dismissing immaterial ESG factors from investment decisions, or neglecting traditional financial factors. Additionally, it does not mandate significant alterations to the existing investment process. ESG integration is about incorporating environmental, social, and governance factors deliberately and systematically into the investment analysis and decision-making process, without imposing restrictions or compromising overall portfolio performance.

ESG integration and exclusionary screening may be mistakenly perceived as synonymous practices. However, these approaches differ fundamentally in two key aspects:

1. Impact on Investment Universe:

Exclusionary screening has the potential to shrink the investment universe as it involves a screening policy that identifies prohibited practices, products, services, and specifies countries, sectors, and companies where investment is restricted.

ESG integration, on the other hand, does not inherently reduce the investment universe. It involves embedding financial information and ESG factors into the security selection and portfolio construction process, allowing for flexibility in buying and selling across all companies, sectors, and/or countries within the investment universe.

2. Approach Nature:

Exclusionary screening is characterized as a "values" approach. It operates through a set of rules that dictate what practices or entities are excluded based on ethical or values-based criteria.

ESG integration is termed a "value" approach. It involves systematically incorporating financial information and ESG factors into the decision-making process for security selection and portfolio construction.

In the case of exclusionary screening, the screening policy is typically applied before any investment analysis occurs. This is in contrast to ESG integration, where financial and ESG information is an integral part of the entire investment process, and companies, sectors, and/or countries within the investment universe can be bought or sold based on this combined analysis.

[a. Regulatory Frameworks and Compliance for Predictive Maintenance in Construction and Transport Industries in Europe](#)

Predictive maintenance aligns well with various regulatory frameworks and compliance requirements in the construction and transport industries in Europe.

Construction Industry

1. Automated Compliance Checking:
 - The construction industry faces complex regulatory compliance requirements, including sustainability assessments. Frameworks for automated compliance checking help domain experts develop and maintain regulations, allowing for the integration of predictive maintenance to meet these standards effectively ([Beach et al., 2013](#)).
2. Building Standards and Sustainability:

- European standards like the Construction Products Regulation emphasize the need for sustainability, durability, and performance of building products. Predictive maintenance can help ensure that construction projects adhere to these standards by preventing unexpected failures and extending the lifecycle of materials (Wall, 2021).
3. Eco-Standards and Environmental Regulations:
- Emerging EU eco-standards for construction products require compliance with environmental sustainability regulations. Predictive maintenance supports these requirements by optimizing resource use and reducing environmental impact ([Aanstoos, 2004](#)).

Transport Industry

1. Monitoring and Asset Management:
 - The European Union's H2020 IM-SAFE project identifies barriers and opportunities for implementing predictive maintenance in transport infrastructure. This project emphasizes the need for data-informed decision-making and standardization across EU countries to ensure the effective monitoring and maintenance of transport assets ([Scibilia et al., 2023](#)).
2. Standardization for Safety:
 - Efforts by the European Commission to standardize maintenance and safety protocols for transport infrastructure highlight the importance of predictive maintenance. This includes developing harmonized standards for monitoring, inspection, and risk-based maintenance to ensure long-term infrastructure safety ([Allaix & Bigaj-van Vliet, 2022](#)).
3. Environmental Sustainability:
 - The EU's regulatory focus on sustainability also impacts the transport sector, with policies encouraging the integration of predictive maintenance to improve the environmental performance of transport infrastructure ([Flores et al., 2016](#)).

Predictive maintenance aligns with and supports compliance with European regulatory frameworks in the construction and transport industries. By integrating predictive maintenance, companies can enhance sustainability, improve resource efficiency, and meet regulatory requirements more effectively.

Figure 5

ESG adoption challenges

ESG adoption challenges

Source: Capital Group ESG Global Study 2022

Note. From *ESG investing statistics, data & trends in 2024*, by Vitali, (2024)

A crucial aspect of ESG integration involves mitigating risk and/or improving returns. Practitioners utilize ESG integration techniques to identify concealed risks that might go unnoticed without the analysis of ESG information and trends.

ESG practitioners also actively seek investment opportunities to boost returns. For instance, some practitioners assess automotive companies, considering their response to trends in car electrification and incorporating this evaluation into revenue forecasts. Another approach involves investing in companies with robust ESG management, anticipating that these companies are poised to outperform their competitors over the long term. This dual focus on risk mitigation and return enhancement underscores the multifaceted role of ESG integration in investment strategies.

Another vital aspect of ESG integration is materiality. Practitioners evaluate all material factors—both traditional financial factors and ESG factors—to identify investment risks and opportunities that are highly likely to impact corporate and investment performance. If both traditional financial and ESG factors are deemed

material, an assessment of their impact is conducted. Conversely, if these factors are found not to be material, no assessment is carried out.

Practitioners consider various factors when determining the materiality of ESG issues, including:

1. Sector and Country Considerations:

Material ESG issues are often associated with specific sectors and countries. These may include regulatory and technological changes linked to the business activities of companies in a sector or the markets where they operate or source and sell.

2. Company Considerations:

Material ESG issues related to a sector may not be universally applicable to all companies within that sector.

Factors such as a company's business lines unrelated to the sector, products or services benefiting from ESG trends, or strong environmental and social management with good governance can mitigate or outweigh sector-specific ESG risks.

3. Time-Frame Considerations:

Practitioners with a long-term investment horizon are likely to integrate ESG factors more consistently than short-term investors.

ESG factors are often low-frequency, high-impact elements that significantly influence long-term performance.

This approach to materiality underscores the nuanced considerations involved in integrating ESG factors into investment decision-making processes.

ESG integration serves as a valuable complement to existing investment processes and practices. The primary augmentation to their procedures involves the acquisition and analysis of ESG information, which is essential for comprehending the key ESG issues impacting a company, sector, or country.

Various approaches are adopted in this integration:

1. Sourcing and Analysis of ESG Information:

The central addition to the process is the sourcing and analysis of ESG information. This step is crucial for gaining insights into the prominent ESG issues that have implications for a company, sector, or country.

2. Valuation Models:

Some practitioners go a step further by developing new valuation models specifically designed to incorporate ESG information.

Others choose to integrate ESG information into their existing models, recognizing the significance of these factors in shaping a comprehensive understanding of investment opportunities and risks.

All in all, this comprehensive integration of ESG information enriches investment strategies by ensuring a more holistic evaluation that goes beyond traditional financial metrics. It reflects an acknowledgment of the importance of environmental, social, and governance considerations in contemporary investment decision-making.

Figure 6

ESG integration

Note. From *The ESG integration framework*, by Principles for Responsible Investment, (2018)

b. Common Regulatory Frameworks and Compliance for Predictive Maintenance in Construction and Transport Industries in Europe

In Europe, the construction and transport industries are integral to economic growth and societal well-being. However, these industries also face significant challenges related to sustainability, safety, and regulatory compliance. To address these challenges, a robust framework of regulatory standards and compliance measures has been established. These frameworks not only ensure the quality and safety of infrastructure but also promote innovation and sustainability. This text explores the most impactful regulatory frameworks and compliance measures in the construction and transport industries in Europe, highlighting their role in enhancing industry standards and driving sustainable practices.

The construction industry is governed by a complex structure of regulations aimed at ensuring the safety, durability, and sustainability of buildings and infrastructure. Key frameworks such as the Construction Products Regulation (CPR), CE Marking, and European standards for service life prediction play crucial roles in maintaining high standards. These regulations ensure that construction products meet stringent performance and safety criteria, facilitating trade and enhancing the quality of construction materials. Additionally, automated compliance checking frameworks have revolutionized regulatory compliance, improving efficiency and accuracy.

In the transport industry, safety and sustainability are paramount. The IM-SAFE project and other European standards for transport infrastructure focus on enhancing the monitoring and maintenance of critical infrastructure. These standards promote predictive maintenance practices, reducing costs and improving safety. Environmental regulations also play a significant role, ensuring that transport projects minimize their environmental impact and comply with water quality standards. Moreover, sustainability certification systems like LCE4ROADS integrate environmental, economic, and social criteria, promoting best practices in road construction and maintenance.

Both industries are increasingly influenced by sustainability regulations. The Nearly Zero-Energy Buildings (NZEB) directive and the Waste Framework Directive are examples of regulations that promote energy efficiency and resource management in construction. These frameworks drive the adoption of renewable energy sources and the recycling of construction and demolition waste, contributing to the circular economy. Similarly, in the transport sector, environmental impact assessments and public service obligations ensure that projects are sustainable and meet public needs. The regulatory frameworks and compliance measures in the construction and transport industries are essential for maintaining high standards of safety, quality, and sustainability. These frameworks

not only protect public interests but also drive innovation and efficiency, ensuring that Europe's infrastructure can meet the demands of the future.

Construction Industry

1. **Construction Products Regulation (CPR):**
 - Emphasizes the need for products to meet specific performance requirements related to safety and sustainability. Ensures that construction products meet specific performance and safety standards, promoting higher quality and safer buildings. This regulation also emphasizes sustainability, pushing companies to adopt greener practices and materials. Compliance with CPR has driven innovation in construction products, enhancing durability and reducing environmental impact. (Wall, 2021).
2. **Building Energy Efficiency Regulations:**
 - These regulations have led to significant improvements in energy efficiency in buildings, reducing operational costs and environmental footprint. They also promote the integration of renewable energy sources, contributing to the EU's overall sustainability goals. Focuses on energy consumption and sustainability, mandating energy efficiency measures in new and existing buildings (Casals, 2006).
3. **European Standards for Service Life Prediction:**
 - ISO standards for predicting the service life of building products to ensure durability and sustainability, by setting standards for predicting the service life of building products, these regulations ensure the longevity and reliability of materials used in construction. This reduces maintenance costs and enhances building safety and performance over time. (Caluwaerts et al., 2014).
4. **CE Marking:**
 - Harmonization of construction products to ensure they meet EU regulatory requirements, particularly regarding environmental sustainability. The harmonization of construction products through CE marking ensures that products meet EU safety and performance standards, facilitating trade within the EU and ensuring high-quality materials are used in construction projects. (Wall, 2021).
5. **Automated Compliance Checking Frameworks:**
 - Systems for automated compliance with building regulations, focusing on sustainability and safety. automation in compliance checking has improved efficiency and accuracy in ensuring regulatory compliance, reducing the risk of human error and speeding up the approval process for construction projects. (Beach et al., 2013).
6. **Waste Framework Directive:**
 - Regulations to manage construction and demolition waste, promoting circular economy principles. Promotes the circular

economy in construction by mandating the management and recycling of construction and demolition waste. This regulation has driven innovation in waste management practices and reduced the environmental impact of construction projects. (Zhang et al., 2021).

7. Eco-Standards for Sustainable Construction:

- Guidelines and standards for integrating sustainability into construction projects, including materials and energy use encourages the integration of environmental sustainability into construction projects, leading to the development of greener buildings and infrastructure. These standards also promote the use of sustainable materials and practices. (Aanstoos, 2004).

8. EU Directives on Sustainable Construction:

- Efforts to harmonize sustainability regulations across member states, addressing various aspects of building sustainability. Harmonizes sustainability regulations across member states, ensuring a consistent approach to sustainable construction practices. This has led to improved environmental performance and innovation in construction methods and materials. (Heijden & Bueren, 2013).

9. Nearly Zero-Energy Buildings (NZEB):

- Regulations targeting the construction of buildings with very high energy performance, integrating renewable energy sources. These regulations have significantly reduced the energy consumption of buildings by promoting high energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources. This contributes to the EU's climate goals and reduces operational costs for building owners. (Annunziata et al., 2013).

10. Regulatory Compliance Frameworks:

- Systems for ensuring ongoing compliance with evolving construction regulations, focusing on sustainability and safety. Ensures ongoing compliance with evolving construction regulations, promoting sustainability and safety in construction projects. These frameworks facilitate the adoption of new technologies and best practices. (Beach et al., 2015).

Transport Industry

IM-SAFE Project Standards:

European Commission standards for the monitoring and safety of transport infrastructure, promoting data-informed predictive maintenance. These standards improve the monitoring and safety of transport infrastructure, ensuring the reliability and longevity of bridges, tunnels, and other structures. Predictive maintenance practices are promoted, reducing maintenance costs and improving safety. (Allaix & Bigaj-van Vliet, 2022).

European Transport Infrastructure Safety Standards:

Policies aimed at improving maintenance protocols and ensuring the safety of transport infrastructure. Enhance the safety of transport infrastructure through improved maintenance protocols and standards. These regulations ensure that transport systems are safe, reliable, and resilient to various risks. (Scibilia et al., 2023).

Environmental Regulations for Transport:

EU regulations focused on reducing environmental impacts and promoting sustainability in transport infrastructure. Promote the reduction of environmental impacts from transport infrastructure projects, ensuring sustainability and compliance with EU environmental standards. This drives innovation in green transport technologies and practices. (Marcucci, 2014).

Waste Management in Transport Projects:

Regulations to manage waste generated by transport infrastructure projects, promoting recycling and resource efficiency. Encourages the recycling and proper management of waste generated by transport infrastructure projects, supporting the circular economy and reducing environmental harm. (Zhang et al., 2021).

Water Framework Directive:

Regulations ensuring that transport infrastructure projects comply with water quality standards and sustainable water management practices. Ensures transport infrastructure projects comply with water quality standards, protecting water bodies from pollution and promoting sustainable water management practices. (Voulvoulis et al., 2017).

Transport Infrastructure Service Life Standards:

Standards for predicting and managing the service life of transport infrastructure to ensure longevity and reliability. Provides guidelines for predicting and managing the service life of transport infrastructure, ensuring the durability and safety of critical transport systems. (Caluwaerts et al., 2014).

Sustainability Certification for Roads:

Certification systems such as LCE4ROADS that assess the sustainability of road projects, integrating environmental, economic, and social criteria. The LCE4ROADS certification system integrates environmental, economic, and social criteria, promoting sustainable road projects and encouraging the use of best practices in road construction and maintenance. (Flores et al., 2016).

European Directive on Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA):

Requires transport projects to undergo assessments of their environmental impact, ensuring they meet sustainability standards. Mandates that transport projects undergo assessments of their environmental impacts, ensuring they adhere to sustainability standards and minimize negative effects on the environment. (Aanstoos, 2004).

Public Service Obligations in Transport:

Regulations ensuring that transport services meet public needs, including sustainability and safety standards. Ensures that transport services meet public needs and comply with safety and sustainability standards, promoting equitable access to transport and improving overall service quality. (Marcucci, 2014).

Energy Efficiency in Transport:

Policies promoting energy efficiency in transport infrastructure projects, integrating renewable energy and reducing carbon emissions. Promotes the integration of energy efficiency measures in transport infrastructure projects, reducing carbon emissions and operational costs, and supporting the EU's climate goals. (Annunziata et al., 2013).

The impact of these regulatory frameworks and compliance measures is profound. In the construction industry, regulations such as the Construction Products Regulation (CPR) and CE Marking have ensured that building materials and processes meet high standards of safety and performance. This has led to the development of more durable and sustainable infrastructure. Automated compliance checking has further streamlined the regulatory process, reducing errors and increasing efficiency.

In the transport industry, frameworks like the IM-SAFE project standards and sustainability certifications have significantly improved the safety and sustainability of infrastructure. Predictive maintenance practices, promoted by these regulations, have reduced maintenance costs and enhanced the reliability of transport systems. Environmental regulations have ensured that transport projects adhere to strict sustainability criteria, minimizing their impact on the environment and promoting the use of green technologies.

Sustainability regulations have driven significant changes in both industries. The Nearly Zero-Energy Buildings (NZEB) directive and the Waste Framework Directive have promoted energy efficiency and waste management in construction, contributing to the EU's climate goals. In the transport sector, environmental impact assessments and public service obligations have ensured that projects are not only sustainable but also meet the needs of the public.

The benefits of these regulatory frameworks extend beyond compliance. They have fostered a culture of innovation and continuous improvement, encouraging

companies to adopt new technologies and best practices. This has led to the development of smarter, more efficient infrastructure that is better equipped to handle future challenges.

The regulatory frameworks and compliance measures in the construction and transport industries are essential for ensuring safety, sustainability, and innovation, thus, maintaining high standards and promoting best practices, these regulations protect public interests and drive the development of resilient and sustainable infrastructure in Europe.

C. Emissions reduction in manufacturing

Unchecked man-made greenhouse gas emissions pose a significant threat to humanity and various species, with the understanding that climate change is reaching potentially irreversible and catastrophic levels.

Given this urgency, effective accounting for corporate greenhouse gas (GHG) performance should be a top priority in ESG reports. Rather than attempting an all-encompassing environmental measurement theory, it is more beneficial to concentrate resources on improving the measurement and reporting of GHG emissions.

One example of environmental management system could be GHG accounting system which should serve as a catalyst for companies to proactively reduce GHG emissions in their value chains, even in the absence of government mandates or carbon taxes.

Customers' willingness to pay for products or services with reduced GHG emissions can be inferred from their purchasing decisions based on valid GHG metrics. Moreover, in the event of a regional or global carbon tax, a well-functioning GHG accounting system becomes crucial for governments to assess and collect taxes. Fortunately, GHG measurement and reporting, being the most critical priority, are also relatively easier to implement quickly.

Several international agreements play a significant role in addressing and mitigating greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions on a global scale. The most important agreements to note are:

1. **United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC):** The foundational international treaty, established in 1992, addressing climate change. Its objective is to stabilize greenhouse gas concentrations in the atmosphere to prevent dangerous anthropogenic interference with the climate system. The annual Conference of the Parties (COP) meetings are a crucial platform for discussing and negotiating global climate action.

2. **Kyoto Protocol:** Adopted in 1997 as an extension of the UNFCCC, the Kyoto Protocol established legally binding emission reduction targets for developed countries (Annex I parties) during the first commitment period (2008-2012). It introduced market-based mechanisms such as emissions trading and the Clean Development Mechanism (CDM).
3. **Paris Agreement:** Adopted in 2015 at COP21 in Paris, the Paris Agreement is a landmark accord under the UNFCCC. It aims to limit global warming to well below 2 degrees Celsius above pre-industrial levels, with efforts to limit it to 1.5 degrees. Unlike the Kyoto Protocol, the Paris Agreement includes all countries, each setting its own nationally determined contributions (NDCs) for emissions reduction.
4. **Montreal Protocol:** While primarily addressing ozone-depleting substances, the Montreal Protocol has inadvertently contributed to climate change mitigation by phasing out substances like chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs) and hydrochlorofluorocarbons (HCFCs), which are also potent greenhouse gases.

Specialized agencies:

5. **International Maritime Organization (IMO):** The IMO, a specialized agency of the United Nations, addresses GHG emissions from the shipping industry. The Initial IMO Strategy on the reduction of GHG emissions from ships was adopted in 2018, aiming to reduce total annual GHG emissions from international shipping by at least 50% by 2050 compared to 2008.
6. **International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO):** ICAO, another UN specialized agency, focuses on reducing GHG emissions from the aviation sector. The Carbon Offsetting and Reduction Scheme for International Aviation (CORSIA) is a market-based mechanism established by ICAO to offset emissions growth from international civil aviation.

While a lot of scientific literature on GHG measurement already exists, with a predominant focus on global and national levels, there has been a notable effort in some articles and initiatives to measure GHGs at the corporate level.

In the late 1990s, the World Resources Institute and the World Business Council for Sustainable Development spearheaded a collaborative effort involving representatives from numerous companies, government agencies, universities, and NGOs. This initiative resulted in the development of the Greenhouse Gas Protocol in 2001, a standard that has been periodically updated and has emerged as the most widely adopted corporate standard in this field.

The Greenhouse Gas Protocol classifies greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions into three scopes:

Scope 1:

Encompasses direct GHG emissions originating from sources that are owned or under the control of a company. Examples include emissions from a company's fleet of vehicles, production equipment, or other on-site processes.

Scope 2:

Involves GHG emissions from non-company-owned facilities that generate electricity, which is then purchased and consumed by the company. This scope addresses the indirect emissions associated with the company's energy consumption.

Scope 3:

Encompasses indirect GHG emissions both upstream and downstream in a company's value chain. Scope 3 emissions represent a broader, more comprehensive view of a company's environmental impact beyond its direct operations.

Many companies have already adopted the Greenhouse Gas Protocol standards, reporting their Scope 1 and 2 GHG emissions as part of their commitment to transparency and sustainability.

1. Scope 1 emissions are relatively straightforward to measure, but for most companies, they may represent a small percentage of their overall impact on global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.
2. Scope 2 emissions, stemming from electricity consumption, were separated from Scope 3 due to their comparably easier measurability and traceability compared to other sources of Scope 3 emissions.
3. Scope 3 emissions, often constituting the largest portion of a company's total greenhouse gas (GHG) footprint, pose the greatest challenge in terms of reliable and comparable measurement across different companies and over time.

The complexity arises from the extensive and varied nature of these emissions, which extend beyond a company's direct operations to include the entire supply chain and downstream impacts. Achieving standardized and comparable measurements for Scope 3 emissions requires navigating a range of factors,

including diverse supplier activities, transportation methods, and end-use consumer behaviours. This complexity makes the consistent and accurate measurement of Scope 3 emissions a significant and ongoing challenge in corporate sustainability reporting. (Katchasuwanmanee, 2016).

For a manufacturer, these challenges may include:

Supply Chain Complexity:

Manufacturers source materials from various suppliers, each with its own set of emissions. Tracking and measuring these emissions across a diverse and often global supply chain can be intricate.

Product Life Cycle:

Understanding the entire life cycle of a product, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal, involves accounting for emissions at every stage. This requires coordination with suppliers, distributors, and even consumers.

Customer Use and Disposal:

Scope 3 also includes emissions associated with the use and disposal of a manufacturer's products. Monitoring how customers use and eventually dispose of products adds another layer of complexity.

Data Availability:

Obtaining accurate and consistent data from suppliers and partners, who may operate under different standards and reporting practices, can be a significant hurdle.

Changing Suppliers:

Manufacturers may switch suppliers over time, introducing variability in the emissions associated with their products.

Figure 7

Scope 3 emissions for large enterprises

Why are Scope 3 emissions so complex to track?

Note. From *Overcoming challenges in understanding and quantifying Scope 3 emissions for large enterprises*, by Terrascope (2023)

Many companies have already adopted the Greenhouse Gas Protocol standards, reporting their Scope 1 and 2 GHG emissions as part of their commitment to transparency and sustainability. The challenges with Scope 3 measurement become evident when considering the complexities faced by a manufacturing company. Unlike Scope 1 and 2 emissions, which are more directly tied to a company's own operations, Scope 3 emissions encompass a broad range of indirect impacts throughout the entire value chain.

Based on GHG Protocol's Scope 3 Calculation Guidance⁶ there are 15 categories under which Scope 3 emissions can be classified. These categories provide a structured framework for organizations to assess and report their indirect emissions throughout the value chain.

The specific categories include:

1. Purchased goods and services
2. Capital goods
3. Fuel and energy-related activities

⁶ Publication available here: <https://ghgprotocol.org/scope-3-calculation-guidance-2>

4. Upstream transportation and distribution
5. Waste generated in operations
6. Business travel
7. Employee commuting
8. Upstream leased assets
9. Downstream transportation and distribution
10. Processing of sold products
11. Use of sold products
12. End-of-life treatment of sold products
13. Downstream leased assets
14. Franchises
15. Investments

Figure 8
The GHG Protocol

Note. From Scope 1, 2, 3 emissions explained, by Circularise, (2023)

In summary, the challenges in Scope 3 measurement for a manufacturer highlight the need for a standardized approach, collaboration throughout the supply chain, and improved data availability and consistency. These factors are crucial for achieving reliable and comparable measurements across companies and industries.

Estimating upstream and downstream greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, particularly for companies with extensive, intricate, and multi-jurisdictional value chains, introduces significant challenges, leading to substantial measurement

errors and the potential for bias and manipulation in a company's environmental (E) reports.

Consequently, many companies opt to avoid Scope 3 reporting altogether, ostensibly due to the inherent measurement difficulties and the limited control they have over upstream and downstream emissions.

The complexity and lack of standardized methodologies for Scope 3 measurements contribute to the hesitancy among companies to include these emissions in their reporting.

This underscores the need for industry-wide efforts to establish more consistent and reliable methods for measuring and reporting Scope 3 emissions, promoting transparency and comparability across organizations.

Addressing the challenges in the greenhouse gas (GHG) reporting framework, particularly the debate around the inclusion of Scope 3 emissions, can be approached by applying fundamental financial and cost accounting principles (Kaplan et al., 2021). This involves adopting a methodology similar to how companies manage production costs throughout their supply and distribution chains.

The process involves accumulating costs and their transfer:

- Companies can accumulate GHG emissions associated with a product by adding the emissions from their own operations to those incurred by their upstream suppliers. This mirrors the way production costs are aggregated.
- Similar to how companies transfer the accumulated costs of production, GHG emissions can be transferred along the supply and distribution chain. Each company records the emissions it directly incurs and those inherited from upstream suppliers, passing this total to immediate customers.

Drawing an analogy with corporate accounting practices, such an approach doesn't necessitate estimating all costs incurred at every stage of the supply chain. Instead, each company records the specific costs it pays to immediate suppliers and receives from immediate customers.

Figure 9

Addressing scope 3 value chain emissions

Note. From *A guide to addressing scope 3 value chain emissions*, by 3Degrees (2021)

This proposed application of financial and cost accounting principles is just one example of a manageable and transparent way to address the complexities of Scope 3 emissions reporting, offering a potential solution for manufacturing companies grappling with measurement challenges in their GHG reporting frameworks.

In 2021, industry and the electric power sector emerged as the leading contributors to global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, collectively comprising almost 60% of the total emissions. Each sector, industry, and the electric power sector individually accounted for 29% of the total GHG emissions, with coal combustion being the primary source. The combined contribution of land use, agriculture, and waste amounted to 20%, excluding the impact of forest fires. Additionally, the transportation sector contributed 15%, while buildings contributed 7% to the global GHG emissions landscape. This sectoral breakdown highlights the significant role of industry and the electric power sector in shaping the overall emissions profile.⁷

⁷ Data collected from <https://rhg.com/research/global-greenhouse-gas-emissions-2022/>

Figure 10

Global emissions by sectors in 2021

Global emissions by sector

Percent share of 2021 net GHG emissions

Source: Rhodium Group

Note. From *Global greenhouse gas emissions: 1990-2021 and preliminary 2022 estimates*, by Rhodium Group, (2023)

Figure 11

Global GHG emissions by sectors between 1990-2021

Global GHG emissions by sector for 1990-2021

Billion metric tons of CO₂

Source: Rhodium Group

Note. From *Global greenhouse gas emissions: 1990-2021 and preliminary 2022 estimates*, by Rhodium Group, (2023)

Similarly, in the period of 30 years there was a significant rise of global GHG emissions in the industry and electricity sector. Agriculture, land use and waste remained steady throughout the years with minor oscillations, along with buildings, while the transportation sector has seen a rise in the GHG emissions landscape over the years.

Wastewater treatment and usage in manufacturing

Besides Greenhouse Gas Emissions, wastewater treatment and its usage have become important measurement factors when it comes to sustainable manufacturing. Many studies and experiments have been conducted in order to find innovative solutions to wastewater treatment and reuse it in manufacturing processes.

Membrane technology is acknowledged as the pivotal solution for addressing the global water scarcity issue. Currently, more than 70% of the world's desalination capacity relies on membrane-based technology (Fritzmann et al., 2007). Moreover, membrane bioreactor technology is emerging as a dominant player in wastewater treatment, making significant strides in this field (Mutamim et al., 2012). Microfiltration and ultrafiltration technologies are also increasingly prevalent in diverse applications, including pre-treating saline water, and are widely utilized in the food, textile, and pharmaceutical industries (Pabby et al., 2015).

While membrane technology is generally regarded as environmentally friendly and sustainable, it is noteworthy that the membrane fabrication process itself falls short of being environmentally friendly. This process results in the generation of over 50 billion litres of wastewater annually, contaminated with toxic solvents like DMF and NMP (Szekely et al., 2014; Jiménez-González et al., 2011).

A study conducted by Razali et al. in 2015 presented a practical and effective method for continuously recycling membrane wastewater, leading to a 99% reduction in waste generation. This innovative continuous adsorptive wastewater treatment proves to be an effective solution for reducing solvent contamination to levels below 10 ppm, enabling safe disposal.

Figure 12

Disposal methods for coagulation bath wastewater

Note. From Pie chart illustrating the findings of a survey regarding disposal methods employed by membrane manufacturing companies for coagulation bath wastewater, by Razali et al., (2015)

Another separate study (Abdel Wahaab & Alseroury, 2019) focused on the treatment of wastewater from one of Egypt's largest electronics factories. The industrial wastewater from electronics manufacturing carries a significant burden of cyanide, toxic metals, and chemical oxygen demand (COD). To address this, a two-step pre-treatment process involving alkaline chlorination and chemical reduction was carried out sequentially to remove cyanide and Cr+6 from the nickel-chrome production line effluent.

Following pre-treatment, the processed water was combined with the final effluent from all production lines and subjected to a coagulation process for ultimate treatment. The outcomes demonstrated the viability of this approach, suggesting that it could be employed to establish an economical and effective wastewater treatment system for effluents generated by the electronics manufacturing industry.

D. Hybrid lifecycle analysis

a. Lifecycle Costing and End-of-Life Management for Predictive Maintenance in Transport and Construction Industries in Europe

Lifecycle costing (LCC) and end-of-life (EoL) management are critical components of predictive maintenance strategies in the construction and transport industries in Europe. As these sectors face increasing demands for sustainability, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness, implementing comprehensive lifecycle approaches becomes essential. LCC evaluates the total cost of ownership over an asset's entire life, encompassing initial investments, operational and maintenance expenses, and disposal costs. Simultaneously, effective EoL management ensures that materials and components are reused, recycled, or disposed of responsibly, supporting the circular economy and reducing environmental impacts.

In the construction industry, LCC provides a framework for making informed decisions that minimize costs and maximize value. By integrating Building Information Modelling (BIM) with LCC methodologies, stakeholders can enhance the accuracy and efficiency of cost assessments, leading to better project outcomes. Standards such as EN 15804 and EN 15978 guide the application of LCC and LCA (Life Cycle Assessment), ensuring consistency and reliability. Additionally, adopting various maintenance strategies, including preventive and predictive maintenance, can significantly impact the long-term performance and sustainability of infrastructure projects.

The transport industry also benefits from LCC and EoL management, particularly in managing complex and extensive infrastructure networks. LCC helps in optimizing investment decisions, maintenance planning, and overall asset management. End-of-life vehicle (ELV) directives and efficient reverse logistics networks play a pivotal role in recovering and recycling materials from retired vehicles, promoting sustainability and economic efficiency. These practices reduce the environmental footprint of transport operations and contribute to the EU's broader sustainability goals.

Lifecycle Costing in Construction

Lifecycle Costing (LCC) in the construction industry involves evaluating the total cost of ownership of a building over its entire life cycle, from design and construction through operation and maintenance to eventual disposal. This comprehensive approach helps in making informed decisions that minimize costs and maximize value over the building's lifespan.

1. **Lifecycle Cost Analysis (LCCA):**
 - LCCA is crucial for evaluating the economic sustainability of projects by considering all cost aspects, including initial investment, maintenance, operation, and end-of-life disposal. It allows stakeholders to compare different design options and maintenance strategies to determine the most cost-effective and sustainable choices (Fregonara & Ferrando, 2020).
2. **Building Information Modelling (BIM) Integration:**
 - The integration of BIM with LCC methodologies enhances the accuracy and efficiency of lifecycle cost assessments. BIM-based tools enable automatic LCC and LCA analyses, providing valuable insights into the economic and environmental impacts of building components and systems throughout their lifecycle (Santos et al., 2020).
3. **Standards and Guidelines:**
 - European standards such as EN 15804 and EN 15978 provide guidelines for conducting LCC and LCA, ensuring consistency and reliability in the assessment process. These standards help in making informed decisions that align with sustainability goals and regulatory requirements (Mirzaie et al., 2020).
4. **Maintenance Strategies:**
 - Different maintenance strategies can significantly impact the lifecycle performance of infrastructure. For instance, preventive maintenance and predictive maintenance can reduce long-term costs and extend the service life of structures by addressing potential issues before they become severe (Gervásio et al., 2015).

End-of-Life Management in Construction

End-of-life (EoL) management involves the processes and strategies for handling buildings and their components when they reach the end of their useful life. Effective EoL management is essential for promoting sustainability and minimizing environmental impacts.

1. **Circular Economy:**
 - The circular economy framework emphasizes the reuse, recycling, and recovery of building materials to minimize waste and reduce the environmental impact of construction activities. This approach supports the EU's sustainability goals and promotes resource efficiency (Mirzaie et al., 2020).
2. **Recycling and Reuse:**
 - Recycling construction materials and reusing building components can significantly reduce the environmental footprint of demolition activities. For example, timber from demolished buildings can be repurposed, reducing the need for new raw materials (Achenbach et al., 2018).

3. Environmental Life-Cycle Costing (ELCC):

- ELCC integrates environmental considerations into the traditional LCC framework, accounting for external environmental costs such as emissions and resource depletion. This comprehensive approach helps in evaluating the true cost of building components and their impact on the environment (Luttenberger & Luttenberger, 2017).

Lifecycle Costing in Transport

Lifecycle Costing in the transport industry involves evaluating the total cost of ownership of transport infrastructure, including initial construction, operation, maintenance, and end-of-life disposal. This approach helps in making cost-effective decisions that ensure long-term sustainability and performance.

1. Lifecycle Cost Analysis for Rail Infrastructure:

- LCCA helps in managing railway infrastructure by considering the long-term impacts of design and maintenance decisions on reliability, availability, and cost. This approach ensures that infrastructure investments are optimized for performance and cost-effectiveness (Zoeteman, 2001).

2. Maintenance Optimization:

- Predictive maintenance strategies, supported by LCCA, can reduce operational costs and enhance the reliability of transport infrastructure. These strategies involve monitoring the condition of assets and performing maintenance activities based on data-driven predictions of potential failures (van den Boomen et al., 2018).

End-of-Life Management in Transport

End-of-life management in the transport sector involves the processes and strategies for handling vehicles and infrastructure components when they reach the end of their useful life. Effective EoL management is crucial for sustainability and resource efficiency.

1. End-of-Life Vehicle (ELV) Directive:

- The EU ELV Directive requires manufacturers to take responsibility for the recovery and recycling of vehicles at the end of their life cycle. This directive promotes the reuse, recycling, and recovery of vehicle materials, reducing environmental impact and supporting the circular economy (Mansour & Zarei, 2008).

2. Reverse Logistics Networks:

- Efficient reverse logistics networks are essential for the collection and processing of end-of-life vehicles. These networks ensure that ELVs are handled in an environmentally responsible manner, maximizing the recovery of valuable materials and minimizing waste (Zarei et al., 2010).

3. Economic and Environmental Benefits:

- Effective EoL management can provide significant economic benefits by recovering valuable materials and reducing disposal costs. Additionally, it supports environmental sustainability by reducing the need for new raw materials and minimizing the environmental impact of waste (Anthony & Cheung, 2017).

Lifecycle costing and end-of-life management are critical components of predictive maintenance strategies in the construction and transport industries in Europe. By considering the total cost of ownership and implementing effective end-of-life management practices, these industries can achieve significant economic and environmental benefits. The integration of advanced tools such as BIM and predictive maintenance technologies enhances the efficiency and accuracy of lifecycle assessments, supporting informed decision-making and promoting sustainability.

In the construction industry, LCC provides a comprehensive framework for assessing the economic and environmental impacts of buildings. For example, a case study in the Netherlands demonstrated the effectiveness of BIM-based LCC and LCA methodologies in evaluating the sustainability of office buildings. This approach facilitates better decision-making by integrating economic and environmental assessments within a digital framework (Santos et al., 2020). Similarly, another study on nearly zero-energy buildings highlighted the importance of incorporating EoL costs in sustainability assessments, showing that selective demolition and waste management can significantly reduce environmental impacts (Vazquez-Lopez et al., 2020).

The transport industry also benefits from LCC and EoL management, particularly in managing complex infrastructure networks. The EU Directive on End-of-Life Vehicles (ELV) mandates the recovery and recycling of vehicles, driving manufacturers to develop efficient reverse logistics networks. This directive not only reduces environmental impacts but also helps manufacturers optimize costs by reclaiming valuable materials (Mansour & Zarei, 2008). Additionally, a study on sustainable procurement in maritime transport emphasized the integration of environmental LCC, which considers both economic and environmental costs, promoting cleaner and more energy-efficient transport solutions (Luttenberger & Luttenberger, 2017).

The implementation of lifecycle costing and end-of-life management in the construction and transport industries is essential for promoting sustainability and economic efficiency. Real-world case studies demonstrate the effectiveness of these methodologies in various contexts. For instance, integrating BIM with LCC and LCA methodologies in the construction sector has proven to enhance decision-making processes, ensuring that projects are both economically viable and environmentally sustainable (Santos et al., 2020).

In the transport sector, the EU's End-of-Life Vehicle Directive has driven the development of efficient reverse logistics networks, optimizing the recovery and recycling of vehicle materials. This not only minimizes environmental impacts but also reduces costs for manufacturers (Mansour & Zarei, 2008). Furthermore, sustainable procurement practices in maritime transport, which incorporate environmental lifecycle costing, highlight the benefits of cleaner and more energy-efficient transport solutions (Luttenberger & Luttenberger, 2017).

These case studies underscore the importance of adopting comprehensive LCC and EoL management practices to enhance the sustainability and efficiency of infrastructure projects. By integrating economic and environmental considerations throughout the lifecycle of assets, the construction and transport industries can achieve significant cost savings, reduce their environmental footprint, and contribute to the EU's broader sustainability goals.

In the construction industry, lifecycle costing helps in evaluating the economic sustainability of projects, while end-of-life management promotes the reuse and recycling of materials, contributing to the circular economy. Similarly, in the transport industry, lifecycle costing ensures that infrastructure investments are optimized for performance and cost-effectiveness, while end-of-life management supports the recovery and recycling of vehicles, reducing environmental impact. Overall, the adoption of lifecycle costing and end-of-life management practices in these industries aligns with the EU's sustainability goals, driving innovation and efficiency. By leveraging these practices, the construction and transport sectors can enhance their resilience, reduce costs, and contribute to a more sustainable future.

Evaluating and reducing the impact of human activities on the environment constitutes

A key aspect of the overarching objective to attain sustainable development while staying within the constraints of Earth's resources. This involves considering the capacity of natural systems to absorb disturbances caused by human actions without undergoing collapse. (Brundtland et al., 1987; IPCC, 2013, 2014; Meadows et al., 1972).

In many countries, there is a common practice of regularly evaluating products, services, processes, and even larger-scale endeavours such as construction and infrastructure projects across various environmental indicators. The objective behind these assessments is to pinpoint the present environmental performance, identify areas that can be enhanced, and gauge the extent of benefits derived from improvement initiatives.

The outcomes of these evaluations frequently play a crucial role in environmental decision-making, influencing choices between specific products or designs and contributing to the formulation and implementation of sustainability policies (Hellweg and Canals, 2014). Consequently, it is apparent that the effectiveness of

these assessments—underscored by their quality, reliability, and robustness—is paramount. This ensures that the information derived from the assessments is dependable for making informed decisions and selecting suitable solutions to enhance environmental performance.

The evolution of assessment techniques for gauging the environmental impact of a product system has given rise to various methods, with the most recent being life cycle assessment (LCA) (Klöpffer, 2014). Defined in the ISO 14040 standard, LCA is characterized as "a compilation and evaluation of the inputs, outputs, and the potential environmental impacts of a product system throughout its life cycle" (ISO, 2006).

While Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) is extensively utilized for environmental profiling, the determination of the system boundary within LCA models remains subjective and lacks a rigorous mathematical foundation. As a result, life cycle models are often developed in an ad hoc manner, making comparisons challenging. This approach may unintentionally omit significant environmental impacts. Rectifying this limitation is crucial to instill greater confidence in life cycle models and their effectiveness in decision-making (Ghosh and Bakshi, 2020).

They devised a framework whose activities are chosen based on their significance, parametric uncertainty, and contribution to network complexity. The importance of activities is assessed through structural path analysis, guiding the construction of life cycle models using uncertainty and complexity indicators. Uncertainty information is derived from the existing life cycle inventory, and complexity is measured by cost or granularity. The life cycle model is systematically developed in a hierarchical fashion by incorporating the most crucial activities until error requirements are met or network complexity surpasses user-specified constraints.

Figure 13

Hybrid LCA model

Note. From *Designing hybrid life cycle assessment models based on uncertainty and complexity*, by Ghosh and Bakshi, (2020)

A fundamental component of a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) involves generating a life cycle inventory, which entails cataloguing and outputs linked to the product system under examination. There are three primary approaches typically employed for constructing a Life Cycle Inventory (LCI). The first is process analysis, also known as a bottom-up approach, where the analysed product system is deconstructed into a sequence of processes representing its life cycle. The second is environmentally extended input-output analysis (EEIOA), or a top-down approach, grounded in macroeconomics. The third is hybrid analysis, which involves a combination of the first two approaches. Each of these methods necessitates modelling a system, utilizing either specific production processes or entire economic systems.

As explained, these methods integrate both process and input-output data in various formats, representing a spectrum of hybridization between traditional process analysis and input-output analysis.

Figure 14

Life Cycle Inventory flow model

Note. From *Life Cycle Inventory flow model*, by Mannan & Al-Ghamdi, (2022)

However, despite the longstanding use of hybrid Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) methods, there is a notable absence of clear and consistent terminology to characterize each of these approaches. This lack of clarity contributes to a level of confusion within the existing literature dedicated to hybrid methods, ultimately diminishing confidence in the hybrid approach. Considering this, it could be argued that there are three primary factors that impede the widespread adoption of hybrid Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) methods in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).

The first one is the already mentioned absence of clarity in discerning the methods employed in specific studies, making it challenging to replicate these approaches.

The second factor is a limited comprehension of the potential advantages offered by hybrid data compared to conventional process or input-output data (Crawford, 2008).

Lastly, there is a lack of automated tools or software that would facilitate the straightforward application of these methods by individuals who are not specialized in hybrid Life Cycle Assessment (LCA).

The hybrid life cycle assessment consists of four main methods:

1. Tiered: This method combines input-output and process coefficients to extend the system boundaries analysed (Zhai and Williams, 2010). It includes information not typically represented in conventional process analysis or Environmentally Extended Input-Output Analysis (EEIOA). The boundaries between process and input-output data are user-defined, allowing for significant variability (Heijungs and Suh, 2002). For instance, some assessments use input-output coefficients for representing all inputs associated with production processes, while use and end-of-life stages are modeled using process data (Changbo et al., 2012).
2. Path Exchange (PXC): Involves the mathematical disaggregation of an input-output matrix, enabling the identification and modification of mutually exclusive pathways, the sum of which represents the entire matrix. The aim is to analyse specific goods and services by tailoring their supply chains with available process data while maintaining system boundary completeness (Treloar 1997; Lenzen and Crawford, 2009). This approach allows for the customization of certain aspects of the supply chain to represent different scenarios.
3. Matrix Augmentation: This method directly modifies the input-output matrix to create one or several additional 'sectors' of the economy. It can involve dividing an existing sector into sub-sectors or creating a new theoretical sector. The objective is to assess a specific good or service existing within a larger sector or one not yet included in input-output tables (Joshi, 1999).
4. Integrated: Integrates process and input-output data within a single matrix framework, using upstream and downstream cut-off matrices to link the two (Suh and Huppel, 2000). These matrices represent inputs from the input-output matrix into a process (upstream cut-off matrix) and sales of goods and services to input-output sectors (downstream cut-off matrix).

Figure 15

Legend for Figures 16,17,18

Note. An explanatory legend for Figures 16, 17, 18, 19. From , by Crawford et al., (2018b)

Figure 16

Tiered LCA Hybrid Method

Note. From *Hybrid life cycle inventory methods–A review*, by Crawford et al., (2018b)

Figure 17

PXC LCA Hybrid Method

Note. From *Hybrid life cycle inventory methods–A review*, by Crawford et al., (2018b)

Figure 18

Matrix Augmentation LCA Hybrid Method

Note. From *Hybrid life cycle inventory methods—A review*, by Crawford et al., (2018b)

Figure 19

Integrated LCA Hybrid Method

Note. From *Hybrid life cycle inventory methods—A review*, by Crawford et al., (2018b)

To enhance clarity and consistency in the growing body of work on hybrid Life Cycle Inventory (LCI), it is recommended to adopt a consistent framework for classifying and defining the four broad types of hybrid analysis identified in the literature.

This approach is crucial for providing a standardized set of definitions. The use of accepted and standardized definitions for the types of LCI methods in Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) studies is advocated to ensure coherence within the field. This practice also facilitates accessibility for researchers and practitioners (Crawford, Robert H. et al. 2018).

IO-based hybrid LCA

In Input-Output (IO)-based hybrid Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), this hybrid technique involves further breaking down significant input-output sectors when more detailed sectoral monetary data, including process and trading information, are available. These refined sectors are then connected to the detailed process-based foreground system. However, it's important to note that since a national input-output table only reflects the pre-consumer stages of a product life cycle based on domestic industries, the use and end-of-life stages must be added to the results obtained from the disaggregated input-output table (Baboulet, 2009). To achieve satisfactory results using this technique, a crucial precondition for the foreground system is to be adequately developed to counterbalance the aggregation errors inherent in input-output data (ISO 1997).

Additionally, the Economic Input-Output Life Cycle Assessment (EIO-LCA) method is designed to estimate the materials and energy resources needed, along with the environmental emissions resulting from economic activities. It serves as both a life cycle assessment and an environmental impact assessment tool for analysing a product or process across its entire life cycle. The approach leverages data on industry transactions, material procurement from other industries, and direct environmental emissions from industries to calculate the total emissions across the entire supply chain.

Figure 20

EIO-LCA evaluation method

Note. From *EIO-LCA evaluation method. In Economic Input-Output Life Cycle Assessment*, by Sherwood et al., (2017)

Double counting incidents

Double counting incidents in hybrid Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) occurs when a given system is described by combining both life-cycle and input-output analysis within the same framework. This integration may initiate a process in both input-output (IO) and life cycle inventory (LCI) data, leading to the possibility of incidents being counted twice. This can distort and bias the final results of a study.

In contrast, in IO-based hybrid LCA, detailed process-specific data can be utilized without causing double counting incidents, as demonstrated by Joshi, 1999. However, addressing this issue is not as straightforward for both the integrated and tiered hybrid LCA frameworks. Additionally, the manner in which these incidents are managed is particularly relevant for the Path Exchange (PXCH) method.

To address double counting incidents in the tiered hybrid Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) method, where a portion of demand from the foreground system is separated from the input-output background system and linked to the process background system, and there is an overlap in the sectors under demand in both the process and input-output systems, Strømman, Peters et al. in 2009 introduced a method.

The underlying algorithm of this method allows for the removal of double-counted monetary flows in the input-output system through the use of a Social Planning Approach (SPA). The criterion for removal is based on ensuring that the sets of input-output paths to be eliminated leave the same monetary value as the process system flows with which they overlap. Their primary emphasis is on eliminating double-counting from the input-output system while conducting the Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), employing Social Planning Approach (SPA) and adjustment techniques.

However, with Integrated hybrid LCA hybridization technique ensures a consistent allocation method throughout the hybrid system and notably prevents double-counting incidents by subtracting commodity flows in a process-based system from the input-output system (Suh, 2004). Specifically, while the inputs included in the upstream cut-off matrix are initially absent from the process database and are added to complete the input bill, the downstream cut-offs are theoretically present in a comprehensive input-output database. Consequently, to prevent double counting, the inputs by processes need to be subtracted from the monetary inputs of the input-output sectors. In essence, the coverage of the process system must be excluded from the input-output system to avoid double counting.

Drawbacks and limitations

Tiered: provides a straightforward enhancement or refinement of a conventional Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) by incorporating an additional background economy. The purpose of this extra economy is to account for the purchases of commodities from the input-output system that may be overlooked in the process-based Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) data. Moreover, literature databases and case studies are extensively documented. However, challenges arise in adequately describing recurring flows through the process-flow diagram approach, and misspecifications due to double counting can occur when sectors under demand in both the process and input-output systems have overlapping coverage (ISO 1997).

Integrated: While this technique avoids the double counting issues specific to the tiered hybrid method and maintains a consistent mathematical framework for the entire life cycle, as mentioned before, facilitating the application of analytical tools such as SPA, it is relatively easy to use. However, it entails high data and time requirements, particularly during the compilation of the downstream cut-off matrix.

E. Resource efficiency strategies

a. Resource Efficiency and Waste Management for Predictive Maintenance in Transport and Construction Industries in Europe

Resource efficiency and waste management are crucial aspects of predictive maintenance in the transport and construction industries. These practices ensure that materials and resources are used optimally throughout the lifecycle of infrastructure and vehicles, minimizing waste and environmental impact while maximizing economic efficiency.

In the construction industry, managing construction and demolition waste (CDW) is essential for reducing the sector's significant environmental footprint. The European Union has established ambitious targets and frameworks to promote circular economy principles, encouraging the recycling and reuse of materials. Effective CDW management practices include systematic implementation of best practices, integration of green supply chain management (GSCM), and utilization of advanced data analytics to improve sustainability and efficiency. Similarly, the transport industry benefits from resource efficiency and waste management practices that enhance the lifecycle performance of vehicles and infrastructure. The EU End-of-Life Vehicle (ELV) Directive mandates the recovery and recycling of vehicle materials, promoting a circular economy and reducing waste. Lifecycle assessments (LCA) and sustainable procurement practices further support the industry's efforts to minimize environmental impacts and optimize resource use.

Construction Industry

1. Construction and Demolition Waste Management:

- Construction and demolition waste (CDW) constitutes a significant portion of total waste generated in Europe. Effective management practices include recycling, reusing, and reducing waste through innovative treatment methods. The European Commission's Circular Economy package sets ambitious targets for CDW, promoting systematic implementation of best practices across the construction value chain (Gálvez-Martos et al., 2018).

2. Efficiency and Sustainability Analysis:

- The efficiency and sustainability of CDW management in the European Economic Area have been analysed using Exploratory Data

Analytics (EDA) and Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA). This approach helps assess the efficiency of countries in reducing and recovering CDW, providing a methodology that can improve CDW policy performance ([Taboada et al., 2020](#)).

3. Economic Aspects of CDW Recycling:

- The economics of CDW management facilities are crucial for achieving sustainability and resource efficiency. Key issues include cost factors, technological integration, and achieving recycling targets set by the Europe 2020 strategy. Effective CDW management ensures technical quality and economic viability of recycled aggregates ([Garbarino & Blengini, 2013](#)).

4. Waste Hierarchy Framework:

- The EU Waste Framework Directive introduces a waste hierarchy paradigm to promote circular economy principles in CDW management. This framework helps analyse the performance of CDW management and guides the transition to high circularity and sustainability in the construction sector ([Zhang et al., 2021](#)).

5. Green Supply Chain Management (GSCM):

- GSCM integrates environmental considerations into the construction process, promoting efficient use of resources and minimizing waste. This approach is aligned with EU goals to reduce CDW by 70% through recycling and recovery by 2020, demonstrating significant cost and social benefits ([Akdag & Beldek, 2017](#)).

Transport Industry

1. End-of-Life Vehicle (ELV) Management:

- The EU ELV Directive mandates the recovery and recycling of vehicles at the end of their life cycle, promoting the reuse of materials and minimizing waste. Efficient reverse logistics networks are essential for managing ELVs, optimizing resource recovery, and reducing environmental impacts ([Mansour & Zarei, 2008](#)).

2. Lifecycle Assessment of Transport Infrastructure:

- Lifecycle assessment (LCA) tools help evaluate the environmental impacts of transport infrastructure throughout its lifecycle. These assessments support decision-making processes to improve resource efficiency and reduce waste in transport projects ([Schmidt et al., 2020](#)).

3. Sustainable Procurement Practices:

- Sustainable procurement practices in the transport industry, including environmental lifecycle costing, promote the use of energy-efficient and environmentally friendly transport solutions. These practices contribute to reducing the environmental footprint of transport operations ([Luttenberger & Luttenberger, 2017](#)).

4. Resource Efficiency Indicators:

- Indicators such as the Resource-Efficiency Capacity Index measure the progress of EU member states towards resource efficiency. These indicators help benchmark performance in areas like waste recycling, energy efficiency, and sustainable transport, guiding policy and practice improvements ([Moreno & García-Álvarez, 2018](#)).

5. Circular Economy in Transport:

- The integration of circular economy principles in the transport industry emphasizes the reuse, recycling, and recovery of materials. This approach reduces waste generation, improves resource efficiency, and contributes to the EU's climate change mitigation goals ([Gallego-Schmid et al., 2020](#)).

Resource efficiency and waste management are pivotal for the sustainable development of the construction and transport industries in Europe. Implementing predictive maintenance strategies that incorporate these principles ensures optimal use of materials, minimizes waste, and reduces environmental impacts.

In the construction industry, best practices in CDW management, economic considerations, and the adoption of green supply chain management significantly enhance resource efficiency. The EU Waste Framework Directive and other regulations provide a structured approach to achieving high circularity and sustainability. Similarly, in the transport industry, managing the lifecycle of vehicles

and infrastructure through efficient ELV management, lifecycle assessments, and sustainable procurement practices leads to significant environmental and economic benefits. Indicators and policies that promote resource efficiency further support the transition to a circular economy, aligning with the EU's broader sustainability and climate goals. By integrating resource efficiency and waste management into predictive maintenance, both industries can achieve long-term sustainability, economic resilience, and environmental protection, contributing to a greener and more resource-efficient Europe.

The industrial manufacturing sector is widely recognized as a critical area, marked by substantial consumption of primary energy and the emission of greenhouse gases. This scenario, coupled with the swift depletion of non-renewable resources and an increasing awareness of environmental issues such as pollution and waste, is compelling industries to prioritize sustainability and energy efficiency.

Within its framework, the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development has identified Responsible consumption and production as one of the seventeen goals aimed at constructing a better world for all individuals.

Figure 21

EU 12 step to a responsible production and consumption

Note. From SDG 12 - *Responsible consumption and production*, by European Commission, (2023) (https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=SDG_12_-_Responsible_consumption_and_production)

Given that energy efficiency is a fundamental requirement for sustainability, the creation of an energy-resource efficient manufacturing system stands out as a significant challenge confronting present-day industries.

Concurrently, the prevalence of advanced technological innovation has led to the emergence of more intricate manufacturing systems, encompassing a diverse array of processes and machines designed to serve various functions.

Moreover, optimizing primary resources involves utilizing fewer materials to produce an equivalent product, while human capital optimization focuses on efficiently deploying personnel through varied operational strategies without compromising existing capacity and product output rates.

Beyond increasingly rigorous regulations such as emission standards, worker exposure standards, and prohibitions on certain materials, there are additional incentives to transition to more environmentally friendly manufacturing solutions.

These include competitive economic benefits:

1. Conservation of energy, water, and materials.
2. Reduced costs associated with waste treatment and disposal.
3. Proactive green behaviour:
4. Corporate image,
5. ISO 14001 certification
6. Eco-labelling.

To aid in the design and implementation of products and their subsequent phases of distribution, utilization, and disposition, various environment-oriented software tools have been developed. An example of one such tool is life cycle assessment software which has been mentioned in the previous section.

The evaluation and surveillance of energy and resource efficiency play a pivotal role in the adoption of sustainable manufacturing practices.

Environmental Management Tools

Environmental management tools are essential for implementing effective predictive maintenance strategies in the transport and construction industries in Europe. These tools help monitor, manage, and mitigate environmental impacts, ensuring sustainable development while maintaining infrastructure and operational efficiency. Predictive maintenance, combined with advanced environmental management practices, enables these industries to proactively address potential environmental issues, reduce emissions, and optimize resource use.

b. Environmental Management Tools for Predictive Maintenance

Construction Industry

- 1. Building Information Modelling (BIM) for Environmental Sustainability:**
 - BIM technology facilitates the prediction, management, and monitoring of environmental impacts throughout the building lifecycle. Green BIM integrates sustainability analysis, supporting the reduction, reuse, and recycling of materials and enhancing low-carbon management practices (Wong & Zhou, 2015).
- 2. Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA):**
 - LCA is a crucial tool for evaluating the environmental impacts of buildings over their entire lifecycle. It helps in decision-making by providing a comprehensive assessment of environmental concerns from construction to demolition (Khasreen et al., 2009).
- 3. IoT and BIM Integration:**
 - Integrating Internet of Things (IoT) with BIM models allows for real-time monitoring and predictive maintenance of building facilities. This integration helps in early detection of faults and efficient management of building systems (Villa et al., 2021).
- 4. Environmental Management Plan (EMP):**
 - EMPs are used to prevent environmental pollution from construction projects. Knowledge-based systems can enhance the application of EMPs by predicting environmental impacts and suggesting mitigation measures (Ooshaksaraie et al., 2010).
- 5. 4D BIM in Life Cycle Management Systems (LMS):**
 - 4D BIM integrates time-related information with 3D models, supporting proactive life cycle design and maintenance management strategies. This integration enhances decision-making and improves the overall sustainability of construction projects (Hallberg, 2009).

Transport Industry

- 1. Markovian Deterioration Models for Bridge Decks:**
 - These models use genetic algorithms to define environmental categories affecting bridge element deterioration, aiding in predictive maintenance and efficient resource allocation (Morcoux et al., 2003).
- 2. Risk-Informed Decision Support Tools:**
 - These tools integrate economic, social, and environmental aspects to optimize railway track maintenance. They use probabilistic risk assessment and Monte Carlo simulations to manage uncertainties and improve maintenance decisions (Sasidharan et al., 2021).
- 3. Environmental Management Systems (EMS) for Railways:**

- EMS based on ISO 14000 standards help railway infrastructure managers systematically manage environmental issues, reducing the negative impacts of rail operations (Fracchia et al., 2012).
- 4. **Predictive Maintenance Frameworks for Parcel Delivery:**
 - IoT-enabled predictive maintenance frameworks monitor the status of packages during delivery, ensuring efficient logistics and reducing the risk of damage (Proto et al., 2020).
- 5. **Web Tools for Sustainable Freight Transport:**
 - These tools help shippers and freight forwarders plan environmentally friendly transport operations by optimizing routes, costs, and emissions (Zeimpekis et al., 2012).

The integration of environmental management tools into predictive maintenance strategies significantly enhances the sustainability and efficiency of the construction and transport industries in Europe. By leveraging technologies such as BIM, IoT, LCA, and advanced decision support systems, these industries can proactively manage environmental impacts, optimize resource use, and ensure long-term sustainability. These tools not only support compliance with stringent environmental regulations but also drive innovation and operational excellence, contributing to a greener and more resilient infrastructure ecosystem.

There are various strategies for sustainable practices that organizations can employ to enhance their sustainability practices:

1. **Mass balance:** Involves assessing the input and output of a process to gauge its efficiency and identify wastage.
2. **Full cost accounting:** Takes into account various costs associated with a process, including materials, energy, labour, waste disposal, and other miscellaneous costs. This comprehensive approach ensures that the true environmental and financial costs of a process are considered, providing a more accurate basis for decision-making.
3. **The product life cycle:** Another crucial element, explained in-depth in the previous section. Minimizing the life cycle equates to reduced environmental impact.
4. **The systematic engineering process:** This process of the product involves conceptual, preliminary, and detailed design stages, followed by production construction and operational use with system support (Blanchard and Fabrycky, 1997). Considering environmental factors at each stage allows organizations to integrate sustainability considerations into the product development and life cycle.

5. Extended producer responsibility (EPR): Imposing on manufacturers is a pivotal approach, creating a crucial intersection between environmental and business benefits. Manufacturers possess a unique capability to facilitate product recovery and remanufacturing by designing products for easy disassembly and component reuse.
6. Product life-cycle value design: Guides decisions on material selection, favouring easily recyclable materials and avoiding unusual or hazardous components, thereby reducing negative environmental impacts (Fishbein, 2000; Toffel, 2002).

Numerous innovative research methods, such as Resources Value Mapping (Papetti et al., 2019), strive to map and categorize activities along with their corresponding energy and resource consumptions based on lean philosophy principles, distinguishing between value-added, non-value-added, and waste. Additionally, redesign of machine tools and the implementation of selective control can markedly enhance energy efficiency without compromising productivity (Duflou et al., 2012).

The concept of a recirculation-based society emphasizes a holistic approach to sustainability, going beyond traditional recycling practices. In this model, the focus is on minimizing both the intake from nature (such as fossil energy and raw materials) and the output into nature (including exhaust gases and waste materials). The goal is to create a closed-loop system where resources are recirculated and regenerated within the human life system, reducing overall environmental impact.

While recycling has been a prominent aspect of environmental policies, the recirculation-based society encourages a broader perspective. It acknowledges that the recycling process itself may require significant additional energy, leading to misconceptions about the high costs associated with recycling.

Figure 22

Circular economy

Note. From Circular economy made in Aachen, by Chehadé & Rummel, (2023)

In this framework, planning production activities involves considering the total material balance. Rather than solely focusing on reducing output by expending additional energy, the emphasis is on decreasing intake and utilizing output materials and energy to synthesize new materials (Ishida, 1999). The concept is particularly relevant for inorganic materials, where natural ecological mechanisms, such as decomposition by bacteria, may not be as effective. Here, the term "recirculation" is introduced, signifying a more comprehensive and sustainable approach compared to traditional recycling.

This approach aligns with the principles of circular economy and sustainable resource management. Inorganic materials are highlighted as having advantages in both intake and output compared to metals or petroleum-based materials like resins. The suggestion is that replacing these materials with inorganic alternatives could yield considerable benefits in terms of resource conservation and environmental impact reduction within the framework of a recirculation-based society.

Sustainable Manufacturing

While the term "sustainable manufacturing" is often used to describe efforts to characterize and reduce the environmental impacts of manufacturing, it is crucial

to recognize that sustainability extends beyond merely analysing and modifying environmental performance.

Sustainability implies a broader perspective, suggesting that a system becomes unsustainable when society's resource consumption and waste production exceed nature's capacity to transform industrial and societal wastes into environmental nutrients and resources. Discussions about sustainability are most applicable within closed systems, such as the one illustrated in the figure below. In this closed system, manufacturing subsystems coexist with human, ecological, and natural subsystems. According to David A. Dornfeld et al., (2013), sustainable manufacturing is a philosophy intricately connected to broader environmental and socioeconomic systems.

Figure 23

Green manufacturing

Note. From A Review on Green Manufacturing: It's Important, Methodology and its Application, by Paul et al., (2014)

F. Clean energy in manufacturing

The adoption of clean energy technologies is essential for the sustainable development of the transport and construction industries in Europe. Predictive maintenance, which uses data analytics and advanced monitoring techniques, can significantly enhance the efficiency and reliability of these clean energy systems. By integrating predictive maintenance strategies, these industries can ensure the continuous, efficient, and environmentally friendly operation of their assets, thereby supporting the European Union's ambitious climate goals.

Condition-Based Maintenance Strategies for ETICS:

- This study explores the impact of different maintenance strategies on the durability and sustainability of External Thermal Insulation Composite Systems (ETICS) used in building construction. By implementing condition-based maintenance models, the service life of ETICS can be significantly extended, promoting energy efficiency and reducing environmental impact (Ferreira et al., 2021).

Efficiency in Energy-Intensive Industries:

- An analysis of energy efficiency trends across various industries, including construction and transport, reveals that technological advancements and proper maintenance strategies are critical for improving energy efficiency. This study highlights the role of predictive maintenance in achieving these improvements (Makridou et al., 2016).

Life-Cycle Assessment of Office Buildings:

- Life-cycle assessments (LCA) of office buildings in Europe and the United States provide insights into the environmental impacts of building materials and maintenance activities. Predictive maintenance plays a key role in minimizing these impacts by optimizing maintenance schedules and reducing energy consumption during the building's operational phase (Junnila et al., 2006).

Industrial Maintenance 4.0:

- The integration of Industry 4.0 technologies in maintenance activities, including the use of artificial intelligence and machine learning, enhances the sustainability of asset-intensive industries. This paper discusses the importance of energy-based maintenance for decarbonizing these industries (Orošnjak et al., 2021).

Sustainable Transport Systems:

- The EU's roadmap for a competitive and resource-efficient transport system outlines the need for clean and efficient travel solutions. Predictive maintenance supports these goals by ensuring the reliability and efficiency of transport infrastructure and reducing the environmental impact of transportation activities (Eißel & Chu, 2014).

Integrating clean energy predictive maintenance in the transport and construction industries is crucial for achieving sustainable development and meeting the European Union's environmental goals. By leveraging advanced technologies such as condition-based maintenance, life-cycle assessments, and Industry 4.0 tools, these industries can significantly enhance their energy efficiency, reduce their environmental footprint, and ensure the long-term sustainability of their operations. The findings from the cited studies underscore

the importance of predictive maintenance in optimizing the performance and sustainability of clean energy systems, ultimately contributing to a greener and more resilient Europe.

Renewable energy is derived from replenishable sources like the sun, water, and wind, which are abundant and widely accessible globally.

a. [UN's Call for Clean Energy Transition](#)

The United Nations has made a strong call for a global shift from fossil fuels to renewable energy to benefit both people and the planet. This urgent transition is seen as critical to avert a climate catastrophe and ensure a sustainable future. UN Secretary-General António Guterres has outlined a comprehensive five-point plan to facilitate this transition, emphasizing the need for a "renewables revolution" to secure a brighter global future.

1. **Renewable Energy as the Only Credible Path Forward:**

- Renewable energy is positioned as the sole viable solution to prevent climate disasters, stabilize energy prices, and ensure energy security. Guterres stresses that renewables must account for over 60% of global electricity by 2030 and reach 90% by mid-century to maintain the global temperature rise below 1.5 degrees Celsius (UN News, 2023).

2. **Five-Point Energy Plan:**

- **Remove Intellectual Property Barriers:** Treat key renewable technologies, including energy storage, as global public goods to enhance accessibility.
- **Diversify and Increase Supply Chains:** Ensure raw materials and components for renewable technologies are available without environmental degradation, creating millions of green jobs.
- **Subsidize the Transition:** Shift subsidies from fossil fuels to clean energy, support vulnerable groups, and modernize power grids to facilitate the transition.
- **Increase Public and Private Investments:** Triple investments in renewables to at least \$4 trillion annually, ensuring financing reaches those who need it most.
- **Strengthen Energy Sovereignty:** Develop renewable energy sources to enhance national energy independence and resilience (UN News, 2023).

3. COP28 Agreement:

- The COP28 conference marked a significant milestone with an agreement that signals the "beginning of the end" of the fossil fuel era. This agreement emphasizes deep emissions cuts, scaled-up finance, and a tripling of renewable energy capacity by 2030. It also calls for phasing out inefficient fossil fuel subsidies and accelerating the transition to clean energy (UNFCCC, 2023).

b. European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) Initiatives

The European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) plays a crucial role in driving the clean energy transition in Europe through various initiatives and partnerships aimed at fostering innovation and sustainability.

1. EIT InnoEnergy:

- Focuses on promoting sustainable energy innovations by investing in technology startups and supporting projects that enhance energy efficiency and the use of renewable energy sources.

2. EIT Climate-KIC:

- A leading climate innovation initiative that brings together public and private sectors to develop and implement climate solutions, including those that promote clean energy and reduce carbon emissions.

3. EIT Urban Mobility:

- Aims to create sustainable urban mobility solutions that reduce environmental impact and improve quality of life in cities through innovative transportation systems and clean energy integration.

The UN's call for a global shift to renewable energy and the EIT's initiatives underscore the critical importance of transitioning to clean energy systems. These efforts aim to mitigate climate change, promote sustainability, and ensure energy security, ultimately benefiting both people and the planet. By embracing renewable energy and supporting innovative solutions, the global community can work towards a more sustainable and resilient future.

Technologies associated with renewable energy are characterized by low carbon emissions, often approaching zero. They are typically considered environmentally

and climate-friendly. Furthermore, considering battery and energy storage technologies, along with exploring carbon capture methods, is essential for minimizing the overall carbon footprint.

Energy transitions can be realized by adopting clean energy sources. Clean energy sources are characterized as low-carbon alternatives that emit fewer greenhouse gases (GHGs) compared to conventional coal and oil.

Examples of such sources include natural gas, compressed natural gas (CNG), liquid petroleum gas (LPG), and nuclear energy.

It is essential to note that the term "clean" energy refers to less polluting forms, recognizing that there is no completely pristine or devoid-of-impact energy source. The analysis, planning, and management of energy transitions can be facilitated through the use of energy models.

These models serve as planning tools, enabling the exploration of the future landscape of global and regional energy systems and assessing the impacts of energy use on both the human and natural environment.

With the sudden onset of COVID-19, wind, solar, hydrothermal, hydrogen, and biomass-based energy systems gained significant momentum, effectively mitigating disruptions in the demand-supply chain.

Certain sources, like wind and solar resources, fall under the category of variable renewable energy (VRE). In this framework, the energy flexibility control of manufacturing systems becomes crucial to align the energy demand of manufacturing systems with on-site VRE generation.

Figure 24

RE-organizing power systems for a green transition

Source: IRENA, 2021a.

Note. From *RE-organising power systems for the transition*, by Solar Now, (2022)

The substantial expansion of wind and solar photovoltaic (PV) capacity over the past decade has led to a rising share of VRE.

The interconnected nature of manufacturing systems introduces additional operational and technical challenges due to their dynamic behaviour. Ensuring consistent throughput when implementing energy control actions poses a challenge.

Stochastic influences from factors such as VRE generation and the behaviour of manufacturing systems necessitate a real-time approach at the level of manufacturing execution systems.

Manufacturers are actively pursuing various renewable energy technologies, with a particular focus on key methods and substitution systems including biomass, solar thermal systems, and electrification:

Biomass:

The versatility and substitution potential of biomass position it as a primary choice for renewable energy in manufacturing. It can effectively replace fossil fuels, serving as fuel for localized energy production. The utilization of biomass for electricity production is emerging as a promising method for the near future. The global production of biomass is estimated at a substantial 146 billion metric tons annually, primarily sourced from wild plant growth (Balat & Ayar, 2005). Looking ahead, biomass holds the potential to offer a cost-effective and sustainable energy

supply, concurrently assisting countries in achieving their greenhouse gas reduction targets. This underscores the role of biomass as a renewable resource with the capacity to contribute significantly to the global energy landscape while addressing environmental objectives.

Solar thermal systems:

Solar energy is considered one of the most crucial renewable resources, widely accessible globally (Shahsavari and Ameri, 2010). There are two primary applications of solar energy: solar thermal and photovoltaic (PV) technologies. Solar thermal technology converts solar energy into useful heat, while photovoltaic technology converts solar energy into electrical energy. However, in PV systems, in addition to converting energy into electricity, the absorption of solar energy also elevates the temperature of the PV cells, leading to a reduction in their efficiency (Baljit & Chan, 2016). Solar thermal systems exhibit significant potential for industrial process heating on a global scale. While traditionally used for low-temperature applications, recent advancements have allowed these systems to cater to applications requiring temperatures of up to 400°C.

Electrification:

Given that electricity constitutes 20% of final energy use in manufacturing, the demand for electricity is expected to continue growing. This growth is attributed, in part, to the electrification of production processes and the expansion of manufacturing industries characterized by high electricity consumption, such as non-ferrous metals. Industry electrification involves linking the electricity and industrial sectors by substituting fossil fuel demand with electricity, facilitating increased integration of renewable electricity and aiding the transition of challenging-to-decarbonize energy sectors. Research indicates that prioritizing the direct electrification of industrial process heat demands is more advantageous than alternatives like shifting to hydrogen-based process systems, even when the latter might offer increased flexibility.

Commercial manufacturing is adopting these methods through innovative approaches such as the establishment of energy-efficient and self-sustaining facilities. Some manufacturing plants are entirely powered by renewable energy sources like wind turbines and solar power.

By embracing and implementing these effective alternatives to traditional fossil fuel burning for energy, the industry is not only contributing to a cleaner environment but also fostering innovation, growth, and competitiveness in the global landscape of clean energy manufacturing.

In 2022, numerous countries, typically reliant on natural gas, faced economic pressures due to soaring prices and turned to more carbon-intensive fuels like coal,

resulting in a 0.6% increase in global coal demand. Notably, China and India, both net importers of natural gas, reported rises in coal usage by 1% and 4%, respectively. However, the United States diverged from this pattern. Disruptions in the coal supply chain prompted an increased reliance on both natural gas and renewables to fulfill energy demand.

Against the backdrop of a worldwide surge in natural gas prices, many nations shifted towards renewable energy sources to meet their energy requirements. Excluding hydropower, global consumption of renewable energy experienced a substantial 13% increase. Among major economies, Russia led with a remarkable 31% surge in renewable consumption. China and India followed with an 18% increase, while the United States recorded a 13% rise. This collective transition from natural gas to renewables played a pivotal role in significantly reducing the carbon intensity of the global economy.⁸

Figure 25

Natural gas and energy consumption

Note. From *Global greenhouse gas emissions: 1990-2021 and preliminary 2022 estimates*, by Rhodium Group, (2023)

⁸ Data collected from: <https://rhg.com/research/global-greenhouse-gas-emissions-2022/>

G. Conclusion

To sum up, this booklet delves into a range of topics encompassing sustainability, environmental responsibility, and energy efficiency within diverse industrial settings. It underscores the significance of the Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) framework for assessing companies' sustainability approaches, emphasizing the lack of a universal ESG reporting standard and the pivotal role of quality departments in achieving ESG objectives. Section two addresses the complexities of measuring and reporting greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, with a specific focus on challenges associated with Scope 3 emissions in manufacturing. The exploration extends to evaluating and minimizing the impact of human activities on the environment, highlighting the role of environment-oriented software tools like life cycle assessment software.

Furthermore, the booklet acknowledges the growing momentum of renewable energy systems, including biomass, solar thermal systems, and electrification, particularly amidst the challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic. It emphasizes the importance of renewable energy sourced from replenishable sources such as the sun, water, and wind.

In conclusion, the booklet offers a comprehensive overview of sustainability challenges and solutions, covering ESG frameworks, GHG emissions reporting, life cycle analysis, renewable energy adoption, and the critical role of energy and resource efficiency across various industrial sectors. The subsequent sections will delve into specific topics such as ESG Compliance & ESG reporting in manufacturing, emissions reduction in manufacturing, hybrid lifecycle analysis, resource efficiency strategies in manufacturing, and the adoption of clean energy in manufacturing.

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PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education and training

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PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

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BOOKLET

Module WN4: Resilience Competences for PM

**Co-funded by
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A. Introduction

Predictive maintenance (PdM) is a method of maintaining equipment based on data analysis and the actual condition of the equipment, to prevent failures and reduce costs and downtime, (Boer et al., 2019). PdM uses sensors that detect various parameters, such as vibration, temperature, or sound, to monitor the behaviour of the equipment and anticipate possible problems. PdM is a modern and efficient approach, that relies on artificial intelligence and advanced digital technologies, (Duncan, 2021; Islam et al., 2024; McKinsley, 2021).

Resilience competences (RC) are the skills and knowledge needed to ensure a resilient enterprise architecture, that can cope with changes and disruptions in the operational environment. RC involves continuous adaptation and improvement of processes, systems, and infrastructure, to maintain an optimal level of performance and safety. RC also requires a strategic vision and a capacity to learn from experience and feedback, (Teguede et al., 2022; Downes, 2020).

The theme “Resilience Competences for Predictive Maintenance” explores the link between PdM and RC, and how they can contribute to creating an agile, innovative, and sustainable enterprise, (Roberts et al., 2017). This theme is relevant for industries that use complex and critical equipment, such as health, chemistry, or food, and that need effective maintenance and a stable and flexible enterprise architecture, (Gallastegui et al., 2021).

Figure 38

Predictive maintenance

Note. From Condition Monitoring and Predictive Maintenance, by Fraunhofer Institute for Industrial Mathematics (ITWM), n.d.

(<https://www.itwm.fraunhofer.de/en/fields-of-application/predictive-maintenance.html>)

- *What is enterprise architecture and how does it relate to PdM?* (Prinsloo & Slade, 2013). Enterprise architecture is a conceptual framework that describes the structure, operation, and evolution of an organization. Enterprise

architecture includes four levels: business level, application level, technology level, and physical level. Each level has its own components, processes, and relationships. PdM is a maintenance method that applies to the physical level, but that has an impact on the other levels as well. For example, PdM can improve the quality of products and services, reduce operational risks, and optimize the use of resources.

- *What does it mean to have a resilient enterprise architecture?* (Çınar et al., 2020). A resilient enterprise architecture is able to cope with changes and disruptions in the operational environment, without compromising performance and safety. A resilient enterprise architecture has the following characteristics: it is adaptable, flexible, robust, scalable, secure, and sustainable. A resilient enterprise architecture can anticipate, prevent, detect, recover, and learn from crisis situations.
- *How to achieve a resilient enterprise architecture for PdM?* (Ifenthaler & Yin-Kim Yau, 2019). To achieve a resilient enterprise architecture for PdM, a holistic and systemic approach is needed, that takes into account all the levels and components of the enterprise architecture. A reference model for digital enterprise architecture applied to PdM is presented in the article Towards Resilient Enterprise Architecture for Predictive Maintenance. This model proposes a series of principles, patterns, methods, and tools to ensure a resilient enterprise architecture for PdM. Among them are: using a common language and standards to facilitate communication and interoperability between levels and components, using smart sensors and cloud platforms to collect, store, and process data about the condition of the equipment, applying advanced analytics and artificial intelligence techniques to generate predictions and recommendations for maintenance, implementing monitoring, alerting, and intervention mechanisms to manage emergency situations, creating scenarios and simulations to test and validate PdM solutions, developing competencies and organizational cultures that support innovation and continuous learning.

B. Resilience skills in Predictive Maintenance

In the fast-paced and dynamic landscape of the transport industry, the role of predictive maintenance personnel stands as a crucial linchpin in ensuring the smooth operation and longevity of transport infrastructure and equipment, (Leitner et al., 2019). This specialized cadre of professionals possesses a unique set of resilience competences essential to navigate the challenges inherent in maintaining complex transportation systems. From adept problem-solving skills to a steadfast commitment to safety and continuous learning, these individuals exemplify a blend of technical expertise and adaptability necessary to proactively address issues, mitigate risks, and sustain the integrity of transport infrastructure.

In this context, a comprehensive understanding and application of resilience competences become paramount to not only uphold operational efficiency but also to tackle unexpected disruptions with precision and efficiency. The following competences are identified as essential factors:

Adaptability is the ability to swiftly adjust to changing circumstances, such as unexpected breakdowns or modifications in maintenance schedules, without compromising the overall preventive maintenance plan, (Lee et al., 2019; Lawrence & Durana, 2021; Jonassen, 2011).

Key Aspect: The ability to quickly adjust to changing situations, such as equipment breakdowns or schedule changes, without affecting the overall maintenance plan.

Benefits: Enables quick response to unforeseen changes, maintaining operational continuity.

Challenges: Adapting swiftly while ensuring quality can be stressful and demanding.

Development: Encourage exposure to diverse scenarios through simulations and cross-training.

Example: In the airline industry, maintenance teams often face sudden aircraft system issues. An adaptable team can swiftly reroute maintenance resources to address these unexpected issues, minimizing flight delays.

Discussion: Adaptability in maintenance requires a deep understanding of system interdependencies and the ability to prioritize tasks under pressure. It's about balancing the urgency of immediate repairs with the importance of long-term maintenance plans.

Summary: Discusses the importance of adaptability in service-oriented industries, highlighting the need to adjust to changing customer needs and operational contexts.

Problem-Solving Skills

Problem-Solving skills describe the proficiency in quickly diagnosing issues within transportation equipment or infrastructure and devising effective solutions to ensure uninterrupted operations, (Wellsandt et al., 2022; Biedenbach & Marell, 2010).

Key Aspect: Quick identification and resolution of issues within transportation equipment or infrastructure.

Benefits: Essential for diagnosing and resolving issues promptly, reducing downtime.

Challenges: Requires analytical thinking and creativity, which can be taxing under pressure.

Development: Foster through regular training on troubleshooting techniques and exposure to varied problem scenarios.

Example: A problem-solving approach was demonstrated when a rapid transit system encountered an unforeseen signalling fault. The maintenance team quickly diagnosed the issue as a software glitch and implemented a patch, avoiding prolonged service disruptions.

Figure 39

Proficiency in quickly diagnosing issues with transportation equipment or infrastructure and devising effective solutions

Note. From *Cloud-Based IoT Applications and Their Roles in Smart Cities*, by Alam, (2021)

Discussion: Effective problem-solving in maintenance involves analytical thinking, a methodical approach to diagnosing issues, and creative solutions that ensure uninterrupted operations.

Summary: Offers insights into problem-solving as a critical skill in technical fields, emphasizing the importance of diagnosing and addressing complex issues effectively.

Technical Proficiency

Thorough knowledge and expertise in the technical aspects of the specific transport equipment and infrastructure being maintained, including understanding of machinery, electronics, and systems, (Meier et al., 2010; Lazarus & Folkman, 1984).

Key Aspect: In-depth knowledge of the technical aspects of transport equipment and infrastructure.

Benefits: Ensures effective maintenance and enhances system understanding.

Challenges: Keeping up with rapid technological advancements.

Development: Continual education and hands-on training with new technologies and systems.

Example: A technician with technical proficiency in railway systems can understand the intricacies of rail signalling and control systems, ensuring efficient maintenance and upgrades.

Figure 40

Transport Sectors

Note. From *Transport Sector Strategy 2019-2024*, by European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD), (2019)

https://www.ebrd.com/documents/transport/strategy-for-transport.pdf&ved=2ahUKEwj2zM6Uo96GAXUU_AIHhCkJAFAQFnoECBwQAw&usq=AOvVaw3QWQFwYYITD3kjYHoAtHh

Discussion: Technical proficiency encompasses understanding machinery, electronics, and systems. It requires ongoing learning to stay abreast of technological advancements.

Summary: Explores technical proficiency in the context of industrial systems, underlining the need for deep knowledge in machinery, electronics, and system operations.

Stress Management

Capability to remain calm and focused under pressure, especially during critical maintenance tasks or emergency situations to ensure safety and timely repairs, (Aven, 2016; Barrett & Mayson, 2007; Shappell & Wiegmann, 2000).

Key Aspect: Maintaining composure and focus under high-pressure situations.

Benefits: Improves decision-making and efficiency under pressure.

Challenges: High-stress situations can lead to burnout and errors.

Development: Offer stress management workshops and promote a supportive work environment.

Example: During an emergency repair on a cargo ship's engine at sea, the maintenance team remained calm and systematically addressed the issue, ensuring the safety of the crew and cargo.

Discussion: Stress management is crucial in maintenance, as high-pressure situations can lead to safety risks if not handled calmly and efficiently.

Summary: Provides a foundational understanding of stress management techniques, especially in high-pressure work environments like maintenance operations.

Risk Assessment

Risk Assessment refers to the skill of evaluating potential risks associated with equipment failure or infrastructure issues and implementing measures to mitigate these risks proactively, (Drucker, 2007).

Key Aspect: Evaluating potential risks associated with equipment failure or infrastructure issues.

Benefits: Proactive identification and mitigation of potential issues.

Challenges: Accurately predicting risks in complex systems.

Development: Training in risk management methodologies and analysis tools.

Example: Prior to a major sporting event, a stadium's maintenance team conducted a risk assessment of all infrastructure, pre-emptively addressing potential failures.

Discussion: Risk assessment involves identifying vulnerabilities, estimating the impact of potential failures, and implementing measures to mitigate these risks.

Summary: Discusses modern approaches to risk assessment, especially in scenarios with potential equipment failures or infrastructure issues.

Resourcefulness

Resourcefulness is the ability to effectively utilize available resources, whether in terms of tools, materials, or manpower, to optimize maintenance processes and minimize downtime, (Hargie, 2016; Argyris, 1999).

Key Aspect: Efficient utilization of available resources to optimize maintenance processes.

Benefits: Optimizes use of available resources, improving efficiency.

Challenges: Limited resources can hinder effective solutions.

Development: Encourage creative thinking and improvisation skills through challenging exercises.

Example: When a manufacturing plant faced a sudden shortage of a critical component, the maintenance team resourcefully modified existing parts to keep the production line running.

Discussion: Resourcefulness in maintenance is about being innovative in using tools, materials, and manpower, especially in resource-constrained situations.

Summary: Highlights the importance of resource optimization in maintenance, focusing on the effective use of tools, materials, and manpower.

Attention to Detail

Attention to detail refers to having a keen eye for detail to perform thorough inspections and identify even the smallest abnormalities or potential failures in transport equipment or infrastructure, (Pulakos et al., 2000).

Key Aspect: A meticulous approach to inspections, identifying even minor abnormalities.

Benefits: Early identification of potential issues, preventing larger problems.

Challenges: Overlooking minor details can lead to significant issues.

Development: Regular training in detailed inspections and mindfulness practices.

Example: In aircraft maintenance, attention to detail is crucial. A technician's ability to spot a small crack in the engine casing can prevent potential flight disasters.

Discussion: This skill is vital in ensuring that all aspects of equipment and infrastructure are functioning correctly and safely.

Summary: Emphasizes the significance of attention to detail in identifying potential issues in transportation equipment, a key factor in preventing accidents.

Time Management

This skill refers to the proficiency in managing time efficiently to adhere to maintenance schedules, ensuring that preventive measures are implemented without disrupting transport operations, (Salas et al., 2005; Reason, 2016; Masten & Reed, 2002; Duffuaa et al., 1999).

Key Aspect: Efficiently managing time to adhere to maintenance schedules.

Benefits: Ensures timely completion of tasks, maintaining schedules.

Challenges: Balancing numerous tasks within tight deadlines.

Development: Time management workshops and practical exercises in scheduling.

Example: Time management is exemplified when a public bus maintenance team completes all scheduled services overnight, ensuring no disruption to daily operations.

Discussion: Effective time management involves planning, scheduling, and executing maintenance tasks within set timeframes.

Summary: Discusses the importance of efficient time management in operational environments, ensuring timely implementation of preventive measures.

Communication Skills

Clear and concise communication with team members, supervisors, and other relevant stakeholders are essential to report findings, discuss maintenance plans, and coordinate activities effectively, (Hollnagel, 2011; Madni & Jackson, 2009).

Key Aspect: Clear and concise communication with all stakeholders in the maintenance process.

Benefits: Enhances collaboration and clarity in maintenance activities.

Challenges: Miscommunication can lead to errors and inefficiencies.

Development: Regular team-building activities and communication skills training.

Example: Effective communication was key when coordinating a multi-team effort to repair a collapsed bridge, ensuring that all parties were informed, and the repair was completed swiftly.

Figure 41

Communication Skills in maintenance industry

Note. From *10 Skills Those Entering the Manufacturing Industry Need*, by SurajMech, (2023) (<https://www.surajmech.com/2023/05/10-Skills-Those-Entering-the-Manufacturing-Industry.html>)

Discussion: This involves reporting findings, discussing plans, and coordinating activities to avoid misunderstandings and errors.

Summary: Highlights the necessity of clear and concise communication in maintenance, crucial for coordinating activities and reporting findings.

Continuous Learning Mindset

A Continuous Learning Mindset describes the willingness to stay updated with the latest technological advancements and industry best practices in maintenance techniques to improve overall efficiency and effectiveness, (Woods, 2006).

Key Aspect: Keeping up to date with technological advancements and best practices.

Benefits: Keeps maintenance practices current and effective.

Challenges: Finding time and resources for ongoing learning.

Development: Provide access to continuous learning opportunities, workshops, and seminars.

Example: A maintenance engineer attending workshops on the latest IoT-based maintenance tools exemplifies a continuous learning mindset.

Figure 42

Continuous Learning Mindset in maintenance industry

Note. From *Having a "Learning" Mindset versus a "Training" Mindset*, by Knox, (2021) (<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/having-learning-mindset-versus-training-hamish-knox>)

Discussion: This mindset is crucial for improving efficiency and staying relevant in a rapidly evolving field.

Summary: Explores the concept of continuous learning, emphasizing the need to stay updated with technological advancements and best practices, (Reason, 1997; Carthey et al., 2001).

Flexibility

Flexibility describes the ability to handle and adapt to changing priorities or unexpected situations, adjusting the maintenance plan accordingly while ensuring minimal impact on transport operations, (Hughes & Ferrett, 2016; Stamatis, 2003; U.S. Department of Labor, Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA), n.d.).

Key Aspect: Adjusting to changing priorities or unexpected situations.

Benefits: Allows for smooth adjustments to changing priorities.

Challenges: Rapid changes can disrupt plans and cause stress.

Development: Encourage an open mindset and adaptability through varied work experiences.

Example: Flexibility was demonstrated when a logistics company's maintenance team quickly shifted their focus from routine checks to emergency repairs due to a sudden equipment malfunction.

Figure 43

Flexibility in maintenance industry

Note. From *6 Things That You Must Know Before Defining Enterprise Maintenance Strategy*, by Balachandran, (n.d.)

(<https://www.maintwiz.com/blog/6-things-that-you-must-know-before-defining-enterprise-maintenance-strategy>)

Discussion: Being flexible ensures minimal impact on operations despite unforeseen changes or challenges.

Summary: Discusses flexibility in workplace settings, particularly in adjusting maintenance plans to minimize operational impact.

Team Collaboration

The capacity to work collaboratively within a team environment requires leveraging collective skills and knowledge to achieve maintenance objectives efficiently, (Salas et al., 2005; Dhillon, 2008; Shull, 2002).

Key Aspect: Working effectively within a team environment.

Benefits: Leverages collective expertise for more efficient problem-solving.

Challenges: Team dynamics can sometimes hinder collaboration.

Development: Promote teamwork through collaborative projects and team-building activities.

Example: Collaborative efforts were evident when a cross-functional team worked together to implement a new maintenance management system in a factory.

Discussion: Collaboration leverages collective skills and knowledge, enhancing the efficiency of achieving maintenance objectives.

Summary: Examines the dynamics of team collaboration, essential for achieving maintenance objectives.

Safety Consciousness

A strong commitment to safety protocols and regulations ensures the well-being of oneself, team members, and the general public while conducting maintenance activities, (Beale & Read, 2013).

Key Aspect: Adhering to safety protocols and regulations.

Benefits: Reduces accidents and ensures compliance with regulations.

Challenges: Complacency or unawareness can compromise safety.

Development: Regular safety training and promoting a culture of safety in the workplace.

Example: Safety consciousness is critical in chemical plant maintenance, where adherence to safety protocols can prevent hazardous accidents.

Figure 44

Safety consciousness in maintenance industry

Note. From *How a Visual Workplace Improves Safety*, by Schindler, (2012) (<https://www.reliableplant.com/Read/28891/visual-workplace-safety>)

Discussion: This competence ensures the well-being of maintenance personnel and the public.

Summary: Addresses the importance of safety protocols in maintenance to protect personnel and the public.

Resilience in Adversity

The skill of resilience in adversity describes the capability to bounce back from setbacks or challenges, maintaining a positive attitude and determination to overcome obstacles during maintenance tasks, (Rausand, 2011; Mobley, 2002).

Key Aspect: Overcoming setbacks or challenges with a positive attitude.

Benefits: Helps in maintaining productivity and morale in tough situations.

Challenges: Continual stress and setbacks can impact resilience.

Development: Encourage a positive work culture and provide support in challenging times.

Example: Resilience was shown by a maintenance team that successfully restored services after a major power outage, despite numerous obstacles.

Figure 45

Resilience in Adversity

Note. From *Thriving, Not Just Surviving in Changing Times: How Sustainability, Agility and Digitalization Intertwine with Organizational Resilience*, by Miceli et al., (2021)

Discussion: This skill involves maintaining determination and a solution-focused approach during challenging maintenance tasks.

Summary: Focuses on the ability to overcome challenges and maintain a positive attitude in adverse situations.

Implementing resilience in maintenance involves

Investing in Advanced Monitoring Tools such as sensors and IoT devices for real-time data collection and analysis. Continually training maintenance personnel to adapt to new technologies and methodologies. And, continuously reviewing and improving maintenance processes based on performance data and evolving industry practices.

Documentation and Record-Keeping

Accurate and comprehensive documentation of maintenance activities includes keeping records of inspections, repairs, and preventive measures taken for future reference, (Nyman & Levitt, 2001).

Key Aspect: Keeping accurate and comprehensive maintenance records.

Benefits: Ensures accurate tracking of maintenance history for informed decisions.

Challenges: Tedious and time-consuming, often overlooked.

Development: Training in documentation best practices and the use of management software.

Example: Detailed logging of all maintenance activities in a hospital's HVAC system ensures that future maintenance is informed and effective.

Figure 46

Records Management

Note. From *Records Management: Maintaining Your Organization's Information*. <https://www.smartsheet.com/record-management>, by Weller, (2017)

Discussion: Proper documentation aids in tracking the history of repairs and preventive measures, essential for future maintenance planning.

Summary: Discusses the importance of accurate documentation and record-keeping in maintenance activities for future reference and planning.

In conclusion, the resilience competences exhibited by preventive maintenance personnel within the transport industry form the bedrock of reliable and sustainable infrastructure and equipment maintenance. Their ability to swiftly adapt, troubleshoot effectively, and collaborate seamlessly underscores their pivotal role in upholding the integrity and functionality of transportation systems. As the industry continues to evolve with technological advancements and ever-changing demands, the resilience demonstrated by these professionals becomes increasingly instrumental. By continually honing their skills, embracing innovation,

and maintaining a steadfast commitment to safety and excellence, these individuals fortify the very foundation upon which the efficiency and reliability of transport infrastructure and equipment rest. Their resilience remains not just a trait but a cornerstone, ensuring the seamless functioning and enduring resilience of the transport industry.

C. Risk assessment tools for proactive problem identification in predictive maintenance

Using Risk Assessment Tools for proactive problem identification in maintenance operations involves several key steps and strategies. These tools help identify potential risks before they lead to equipment failure, thereby enabling preventive action. Here's how to effectively use them, (Mitchell, 2013; Bhamra et al., 2011; Herbane, 2010; Bowerman et al., 2004; Haddow et al., 2007):

1. Selecting Appropriate Risk Assessment Tools

Identify Suitable Tools: Choose tools that are relevant to your specific industry and equipment. Common tools include Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA), Risk Matrix, Hazard and Operability Study (HAZOP), and Root Cause Analysis (RCA). Choosing and customizing the right risk assessment tools is critical for effective predictive maintenance. Below is a list of platforms and software that are commonly used for different risk assessment methodologies. These tools can be adapted to suit specific industry requirements and equipment characteristics:

Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA)

- ReliaSoft XFMEA: A comprehensive tool for performing FMEA and ensuring that failure modes are identified and addressed.
- IQS Trubox: Offers FMEA capabilities as part of its broader quality management suite.
- APIS IQ-Software: Specialized in FMEA analysis, allowing for detailed risk assessment and documentation.

Figure 47

FMEA failure mode and effects analysis process

Note. From *Failure Modes and Effects Analysis*, by Spina, (2022)

(<https://medium.com/globant/failure-modes-and-effects-analysis-5441adc5f670>)

Risk Matrix

- BowTieXP: Advanced software that allows for risk matrix creation along with bowtie diagram analyses.
- Risk Matrix Tool by Palisade: Part of the DecisionTools Suite, this tool offers intuitive risk matrix development.
- Cority: Provides a risk matrix tool as part of its environmental, health, safety, and quality (EHSQ) software solutions.

Figure 48

FMEA failure mode and effects analysis process

Note. From *What is a risk matrix?*, by Papadopoulou, (2022) (<https://www.polonious-systems.com/what-is-a-risk-matrix>)

Hazard and Operability Study (HAZOP)

- PHAWorks RA Edition: A comprehensive tool for conducting HAZOP and other process hazard analyses.
- Process Safety Office® SuperChemicals™: A tool that integrates HAZOP study with advanced process safety management features.
- Canary Labs: Offers data historian and trending solutions that can aid in HAZOP studies by providing historical operational data.

Figure 49

Study process of Hazard and Operability Study (HAZOP)

Note. From *Study process of Hazard and Operability Study (HAZOP)*, by The Safety Master, (n.d.) (<https://www.thesafetymaster.com>)

Root Cause Analysis (RCA)

- Cause Mapping® by ThinkReliability: A tool that simplifies the process of conducting root cause analysis through cause mapping.
- RealityCharting®: A visual tool to help identify root causes and develop effective solutions.

TapRoot®: Offers a systematic process and tools for root cause analysis and problem-solving.

Figure 50

Steps of Root Cause Analysis (RCA)

Note. From *Root Cause Analysis [Video]*, by Nevada Department of Health and Human Services, (2017) (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TKv4Mw7qQbl>)

Customization Aspects

Configurability: Ensure that the tool allows for customization to align with specific maintenance processes and industry requirements.

Integration Capabilities: The tool should seamlessly integrate with existing maintenance management systems (like CMMS or EAM systems).

Scalability: Choose tools that can scale as the scope of your maintenance operations grows.

Additional Considerations: Training and Support: Ensure that the vendor provides adequate training and support for the tool.

Compliance and Standards: Check if the tool complies with industry standards and best practices.

2. Gathering and Analysing Data

To effectively manage and analyse data for predictive maintenance, selecting platforms that excel in data collection and analysis is crucial. These platforms

should be capable of aggregating data from various sources like equipment logs, sensors, maintenance records, and operator feedback, and then analysing this data to uncover patterns, trends, or anomalies indicative of potential risks. Here are some recommended platforms for these purposes:

Platforms for Data Collection

- PI System by OSIsoft: A comprehensive data management system that captures data from various sources, including sensors and equipment logs, ideal for industrial environments.
- IBM Maximo: Offers robust asset management and maintenance features, including the ability to collect and analyse data from various sources.
- ThingWorx (PTC): An IoT platform that excels in collecting sensor data and integrating it with other data sources for comprehensive analysis.
- Splunk: Known for its ability to ingest and analyse massive amounts of data, including machine data and logs, useful for identifying trends and anomalies.
- Honeywell Forge: A powerful industrial IoT platform that collects and analyses data from diverse industrial equipment.

Figure 51

Data Collection in maintenance industry

Note. From *Data Collection in maintenance industry*, by Atera, (n.d.) (<https://www.atera.com>)

Platforms for Data Analysis

- Tableau: A leading data visualization tool that can analyse maintenance data and present it in an easily interpretable format.
- SAS Analytics for IoT: Offers advanced analytics capabilities, including AI and machine learning, to analyse data from IoT devices.
- Microsoft Power BI: A powerful business intelligence tool that can integrate with various data sources for comprehensive analysis.
- Predix (by GE Digital): An industrial IoT platform designed for data analysis and operational insights, particularly in heavy industries.
- MATLAB and Simulink: Offer a powerful environment for analysing engineering data and developing predictive maintenance algorithms.

Figure 52

Data Analysis in maintenance industry

Note. From *Operational Predictive Maintenance Market Analysis 2023|Challenges & Opportunities 2030*, by Market Reports World, (2023) (<https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/operational-predictive-maintenance-market-analysis>)

Integration and Customization

- Integration Capabilities: Ensure the platforms can integrate with existing systems like CMMS or ERP systems.
- Customization: Look for tools that offer customization to tailor the data collection and analysis process to your specific industry needs and equipment types.
- Additional Considerations
- Scalability: Choose platforms that can handle the growing volume and complexity of data.
- User-Friendly Interface: Tools should have an intuitive interface for ease of use by maintenance teams.
- Security: Given the sensitive nature of data, ensure the platforms have robust security measures in place.
- Data Collection: Collect data from various sources such as equipment history logs, sensor data, maintenance records, and operator feedback.
- Data Analysis: Analyse the data to identify patterns, trends, or anomalies that could indicate potential risks or emerging issues.

Figure 53

Open-source big data pipeline analysis technologies

Note. From *Big data and stream processing platforms for Industry 4.0 requirements mapping for a predictive maintenance use case*, by Sahal et al., (2020)

3. Identifying Potential Risks

To effectively conduct Failure Modes Identification and Hazard Identification, various specialized software and tools can be utilized. These tools assist in performing methodologies like Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) and Hazard and Operability Study (HAZOP) systematically and efficiently. Below are some recommended platforms for these specific purposes:

Platforms for Failure Modes Identification (FMEA)

- ReliaSoft XFMEA: This software is specifically designed for FMEA. It helps in identifying potential failure modes, analysing their effects, and prioritizing actions based on risk.
- IQS Trubox FMEA Module: Part of the IQS Trubox quality management suite, this module facilitates detailed FMEA processes, allowing for comprehensive risk analysis and management.
- APIS IQ-Software: Widely used for FMEA, APIS IQ-Software supports complex analyses and is suitable for various industries, including automotive, aerospace, and manufacturing.
- Siemens PLM Software - Teamcenter: Provides FMEA capabilities integrated within their product lifecycle management suite, useful for managing risks throughout the product lifecycle.

Figure 54

FMEA for Identifying Potential Risks

Note. From *What is FMEA*, by Datalyzer, (n.d.)
(<https://datalyzer.com/resources/what-is-fmea/>)

Platforms for Hazard Identification (HAZOP)

- PHAWorks RA Edition by Primatech: A dedicated tool for process hazard analysis, including HAZOP. It facilitates team collaboration and systematic hazard analysis.
- Process Safety Office® SuperChems™: This tool integrates HAZOP study with advanced process safety management features, making it suitable for complex industrial environments.
- Canary Labs Hazard Analysis Tools: Focuses on data historian and trending solutions that support HAZOP studies by providing historical operational data analysis.
- RiskyProject Professional by Intaver Institute: While primarily a project risk management software, RiskyProject includes features that can support HAZOP analysis, especially in project-driven environments.

Integration and Customization

- Integration Capabilities: These tools should seamlessly integrate with other maintenance and operation systems for holistic risk management.
- Customization: The ability to customize these tools to specific industry needs and equipment types is crucial for effective analysis.
- User Considerations
 - User Interface: Look for tools with an intuitive interface for ease of use.
 - Training and Support: Ensure the vendor offers adequate training and support for these tools.
 - Reporting Capabilities: Efficient reporting features will help in communicating the findings effectively to all relevant stakeholders.
- These platforms are designed to help maintenance and safety teams in identifying potential failure modes and hazards systematically, thereby enabling proactive measures to mitigate risks and ensure safe and reliable operations.
- Failure Modes Identification: Use tools like FMEA to identify potential failure modes of equipment components and their possible effects.
- Hazard Identification: Use tools like HAZOP to systematically identify hazards in the processes and operations.

Figure 55

Integration and Customization of Potential Risks

Note. From *What Are the Risks of Custom Software Development?*, by McCarty, (n.d.) (<https://www.gavant.com/library/what-are-the-risks-of-custom-software-development>)

4. Assessing Risks

For effective risk evaluation and prioritization in maintenance operations, it's important to use tools that can assess the likelihood and impact of identified risks and help in their prioritization. Here are some recommended platforms and tools that are designed for these purposes:

Platforms for Risk Evaluation

- BowTieXP: This software is renowned for its risk evaluation capabilities, particularly using the bowtie method. It allows users to visualize risks in terms of cause and consequence, facilitating effective risk assessment and management.
- RiskPoynt Barrier Model: RiskPoynt is a tool that integrates risk matrix methodologies with real-time data to evaluate and monitor operational risks continuously.
- Palisade @RISK: Part of the DecisionTools Suite, @RISK integrates with Microsoft Excel to provide risk analysis using Monte Carlo simulation, which can be very effective in evaluating the probability of risk occurrences and their impacts.

- Cority Risk Management Software: Offers a comprehensive suite for risk evaluation, including the creation of risk matrices and risk assessment tools tailored to specific industry needs.

Tools for Risk Prioritization

- Qualitative Risk Analysis Matrix (part of various EHS software): Many Environmental, Health, and Safety (EHS) software platforms include tools for creating and utilizing risk matrices for qualitative risk analysis and prioritization.
- SAP Risk Management: Part of the SAP GRC suite, this tool helps in identifying, analysing, and prioritizing risks, providing a clear view of the risk landscape.
- LogicManager: This risk management software provides robust tools for risk prioritization, helping organizations to focus on the most critical risks.
- IsoMetrix: A versatile software solution for governance, risk, and compliance, IsoMetrix includes features for risk assessment and prioritization, tailored to various industry sectors.

Integration and Customization

- Integration Capabilities: These tools should ideally integrate with existing maintenance management systems for a unified approach to risk management.
- Customization: The ability to customize risk matrices and prioritization criteria based on specific operational contexts and industry standards is important for effective risk management.
- Additional Considerations
- User-Friendly Interface: Tools should be user-friendly to ensure they are accessible to all relevant personnel, not just risk specialists.
- Reporting and Visualization: Effective reporting and visualization capabilities are essential for communicating risk assessments and priorities to stakeholders.
- Scalability: Choose tools that can scale with the organization's growth and evolving risk landscape.
- Risk Evaluation: Evaluate the identified risks in terms of their likelihood of occurrence and potential impact on operations using a Risk Matrix or similar tools.
- Prioritization: Prioritize the risks based on their severity and the urgency of addressing them.

By utilizing these platforms, maintenance teams can systematically evaluate and prioritize risks, ensuring that resources are focused on the most critical areas to enhance safety and operational reliability.

5. Implementing Preventive Measures

Developing and implementing effective mitigation strategies for high-priority risks in maintenance operations is essential to minimize potential disruptions and enhance safety. Monitoring and reviewing these strategies on an ongoing basis ensure their continued relevance and effectiveness. Continuously monitor the effectiveness of these strategies and review them regularly to ensure they remain relevant and effective.

Mitigation Strategies

- Identify High-Priority Risks: Prioritize risks based on their severity and urgency. Focus on risks that have the potential for significant impact on operations and safety.
- Redesign Processes: If certain maintenance processes are prone to risks, consider redesigning them to reduce vulnerabilities. For example, if a maintenance procedure poses safety hazards, revise it to incorporate safer practices.
- Equipment Upgrades: Assess whether equipment upgrades or enhancements can mitigate risks. Upgrading outdated equipment with modern, safer, and more reliable alternatives can be an effective strategy.
- Stricter Maintenance Schedules: Implementing more frequent and rigorous maintenance schedules can help prevent potential failures. Regular inspections, servicing, and preventive maintenance activities should be part of the strategy.
- Training and Skill Development: Ensure that maintenance personnel are adequately trained and possess the necessary skills to address high-priority risks. Training programs can focus on safety protocols and best practices.
- Use of Technology: Employ technology solutions such as predictive maintenance tools, condition monitoring systems, and IoT sensors to detect issues early and address them proactively.

Platforms for Developing Mitigation Strategies

- SAP Asset Strategy and Performance Management (ASPM): SAP ASPM is designed for risk-based asset management. It helps in developing strategies to mitigate risks by providing insights into asset performance and health.
- IBM Maximo: IBM Maximo offers comprehensive asset management capabilities, including the ability to plan and implement mitigation strategies for high-priority risks.

- Infor EAM: Infor Enterprise Asset Management provides tools for risk assessment and mitigation, allowing organizations to develop strategies and prioritize actions.
- AVEVA Asset Information Management: AVEVA offers solutions for risk-based asset integrity management, assisting in the development of mitigation strategies to ensure equipment integrity.
- Oracle Maintenance Cloud: Oracle's Maintenance Cloud offers maintenance planning and asset management capabilities, supporting the development and execution of mitigation strategies.

Figure 56

Data platforms Implementing Preventive Measures

Note. From *How health care should take advantage of the cloud*, by Linthicum, (2018) (<https://www.infoworld.com/article/3294712/how-health-care-should-take-advantage-of-the-cloud.html>)

Monitoring and Review

- Establish Key Performance Indicators (KPIs): Define measurable KPIs that are linked to the effectiveness of mitigation strategies. These may include metrics like equipment uptime, incident frequency, or safety performance.
- Continuous Monitoring: Implement systems and processes for ongoing monitoring of KPIs. This could involve real-time data collection through sensors or regular inspections.
- Regular Reviews: Schedule periodic reviews of mitigation strategies and their outcomes. Assess whether the implemented measures are achieving the desired results.
- Feedback Loops: Create mechanisms for collecting feedback from maintenance personnel, operators, and other stakeholders. Their insights can inform adjustments to the mitigation strategies.

- **Adaptability:** Be prepared to adapt and refine strategies based on changing circumstances, emerging risks, or new insights. Flexibility is key to maintaining effectiveness.
- **Documentation:** Keep comprehensive records of the mitigation strategies, their implementation, and the results of monitoring and reviews. Documentation is vital for accountability and future reference.
- **Root Cause Analysis:** In the event of failures or incidents, conduct root cause analysis to understand why mitigation strategies may have fallen short and use the findings to improve strategies.
- **Communication:** Communicate the outcomes of reviews and any necessary adjustments to all relevant stakeholders, including maintenance teams, management, and safety personnel.

Platforms for Monitoring and Review

- **IBM Watson IoT:** IBM Watson IoT provides real-time data monitoring capabilities for equipment and assets. It can be used to monitor the effectiveness of mitigation strategies.
- **Schneider Electric EcoStruxure Asset Advisor:** This platform offers remote monitoring and predictive analytics for critical equipment, aiding in continuous assessment.
- **Dude Solutions MaintenanceEdge:** Dude Solutions provides maintenance management software with monitoring features, enabling ongoing tracking of asset performance and risk.
- **Fiix:** Fiix offers maintenance and asset management software with monitoring and reporting capabilities to assess the impact of mitigation strategies.
- **Uptake:** Uptake provides industrial AI and analytics solutions that can be used for real-time monitoring and evaluation of asset health and risk mitigation.

6. Training and Involvement

Staff Training: Train maintenance staff and operators in using risk assessment tools and recognizing early warning signs of potential problems.

Stakeholder Involvement: Involve various stakeholders, including maintenance teams, operators, and management, in the risk assessment process for a comprehensive understanding of risks.

Figure 57

Training and Involvement

Note. From *Does Your Company Have an Effective Safety Management System?*, by Tompkins, (2016) (<https://incident-prevention.com/blog/does-your-company-have-an-effective-safety-management-system>)

Staff Training

1. Identify Training Needs: Assess the specific training needs of maintenance staff and operators. Determine the level of expertise required to effectively use risk assessment tools and recognize early warning signs.
2. Select Training Programs: Choose appropriate training programs or courses that align with the identified needs. Consider both in-house training and external certifications.
3. Hands-On Training: Ensure that training includes practical, hands-on sessions where staff can apply risk assessment tools in real or simulated scenarios.
4. Continuous Learning: Promote a culture of continuous learning and skill development. Encourage staff to stay updated on industry best practices and emerging risks.
5. Safety Training: Integrate safety training into risk assessment training. Emphasize the importance of safety protocols and procedures during maintenance activities.
6. Feedback Mechanism: Establish a feedback mechanism where staff can provide input on the effectiveness of the training programs and suggest improvements.

Staff Training Platforms:

- LinkedIn Learning: Offers courses on predictive maintenance, reliability engineering, and related topics. Employees can access training materials at their own pace.

- Udemy for Business: Provides a wide range of courses on predictive maintenance techniques, data analysis, and industrial automation. Companies can assign courses to employees.
- Coursera for Business: Offers courses from top universities and institutions on maintenance strategies, data analytics, and more. Allows organizations to create custom learning paths.
- edX for Business: Provides access to courses on predictive maintenance, machine learning, and asset management. Companies can offer certifications to employees.
- Skillsoft: Offers a library of courses on maintenance best practices, asset reliability, and data-driven maintenance. Includes reporting and tracking features.

Stakeholder Involvement

1. Identify Stakeholders: Identify all relevant stakeholders, including maintenance teams, operators, management, and safety personnel, who should be involved in the risk assessment process.
2. Collaborative Workshops: Organize collaborative workshops or meetings where stakeholders from different departments can come together to discuss and assess risks.
3. Brainstorming Sessions: Encourage brainstorming sessions where stakeholders can share their insights and experiences regarding potential risks and mitigation strategies.
4. Risk Assessment Teams: Form cross-functional risk assessment teams that include representatives from various departments. These teams can collectively identify and evaluate risks.
5. Regular Meetings: Schedule regular meetings or review sessions to keep stakeholders informed about the progress of risk assessments and any actions taken.
6. Transparent Communication: Maintain transparent communication channels so that all stakeholders are aware of the identified risks, mitigation plans, and their roles in the process.
7. Feedback and Reporting: Establish a system for stakeholders to provide feedback on risk assessments and report any observed early warning signs or safety concerns.
8. Empowerment: Empower stakeholders to take ownership of safety and risk management. Encourage them to proactively raise concerns and suggest improvements.

Stakeholder Involvement Platforms:

1. Microsoft Teams: Facilitates collaboration and communication among maintenance teams, operators, and management. It allows for meetings, discussions, and document sharing.
2. Slack: Provides a platform for real-time messaging and collaboration. Teams can create channels for specific maintenance projects and discussions.
3. Trello: Offers a visual project management tool where stakeholders can organize tasks, track progress, and collaborate on maintenance projects.
4. Asana: Allows teams to manage projects and tasks collaboratively. It can be used for tracking maintenance-related activities and sharing updates.
5. SharePoint: A Microsoft platform for document management and collaboration. It can be customized to create shared spaces for maintenance-related documents and information.
6. Jira: Originally designed for software development, Jira can be adapted for maintenance project management and issue tracking. It's suitable for more technical teams.
7. Monday.com: Provides a visual project management and collaboration platform that can be customized for maintenance projects and task assignments.
8. Basecamp: Offers project management and collaboration tools for teams. It can be used for coordinating maintenance activities and sharing project updates.
9. Miro: A collaborative online whiteboard platform where stakeholders can brainstorm, plan, and visualize maintenance processes and strategies.
10. Zoho Projects: Provides project management and collaboration features for teams. It can be customized for maintenance project tracking and documentation.

7. Documentation and Reporting

Record-Keeping:

- Structured Documentation: Maintain a structured and organized system for documenting the risk assessment process. Use digital tools or software for consistency.
- Capture Data: Record all relevant data, including identified risks, their severity, potential impacts, and recommended mitigation strategies.
- Timeline Tracking: Include timestamps to track when risk assessments were conducted and when actions were taken.
- Version Control: Implement version control for documents to ensure that the most up-to-date information is always accessible.
- Digital Storage: Store documentation in a secure digital format that allows for easy retrieval and sharing among team members.
- Cross-Referencing: Cross-reference documents to link risk assessments with maintenance plans and procedures.

Figure 58

Corrective action documentation

Note. From *Corrective and Preventive Action Management*, by Quality Assurance Solutions, (n.d.) (<https://www.quality-assurance-solutions.com/corrective-and-preventive-action-management.html>)

Documentation Platforms:

- Microsoft SharePoint: SharePoint allows for structured document management and collaboration. It's suitable for creating a centralized repository for risk assessment records.
- Google Drive: Google Drive offers cloud-based document storage and collaboration tools. It can be used for storing and sharing risk assessment documents.
- Dropbox Business: Dropbox Business provides a secure platform for storing and sharing documents. It offers version control and access controls.
- Box: Box is a cloud content management platform that can be customized for document storage and collaboration, including risk assessment records.
- Notion: Notion is a versatile workspace tool that can be adapted for structured documentation of risk assessments and reporting.
- Evernote Business: Evernote Business allows for note-taking and organization of risk assessment findings and actions. It's suitable for teams.
- Confluence: Confluence by Atlassian is a collaboration platform that can be customized for documentation and knowledge sharing related to risk assessments.

Reporting:

- **Scheduled Reports:** Establish a regular reporting schedule to inform relevant stakeholders about the outcomes of risk assessments. This could be monthly, quarterly, or as needed.
- **Clear Communication:** Present information in a clear and concise manner. Use visual aids such as charts and graphs to enhance understanding.
- **Executive Summaries:** Include executive summaries that provide a high-level overview of key findings and actions taken.
- **Distribution Lists:** Maintain updated distribution lists to ensure that reports reach the appropriate individuals, including maintenance teams, management, and safety personnel.
- **Actionable Insights:** Highlight actionable insights and recommendations. Clearly state any changes made to maintenance plans or procedures as a result of risk assessments.
- **Feedback Loop:** Encourage stakeholders to provide feedback on the reports and use their input for continuous improvement.
- **Archiving:** Archive historical reports for reference. This allows for tracking changes and trends over time.
- **Accessibility:** Ensure that reports are accessible to relevant parties when needed, especially in emergency situations.
- **Compliance:** Ensure that reports adhere to any regulatory requirements or industry standards related to risk assessment and reporting.
- **Training:** Provide training to staff involved in documentation and reporting to maintain consistency and quality.

Reporting Platforms:

- **Microsoft Power BI:** Power BI is a business analytics tool that can be used for creating interactive and visually appealing reports based on risk assessment data.
- **Tableau:** Tableau is a data visualization and reporting tool that can help in presenting risk assessment outcomes in a visual format.
- **Google Data Studio:** Google Data Studio enables the creation of dynamic and shareable reports using data from risk assessments and maintenance activities.
- **Sisense:** Sisense is a data analytics and reporting platform that can be customized for generating reports on risk assessment findings.
- **QlikView:** QlikView is a data discovery and reporting tool that can be used for creating insightful reports on risk assessment data.
- **TIBCO Spotfire:** TIBCO Spotfire provides advanced analytics and reporting capabilities for visualizing and analysing risk assessment results.

- Microsoft Excel: Excel can be a simple yet effective tool for creating basic risk assessment reports. It's widely accessible and can be customized.
- Smartsheet: Smartsheet offers project management and collaboration features, making it suitable for tracking and reporting on risk assessment actions and progress.
- PowerPoint: PowerPoint can be used to create visual presentations summarizing risk assessment findings and actions taken.
- Report Writing Software: Consider industry-specific report writing software that aligns with your organization's needs for risk assessment reporting.

8. Continuous Improvement

Figure 59

Implement the plan-do-check-act principle

Note. From *Focusing on Continuous Improvement in the Workplace*, by Creative Safety Supply, (2022) (<https://www.creativesafetysupply.com/articles/continuous-improvement>)

Feedback Loops:

- Feedback Mechanisms: Implement mechanisms for collecting feedback from maintenance teams, operators, and other stakeholders involved in the risk assessment process.
- Regular Reviews: Conduct regular reviews of risk assessment outcomes with relevant teams. This can be done through meetings, surveys, or feedback forms.

- Open Communication: Foster an open communication culture where team members feel comfortable providing feedback and suggesting improvements.
- Actionable Feedback: Act on feedback received promptly. Address identified issues and make necessary adjustments to the risk assessment process.
- Feedback Analysis: Analyse feedback data to identify recurring issues or trends. This can help in addressing systemic problems.
- Continuous Training: Provide ongoing training to staff involved in risk assessment to ensure they are aware of best practices and can provide valuable feedback.
- Documentation: Document feedback and the actions taken to address it. This helps in tracking improvements over time.

Feedback Loops Platforms:

- Microsoft Teams: Use Teams for conducting feedback meetings, surveys, and discussions with maintenance teams, operators, and stakeholders. It provides a collaborative environment for feedback collection.
- Slack: Create channels in Slack for feedback discussions and maintain open communication channels for team members to share insights and suggestions.
- SurveyMonkey: Use SurveyMonkey to create and distribute surveys for collecting structured feedback from maintenance teams and stakeholders.
- Google Forms: Google Forms is a simple and free tool for creating feedback forms and surveys. Responses can be collected and analysed in Google Sheets.
- Trello: Set up Trello boards for tracking feedback and action items. Assign cards to team members responsible for implementing improvements.
- Asana: Asana can be used for managing tasks related to addressing feedback. Create tasks and projects for continuous improvement initiatives.
- Zendesk: Zendesk offers customer support and feedback management solutions that can be adapted for internal feedback collection and tracking.

Adaptation to Changes:

- Monitoring Changes: Continuously monitor changes in equipment, technology, or the operational environment that may impact risk assessments. This includes updates to machinery, software, or safety regulations.

- Change Management: Establish a structured change management process that includes a risk assessment component. Assess the impact of changes on existing risk assessments.
- Regular Updates: Review and update risk assessment procedures and documentation regularly to reflect changes. This should be done in collaboration with relevant experts and stakeholders.
- Risk Reassessment: When significant changes occur, conduct a reassessment of risks associated with affected equipment or processes. Ensure that risk assessments remain accurate and up to date.
- Emergency Response: Develop contingency plans and emergency response protocols for scenarios where changes may pose immediate risks.
- Cross-Functional Teams: Involve cross-functional teams in the adaptation process to gather diverse perspectives and insights.
- Documentation Updates: Update risk assessment documentation, including risk matrices, hazard assessments, and mitigation plans, to align with changes.
- Training: Provide training to staff on updated risk assessment procedures and any changes that affect their roles or responsibilities.
- Testing: Test and validate the effectiveness of risk assessment updates in real-world scenarios to ensure they address new challenges.
- Lessons Learned: Capture lessons learned from previous changes and use them to inform future adaptation efforts.

Adaptation to Changes Platforms:

- Change Management Software: Invest in change management software such as Prosci or ChangeScout to manage and track changes, including their impact on risk assessments.
- Jira: Jira by Atlassian can be configured to handle change management and issue tracking. It's suitable for technical teams and project management.
- SharePoint: SharePoint can serve as a central repository for change-related documents and risk assessment updates. It facilitates collaboration among teams.
- Confluence: Confluence, also by Atlassian, can be used for documenting and communicating changes and updates to risk assessments.
- Lucidspark: Lucidspark is a virtual whiteboard platform that can facilitate brainstorming and planning sessions related to adaptation to changes.
- Miro: Miro is another collaborative online whiteboard tool that can be used for visualizing and planning adaptations to the risk assessment process.

- Change Tracking Software: Explore specialized change tracking software solutions that help organizations manage and document changes in real-time.
- Learning Management Systems (LMS): LMS platforms like Moodle or TalentLMS can be used for training staff on updated risk assessment procedures and changes.
- Project Management Tools: Platforms like Monday.com or Smartsheet can assist in project management related to adaptation efforts.
- ERP Systems: If your organization uses an Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP) system, it may have modules or functionalities for change management and risk assessment adaptation.

Key Considerations:

Technology Integration: Utilize advanced technologies like predictive analytics and IoT devices for more accurate and real-time risk assessment.

Compliance and Standards: Ensure that the risk assessment process complies with relevant industry standards and regulations

D. Equipping predictive maintenance experts with resilience competences

In this module, we delve into the critical concept of resilience in maintenance operations, a key factor in ensuring the longevity, safety, and efficiency of industrial and transport equipment, (Wallace & Webber, 2017; Siegel, 2016). Through a series of carefully structured sessions, participants will gain in-depth knowledge and practical skills in various aspects of resilience, including human safety systems, advanced risk assessment tools, structural integrity assessment, and effective strategies for both mitigating potential failures and recovering from disruptions.

As industries increasingly rely on sophisticated technology and face a myriad of operational challenges, the need for maintenance expert's adept in resilience competences has never been greater. This module is not just about imparting theoretical knowledge; it's a journey towards transforming maintenance practices by instilling a proactive, adaptive, and comprehensive approach to maintenance challenges. Whether you are looking to enhance your skill set or aiming to implement cutting-edge maintenance practices in your organization, this module is your stepping stone to becoming a leader in resilient predictive maintenance, (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2018; Dhillon, 2008; Reason, 1997).

Learning Objectives:

- Understand the importance of resilience in Predictive Maintenance.
- Acquire knowledge of Human Safety Systems in maintenance operations.
- Learn to use Risk Assessment Tools for proactive problem identification.
- Gain proficiency in Structural Assessment for predictive maintenance planning.
- Develop Mitigation Strategies to address potential failures.
- Explore Forecasting Tools for predictive analysis.
- Learn Efficient Recovery Planning for quick response to disruptions.

Resilience in Predictive Maintenance

The concept of resilience in maintenance operations refers to the ability of a maintenance system to effectively anticipate, respond to, adapt, and recover from unexpected disruptions or changes while maintaining continuous operations. This concept is increasingly important in various industries, especially those relying heavily on machinery and infrastructure, such as manufacturing, transportation, and energy sectors, (Bhamra et al., 2011).

- Adaptation refers to the capability to adjust strategies and processes in the face of changing conditions or in the aftermath of a disruption. Adaptation

involves learning from experiences and incorporating those lessons into future maintenance practices.

- Recovery refers to the ability to return to normal operations as quickly and safely as possible after a disruption. This includes having contingency plans in place and the ability to execute them effectively.
- Continuous Improvement refers to integrating lessons learned from past experiences into maintenance strategies and operations. This involves ongoing training, updating procedures, and investing in new technologies that enhance the resilience of maintenance operations.

In practice, resilience in maintenance operations is about creating a robust system that is not only reactive to immediate issues but also proactive in preventing future problems. It encompasses a holistic approach that includes risk management, safety protocols, resource management, and the use of advanced technologies like predictive analytics and IoT devices for real-time monitoring and decision-making.

The goal of resilience in predictive maintenance

The goal of resilience in maintenance is to ensure that operations are not just efficient and effective under normal conditions, but also robust and adaptable in the face of challenges, thereby minimizing downtime, reducing costs, and maintaining high levels of safety and quality. Resilience in maintenance operations plays a crucial role in ensuring the longevity, safety, and efficiency of industrial and transport equipment through several key mechanisms, (Bhamra et al, 2011):

1. Longevity of Equipment

Proactive Maintenance

Resilient maintenance strategies often involve proactive approaches like predictive maintenance, where potential issues are identified and addressed before they escalate. This reduces wear and tear and extends the life of equipment.

Regular Assessments and Adaptations

Ongoing assessments and adaptations of maintenance strategies based on new data, technologies, and practices help in keeping the equipment in optimal condition over a longer period.

Stress Testing and Upgrades

Regular stress testing and upgrades based on the latest standards and technologies ensure that equipment can withstand evolving operational demands.

2. Safety

Anticipatory Actions

By anticipating potential failures and risks, resilient maintenance systems can implement pre-emptive measures, reducing the likelihood of accidents and ensuring safer operational environments.

Emergency Preparedness

Effective training and emergency response plans ensure quick and safe actions in case of equipment failure, minimizing the risk of injury or damage.

Compliance with Safety Standards

Regularly updating maintenance procedures to comply with the latest safety standards and regulations keeps equipment safe for use and minimizes hazards.

3. Efficiency

Minimized Downtime

By predicting and preventing failures, maintenance downtime is significantly reduced, leading to higher operational efficiency.

Resource Optimization

Resilient maintenance systems optimize the use of resources, including manpower, materials, and tools, ensuring that maintenance activities are carried out efficiently.

Data-Driven Decisions

Utilizing data analytics and IoT for maintenance decisions leads to more precise, timely, and efficient maintenance actions.

Implementing Resilience in Maintenance

Implementing resilience in maintenance involves investing in advanced monitoring tools, such as sensors and IoT devices for real-time data collection and analysis.

Training and Development

Continually training maintenance personnel to adapt to new technologies and methodologies.

Regular Review and Improvement

Continuously reviewing and improving maintenance processes based on performance data and evolving industry practices.

The resilience in maintenance operations ensures longevity, safety, and efficiency by adopting a proactive, anticipatory approach, utilizing modern technologies, adhering to safety standards, and continuously adapting and improving maintenance practices.

E. Resilience Training based on demonstrative videos

In order to underline the profound significance of Resilience within maintenance operation, the primary objective of the following chapter is to establish a rigorous understanding of resilience, defined as the capacity to anticipate, prepare for, respond to, and adapt to incremental changes and sudden disruptions. By drawing on video resources, you are invited to deepen your knowledge on this topic. Through comprehensive analyses of real-world case studies, we illuminate the tangible impact of resilience on overall maintenance efficiency and, critically, human safety. Drawing insights from diverse industries, we underscore the indispensable role of resilience in mitigating risks and safeguarding the well-being of maintenance personnel. By navigating through the intricate interplay of anticipation and adaptation, we endeavour to equip participants with the essential skills and knowledge needed to navigate the dynamic landscape of maintenance operations with precision and efficacy.

Session 1: Introduction to Resilience in Predictive Maintenance

Objective:

Establish the significance of resilience in Predictive Maintenance.

- Definition of resilience in the maintenance context.
- Case studies showcasing the impact of resilience on overall maintenance efficiency.
- Discussion on the role of resilience in ensuring human safety.

Definition of Resilience in Maintenance:

Understanding resilience as the ability to anticipate, prepare for, respond to, and adapt to incremental changes and sudden disruptions in maintenance operations.

Case Studies: Analysis of real-world incidents where resilience in maintenance led to improved outcomes. For example, the aviation industry's response to mechanical failures.

Role of Resilience in Human Safety: Discussing how resilient maintenance practices contribute to overall safety in operations.

Video resource: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mveN-1r7XiA>

Example: An airline company employing resilience strategies to quickly adapt to an unexpected engine failure, minimizing flight delays and ensuring passenger safety.

References: Woods (2006), Reason (1997), Carthey et al. (2001):

- *Summary:* This session introduces the concept of resilience in the maintenance context, utilizing case studies and discussions on human safety.
- *Key Aspects:* Understanding resilience as anticipative, responsive, adaptive, and absorptive capacity in maintenance operations.
- *Challenges:* Balancing rapid response with thorough analysis; integrating resilience into existing processes.
- *Benefits:* Enhanced ability to handle unexpected disruptions, leading to improved maintenance efficiency and safety.

Session 2: Human Safety Systems in Predictive Maintenance

Objective: Understand and implement safety systems to ensure the well-being of maintenance personnel.

- Overview of Human Safety Systems in maintenance operations.

Overview of Human Safety Systems

Exploring systems designed to protect personnel during maintenance tasks.

Identification of Safety Hazards

Techniques for identifying potential hazards in maintenance operations.

Implementation of Safety Protocols

Best practices for developing and implementing safety protocols.

Video resource: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0Sc3VBsvFHw>

Example: A chemical plant implementing advanced safety systems, such as automated emergency shutdowns, following a safety audit that identified potential hazards.

Reference: International Labour Organization (2010), Hughes & Ferrett (2016), OSHA Guidelines (n.d.).

- *Summary:* Focuses on implementing safety systems and identifying hazards in maintenance operations.
- *Key Aspects:* Overview of safety systems, hazard identification, and implementation of safety protocols.
- *Challenges:* Keeping up with evolving safety standards and ensuring compliance.

- Benefits: Reduced risk of accidents and improved well-being of maintenance personnel.

Session 3: Risk Assessment Tools for Proactive Maintenance

Objective: Learn to use tools for identifying and assessing risks in maintenance processes.

- Introduction to risk assessment methodologies.
- Group exercises for practical application in maintenance scenarios.

Introduction to Risk Assessment Methodologies: Covering different methodologies like FMEA (Failure Modes and Effects Analysis) and HAZOP (Hazard and Operability Study).

Video resource: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=whbfvjg-y24>

Example: A power plant using Failure Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) to identify potential risks in turbine operations and taking pre-emptive actions.

Hands-On Training with Risk Assessment Tools: Practical training sessions using specific tools and software.

Group Exercises: Applying these tools in simulated maintenance scenarios.

Session 4: Structural Assessment in Predictive Maintenance

Objective: Acquire skills in assessing the structural integrity of equipment and systems.

- Techniques for structural assessment in predictive maintenance.

Summary: Skills in assessing the structural integrity of equipment and systems.

Key Aspects: Techniques like NDT and SHM, and applying these in maintenance planning.

Challenges: Identifying structural issues that are not immediately apparent.
Benefits: Ensuring the structural health of equipment, preventing catastrophic failures.

Techniques for Structural Assessment: Discussing methods like non-destructive testing (NDT) and structural health monitoring (SHM).

Video resource: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gYJoYUOjw2Q>

Example: A bridge maintenance team employing Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) techniques to detect early signs of stress corrosion cracking in the bridge cables.

Case Studies: Examples of structural assessments in various industries.

Application in Maintenance Planning: Integrating structural assessment findings into maintenance planning.

References: Shull (2002), Beale & Read (2013), Rausand (2011).

Session 5: Mitigation Strategies for Potential Failures

Objective: Develop strategies to address and mitigate potential failures.

- Identification of common failure scenarios.

Summary: Developing strategies to mitigate and address potential failures.

Key Aspects: Identifying common failure modes and formulating effective strategies.

Challenges: Designing strategies that are effective across various scenarios.

Benefits: Reduced downtime and improved reliability of equipment.

Identification of Common Failure Scenarios: Analysis of typical failure modes in different types of equipment.

Formulation of Mitigation Strategies: Creating effective strategies to address identified risks.

Video resource: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t0qbZGMuZgY>

Example: A data centre developing mitigation strategies, like installing backup generators, to address potential failures identified in its power supply system.

Simulation Exercises: Practical application of these strategies in simulated environments.

References: Mobley (2002), Nyman & Levitt (2001), Mitchell (2013).

Session 6: Forecasting Tools for Predictive Analysis

Objective: Explore tools and techniques for predicting maintenance needs.

Summary: Exploring tools for predictive maintenance needs.

Key Aspects: Introduction to predictive analytics and machine learning for maintenance forecasting.

Challenges: Integrating and interpreting data from diverse sources.

Benefits: Improved maintenance scheduling and resource allocation.

Introduction to Forecasting Tools: Covering tools like predictive analytics and machine learning algorithms.

Practical Demonstrations: Hands-on experience with forecasting software.

Video resource: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LrGOTOdou2s>

Example: A manufacturing facility using machine learning algorithms to predict when critical machinery components are likely to fail and scheduling maintenance accordingly.

Collaborative Exercises: Using these tools in group settings to predict maintenance needs.

References: Siegel (2016), Bowerman et al., (2004), Hyndman & Athanasopoulos (2018).

Session 7: Efficient Recovery Planning

Objective: Learn to plan and execute efficient recovery strategies in the event of disruptions.

Strategies for Quick Recovery: Techniques for rapid response and recovery in maintenance operations.

Recovery Plan Development: Creating comprehensive plans for various disruption scenarios.

Video resource: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c2WRVclyFcg>

Example: A logistics company creating recovery plans for different scenarios, such as natural disasters or system hacks, to ensure quick resumption of operations.

References: Wallace & Webber (2017), Herbane (2010), Haddow et al., (2017).

Assessment:

Objective: Evaluate participants' understanding and application of resilience competences in Predictive Maintenance.

Example: Teams in a training program are given a scenario of a sudden breakdown in a water treatment plant and asked to develop a comprehensive resilience plan, addressing immediate repairs, communication strategies, and long-term improvements.

F. Future trends in resilience skills for predictive maintenance

1. Anticipating technological changes and skills requirements in the field of predictive maintenance

Predictive maintenance has emerged as a critical discipline for organizations seeking to optimize operational efficiency, reduce downtime, and enhance asset reliability. As technology continues to evolve, organizations must proactively anticipate future changes and adapt their skills requirements to stay competitive in this dynamic landscape. In this article, we explore key technological trends shaping predictive maintenance and the corresponding competencies needed to thrive, (Meddaoui et al., 2023; Sensemore, 2024; Stefanini et al., 2023).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML)

Role in Predictive Maintenance: AI and ML algorithms are revolutionizing predictive maintenance by automating processes, improving accuracy, and uncovering valuable insights. Here's how they contribute:

- **Anomaly Detection:** AI models analyse historical data to identify abnormal patterns or deviations from expected behaviour. Early anomaly detection allows organizations to address potential failures before they escalate.
- **Predictive Modeling:** ML algorithms predict equipment failures based on historical data, sensor readings, and other relevant factors. By forecasting maintenance needs, organizations can schedule interventions proactively.
- **Prescriptive Analytics:** AI provides actionable recommendations for maintenance tasks. For example, it can suggest optimal maintenance schedules or recommend specific actions based on real-time conditions.

Skills Requirements: To harness the power of AI and ML in predictive maintenance, professionals need the following competencies:

- **Data Science:** Proficiency in data preprocessing, feature engineering, and model selection.
- **Algorithm Development:** Understanding of regression, classification, and time-series analysis.
- **Domain Knowledge:** Bridging AI techniques with domain-specific insights (e.g., understanding machinery behaviour).

Internet of Things (IoT)

Connecting Assets and Systems: IoT devices and sensors play a pivotal role in predictive maintenance. They enable real-time monitoring, data collection, and remote diagnostics. Consider the following:

- **Sensor Networks:** Organizations deploy sensors across critical assets (e.g., turbines, pumps, conveyor belts). These sensors continuously collect data on temperature, vibration, pressure, and other relevant parameters.
- **Edge Computing:** IoT devices process data at the edge (near the source), reducing latency and enabling real-time decision-making. Edge analytics can identify anomalies and trigger alerts.

Skills Requirements: Professionals working with IoT-driven predictive maintenance should possess:

- **Sensor Integration:** Knowledge of sensor types, calibration, and installation.
- **Data Handling:** Ability to manage large volumes of sensor data efficiently.
- **Security Awareness:** Understanding of IoT security protocols to prevent cyber threats.

Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR)

Enhancing Training and Support: AR and VR technologies transform how maintenance experts learn, troubleshoot, and perform tasks:

- **AR for Guided Maintenance:** Technicians wear AR glasses that overlay digital information (such as repair instructions or schematics) onto the physical equipment. This improves efficiency and reduces errors.
- **VR Simulations:** VR environments allow technicians to practice complex maintenance procedures virtually. They can simulate scenarios without risking damage to actual equipment.

Skills Requirements: Professionals leveraging AR and VR should be adept at:

- **AR Development:** Creating interactive overlays and integrating them with real-world objects.
- **VR Simulation Design:** Building realistic training scenarios and ensuring user immersion.

Autonomous Systems

Complex Maintenance Tasks: Autonomous drones, robots, and vehicles are increasingly used for maintenance tasks:

- **Inspections:** Drones equipped with cameras and sensors can inspect large structures (e.g., wind turbines, pipelines) efficiently.

- Repairs: Robots can perform routine repairs, reducing the need for human intervention in hazardous environments.

Skills Requirements: Professionals working with autonomous systems require:

- Robotics Knowledge: Understanding kinematics, control algorithms, and safety protocols.
- Remote Monitoring Skills: Ability to oversee autonomous operations from a control centre.
- Adaptability: As autonomous technologies evolve, professionals must stay updated.

Sustainability Considerations

Predictive maintenance intersects with sustainability efforts:

- Energy Efficiency: Organizations must consider the environmental impact of maintenance activities. Using energy-efficient practices aligns with sustainability goals.
- Lifecycle Assessment: Professionals should evaluate the entire lifecycle of equipment, from manufacturing to disposal, considering environmental implications.

Anticipating technological shifts and fostering relevant competencies will empower organizations to navigate the ever-changing landscape of predictive maintenance successfully. By staying informed, investing in training, and fostering a culture of adaptability, professionals can ensure operational excellence while contributing to a sustainable future.

2. Strategies to remain competitive and meet future needs

In a world of continuous change, predictive maintenance plays a crucial role in maintaining the efficiency and reliability of equipment and infrastructure. To remain competitive and meet future needs in the field of predictive maintenance, organizations can adopt several strategic approaches. Predictive maintenance is a cornerstone of operational excellence, and staying ahead requires a proactive approach guided by a few key strategies: (Forbes, 2021; Monash Business School, 2017)

Investment in Continuous Learning and Development

- *Upskilling Workforce:* Organizations should invest in continuous training and development for their predictive maintenance experts. This ensures that they stay abreast of technological advancements and evolving skill requirements.

- *Data Literacy:* Training programs should focus on data literacy, statistical analysis, and understanding AI-driven insights.
- *Cross-Functional Collaboration:* Encourage collaboration between maintenance teams, data scientists, and domain experts to foster a holistic understanding of predictive maintenance.

Collaboration with Educational and Research Institutions

- *Partnerships:* Collaborate with universities, research centres, and industry associations. These partnerships provide access to cutting-edge knowledge, research, and emerging technologies.
- *Joint Projects:* Engage in joint research projects to explore innovative solutions and stay informed about the latest trends.

Fostering a Culture of Innovation and Adaptability

- *Innovation Hubs:* Create dedicated spaces or teams focused on exploring new technologies and experimenting with predictive maintenance solutions.
- *Agile Mindset:* Encourage employees to embrace change, adapt quickly, and learn from failures.
- *Hackathons and Ideation Sessions:* Regularly organize events where teams brainstorm and prototype novel approaches to predictive maintenance challenges.

Monitoring Industry Trends and Best Practices

- *Industry Reports and Conferences:* Stay informed about the latest trends, case studies, and best practices in predictive maintenance.
- *Benchmarking:* Compare your organization's practices with industry leaders. Identify gaps and areas for improvement.

Adapting Training Programs and Certifications

- *Continuous Curriculum Updates:* Revise training programs to reflect technological changes. Include modules on AI, ML, IoT, and digital twin frameworks.
- *Certifications:* Encourage employees to pursue relevant certifications (e.g., Certified Maintenance and Reliability Professional) to validate their expertise.

Leveraging Data-Driven Insights

- *Advanced Analytics:* Invest in tools that provide real-time insights from sensor data, historical records, and machine learning models.

- *Predictive Models:* Develop and refine predictive models for specific equipment types. Use them to optimize maintenance schedules and reduce downtime.

Ethical Considerations and Transparency

- *Data Privacy and Security:* Ensure compliance with data privacy regulations (e.g., GDPR) and protect sensitive information.
- *Transparency:* Be transparent with stakeholders about how predictive maintenance decisions are made using AI algorithms.

Sustainability Integration

- *Green Technologies:* Consider environmental impact when implementing predictive maintenance. Choose for energy-efficient solutions.
- *Circular Economy:* Explore ways to extend the lifecycle of equipment through refurbishment, reuse, and recycling.

By embracing these strategies, organizations can not only remain competitive but also position themselves as pioneers in predictive maintenance. The ability to adapt, learn, and innovate will be crucial in meeting future needs and achieving operational excellence.

The organizations that proactively invest in training, foster collaborations, embrace continuous learning, monitor trends, and adapt their training programs will be well-prepared to meet the challenges of predictive maintenance in the future.

G. Conclusion

This comprehensive module serves as a pivotal initiative aimed at empowering Predictive Maintenance experts with a robust array of competences and expertise vital for enhancing resilience within their operational domains. Engaging in this program provides professionals in this field with not just theoretical knowledge but also practical, hands-on skills that are indispensable for navigating the ever-evolving landscape of maintenance operations. The ultimate objective is to equip these experts with a profound understanding of cutting-edge methodologies, technological advancements, and adaptive strategies that form the bedrock of resilience in their field.

Safety takes centre stage within this module, emphasizing its paramount importance. The module underscores the significance of cultivating a culture of vigilance and precision, with a dual focus on safeguarding the well-being of maintenance personnel and preserving the integrity and reliability of the entire maintenance process. By adopting this holistic approach, the module aims to instil a mindset oriented towards continuous improvement, innovation, and strategic resilience. This approach ensures not only the effectiveness but also the long-term sustainability of maintenance endeavours, even in the face of evolving challenges and complexities.

The overarching objective of this module is to equip these experts with a profound understanding of cutting-edge methodologies, technological advancements, and adaptive strategies that serve as the cornerstones of resilience in their specialized domain. It is not merely about imparting knowledge; it's about cultivating a mindset geared towards proactive problem-solving and continuous improvement. Resilience, in the context of maintenance, extends beyond just the ability to bounce back from setbacks - it encompasses the capacity to anticipate challenges, mitigate risks, and ensure the uninterrupted functionality of critical industrial and transport equipment.

One of the central tenets of this module is safety - a theme that runs through every aspect of the curriculum. Safety is paramount in maintenance operations, and this module underscores its significance. It emphasizes the need to foster a culture of vigilance and precision, where every action and decision is guided by the utmost concern for the well-being of maintenance personnel and the unwavering commitment to safeguarding the integrity and reliability of the entire maintenance process.

Through a structured and dynamic learning environment, this module seeks to go beyond traditional approaches. It encourages professionals to embrace innovation and embrace the latest technological advancements. It challenges them to think strategically and adapt proactively to evolving challenges and complexities in maintenance operations. By doing so, it ensures not only the efficacy but the sustainability of maintenance endeavours.

Through a blend of theoretical insights and practical know-how, this module empowers Predictive Maintenance experts to be at the forefront of resilience, ready to tackle whatever challenges come their way. It equips them with the tools and mindset needed to not only adapt to change but to thrive in it, making a lasting impact on the reliability and efficiency of maintenance operations.

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PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education and training

Funded by
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PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

BOOKLET

Module WN5: Innovation and Entrepreneurship Competences for PM

**Co-funded by
the European Union**

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A. Introduction

Predictive maintenance, the sole focus of the PreMETS project, is a proactive maintenance approach that leverages data analysis tools and techniques to identify potential faults in equipment, assets, and processes, enabling businesses to address these issues before they escalate into failures (Mobley, 2001; Sabado, 2023). This approach is crucial for ensuring the operational integrity and efficiency of various industries, as well as the sustainability of businesses (Mobley, 2001). In the context of predictive maintenance, the latest trends and innovations, such as artificial intelligence, the Internet of Things, and digital twins, play a significant role in impacting businesses (StartUs Insights, 2022). These technological advancements have revolutionized the way maintenance is predicted and managed, enabling the early detection of potential failures and the optimization of maintenance schedules. Moreover, the application of predictive maintenance is not limited to specific industries, as it is essential for maximizing profits, minimizing downtime, and ensuring asset integrity across various sectors (Relayr, 2023).

In the realm of predictive maintenance, the role of innovation and entrepreneurship competences is paramount (Kyndt & Baert, 2015). The integration of these competences is essential for driving the successful implementation of predictive maintenance strategies. According to Kruger and Steyn (2020), entrepreneurial competencies are crucial for utilizing technologies of Industry 4.0, such as predictive maintenance and improved asset utilization. This underscores the need for a deep understanding of entrepreneurial skills and knowledge in the context of technological advancements.

Furthermore, the increasing availability of data and technological advances, such as AI and machine learning, are driving changes in predictive maintenance (Artesis, 2022; Wen et al., 2022). These changes highlight the need for a comprehensive understanding of digital literacy and data analytics in implementing effective predictive maintenance strategies. The use of AI in predictive maintenance, for instance, allows for the analysis of large amounts of data in real-time, making it possible to identify patterns and trends that can be used to predict equipment failures (Deloitte, n.d.). According to Joshi (2023), the technological proficiency & the importance of entrepreneurial competences, such as opportunity recognition, risk management, and resource mobilization, cannot be overstated. The study of Kruger and Steyn sets an example that emphasizes the optimization of activities with AR and data analytics, highlighting the need for entrepreneurial competences in leveraging these technologies (Kruger & Steyn, 2020). This further underscores the critical role of entrepreneurial thinking and skills in successfully integrating predictive maintenance into business models.

The integration of innovation and entrepreneurship competences is essential for driving the successful implementation of predictive maintenance strategies. This

guide aims to provide a detailed overview of predictive maintenance, the latest technological trends, and the essential competencies for innovation and entrepreneurship in the context of predictive maintenance, catering to a diverse audience, including maintenance professionals, engineers, entrepreneurs, business leaders, and academia.

Definition and Historical Context of Predictive Maintenance

Predictive Maintenance (PM) is defined as a maintenance strategy that involves predicting failures and performing maintenance at a precise time to prevent the likelihood of failure. This approach is data-driven, utilizing data collected over time to monitor the state of equipment and identify patterns that can help predict and prevent failures (Kane et al., 2022). These practices are used to identify potential faults in equipment, assets, and processes, enabling businesses to address these issues before they escalate into failures (IBM, n.d.) which is crucial for ensuring the operational integrity and efficiency of various industries, as well as the sustainability of businesses.

Historically, the concept of PM emerged from the need to improve upon traditional maintenance practices, which often led to unexpected downtime due to unplanned equipment failures. The history of predictive maintenance practices can be traced back to the 1940s, when C.H. Waddington developed a process for improving maintenance planning for the British (IndustrialMatrix, 2023). The evolution of PM is closely linked with the advent of Industry 4.0 and the development of smart systems. These technological advancements have enabled more sophisticated predictive maintenance strategies, reducing downtime costs and increasing equipment availability (Kane et al., 2022). It has evolved significantly, with the increasing availability of data and technological advances, such as AI and machine learning (Achouch et al., 2022). The use of AI in predictive maintenance allows for the analysis of large amounts of data in real-time, making it possible to identify patterns and trends that can be used to predict equipment failures (Bousdekis et al., 2019). Predictive maintenance is one of three leading maintenance strategies used by businesses, the others being reactive maintenance and preventive maintenance. Furthermore, according to IBM, It uses time series historical and failure data to predict the future potential health of equipment and anticipate problems in advance. The historical development of PdM also includes the transition from basic condition monitoring systems, which required expert knowledge and were costly to reconfigure, to more automated and sophisticated systems. These advanced systems use techniques like dictionary learning for condition monitoring, automating the process and making it more efficient.

In Europe, the application of PM has been particularly notable in various industries, including manufacturing and healthcare. For instance, a study on Heating,

Ventilation, and Air Conditioning (HVAC) systems in an Italian hospital demonstrated the effectiveness of predictive maintenance in forecasting faults and ensuring equipment availability (Satta et al., 2017). Along with the benefits offered by PM alone, the integration of innovation and entrepreneurship competences is essential for driving the successful implementation of predictive maintenance strategies, as it requires a deep understanding of entrepreneurial skills and knowledge in the context of technological advancements. This evolution reflects the field's response to the challenges of maintaining increasingly complex and critical systems in various industries.

Traditional practices vs Predictive practices

Predictive maintenance and traditional maintenance approaches, such as preventive and reactive maintenance, differ in their approach to maintenance planning and execution:

- **Preventive maintenance** is a time-based approach that involves performing maintenance tasks at predetermined intervals, regardless of the equipment's actual condition (PRUFTECHNIK, 2023).
- **Reactive maintenance**, on the other hand, is a "run-to-failure" approach that involves repairing equipment only after it has broken down (Uptime AI, 2022).
- **Predictive maintenance**, in contrast, is a proactive approach that leverages data analysis tools and techniques to identify potential faults in equipment, assets, and processes, enabling businesses to address these issues before they escalate into failures (Beneke, 2023). Predictive maintenance utilizes condition-monitoring equipment to assess the performance of assets through a more real-time, data-driven approach, therefore, identifying the potential for issues before they occur. One of the main differences between predictive maintenance and traditional maintenance approaches is the use of data and technology. Predictive maintenance relies on real-time data to identify potential issues, while traditional maintenance approaches rely on predetermined schedules or reactive measures (Beneke, 2023). Predictive maintenance also utilizes advanced diagnostic techniques and artificial intelligence (AI) to analyze data and predict equipment failures, enabling businesses to address these issues before they escalate into failures.

Traditional maintenance approaches may result in unnecessary maintenance activities and associated costs, as they do not consider the real-time condition of the equipment (Beneke, 2023). Another key difference between predictive maintenance and traditional maintenance approaches is the potential for cost savings. Predictive maintenance can help businesses save costs by reducing downtime, minimizing the frequency of maintenance, and avoiding the need for expensive repairs or replacements that often result from reactive maintenance. Predictive maintenance can also extend the life of equipment by detecting and

addressing potential issues promptly, preventing the wear and tear that can lead to major damages. In contrast, traditional maintenance approaches may result in higher costs due to unnecessary maintenance activities, equipment downtime, and reactive repairs (PRUFTECHNIK, 2023). Predictive maintenance is becoming increasingly popular, and businesses are transitioning to it to maximize profits and asset integrity while minimizing downtime and expensive reactive maintenance (Uptime AI, 2022).

Technological advancements, Industry 4.0 and Relevance of Predictive Maintenance

Technological advancements, particularly in the Industry 4.0 era, have significantly affected predictive maintenance, making it more important and beneficial for companies. The increasing adoption of smart technologies, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), cyber-physical systems, and advanced analytics, has enabled businesses to predict equipment failures and address issues before they escalate into problems (Achouch et al., 2022). This has led to several advantages and benefits, including:

1. **Cost savings:** It can help companies reduce maintenance costs by up to 25% and increase overall equipment effectiveness by 25-30% (HiTech Nectar, 2023). By identifying potential issues early on, businesses can address problems before they cause more serious damage, thus improving asset reliability and lifespan.
2. **Improved efficiency:** It allows organizations to plan and schedule maintenance activities more effectively, leading to increased productivity and reduced downtime. This can result in a more efficient use of resources and better overall performance.
3. **Prolonged equipment life:** By identifying and addressing potential issues early on, predictive maintenance can help extend the life of equipment, reducing the need for expensive replacements and minimizing waste (HiTech Nectar, 2023).
4. **Increased safety and reliability:** Furthermore, it can help companies improve safety and reliability by identifying potential equipment failures and addressing them before they occur (Achouch et al., 2022). This can lead to a safer and more stable operating environment, which is essential for businesses in various industries.
5. **Real-time monitoring and insights:** As it leverages advanced data analysis techniques and real-time monitoring to provide valuable insights into equipment performance and potential issues (HiTech Nectar, 2023). This allows businesses to make informed decisions and optimize their maintenance strategies for maximum efficiency and cost savings.

By harnessing advanced technologies and data analysis techniques, businesses can improve asset performance, reduce downtime, and achieve greater success in managing their maintenance programs (Bach et al., 2023).

The improvement in asset performance and reduced downtime can be achieved through various mechanisms. By monitoring equipment in real-time and identifying potential issues early on, organizations can address problems before they cause more serious damage, thus improving asset reliability and lifespan. By leveraging the power of data and analytics, organizations can ensure that their equipment is operating at peak performance and avoid costly downtime (Bruhati, 2023).

Some challenges...

Some of the challenges in adopting predictive maintenance include:

1. **Data quality and reliability:** According to Wickern (2019) predictive maintenance relies on large amounts of data, which need to be accurate and reliable. Noisy or erroneous data from harsh industrial scenarios can make it difficult to identify potential issues and develop effective maintenance strategies (Nunes et al., 2023).
2. **Lack of skilled workforce & cooperation needs:** Implementing predictive maintenance solutions requires skilled personnel who can analyze and interpret data. However, there is currently a shortage of qualified personnel with the necessary skills and expertise, making it difficult for companies to implement and maintain these solutions (Nunes et al., 2023).
3. **Integration with legacy systems:** Many companies have legacy systems incompatible with modern predictive maintenance solutions. Integrating these systems can be challenging and require significant investment, which can hinder adoption.
4. **High implementation costs:** Implementing predictive maintenance solutions can be expensive, especially for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) with limited budgets. The cost of hardware, software, and skilled personnel can be a significant barrier to adoption, especially for companies just starting out.
5. **Data security and privacy concerns:** As predictive maintenance solutions rely on large amounts of data, there are concerns around data security and privacy. Companies need to ensure that the data they collect and store is secure and compliant with relevant regulations.
6. **Lack of awareness:** Many companies are unaware of the benefits of predictive maintenance or do not fully understand their potential. This lack of awareness can be a barrier to adoption, as companies may need to realize the value that these solutions can provide.

Indeed, predictive maintenance is a powerful tool that can help organizations improve asset performance, reduce downtime, and achieve greater success by proactively managing their maintenance programs (Bruhati, 2023). Although the benefits it offers are of high importance and the results seem promising, the

requirements for excellent up-skilled workforce, high implementation cost and awareness of the needs of the given company, are some of the considerations that hold companies away from its implementation.

B. Fundamentals of Innovation

In predictive maintenance, innovation is key to enhancing efficiency and effectiveness. Various types of innovations have been developed, each playing a significant role in the field.

Artificial intelligence and Predictive Maintenance

One major innovation type involves the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT). This combination has led to the development of intelligent maintenance frameworks. These frameworks use machine learning algorithms, including probabilistic reliability modelling with deep learning, and are supported by real-time data collection through wireless smart sensors (Zheng et al., 2020). This approach significantly improves the predictability and adaptability of predictive maintenance systems.

AI technologies, an example of that could be machine learning algorithms, play a crucial role in PM's implementation. These algorithms analyze large amounts of data collected by IIoT devices to predict equipment failures. The use of probabilistic reliability modelling with deep learning allows for more accurate predictions and efficient maintenance planning (Zheng et al., 2020). This approach not only enhances the reliability of equipment but also optimizes maintenance schedules, reducing downtime and costs.

The IIoT contributes to predictive maintenance by providing a network of smart sensors and devices that continuously monitor the condition of industrial equipment. These sensors collect real-time data on various parameters, such as temperature, vibration, and noise. This data is then processed and analyzed using AI algorithms to detect anomalies and predict potential failures (Chevtchenko et al., 2023).

Moreover, the integration of AI and IIoT facilitates the development of intelligent maintenance systems. These systems are capable of continuously integrating and deploying machine learning models, thereby adapting to changing conditions and improving decision-making processes in the field (Zheng et al., 2020).

The trend of using machine learning to bridge AI and IoT in predictive maintenance is evident across various industries. For instance, in the manufacturing sector, predictive maintenance applications using AI and IoT have

led to significant productivity increases and reductions in machine downtime (Samatas et al., 2021).

The integration of AI and IIoT in predictive maintenance represents a paradigm shift in maintenance strategies. This integration enables more accurate predictions, efficient maintenance planning, and real-time monitoring, significantly enhancing the reliability and performance of industrial equipment. Advances in technology and processes.

An innovative approach to predictive maintenance involves the use of advanced circuit design techniques, integrated with artificial intelligence (AI) solutions, to improve the predictability and adaptability of each component for PM (Molęda et al., 2023). This approach leverages the benefits of AI and advanced circuit design to enhance equipment performance and reduce downtime. One example of that would be that, according to Dosluoglu & MacDonald (2022), their study presents a new circuit design approach based on circuit-level AI solutions, integrated within control and calibration functional blocks during circuit design. This approach aims to encourage the development of new Electronic Design Automation (EDA) tools, such as automatic digital design tools, which can help identify circuit parameters that adequately define the operating conditions. The integration of a supplementary AI block within the control loop is also considered, as system integration topics.

The benefits of this innovative approach to PM include:

1. **Improved equipment performance**
2. **Reduced downtime**
3. **Cost savings**
4. **Increased safety and reliability**
5. **Real-time monitoring and insights**

Furthermore, according to Chen et al. (2023), the development of digital twin technology has revolutionized predictive maintenance by enabling accurate equipment status recognition and proactive fault prediction. This shift from reactive to proactive maintenance scheduling enhances enterprise reliability, minimizes downtime, and improves competitiveness. However, the role of machine learning in digital twin-based predictive maintenance remains underexplored.

Predictive Maintenance and Machine Learning

Machine learning (ML) has become a cornerstone in the field of predictive maintenance, revolutionizing how industries approach equipment maintenance and failure prevention.

There is a plethora of usages of ML in PM but the most common one is anomaly detection. Anomaly detection algorithms focus on identifying failures that must be prevented. These algorithms deal with time-series data and are designed to recognize patterns indicative of impending equipment failure. The challenge lies in the lack of annotated anomalous data, which has led to the development of specialized evaluation frameworks for temporal unsupervised anomaly detection algorithms (Carrasco et al., 2021). Moreover, this approach helps in reducing unexpected downtime and increasing equipment availability (Kane et al., 2022).

Different ML formulations are used to predict incoming failures and schedule maintenance based on sensor information in industrial machines. These formulations range from simple threshold-based techniques to sophisticated supervised learning methods. For instance, Support Vector Machines (SVM) and their variations have been applied in real-world case studies, demonstrating that while simple models can be effective, more complex approaches enhance predictions with well-chosen parameters (Hamaide et al., 2022).

In addition, ML models such as Artificial Neural Networks, Support Vector Machines, and Random Forests are prevalent in predictive maintenance applications, especially when combined with IoT technologies. These models analyze data from various sensors, like temperature and vibration sensors, to predict equipment failures (Samatas et al., 2021).

ML techniques have been applied in specific sectors like semiconductor lasers for optical communication systems. Here, ML-based frameworks are used for real-time health monitoring and prognosis, enhancing the reliability of these critical components.

Following the process advancements we have witnessed, the evolution of PM systems has led to the development of various architectures, like the Open System Architecture for Condition Based Monitoring (OSA-CBM), cloud-enhanced PdM systems, and PdM 4.0. These architectures aim to minimize costs, maximize availability/reliability, and optimize multiple objectives (Ran et al., 2019).

C. Entrepreneurial Mindset in Predictive Maintenance

What is the entrepreneurial mindset?

An entrepreneurial mindset refers to a specific way of thinking that focuses on recognizing opportunities, taking initiative, and being innovative. This aspect is usually reserved for smaller initiatives where the risk/reward ratio is more evenly distributed, but it could provide significant benefits to an individual that their success depends on several non-human parameters.

One of the aspects of entrepreneurial thinking and more so related to predictive maintenance is looking at challenges as opportunities for improvement or innovation. In predictive maintenance, this could mean finding new ways to use data and technology to predict equipment failures more accurately or developing more efficient maintenance strategies.

For example, in the context of Industry 4.0, an entrepreneurial mindset might involve integrating advanced technologies like AI and IoT into maintenance practices. This approach not only improves efficiency but also opens up new opportunities for market leadership and differentiation (Dosluoglu & MacDonald, 2022; Zheng et al., 2020).

An entrepreneurial mindset also means being proactive about addressing potential issues before they become major problems. This proactive approach is preferred in an ever-changing environment that requires someone to be ahead of the competition and who wants to minimize losses to, until previously, hard-to-predict parameters.

What is adaptive thinking?

Although adaptive thinking might be beneficial to the everyday life of an individual, it still remains an important asset to PM. In short, it is considered the ability to adjust your thoughts and actions in response to changing situations and new information. Furthermore, adaptive thinking promotes the need to be flexible and open-minded, ready to change course when necessary. This kind of thinking is crucial in today's fast-paced world where new challenges and opportunities arise constantly.

Some key aspects of adaptive thinking include:

1. **Effective planning:** Developing a plan of action and preparing for potential challenges.
2. **Careful monitoring of performance:** Regularly evaluating one's progress and adjusting strategies as needed.
3. **Impulse control:** The ability to delay gratification and resist the urge to act impulsively.
4. **Adaptive thinking in this context means going beyond just learning & doing content;** it's about helping entrepreneurs and businesses to develop the ability to use their knowledge in different, often unpredictable situations.

Moreover, adaptive thinking is not limited to technical fields. It's also about how individuals use their resources to create new opportunities, as seen in entrepreneurial behaviour, mentioned in the previous section. This way of doing thing includes using adaptive thinking to navigate different stages of a task, such as in object navigation, where one must decide whether to search for or navigate to a target.

Combining both to implement Predictive Maintenance procedures

An entrepreneurial mindset and adaptive thinking can be beneficial in implementing predictive maintenance procedures effectively. An entrepreneurial mindset encourages considering a broader perspective, such as exploring how to leverage the wealth of information generated by the Internet of Things (IoT) for new opportunities, including devising predictive maintenance algorithms to reduce downtime in manufacturing, creating smart cities, or developing personalized healthcare solutions (Moore, 2023). Adaptive thinking is also essential in predictive maintenance, as it requires a whole new level of domain expertise to understand the latest trends and key data analytics.

According to Kumudun (2023), implementing predictive maintenance requires a change in mindset from a reactive maintenance approach to a proactive one. Although the study focuses in the building sector, their main takeaways apply to several sectors such as being willing to adopt advanced technologies such as sensors, data analytics, and machine learning algorithms and invest in the necessary training for their teams.

Based on research and real-life world examples that will be presented later on, an entrepreneurial mindset and adaptive thinking can be beneficial in implementing predictive maintenance procedures effectively. The combination of both following PM procedures provides organizations with many strategic advantages, including enhanced operational efficiency, cost savings, improved safety, sustainable production, better inventory management, and increased equipment uptime. However, the struggle for most companies is that they have adopted a certain way of doing things and it is hard to change the mindset from a reactive maintenance approach to a proactive one, especially if that means more resources and human staff for a positive outcome that requires time to Return on Investment. For this reason, starting small by implementing a pilot predictive maintenance program for a few systems or equipment to test its effectiveness and demonstrate its value is also recommended Kumudun (2023).

D. Marketing and Branding Strategies

Marketing and branding are crucial for entrepreneurs, especially in the fields of maintenance and operations.

Marketing Fundamentals

1. **Holistic Marketing Approach:** Marketing should be viewed as a comprehensive framework, encompassing every aspect of the business.
2. **Market Ownership Mindset:** Entrepreneurs should focus not just on selling products or services but on owning their market segment. This involves understanding and shaping the market to fit their unique offerings.
3. **Customer Relationship Strategy:** Central to marketing in maintenance and operations is building and maintaining strong customer relationships. This involves understanding customer emotions, ideas, and gaining their support.
4. **Bootstrap Marketing for Start-ups:** Start-ups in particular should follow principles like getting operational fast, focusing on high-value products, and managing growth and cash flow carefully. This approach helps in creating a lean and efficient marketing strategy.
5. **Operational and Marketing Capabilities:** Both operational and marketing capabilities are crucial for firm performance. Operational capability becomes particularly important during economic downturns (Ahmed et al., 2014).
6. **Innovation-Oriented Marketing:** Entrepreneurial marketing differs from traditional marketing by being more innovation-oriented, preferring interactive methods, and targeting markets through "bottom-up" self-selection (Stokes, 2000).
7. **Service Management Principles:** For businesses involved in service maintenance, understanding and applying principles like continuity in service management and quality specification in service processes and objects is key (Trienekens et al., 2004).
8. **Synergy between Marketing and Operations:** Achieving synergy between marketing and operational objectives in service businesses requires understanding key operational issues and how they impact marketing strategies (Lovelock, 1992).

Branding Fundamentals

1. **Brand Positioning and Integration:** Effective branding requires clear positioning in the market and integration of the brand into every aspect of the business. This approach ensures consistency in message and customer experience (Keller & Lehmann, 2006).

2. **Internal Branding and Corporate Culture:** The role of internal branding is paramount, focusing on employees as key players in building and maintaining the brand.
3. **B2B Branding:** In a B2B context, branding assists in decision-making processes and communication, building relationships, and creating brand equity. This shows the importance of branding not just in B2C but also in B2B markets (Leek & Christodoulides, 2011).
4. **Entrepreneur's Role in Branding:** During the early phases of start-ups, the entrepreneur plays a critical role in developing the corporate identity, which includes aspects like corporate culture, behaviour, design, and communication.
5. **Personal Branding of Entrepreneurs:** An entrepreneur's personal brand, encompassing traits and values, significantly impacts the overall brand of the SME. The entrepreneur's influence is a crucial factor in shaping the company's brand identity.
6. **Employer Brand Management:** Aligning employees' brand experience with the desired customer brand experience is crucial. This alignment ensures consistency in the brand experience delivered to customers.
7. **Corporate Brand as a Competitive Advantage:** A strong corporate brand can be a significant resource for a sustainable competitive advantage, especially if it is rare, durable, and difficult to imitate or substitute.
8. **Dynamic Corporate Brand Management:** Corporate brand management is a dynamic process that requires continuous adjustments and an integrated approach across the organization.

Essentials of Marketing in Predictive Maintenance

1. **Targeting Early Adopters:** Sellers of predictive maintenance solutions should focus on early adopters of innovation. These are customers who are receptive to new technologies and can act as trendsetters in their respective industries (Ray, 2021).
2. **Highlighting Cost Reduction:** It's crucial to emphasize how predictive maintenance can reduce the total cost of ownership. This involves demonstrating how these solutions save costs over time by preventing expensive breakdowns and enhancing equipment longevity.
3. **Leveraging IoT and Data Science:** The integration of IoT and data science capabilities in predictive maintenance is a key selling point of its own, for the reasons mentioned in the previous sections. In short, it provides confidence to the customers that there is an extra safety net if something goes wrong.
4. **Improving Customer Satisfaction:** Implementing predictive maintenance strategies can significantly improve productivity and customer satisfaction, giving companies a competitive edge (Carnero & Cárcel-Carrasco, 2021).

Branding Fundamentals in Predictive Maintenance

1. **Building a Strong Brand Image:** Companies should create a brand image that resonates with reliability, innovation, and efficiency. This helps in positioning the company as a leader in the predictive maintenance sector.
2. **Emphasizing Technological Expertise:** Branding efforts should focus on presenting and promoting the technological advancements done in the company as a way to HOW their practices and procedures differ from the competition. This positions the company as a tech-savvy and forward-thinking solution provider (Naskos et al., 2019).
3. **Communicating Long-Term Benefits:** Brand messaging should clearly communicate the long-term benefits of predictive maintenance, such as cost savings, increased equipment uptime, and overall efficiency improvements.
4. **Fostering Trust and Reliability:** Establishing a brand associated with trust and reliability is crucial, especially in a field where the stakes of equipment failure are high.

Campaign Creation Guide for Entrepreneurs and Professionals in Predictive Maintenance

1. Define Your Objectives:

- a. **Set Specific Goals:** Clearly define what you want to achieve, such as increasing service subscriptions or growing your email/customer list by specific percentages or numbers within a defined timeframe.
- b. **Align with Business Goals:** Ensure your marketing objectives support your overall business strategy, whether it's entering new markets or strengthening your position in existing ones.
- c. **Adopt SMART Goals:** Make objectives Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, and Time-bound to ensure clarity and focus.
- d. **Budget and Resource Realism:** Set realistic goals considering your available budget and resources. Avoid over-ambitious targets that are unattainable with your current capabilities.
- e. **Competitor and Customer Insight:** Benchmark against competitors and incorporate customer feedback to set objectives that address market gaps and customer needs effectively.

2. Understand Your Audience

- a. **Conduct Target Market Analysis:** Delve into who your potential customers are. This involves understanding the industries that most need predictive maintenance, such as manufacturing, transportation, or healthcare. Assess their specific needs, challenges, and how your service can address these issues.
- b. **Develop Customer Personas:** Create detailed profiles of your ideal customers. Include demographic information, job roles (like facility

managers or operations directors), pain points (such as frequent equipment downtime), and motivations for using predictive maintenance services.

- c. **Gather Customer Insights:** Utilize surveys, interviews, and feedback from current clients to gain deeper insights into customer preferences and behaviours. Understand what drives their decisions, their preferred communication channels, and any objections they might have towards adopting predictive maintenance.
- d. **Analyze Competitor Customers:** Look at your competitors' customer base to identify any underserved market segments. Understanding why customers choose your competitors can provide valuable insights into how to position your own services.
- e. **Stay Informed on Industry Trends:** Keep abreast of trends and changes in the industries you serve. This can include technological advancements, regulatory changes, or evolving industry challenges, all of which can influence customer needs and preferences.

3. Craft Your Message:

- a. **Value Proposition:** Clearly articulate the benefits of your predictive maintenance services.
- b. **Key Messaging:** Develop compelling messages that resonate with your target audience. Ensure clarity and consistency across all communications.

4. Choose the Right Channels:

- a. **Digital Marketing:** Utilize SEO, content marketing, social media, and email marketing to reach your audience online.
- b. **Traditional Marketing:** Depending on your audience, traditional methods like print ads, direct mail, or industry events can be effective.

5. Develop Engaging Content:

- a. **Educational Content:** Create blog posts, whitepapers, case studies, and videos that educate your audience about the importance and benefits of predictive maintenance.
- b. **Testimonials and Case Studies:** Share success stories and testimonials from satisfied customers to build credibility and trust.

6. Plan Your Budget

- a. **Determine Overall Budget:** Start by establishing the total amount of money you can allocate to your marketing campaign. This should be based on your overall business financial plan and the expected return on investment (ROI) from the campaign.
- b. **Allocate Budget Across Channels:** Divide your total budget across various marketing channels based on their effectiveness and your

audience's preferences. Allocate more funds to channels that have historically provided a good ROI or are more likely to reach your target audience effectively, such as digital marketing for tech-savvy industries.

- c. **Consider Costs for Different Activities:** Break down your budget to cover different aspects of the campaign, including content creation, advertising, tools and software for analytics and CRM, and any outsourced services like graphic design or copywriting.
- d. **Plan for Flexibility:** Keep a portion of your budget flexible for unforeseen opportunities or adjustments. Market trends can change rapidly, and having some budgetary leeway allows you to adapt your campaign to these changes.
- e. **Monitor and Review Spending:** Regularly monitor your spending against the budget. This will help you understand which areas are over or under-spending and adjust accordingly. Post-campaign, review the budget utilization against the campaign outcomes to learn and improve future budget planning.

7. Execute Your Campaign:

- a. **Launch Plan:** Develop a timeline for rolling out different components of your campaign.
- b. **Channel Strategy:** Execute your campaign across chosen channels, ensuring consistent messaging and branding.

8. Monitor and Optimize

- a. **Implement Analytics Tools:** Utilize digital analytics tools to track the performance of your campaign across various channels. This includes monitoring website traffic, engagement metrics on social media, email open rates, and conversion rates from advertisements.
- b. **Set Key Performance Indicators (KPIs):** Identify specific KPIs that align with your campaign objectives. These could include lead generation numbers, customer acquisition costs, click-through rates, and overall return on investment (ROI). Regularly track these KPIs to gauge the campaign's success.
- c. **Gather Customer Feedback:** Collect feedback from customers and prospects through surveys, social media interactions, and direct communication. This feedback is invaluable for understanding the audience's response to your campaign and making necessary adjustments.
- d. **Conduct A/B Testing:** Implement A/B testing for various elements of your campaign. This helps in identifying the most effective strategies and optimizing your campaign for better performance.
- e. **Regular Review and Adjustment:** Schedule regular intervals to review the campaign performance data. Be prepared to make adjustments

based on this data and evolving market conditions. This could involve reallocating budget, tweaking messaging, or changing the focus of the campaign.

9. Follow-Up and Relationship Building:

- a. **Lead Nurturing:** Engage with leads through follow-up emails, newsletters, and personalized communication to show your customers how your PM implementations provide concrete results.
- b. **Customer Relationship Management (CRM):** Use CRM tools to manage customer interactions and build long-term relationships, depending on your business format.

10. Evaluate and Learn. Post-Campaign Analysis:

- a. **Assess Against Objectives:** After the campaign concludes, compare the results against your initial objectives. Evaluate how well the campaign met goals such as lead generation, sales increases, or enhanced brand awareness. This assessment should be quantitative, using the KPIs you set at the beginning.
- b. **Analyze Campaign Data:** Dive deep into the data collected during the campaign. This includes website analytics, engagement metrics, conversion rates, and customer feedback. Look for trends and patterns that indicate what worked well and what didn't.
- c. **Gather Team Feedback:** Involve your team in the evaluation process. Discuss the challenges faced, the effectiveness of different strategies, and any operational insights. This team should not only consist of managers and office workers but also your IT and maintenance staff. Team feedback can provide valuable perspectives that are not always apparent in quantitative data.
- d. **Learn from Successes and Failures:** Identify the most successful elements of the campaign and understand why they worked. Equally important is to analyze the aspects that didn't perform as expected and learn from these shortcomings. This dual approach helps in refining future marketing strategies.

Document Insights and Best Practices: Compile a report or a set of documents that capture key learnings, successful strategies, and areas for improvement. This documentation will serve as a valuable resource for planning and executing future campaigns. This material can be used for **9** as well.

E. Identifying Opportunities & Market Analysis

To summarize the already shared information it is evident that incorporating predictive maintenance (PM) into maintenance and operations presents a significant market opportunity for several reasons:

1. **Increasing Demand for Efficiency:** Predictive maintenance allows businesses to streamline their maintenance processes, decrease unnecessary downtime, and increase the lifespan of their machines, leading to improved operational efficiency.
2. **Cost Savings:** Predictive maintenance is highly cost-effective, saving roughly 8% to 12% over preventive maintenance and up to 40% over reactive maintenance, resulting in significant cost savings.
3. **Technological Advancements:** Predictive maintenance relies on advanced technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), predictive analytics, and artificial intelligence (AI), enabling businesses to make data-driven decisions and optimize their maintenance processes (IBM, n.d.).
4. **Growing Focus on Sustainability:** By preventing unexpected breakdowns and optimizing maintenance schedules, predictive maintenance contributes to sustainability by reducing resource wastage and minimizing the environmental impact of maintenance activities.
5. **Competitive Advantage:** Embracing predictive maintenance can provide businesses with a competitive edge by increasing product availability, reducing maintenance costs, and improving operational efficiency, which are essential factors for staying ahead in the market.
6. **Data-Driven Decision Making:** Predictive maintenance enables businesses to make informed decisions based on data collected from assets, leading to more accurate and efficient maintenance planning and resource allocation (IBM, n.d.).
7. **Regulatory Compliance:** With the increasing need to comply with industry regulations, predictive maintenance helps businesses ensure that their assets are well-maintained and meet the required standards, thus contributing to regulatory compliance (Hancock, 2023).
8. **Customer Satisfaction:** By minimizing unexpected downtime and ensuring the reliability of equipment, predictive maintenance contributes to improved customer satisfaction, as it leads to more consistent and reliable service delivery.
9. **Long-Term Profitability:** The cost savings, efficiency improvements, and competitive advantages offered by predictive maintenance contribute to long-term profitability, making it a strategic investment for businesses.

In order for an individual or business to successfully take advantage of those opportunities they must yield the correct skills, practices and experienced staff, to conduct market research and needs analysis, followed by the correct implementation of PM on existing, traditional procedures.

Market analysis and opportunity identification are essential skills for businesses looking to incorporate predictive maintenance into their line of work. Strategic thinking is crucial in identifying opportunities and developing a plan to capitalize on them. The following skills are necessary for market analysis and opportunity identification in predictive maintenance:

1. **Technical Skills:** Technical skills are essential for implementing predictive maintenance solutions. These skills include algorithmic/statistical/programming skills, which are needed to implement technical solutions to problems (Hancock, 2023).
2. **Business Skills:** Business skills are necessary for communicating thoughts and ideas among groups of interested parties. Business and data analysts who have worked in certain industries for long periods of time and know their business very well are increasingly being called upon to participate in predictive analytics projects.
3. **Data Analysis Skills:** Data analysis skills are essential for analyzing data collected from assets and making informed decisions based on the data. These skills are necessary for accurate and efficient maintenance planning and resource allocation (Grand View Research, 2023).
4. **Domain Knowledge:** Domain knowledge is important since it allows businesses to apply their particular analytics skills to their specific industry. Every business has its own nuances when it comes to solving analytic problems, and domain knowledge is necessary to understand these nuances.
5. **Strategic Thinking:** Strategic thinking is crucial in identifying opportunities and developing a plan to capitalize on them. It involves analyzing the market, identifying trends, and developing a plan to stay ahead of the competition.
6. **Communication Skills:** Communication skills are necessary for presenting findings and ideas to stakeholders. Having good presentation and documentation skills are important in communicating the results of market analysis and opportunity identification.
7. **Adaptability:** Predictive maintenance is a rapidly evolving field, and businesses need to be adaptable to stay ahead of the competition. Being able to adapt to new technologies and changing market conditions is essential for success.

According to all of the above, market analysis and opportunity identification are essential skills for businesses looking to incorporate predictive maintenance into their line of work. More specifically technical skills, business skills, data analysis skills, domain knowledge, strategic thinking, communication skills, and adaptability are all necessary for success in this field.

More specifically on: Market Dynamics & SWOT Analysis

1. **Understanding Market Dynamics:** Grasping the current trends and dynamics in the predictive maintenance market is crucial. This includes recognizing the growing demand for efficiency, the role of technological advancements like IoT and AI, and the increasing focus on sustainability (Tan Jing Yu et al., 2020).
2. **Customer Needs and Preferences:** Identifying customer needs in different industries, such as manufacturing or transportation, is essential. This involves understanding their specific challenges and how predictive maintenance can address these issues (Zhu, 2022).
3. **SWOT Analysis:**
 - **Strengths:** Assess the strengths of predictive maintenance, such as cost savings, improved efficiency, and the ability to leverage data for better decision-making.
 - **Weaknesses:** Identify potential weaknesses or barriers, like the initial cost of implementation or the need for specialized skills.
 - **Opportunities:** Look for market opportunities, such as industries that are yet to adopt predictive maintenance or areas where current solutions are inadequate.
 - **Threats:** Consider threats, including competitive pressures or technological changes that could make current predictive maintenance solutions obsolete.
4. **Competitive Landscape:** Analyze the competitive landscape to understand what similar services are offered and identify gaps in the market. This can help in positioning your predictive maintenance services more effectively.
5. **Economic Value and ROI:** Understand the economic value of implementing predictive maintenance. This includes conducting cost-benefit analyses and considering the return on investment for different predictive maintenance strategies (Tan Jing Yu et al., 2020).
6. **Data-Driven Decision Making:** Utilize data analytics and machine learning to analyze market trends and customer behavior.

As effective as SWOT analysis is, one has to remember that additionally, there are several other techniques and procedures that can be used, such as identifying problems that can be solved, researching the competition, analyzing consumer segmentation, and exploring foreign markets. The utilization of those depends on the needs and requests of each established market. It is also important to evaluate personal passions and skills, experience life, read, educate oneself, and consider different perspectives. By combining these skills and techniques, learners can effectively analyze the market and identify innovation niches to create new value for customers and achieve future organizational growth.

F. Implementation: Strategies and Challenges

This module addresses the practical aspects of implementing predictive maintenance (PdM), discussing strategies, best practices, and common challenges faced by professionals in the field.

The adoption of predictive maintenance is a natural step towards optimizing industrial maintenance. Surveys of various industrial sectors in European countries highlight the increased interest in this topic by most companies. Implementing PdM is a complex undertaking for a company/organization, as it requires detailed planning of hardware, software, personnel and training requirements. Therefore, the majority of these companies are only considering predictive maintenance in their future strategy and are currently only at the beginning of its implementation. In many cases, this is due to a lack of sufficient knowledge within the organization and systematic guidance for maintenance personnel.

Other barriers to implementing predictive maintenance in companies include:

- unwillingness to innovate,
- unclear scope and structure,
- and uncertainty about the financial benefits and appropriate business model.

To pave the way for future successful applications, developing step-by-step guidelines for the development of predictive maintenance implementation is beneficial.

Taking into account the complexity of requirements, outsourcing PdM tasks to an expert company becomes a feasible option. In the choice of an internal venture, the success of a predictive Maintenance largely depends on decisions on the following key points:

1. Identification the relevant elements to be monitored.
2. Identification of parameters indicating deterioration.
3. Selection of appropriate PdM techniques
4. Determination of sensor locations.
5. Setting critical thresholds for each variable.
6. Defining the inspection interval:
 - a. Continuously;
 - b. Or at state-dependent intervals;
 - c. Or at regular intervals that can be determined based on expert and/or manufacturer and/or previous results.
7. Selection of a suitable CMMS system that manages the maintenance program. (Selcuk S., 2017)

To successfully implement PdM, one needs to consider the following points.

1. In most cases, combining PdM with TBM is the best solution. TBM is preventive maintenance (or time-based maintenance - routine or periodic or interval based or time-directed or planned maintenance, whereas PdM is based on information that indicates deterioration, which may result in more energy consumption only and/or, in more progressive cases, will result in failure. PdM not only aims for failure prevention but also for efficient operation, hence improved safety, product quality, reliability, availability and reduction in energy cost.
2. There is not just one technique that is sufficient for all the equipment/machinery in one site. In particular, vibration analysis and oil analysis complement each other. Each PdM technique was developed to pick up certain signs of deterioration of a specific component. Monitoring a particular component by more than one PdM technique provides more reliable and comprehensive information about the condition of the component.
3. Data should be collected when the system is healthy; this is the core data.
4. Collection of system status data should be avoided but without using them. Data should be transformed into information, then into decisions and finally into action.
5. Note that measurements sometimes change as a result of operational changes such as load, speed or temperature, rather than deterioration of the monitored system. Therefore, distinction is of paramount importance to avoid false alarms. For example, vibration during operation at 50% load can increase by as much as 400% without changing the mechanical state of the of the compressor.
6. For effective management, it is necessary to look for the cause of the failure, rather than just treat the symptoms. Existing process models and guidance are based on theoretical expertise; however, they often lack complexity and insight into the specific challenges of industrial processes. In addition, most theoretical models focus on specific aspects of the overall process or target only specific areas of application. In other words, they are lacking the complexity of real-world applications.
7. Because no two plants can have the same requirements, adaptation without adaptation should be prevented.

Tiddens, Tinga and Braaksma (2022) proposed four elements to support effective maintenance techniques (MT)-based decision-making. Each of the elements contains several options from which one should be selected. The proposed framework indicates the best option for each of the four elements that will be present in each PdM implementation process. Since each element contains several options, the possible ways to make decisions within the PdM framework (i.e., combinations of options of the elements) are numerous, and choosing the right option is a major challenge. The elements can be considered in a different order.

Initiation

The first step is initiation, which justifies what, why and how to apply maintenance techniques. Technology can be induced by technology: a new technology is available or a new application of that technology. Often the initiation is a combination of technology impulse and decision impulse.

This process of project initiation coincides with the selection of equipment to be considered and is closely related to deciding what to monitor and what data to collect, selecting MT and constructing a solid business case to convince stakeholders and investors. The business case analysis requires balancing the decrease in the number and consequences of failures and maintenance costs with the cost of PdM implementation.

Monitoring and data collection

The second element of the PdM decision-making process is related to the selection of parameters for monitoring and input data collection. Data can be collected not only from monitoring systems, but also from historical records. These historical records include events, reflecting what happened to the machine, such as breakdowns, overhauls and corrective actions. It should be noted that data collected for less advanced techniques, such as technical knowledge for experience-based forecasts, can also be used for more advanced techniques, such as model-based forecasts, but then they must be correlated with more advanced information.

Several types of data collection and monitoring strategies can be used, for example:

- (1) Asset history data can be collected from technical knowledge, inspections and historical records of, for example, failures or costs.
- (2) Usage and process data include operational data, such as hours worked, mileage or tons produced.
- (3) Load data describe the loads exerted on the system. These include environmental data, e.g., include environmental data like temperature and humidity.

Maintenance techniques

The third element relates to selecting the appropriate MT and conducting a maintenance analysis.

The available data and the required outcome (again depending on the asset, its criticality and the preservation and use of that asset) determine which MT should be selected. This requires prior consideration of the quantity and quality of available data and the possibilities for their collection and also a challenging decision-making process. There is little consensus among researchers on which classifications of forecasting are most appropriate: based on the type of method and based on the type of input data.

Decision making

The last element focuses on actual maintenance decision-making, such as direct repair decisions or replacement or life extension decisions. However, it also includes related aspects, such as logistics and sourcing issues (supply chain design), scheduling (when systems can be used) and inventory options (how many spare parts, when, where). The quality of this decision-making process largely depends on the type of information available. This element presents three options with different decision-making potential: detection, diagnostics and predictive diagnostics.

External and internal restrictions

Finally, in addition to the four proposed elements, general restrictions on the use of PdM are created by internal and external laws and regulations. Examples of such restrictions are standards for forecast accuracy (the required type of recommended techniques) or restrictions on data collection capabilities (e.g., restrictions on the disclosure of global positioning system [GPS] positions in military applications). These limitations and restrictions will affect the choices made in each of the proposed elements.

More information on the various steps can be found in the work of (Tiddens et al., 2022).

The need for a systematic process to support the implementation of predictive maintenance has already been articulated above and has been highlighted by several authors. However, few process models have been identified that provide both application-independent and detailed guidance for implementing predictive maintenance in an enterprise. Although there are several process models in academic research that describe (parts of) the process of implementing predictive maintenance, they are mostly theoretical only.

Research papers on predictive maintenance offer some interesting models to ease its implementation in the companies. One of such models is the one presented by Wagner and Hellingrath (2021).

The model was primarily developed for Prognostics and Health Management (PHM) approaches for production plants, but it can be easily applied to other sectors with slight adaptations.

The identified process reference model has a hierarchical structure with respect to three levels of detail. At the top level, a phase model was developed that provides general phases to follow. These phases are specified at the second level in terms of concrete processes for each defined phase. At the lowest level, the specific steps

and tasks (referred to as process elements) to be performed to implement PdM are described. When implemented by a company, the model requires adaptation (in terms of omitting or adding processes and process elements) to better meet application-specific needs.

In order to structure the process model, different phases were distinguished for PdM implementation, with a set of defined steps. These steps have been then grouped into distinct phases to be performed during the implementation of predictive maintenance.

PdM implementation commences in the Preparation Phase (PP) This phase includes all the steps required to define the range and purpose of the project, as well as the specific implementation concept. This phase should be divided into the project preparation phase and the candidate preparation phase.

In the next phase - PHM design (PHM) - algorithms are generated to anomaly detection, diagnosis and prognosis for each candidate. Next the solution is evaluated against predefined performance indicators and requirements, as well as consideration of possible mitigation measures.

Parallel to the PHM design phase, the technical architecture of the system (technological architecture) is determined, which should allow real-time access to data (sensory) data. The system architecture (SA) design therefore includes the physical/distribution architecture as well as the logical/information architecture and results in the final implementation of the system, including verification and validation of the system. In addition to the system architecture maintenance database is configured.

In Phase (CSD), the developed algorithms are implemented, and their maintenance is performed. In addition, existing processes are redesigned to match the new requirements, and the resulting change is then implemented, including appropriate staff training and change management.

Finally, the PdM (PA) application covers the use of predictive maintenance in the company. It defines the steps related to anomaly detection, diagnostics, prognostics and health management with consideration of the developed PHM algorithms. The PdM application process allows returning to early phases in case of required revisions to PHM algorithms, as well as the necessary maintenance process and technical adjustments to the system.

The preparatory phase consists of six additional processes, which define detailed steps for each element defined at the process level. Generally, the preparation phase depicts a critical element (Wagner & Hellings, 2021)

Project specification in the PP phase begins with an as-is analysis and an assessment of the company's maturity, mainly with regard to its technological readiness. Based on these results, goals and objectives are defined. In addition, project stakeholders must be identified, from members of the board of directors to machine operators but may also include people from outside the company (e.g., customers). In particular their expectations, responsibilities and potential impact on project results are important.

Candidate identification aims to identify a list of suitable PdM candidates that are further considered in the design of the PHM method. In order to define potential PdM candidates existing equipment is initially identified. Based on the list of equipment, potential candidates are then evaluated.

The candidate preparation sub-phase takes as input one candidate. When determining the prerequisites, a team consisting of various experts is first formed for a particular candidate. The team is then responsible for identifying and defining the failure modes and required parameter measurements. These are evaluated against existing sensor capabilities to determine whether further sensor measurements are needed. Finally, a preliminary analysis is performed in terms of analytical feasibility and candidate data, which allows for early cancellation of the candidate in the case of infeasibility without having to follow the steps up to the final feasibility analysis. In cases where available measurements are insufficient, additional sensors should be installed (Wagner & Hellingrath, 2021).

Finally, the development of the candidate concept defines and formulates the implementation of the candidate. For this reason, the requirements for the candidate, including the PHM target task, as well as performance metrics, are defined based on detailed system requirements. These specifications are used to develop a complete concept as well as a comprehensive usage description. In addition, an ROI analysis can be performed for a specific candidate.

The phase ends with a final feasibility assessment and a decision on further examination of the candidate.

This theoretical model was extended and validated with knowledge and best practices from industrial applications. To gather information from industrial applications, eleven industry experts with medium to long experience in PdM were addressed using semi-structured interviews. The companies with internal implementations are active in the steel, automotive, aerospace, as well as in the wind energy industry. In addition, research and management consultancies, as well as solution providers, were considered with experience in multiple diverse projects.

A large number of identified steps are followed by most companies. These include requirements engineering, machine/candidate selection, technical infrastructure, data preparation, model development, implementation, and continuous verification. This shows the model is applicable throughout the industry.

To develop and implement PdM in a company, not only are the individual steps important, but the required skills and overall organization of the project also positively contribute to the success of the project. PReMMa was designed to be versatile and adaptable to specific project characteristics and scope. The process reference model includes not only the reference process, but also the required team structure with key skills and related project management tasks. The surveyed experts confirmed that a structured, predefined process is needed for the successful implementation of a predictive maintenance project. They emphasized that the development of a structured process was crucial to their success, while without a defined process they encountered many difficulties. This made it possible to communicate the project concept and required steps to the support team and management, as well as to offer guidance throughout the project. PReMMa can therefore be used to define the appropriate process for a PdM project by presenting the relevant tasks to be performed. For its general applicability, the process reference model developed is not exhaustive for specific application-dependent requirements and challenges. It provides a structured approach that outlines the basic stages. However, the detailed design and customization for the specific application context must be performed by the company itself. In particular, PReMMa is designed to develop data-driven approaches. In cases where physics-based approaches are more suitable, several steps require adaptation during the PHM design phase (Wagner & Hellingrath, 2021).

G. Creativity, Adaptability and Problem Solving Skills

With the rise of digitalisation, the relationship between creativity and problem solving, which are the pillars of modern innovation, is increasingly evolving. They are shaping our world and offering new opportunities and solutions to modern challenges.

Today, widely used technologies and the internet are impacting every aspect of our lives, from communication, commerce and education to healthcare. Digitalisation is also characterised by unique challenges from adaptation needs to technological advances to cyber security and information overload.

The primary tools to address these challenges are creativity and problem solving. They enable both individuals and organisations to adapt to an ever-changing environment and innovate further. (Coetzee, 2023).

Innovation is the process of combining new ideas and insights to create new value. There are 4 different types of innovation: (Creativity Guidebook Incrementa, 2020)

1. **Product innovation** - the creation of significantly improved or new goods/services, for example: GPS.
2. **Process innovations** - the development of a significantly improved or new production/supply process, for example: the introduction of a new automated machine into a production line.
3. **Marketing innovations** - implementation of new marketing methods, introducing significant changes, for example, in design, advertising, pricing, packaging.
4. **Organisational innovations** - implementing new methods in work organisation, business practices, for example, implementing a new training system.

Adaptability is the ability to adjust to unpredictable circumstances or events and to change effectively. It is an important asset for both individuals and organisations. (Iceberg, (n.d.)).

Why is adaptability important?

It is very important to keep up to date with industry trends and best practice. This often requires individuals to quickly learn new technologies or pursue new roles and responsibilities. Rapid adaptation to changes in the workplace, flexibility and the ability to learn, enables individuals to contribute to the organisation in different ways, which is essential to stay ahead of the competition and improve any processes.

The benefits of adaptation

The ability to adapt and learn new skills, opens the door to new perspectives. It is linked to the ability to take on new roles, for organisations to streamline their operations, to go beyond traditional directions, to introduce all sorts of new solutions, which can lead to faster growth. The role of adaptability is very important in the process of accepting change, not resisting it. Developing this way of thinking allows one to develop solutions to problems that may not have been immediately obvious. People with adaptive capacity use patterns from analytical thinking, from different sets of data in a logical and complex way.

Fundamentals of problem solving

Problem solving requires clear communication in which all concerns and perspectives are taken into account. In an environment where no one talks openly with each other, it is difficult to identify a problem. It is worth remembering that although every problem is different - the strategies and methods used when solving them can be methodical and focus on a few steps. This is the only way to avoid hasty decisions and constant crisis. (Coetzee, 2023).

Here are the 6 steps of the problem-solving process - with a well-defined plan and goals: (Chmielecki, 2018)

1. Define the problem

The first step is to define the problem - only then can a solution be found. It is possible that you know something is wrong in the company, but you don't know what. So, you want to find the source of the problem so you can fix it and make sure the problem doesn't come back.

In this part of the process, it is useful to ask yourself questions:

What is happening?

What are the symptoms?

Where is the source?

What is the source of the problem?

What will be the consequences if we do not solve the problem?

Why has the problem arisen?

2. Describe the problem

The team needs to describe the problem, and it is also worth considering how the problem might be seen by someone from the outside - who would be looking at it from a neutral perspective. Sometimes an important detail emerges in such a process that strongly and decisively influences the next steps in the process.

In this part of the process, it is useful to ask yourself questions:

How do the people affected by the problem see it?

How can we describe the problem to someone from the outside?

3. Take the problem apart

The team makes a detailed analysis of the problem.

In this part of the process, it is useful to ask yourself questions:

How does it affect the people involved (directly and indirectly)?

What are the most harmful aspects?

What are the least harmful aspects?

How will the situation develop over the next hours, days, months?

4. Brainstorm to generate options

Next, brainstorm and find potential solutions to the problem. Look at the problem from all angles and take a broad perspective. Don't decide immediately on the first solution.

When brainstorming, remember 2 important rules:

- let the ideas flow
- in this phase all ideas are accepted

5. Choose a solution

Choose one solution - one that everyone agrees on. Once you've made that decision, everyone should respect it and be consistent about it - there is no time for endless debating.

6. Control the results

Monitor the results of the solution adopted by the team and determine whether it has effectively eliminated the problem - if not, start the whole process over again and find a more effective solution.

The basics of problem solving are also used in predictive maintenance. Unexpected downtime or machine failure means all sorts of inconvenience. With predictive maintenance, we find out about the problem even before the breakdown occurs, which gives us the opportunity to plan repairs before they start to generate even more costs and become even more inconvenient. Today's best technologies and tools enable hidden faults to be quickly discovered or ruled out.

Predictive maintenance makes it possible to:

1. find, identify and efficiently and cost-effectively fix minor problems that could lead to situations that require more costly and demanding repairs.
2. avoids unnecessary downtime and other inconveniences.
3. Ensures continuity of production.
4. Controlling costs.
5. Extending the life of equipment while deferring replacement costs.

Creative problem solving is a structured process that combines practical problem-solving techniques together with creative thinking. In this respect, it can be useful to apply creativity techniques, examples of which are given below: (Creativity Guidebook Incrementa, 2020)

Brainstorming

Brainstorming is all about creating a free and open environment that encourages everyone to participate. It gets team members to share their knowledge and creativity without any fear of negative consequences. You can brainstorm in a group or by yourself. Both have benefits. Brainstorming by yourself can generate a lot of ideas which you might not feel comfortable to suggest in a group. Brainstorming in a group can benefit from the collective experience in the group. Not everyone feels comfortable speaking up in a group and so you should manage ideation according to the preferences of you and your staff.

What does it do?

Brainstorming encourages people to come up with thoughts and ideas that can, at first, seem a bit crazy. Some of these ideas can be worked on to develop original, creative solutions to a problem, while others can generate even more ideas. This helps to get people unstuck by getting the to move out of their normal ways of thinking.

You're trying to open possibilities and break down incorrect assumptions about the problem's limits. Judgment and analysis at this stage stunt idea generation and limit creativity.

How do I do it?

1. Prepare the group – environment, resources, refreshments, a diverse group of participants
2. Present the problem and tell everyone you are all there to generate ideas
3. Guide the conversations and encourage everyone to participate
4. Capture the ideas
5. Sort through the ideas and identify themes
6. Evaluate ideas at the end of the session – this is the time to explore solutions further, using conventional approaches.

SCAMPER

Use SCAMPER as a tool to find ways to improve an existing product or come up with ideas for a new one. It's based on the notion that everything new is a modification of something else.

What does it do?

It uses a set of directed questions to help you come up with new ideas. It works by forcing you to ask yourself a set of questions you normally wouldn't think about.

How do I do it?

To use the SCAMPER technique, first state the problem you'd like to solve or the idea you'd like to develop. It can be anything: a challenge in your business; or maybe a product, service or process you want to improve. After pinpointing the challenge, it's then a matter of asking questions about it using the SCAMPER checklist to guide you.

Consider, for instance, the problem "worked example to be determined"

S = Substitute i.e., swap components, materials or people

C = Combine i.e., mix, combine with other assemblies or services, integrate

A = Adapt i.e., alter, change function, use part of another element

M = Modify i.e., increase or reduce in scale, change shape, modify attributes

P = Put to other use

E = Eliminate i.e., remove elements, simplify, reduce to core functionality

R = Reverse i.e., turn inside out or upside down.

Mind Maps

What does it do?

A mind map is a diagram you draw to organise information in a visual way and to show relationships between ideas.

How do I use it?

You can create one as follows:

1. Think of an idea or concept
2. Write or draw the idea an image in the centre of a blank page
3. Add other words, images or any kind of visual keys connected to the central idea
4. Make your branches curved or straight-lined... whatever appeals to you
5. Use one key word per line.
6. Use images throughout.

You can draw mind maps by hand, as rough notes during a meeting or conversation.

Figure 60

Hand drawn mind map output example

Note. From *Creativity: What Do SME's Need to Know?*, by Creativity Guidebook Incrementa (2020)

Cause and Effect Analysis

Also called a Fishbone or Ishikawa diagram, this is like a combination of Brainstorming and a Mind Map.

What does it do?

You can use it to find out the real cause of the problem you are about to try to solve. That means you will have a much better chance of solving the whole problem and not just part.

How do I do it?

You can create one as follows:

1. Identify the problem.
2. Work out the major factors involved.
3. Identify possible causes.
4. Analyse your diagram.

(Creativity Guidebook Incrementa, 2020)

Modern technology provides grandiose tools for creative problem solving, such as (Coetzee, 2023):

Artificial intelligence - a creative tool that can automate repetitive tasks, thus enabling more innovative changes by eliminating routine work. The rapid development of artificial intelligence is a huge potential for predictive maintenance, as it affects almost all sectors and is nothing new in manufacturing and is widely used in organisations' security systems. Both machine learning and artificial intelligence improve predictive maintenance by detecting anomalies and providing early warnings, automating data analysis, improving performance, optimising maintenance schedules and making accurate predictions.

Data analytics - analytics and access to vast amounts of data can improve data processing. Big Data technology enables the processing, storage and analysis of a multitude of data collected from various sources, e.g. maintenance records and historical data, sensors. Predictive analytics uses this data to identify anomalies, patterns and correlations, providing insight into equipment health and performance. Big Data platforms enable effective forecasting and accurate modelling through patterns that have been retrieved from vast databases. These predictions provide the ability to access insightful information to help make business decisions quickly and accurately. (Matuszak, 2023)

Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) - this is a technology for which the use of data is important and includes the industrial application of networked devices. IIoT sensors used in automated predictive maintenance systems are used to detect problems, abnormalities related to the operating condition of machines, for example: wear on parts, temperature fluctuations or vibration. Internal sensors can be used to predict equipment failures before they occur, thanks to their ability to collect, real-time data from machines. (Abas Business Solutions Poland 2020)

Digital twins - this is a sector that is crucial in both predictive maintenance, manufacturing and healthcare. Digital twin technology is a virtual replica of a physical system or asset that simulates its characteristics, performance and

behaviour in real time. Digital twins are a valuable tool for maintenance teams in predictive maintenance as they help optimise maintenance activities, proactively manage assets, improve overall asset reliability and performance. They provide real-time condition monitoring, anomaly detection predictive analysis, maintenance optimisation, training and continuous improvement. (Matuszak, 2023)

Immersive technologies - i.e., those that connect reality with the digital world. These include augmented reality (AR) and virtual reality (VR), which offer significant advantages for predictive maintenance. Immersive technologies enable visualisation and simulation, but also help with remote assistance, remote machine monitoring, improved knowledge and documentation management and interactive maintenance procedures. (Matuszak, 2023)

Problem solving is inherently adaptive. It encourages individuals and organisations to embrace change and respond creatively to different types of unforeseen problems, a key skill in the rapidly evolving field of predictive maintenance. Creativity and problem-solving skills, enables us to harness the power of technology, adapt to constant change and address relevant issues.

H. Case Studies and Best Practices

Costly production downtimes that are associated with unforeseen machine service events are, among other things, a source of loss for manufacturing companies. Frequent and long-lasting breakdowns make the production process unprofitable. It is therefore very important to eliminate such situations in order to avoid their unpleasant consequences and ensure production continuity. Today, in the global market, the most advanced method of optimising equipment operation is predictive maintenance. It allows work to be organised optimally and breakdowns to be eliminated before they occur. However, when implementing PdM, it is important to bear in mind that various decision-making processes are required to select the most appropriate diagnostic technique. If the wrong decision is made, the implementation of predictive maintenance may fail, resulting in economic losses. Thus, to be fully effective, PdM needs correct strategic decisions, appropriate data collection and monitoring tools.

The most common mistakes made when implementing PdM:
(Hart, 2018)

1. Choosing the wrong equipment

In order to increase the reliability of a company's equipment, it is important to choose the right monitoring system. The most common mistake that companies

make is skipping two key steps, which are failure management, which is based on reliability, and criticality analysis of machinery. This can result in overlooking the company's equipment, which should be constantly tested, and failing to use additional condition monitoring technologies (not every technology can mitigate every failure). Identifying opportunities to mitigate failures in the various machines of the enterprise by applying PdM and performing RCM (Reliability Centered Maintenance) analysis is the best approach. This will capture those resources that are most suitable for the application of different technologies and reduce unnecessary PM (Preventive Maintenance).

2. Inadequate selection of staff

Inappropriate selection of staff for PdM analysis and testing is a common mistake. In order to select staff appropriately, it is necessary to take into account, among other characteristics: computer literacy, problem-solving skills, willingness for self-development and training, knowledge of the company's system and equipment.

3. Providing inadequate training

Very often, predictive maintenance staff receive little or no training, which is limited only to traditional training on the supplier's system. Often, employees are deprived of important and valuable training that affects the success and effectiveness of PdM in the company. Training in collecting and analysing data in predictive maintenance is crucial, as deficiencies in this area will affect the entire process.

4. Lack of repeatability

It is very important that the system is based on consistency and repeatability, as this leads to reliability. Many variables affect the accuracy of the data collected and the analysis regarding the condition of the equipment and the corrective actions to be performed. Examples of variables that need to remain consistent are data collection under the same conditions, location and using the same techniques, the parameter settings of the instruments for testing the same equipment must be the same every time.

5. Untimely collection and analysis of data

Untimely data collection and analysis can lead to unidentified failures, resulting in unplanned production stoppages. The most common reasons for such situations are, for example: a lack of responsibility for completing tasks in a timely manner, poor planning practices, and a lack of adequate training for employees, leaving them unsure of the tasks they are performing. It is important to make sure that condition monitoring specialists are performing their duties correctly, which ensures the success of PdM. Be aware that there are many risks that can contribute to preventing employees from performing their tasks.

6. Lack of measurement and documentation of regularity in PdM

The lack of predictive indicators that should be both recorded and reported is a common shortcoming in predictive maintenance. Through deficiencies in documenting and communicating the regularity of the PdM programme, Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), which enable the performance of activities to be measured across different areas, are often not identified. Thus, when measuring the performance of a predictive maintenance programme, it is important to:

- identify a target for each indicator
- identify the indicators to be measured
- establish a formula for measuring these indicators
- choose the method of communication
- select the frequency of measurement
- identify the people who will be in charge of measuring and reporting on the indicators.

It is very common for documentation of PdM correctness to be inconsistent. Some companies initially report the successes of the predictive maintenance program, but many companies quickly abandon this and no longer document the successes that PdM provides them. It is strongly recommended that a consistent template be created to document the successes of predictive maintenance. Such a scorecard should record the nature and number of events that have been completed as part of a proper condition monitoring program and include the cost savings that have been achieved during the year. It is important to identify the amount of cost savings achieved to be able to identify exactly what savings need to be reported. It is important that the scorecard is successively and consistently communicated to those who influence the future of the program.

7. Using predictive maintenance only as a tool to assess the condition of machines

A common mistake is to use predictive testing only for machine condition assessment. Due to the diverse and wide-ranging capabilities of predictive maintenance technology, it is important that it is used in many areas. The most common applications are:

- monitoring the condition of machinery and equipment
- acceptance testing of new and repaired equipment
- investigating energy savings using infrared and ultrasound
- using infrared thermography, the possibility of carrying out inspections of built-up roofs.

Using the diversity of predictive maintenance technology, it will be possible to demonstrate its advantages not only at the very beginning of the PdM program, but also in subsequent years.

8. Lack of continuous improvement

The lack of development and improvement of the monitoring system is another common mistake. The basis for a properly functioning predictive maintenance program is its dynamic nature. As time passes, various changes occur and the need to update the PdM program arises. Its key elements that require continuous improvement are periodic reviews, program management, data for analysis and performance indicators.

The following elements require frequent review:

1. machines to be monitored - the list of machines to be tested will change as new machines are introduced and old ones are phased out.
2. Instruments to be tested - they change or improve their functionality.
3. Frequency of monitoring - the frequency of intervals to be tested can be increased or decreased as required.
4. Additional training or certifications - additional certifications or training may be needed over time.
5. Use of additional applications.

By avoiding the most common mistakes in implementing predictive maintenance and following best, proven practices, it will be possible to implement a PdM program with great success and benefit.

Predictive maintenance using BMW as an example

BMW, wishing to avoid unplanned production downtime and the associated costs, has implemented one of the key elements of an intelligent factory, which is undoubtedly predictive maintenance with continuous monitoring. BMW has relied on data analysis, the use of sensors and artificial intelligence in its production process. A cloud platform has been introduced, to which connected machines and equipment continuously transmit process and condition data, which is analysed automatically. It is possible to deactivate certain components of the system, which can be switched on or off as required. Pdm also allows maintenance processes to be adapted to real conditions, meaning that maintenance is decoupled from current production, i.e., scheduled outside of production time, and carried out more economically, targeting as well as saving resources. (BMW Group, 2021)

Pdm is used by BMW in the production of, for example, electric motor housings and, with the system in place, is able to detect any anomalies, thanks to artificial intelligence algorithms or simple statistical models. The production worker is informed in advance of required maintenance through the use of alarms and visualisation.

Special software, which is used in the production of the bodywork, collects data from welding clamps around the world, which perform around 15,000 welds per day, and then transmits the data to the cloud in order to detect possible failures in

advance. Using algorithms, this data is processed and analysed and then made available for use worldwide to support maintenance processes.

Predictive maintenance also has applications on car assembly lines. The machines and equipment that control the conveyors continuously monitor, analyse and transmit data on, for example, temperature or electrical currents. In this way, employees have information about the current state of the conveyor, its position and what it is doing at any given time.

Using the BMW plant as an example, it can be seen that predictive maintenance based on continuous and ongoing monitoring of machinery and equipment is able to replace periodic maintenance and predict the risk of failure early enough to be able to react in time and prevent it or develop an alternative plan for the situation.

The benefits of implementing predictive maintenance systems are not only technical, but also organisational and economic. When PdM is in use, any costs incurred, are recouped through reduced expenditure on overhauls and repairs to machinery and equipment, their service life is extended, the number of unplanned failures and the stock of spare parts is reduced. (Kacperek, 2021)

The use of predictive maintenance in pneumatics technology

Pneumatics components (air-operated valves, cylinders or actuators) are commonly used in industrial automation systems to control machines and processes. They are used to drive moving equipment (e.g., grippers or sealers), in packaging machines, to control pilot valves (in oil refineries) and switching valves used in materials handling. Pneumatic devices are characterised by fast and repetitive movements, it is of great importance for the functionality of machines, yet the functions it performs are simple.

Thus, if pneumatic systems start to malfunction or fail due to insufficient maintenance, unplanned downtime will be created, and production efficiency will suffer. By manufacturers in the automation and pneumatics industry, a more extensive and improved predictive maintenance program has been developed. It includes the use of the Industrial Internet of Things in production systems and new and improved sensors. This provides the opportunity to keep more systems and machines running, which are based on data processing.

Manufacturers of pneumatic components are constantly improving materials and investing in new designs to increase the service life and reliability of their products. This includes, for example, replacing metal components with ones that have better airflow and are more wear-resistant (polymers). As a result, the equipment runs more efficiently and more smoothly.

Based on cooperation between pneumatic component manufacturers and those in the automation industry, the main parts of failures have been identified and new

approaches are currently being developed to use sensors housed in valves, cylinders or actuators to obtain more comprehensive data that relates to changes in the performance of machines over their lifetime.

Quality improvements have contributed to a significant increase in product life. Previously, valve systems had a service life of 100 million cycles, whereas they are now capable of up to 140 million failure-free cycles. It is predictive maintenance that is becoming increasingly important in pneumatics, making the products under development last significantly longer. Continuous monitoring of the operation of equipment and repairing the one that malfunctions makes a huge difference in achieving the service life of that machine as stated by its manufacturer.

For example, pneumatic cylinders fitted with hydraulic dampers, which lose their effectiveness over time through fluid leakage. When the machine is first commissioned, the optimum cycle time and the actuator's service life is determined by tests carried out by the manufacturer.

In this system, the predictive maintenance used is designed to monitor the actuator's performance, with sensor data monitoring the status of this component. When the sensors report that the actuator accelerates between cushioning and stopping, this could mean that fluid has leaked in the shock absorber and it should be replaced immediately with a new one, even though it has not reached its target number of cycles and is not running badly. Failure to do so could result in unplanned machine shutdowns or the production of faulty products.

For maintenance in pneumatics, the most effective approach would be to use a predictive strategy, which is based on the analysis and use of data, together with a preventive strategy, which would use this information to plan machine shutdowns for the duration of their servicing. This combination of maintenance would minimise pneumatic component failures, unplanned downtime and keep production systems running. (Densley, 2018)

I. Latest developments and trends

In today's global business environment, companies in the industrial sector, need to be both competitive, efficient and flexible in order to be able to meet the demands of a market that is constantly changing. This can be achieved with production management optimisation and predictive maintenance as key elements. Significant benefits can accrue to today's businesses: minimising machine downtime, increasing productivity, reducing costs and making better use of resources. (Gajowiec, 2023)

Predictive maintenance (PdM) is an innovative strategy that allows for predictive action and a shift from a reactive approach to machine maintenance to a proactive one. By using advanced technologies, such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning, Big Data analytics or the Internet of Things (IoT), businesses can monitor the health of their machines in real time, plan timely maintenance and predict breakdowns.

Companies that have implemented a predictive maintenance strategy can count on a number of benefits, such as: (Gajowiec, 2023)

- **Increased machine availability:** With the help of continuous condition monitoring, machine availability can be increased by eliminating downtime that was caused by breakdowns and by scheduling maintenance on those machines that do not negatively affect production.
- **Minimising breakdowns:** By analysing telemetric data and closely monitoring the condition of machines in real time, it is possible to detect potential failures or problems even before they occur. This avoids costly production downtime and breakdowns.
- **Optimised maintenance planning:** Predictive maintenance allows an individual approach to each machine, avoiding scheduled maintenance and inspections that are based on time intervals. Predictive algorithms allow maintenance to be scheduled only when it is actually needed, thus minimising costs and preventing unnecessary downtime.

"According to a Deloitte report, companies that have invested in predictive maintenance have seen a 15-20% reduction in maintenance costs (Deloitte, "Predictive Maintenance: How Data Can Increase Production," 2020)."

The modern strategy that is PdM allows companies to proactively manage the maintenance of plant and machinery. Advanced information technology allows maintenance planning to be optimised, failures to be predicted and the condition of equipment to be monitored on an ongoing basis. With its help, companies can reduce costs, increase productivity and availability of machines, which in turn translates into a competitive advantage in the market.

Predictive maintenance, digitalisation and automation are becoming indispensable elements of Industry 4.0. These state-of-the-art technologies offer the possibility of completely automating production lines and maintenance. Advanced maintenance and diagnostic systems, intelligent machines and collaborative robots definitely increase the precision and efficiency of operations. The report, which was published by the Boston Consulting Group in 2021, shows that companies that have invested in automating and digitising their processes have begun to see significant increases in error reduction, production efficiency and production flexibility. (Gajowiec, 2023)

Predictive maintenance and digitalisation in production management means using advanced information technology to transform traditional processes into automated and digital processes. Among other things, it is the introduction of a system that is designed to manage production, such as Manufacturing Execution Systems - MES, which provides the opportunity for ongoing, continuous production monitoring, data collection and analysis and reporting. Digitalisation can also implement virtual production models, such as: Digital Twins, which provides the ability to simulate, test and optimise production processes before implementing them into the real environment.

The introduction of modern technology also presents some challenges, examples of which are outlined below:

Investment and costs: The implementation of new and advanced technologies, usually involves a significant financial outlay. For smaller scale businesses, this can be most acute.

Data security: Protecting data from cyber-attacks or unauthorised access requires adequate security.

Training and technical support: In the event of failures or other technical problems, proper support must be in place and employees must be properly trained in the use of the modern technologies deployed. (Gajowiec, 2023)

The key trends transforming the industry and enabling companies to be more competitive, efficient and precise are automation and digitisation, including predictive maintenance. These advanced technologies enable companies to make better use of resources, automate and optimise processes. However, this requires the right investment, technical support and planning to ensure that the company becomes more competitive in the market and successful.

The modern approach of coordinating production and predictive maintenance is based on automation, digitisation and the integration of management systems, which is becoming a key element in order to achieve a company's competitiveness and productivity. Thanks to these trends, companies can significantly increase their productivity, save costs and respond more precisely to ever-changing market conditions, which will significantly strengthen their position in the market.

Current trends in predictive maintenance

One of the biggest influencers of current trends in the manufacturing sector is Industry 4.0. With its emergence, companies can effectively use new technologies to properly monitor and accurately understand actions taken in real time, resulting in the creation of a smart factory.

5 predictive maintenance trends in the industry: (Matuszak, 2021)

1. Increasing use of virtual technology:

Virtual technology should be more widely used as a diagnostic and troubleshooting method in predictive maintenance to improve operations and communication. Various technologies, e.g., artificial intelligence (AI), sensors, etc., allow workers to perform accurate maintenance processes in real time. Manufacturers are enabled to make data-driven decisions by computer systems that have the ability to identify trends and draw logical conclusions.

2 Incremental production:

One of the main objectives of PdM is to ensure that all the equipment that is involved in production is operating at maximum efficiency. Incremental manufacturing, which is also referred to as 3D printing, is being adopted by many industrial sectors. 3D printing helps to create parts for a variety of uses. This manufacturing is becoming increasingly popular, both in consumer and industrial settings.

3 Internet of things (IoT)

The Internet of Things allows manufacturers to access real-time data and information to help monitor and connect the various components of their business. They can use this data to optimise, improve and adapt any aspect of their manufacturing processes. Through the use of sensors and cloud connectivity via the internet, IoT is enabling the sector to grow. The Internet of Things gives businesses the opportunity to streamline production, improve safety and reduce costs. Its capabilities can also be used to create new products.

4 Data acquisition and analysis:

Effective forecasting, data analysis and accurate modelling is made possible by an ever-growing pool of business data. Much of the data is acquired from sensors that detect and respond to inputs from the physical element, controlling and monitoring conditions at various locations (speed, pressure, temperature). This data is becoming an increasingly important part of the IoT.

Companies need to prepare for change and be innovative in order to benefit their operations. Predictive maintenance helps companies to reduce downtime, maintenance costs, prevent problems and extend the life of machines.

5 PdM as a service (MaaS):

Predictive maintenance in the form of Maintenance as a Service (MaaS) will start to change the maintenance used by companies. Cloud technology, thanks to its ability to acquire and process massive amounts of data, will significantly improve the capabilities and maintenance services that are increasingly common in specialised machine maintenance.

These services:

- provide maintenance information using interactive technical support, instructions, videos.
- predict the life of a product
- based on analytical data, configure business and IT systems
- provide detailed reports and statistics on the performance of equipment.

Modern technology plays a very important role in many industries, but not all entrepreneurs are proficient with modern technology. In order to keep up with trends and prepare the company for change, entrepreneurs need to be open to all technological innovations. They also need to prepare their employees for upcoming changes and the processes of introducing technology. (Matuszak, 2021)

Technology in marketing

In the field of marketing, comprehensive high-tech support can be provided by artificial intelligence (AI), which includes image and content generation, target group analysis and customer communication.

The functionality of artificial intelligence can already be used effectively today in the area of: (Dziwirek, 2023)

1. Customer communication

By using advanced systems that process natural language into a chatbot and can be placed on a website or in an app, they are able to understand the customer's question and provide a quick, precise answer, which improves service efficiency. Copywriting is also supported by artificial intelligence, which delivers good quality content. Generating personalised offers is possible by analysing customer data, where AI quickly creates product descriptions or advertising content in line with the brand. This makes marketing activities more effective, with consistent and targeted communication.

2 Content generation

Artificial intelligence is a tool that significantly supports creativity in marketing. If we concretise the directions and provide appropriate input, AI has the ability to quickly generate relevant content. AI also has the ability to provide all kinds of information, regarding various industry events or changing trends. Nevertheless, human input in the content creation and editing process is essential, as the generator will not replace the copywriter, but will significantly speed up the copywriter's work.

3. Image generation

Artificial intelligence is able to generate realistic or abstract visualisations, images and illustrations. This opens up possibilities for new forms of creativity that allow experimentation with design.

4 Using AI in advertising campaigns

Refining advertising campaigns using artificial intelligence, which is key, makes it possible to accurately identify trends and patterns. This involves actions that are supported by algorithms that analyse all marketing campaign data. This makes it possible to suggest the timing of advertisements, optimise promotion channels and accurately personalise content, resulting in more effective marketing messages and greater engagement.

As technology advances, AI tools will become more effective and integrated, making it even more helpful in working on fine-tuning strategies and brand promotion. With algorithms that are able to analyse vast amounts of data and learn, it is predicted that AI will become an even more advanced tool, used to analyse trends in market changes and recognise patterns. With the development of modern natural language processing technology, it can bring advanced customer communication through speech-based interactions.

Thus, artificial intelligence plays a key role in the transformation of modern marketing. However, this does not change the fact that the human contribution to the marketing process is undeniable and of paramount importance, as it is a harmonious collaboration between creativity and technology. In a dynamic digital environment, such interaction is key to achieving optimal results. (Dziwirek, 2023)

J. Conclusion

Integrating Predictive Maintenance, Innovation, and Marketing for Future Success

The "PreMETS WP2.2 Booklet" offers a comprehensive exploration of the intersection between predictive maintenance, innovative mindsets, and strategic marketing. By examining the core concepts presented in each chapter, we can identify vital strategies and anticipate future trends transforming how predictive maintenance professionals deliver enhanced results within their organizations.

Key Learnings at a Glance

- **Fundamentals of Innovation:** A thorough grasp of core innovation principles – from recognizing emerging needs to cultivating creative problem-solving – becomes vital for predictive maintenance professionals. It opens doors to continuous improvement not just in technical maintenance activities but in processes and methodologies, fostering an internal culture of progress.
- **Entrepreneurial Mindset in Predictive Maintenance:** An entrepreneurial spirit allows predictive maintenance professionals to go beyond troubleshooting and become solution architects. This includes exploring potential new service models, proactive cost saving initiatives, and data-driven proposals that resonate with business stakeholders.
- **Marketing and Branding Strategies:** Often an overlooked skill within the technical domain, the power of marketing and branding cannot be underestimated. Predictive maintenance teams who can clearly articulate successes, communicate benefits across stakeholder groups, and position themselves as value generators will garner more support and resources for future innovative initiatives.
- **Identifying Opportunities & Market Analysis:** Analyzing trends, pinpointing emerging challenges in one's industry, and maintaining a pulse on competitor advancements remain essential skills for staying ahead. Predictive maintenance becomes all the more powerful when teams use insights as triggers for innovation, rather than relying solely on a reactive mode.

Future Trends Shaping the Field

- **Digital Twins and Simulation:** Predictive maintenance is already heavily interwoven with the concept of IoT and advanced sensors. Building on this, a move toward 'digital twins,' or advanced virtual representations of assets, holds significant potential for deeper diagnostics, failure scenario simulations, and optimized maintenance planning prior to real-world intervention.

- **Edge Computing for Faster Real-Time Insights:** Data processing will increasingly shift closer to the source, empowering real-time anomaly detection and near-instantaneous decision-making at the equipment level. Professionals must stay updated on cutting-edge monitoring technologies.
- **Predictive Maintenance in Service Delivery:** This domain expands beyond just monitoring one's own assets. As more companies adapt 'equipment as a service' models, predictive maintenance capabilities integrated into product offerings could become a lucrative additional revenue stream while increasing customer satisfaction through proactive performance management.

Holistic Success: Integrating for Enhanced Impact

Combining knowledge across predictive maintenance, innovation, and marketing creates a powerhouse of capabilities within any organization. For those committed to maximizing value, these elements should not function in isolation, but instead create a continuous cycle of mutual enhancement:

- **Data as the Driving Force:** Predictive maintenance generates insights for better product/service designs. Data on failures, operating conditions, or environmental factors informs innovations that lead to a new generation of more dependable products or services.
- **Innovation Sparks Differentiation:** When predictive maintenance strategies themselves become innovative (leveraging advanced analytics, cloud architectures, etc.), a clear competitive advantage appears. Marketing this expertise not only attracts more customers but also drives internal support for the predictive maintenance function.
- **Customer-Centric Outcomes:** Integrating predictive maintenance initiatives with a customer-centric focus is crucial. Understanding how minimizing downtime and optimizing asset lifecycles translate into better customer experiences, product quality, or environmental responsibility will become key differentiators.

Outlook

The future of predictive maintenance belongs to professionals who are more than specialized technicians. It demands visionaries with an entrepreneurial spirit to explore untapped applications, analysts adept at converting data into strategic advantage, and communicators ready to champion their efforts with compelling impact narratives for decision-makers across the organization.

The "PreMETS WP2.2 Booklet" provides a blueprint for success in this field. By cultivating the insights highlighted throughout the booklet, you will position yourself not only as a skilled technician but also as a dynamic strategist. Continue learning, adapting, and embracing the power of collaborative innovation for an exciting, influential career within predictive maintenance.

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PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

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BOOKLET

Module WN6: Re-learning how to learn in a digital environment

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A. Introduction

Welcome to our comprehensive booklet on "Re-learning how to learn in a digital environment." This guide is designed for educators, professionals, and students in the fields of construction and transportation who are eager to explore and implement effective learning strategies tailored to the evolving demands of predictive maintenance. As the landscape of these industries continues to embrace technological advancements, the need for specialised knowledge and skills in predictive maintenance has never been more critical. This booklet aims to bridge the gap between traditional educational methods and the dynamic requirements of modern infrastructure maintenance.

We begin by exploring the foundational aspects of the learning environment necessary for mastering predictive maintenance. A conducive learning environment is pivotal in nurturing the skills and knowledge required to excel in this field, encompassing both physical spaces and digital platforms. Delving into the concept of Personal Learning Environments, we discuss how individuals can curate their educational tools, resources, and networks to foster a personalised learning journey. This section emphasises the importance of self-directed learning in acquiring the competencies needed for predictive maintenance in construction and transport sectors. Understanding the diverse learning preferences and needs is crucial in crafting effective educational programs. This part of the booklet categorises student typologies, offering insights into how different learners engage with and process information.

Building on student typologies, we present detailed profiles of student types, highlighting their unique characteristics, strengths, and challenges. This section aims to help educators and learners alike to identify and leverage their learning preferences for better outcomes in the study of predictive maintenance. We outline a pedagogical framework that supports the effective delivery of predictive maintenance education. This framework integrates traditional and innovative teaching methodologies, ensuring a comprehensive learning experience that addresses the theoretical and practical aspects of the field.

Emphasising the role of active learning strategies, this section explores how hands-on experiences, problem-solving exercises, and collaborative projects can enhance the understanding and application of predictive maintenance practices in real-world scenarios. We conclude our booklet with a synthesis of the key points discussed, reiterating the significance of aligning educational strategies with the specific demands of predictive maintenance in construction and transport. Our closing thoughts focus on the future of learning in these industries and the ongoing evolution of educational practices to meet the challenges of tomorrow. This booklet serves as a guide to understanding and implementing tailored learning environments that foster the development of essential skills in predictive

maintenance. Through personalized learning paths, pedagogical innovations, and active engagement, we envision a future where professionals in construction and transport are well-equipped to address the maintenance challenges of modern infrastructure with expertise and confidence.

B. Learning environment

Online learning environment

In the realm of online learning, students are likely to encounter materials and information in formats that diverge from what is traditionally found in a physical classroom setting. This mode of education caters to a broad spectrum of learners and is increasingly becoming a norm across various educational levels, from elementary through to higher education. The expectation of adjusting to different ways of demonstrating understanding, especially with the likelihood of encountering varied methods of assessment, is crucial for optimising the learning experience. The degree to which these differences affect a learner can depend on several factors, including the nature of the subject being studied, the range of learning materials provided by instructors, and the individual's personal learning preferences.

Online education's versatility in presenting content and assessing student understanding promotes a more personalised and flexible learning pathway. This adaptability can enhance engagement and comprehension for diverse learners, accommodating different styles and preferences. However, navigating this varied landscape requires learners to be adaptable and open to embracing new formats and methodologies for expressing their knowledge and understanding.

Online learning, as highlighted by Scott P. and Vanoirbeek C. (2007), offers unparalleled opportunities for individuals across the educational spectrum. This form of learning enables students, trainees, and educators to not only acquire and develop core skills but also to maintain essential knowledge over time. The flexibility and accessibility provided by online learning platforms break down traditional barriers to education, allowing for a more inclusive and broad-reaching approach to learning. Through such platforms, learners of various backgrounds and circumstances have the chance to pursue their educational goals, making lifelong learning a more attainable and customizable experience. This perspective underscores the transformative potential of online education in fostering a more informed and skilled global community.

Asynchronous Online learning

Asynchronous learning is a flexible approach to education that allows for interaction with course content on an individual schedule, distinct from the traditional synchronous learning environment where students and instructors are present at the same time and place. This method is particularly beneficial in online

learning environments, where participants might be spread across various time zones and have differing personal and professional commitments.

In asynchronous learning, instructors curate a series of units or modules that students work through independently. These units can include a variety of materials and activities, such as assigned readings, pre-recorded lectures or videos, online quizzes, discussion forums, and written assignments. The role of the instructor in this setting shifts towards a facilitator, offering guidance, providing feedback on assignments, and assessing student progress at intervals that align with the course structure.

Real-Life Examples of Asynchronous Learning:

Online University Courses:

Many online degree and certification programs offered by universities worldwide use asynchronous learning. For example, the Open University in the UK offers distance learning courses where students access study materials, participate in forums, and submit assignments online at their own pace.

Professional Development Platforms:

Websites like Coursera, LinkedIn Learning, and Udemy offer asynchronous courses on a wide range of topics, from business and technology to personal development. Users can enrol in these courses at any time and complete them according to their schedules.

Corporate Training:

Many organisations have adopted asynchronous learning platforms to train their employees. This could include compliance training, software training, or skill development courses. Employees can access these courses at convenient times, ensuring ongoing professional development without impacting their daily work responsibilities.

K-12 Supplemental Education:

Services like Khan Academy and platforms offering [MOOCs](#) (Massive Open Online Courses) provide asynchronous learning opportunities for K-12 students. These platforms supplement classroom learning with additional resources, exercises, and instructional videos that students can explore independently.

Language Learning Apps:

Apps like [Duolingo](#) or [Babbel](#) offer asynchronous language learning, where learners progress through lessons and exercises at their own pace, practising reading, writing, listening, and speaking skills without the need for a live instructor. Asynchronous learning models are characterised by their flexibility, accessibility, and the ability to tailor education to fit the needs of individual learners. This approach has expanded educational opportunities for many, making learning more inclusive and adaptable to the varying demands of today's busy lifestyles.

Recorded sessions in online learning environments offer several advantages that cater to the diverse needs and schedules of students. These sessions not only provide the flexibility for students to engage with the material at their own pace but also allow for a deeper understanding and retention of the content. Students benefit from the ability to pause, rewind, and rewatch lectures, enabling them to grasp complex topics more thoroughly or revisit the material as revision before assessments.

The asynchronous nature of these courses also supports more inclusive participation in discussions. Unlike live sessions where time constraints might limit student engagement, online forums and discussion groups offer all students the opportunity to contribute questions and insights. This method democratizes the learning process, ensuring that every student has a voice and can share their perspectives or seek clarification without the pressure of a real-time environment. Moreover, the flexibility to access course materials and participate in discussions according to one's schedule is particularly beneficial for those balancing educational pursuits with other responsibilities, such as work or family commitments. It also provides a safety net for students who might face unexpected challenges, such as health issues or personal emergencies, allowing them to continue their studies without falling significantly behind.

Watching recorded sessions may lead to students feeling a reduced sense of connection with their instructor, as the interactive and immediate feedback loop of live classes is absent. Similarly, the lack of visual and interactive presence with peers can contribute to a sense of isolation from the course community. The convenience of accessing recordings at any time can also inadvertently encourage procrastination, with students potentially delaying engagement due to the flexibility offered.

Asynchronous learning, while flexible, demands strong self-motivation and organisational skills from students. Without the structure of scheduled class times, students must independently initiate study sessions and manage their time effectively to meet deadlines. This mode of learning places a premium on the ability to work autonomously, requiring a significant level of commitment and the development of independent learning strategies to succeed. This approach to learning not only accommodates individual learning styles and schedules but also fosters a more engaging and supportive educational experience. By removing the barriers of time and location, recorded sessions and asynchronous discussions ensure that education is accessible and adaptable to the needs of every student, promoting a more inclusive and effective learning environment.

Synchronous Online learning

Synchronous Online Learning (SOL) is an educational approach that facilitates real-time interaction among instructors and students who are geographically

separated. This method became especially significant during the COVID-19 pandemic, as it allowed for continued learning despite physical distancing measures. SOL is characterised by several key features and practices that mimic the traditional classroom experience in a virtual setting.

Key components of SOL include virtual classrooms, online chat sessions, simulations and virtual labs, live online assessments, guest speaker sessions, and synchronous peer-to-peer learning. Virtual classrooms, for example, are digital spaces that replicate the physical classroom environment, equipped with interactive tools like video conferencing, chat features, and whiteboards. These enable educators to deliver lectures, facilitate group activities, and promote collaborative learning, thereby fostering a community feeling among students. Similarly, online chat sessions provide a platform for real-time text-based communication, allowing for immediate problem-solving and enhanced communication.

SOL operates through a structured process beginning with setting up a virtual classroom environment using platforms that support live communication and collaboration. Educators schedule live sessions, inviting students with details on how to join. During these sessions, live interaction takes place with presentations and content delivery, discussions and Q&A sessions, group activities, and live assessments to gauge student understanding. This approach not only supports active learning but also offers the flexibility for learners to participate from anywhere, breaking down geographical barriers and making education more accessible. The benefits of SOL include a better feedback loop, the opportunity to build a strong learning community, real-time interaction, and a structured learning environment that can be personalised to meet students' needs. It enhances the learning experience by providing immediate clarifications and fostering a more engaging and dynamic educational setting.

For more detailed insights into the practices and benefits of Synchronous Online Learning, consider exploring sources like [Muvi One](#) and [Wikipedia](#), which discuss the operational aspects and advantages of this learning approach in depth.

Synchronous online learning involves real-time interaction between instructors and students who are not in the same physical location. This educational approach utilises various digital tools to facilitate live audio and video streaming, enabling presentations, discussions, and collaborative activities akin to traditional classroom settings. Examples of these tools include video conferencing platforms like Zoom or Google Meet, which offer functionalities for live chats, breakout rooms for group activities, and features for sharing and editing documents in real time.

In this learning model, instructors can immediately assess students' understanding and dynamically adjust their teaching strategies to address learning needs. This immediacy helps create a more engaging and responsive

educational experience, fostering a sense of presence and direct support from instructors. For instance, an instructor might use live polls or quizzes to gauge comprehension and then tailor the session based on student responses.

The benefits of synchronous learning extend to promoting a stronger sense of community among participants. Real-time classes and activities, such as workshop-style sessions or collaborative projects, encourage active participation and help build connections between students and instructors. Additionally, scheduled live chats or virtual office hours provide opportunities for direct, conversational interaction, offering timely support and clarifications on course material. However, synchronous learning also presents challenges, including the need for all participants to be available at set times, which can be problematic for students in different time zones or those with conflicting commitments. Technical issues may also hinder participation. Furthermore, meeting accessibility standards, such as providing live captioning for presentations, can be more complex in real-time environments, potentially excluding some students from fully engaging in the learning process. To address some of these challenges, educators are encouraged to record live sessions for later viewing, ensuring that students unable to attend can access the material. Offering asynchronous discussion forums alongside live sessions can also help accommodate diverse schedules and learning preferences, ensuring a more inclusive educational environment.

Successful online learners

Successful online learners exhibit a range of characteristics that enable them to navigate the unique challenges of virtual classrooms effectively. These traits not only enhance their learning experience but also contribute to achieving their educational goals in a more self-directed and flexible learning environment.

Key Characteristics of Successful Online Learners:

Persistence: This is crucial for overcoming technical issues and other challenges that may arise during online learning. It involves the willingness to seek help, maintain daily engagement with coursework, and persevere through difficulties.

Effective Time Management: Successful online students can manage their schedules without the need for in-person reminders. They create and adhere to a study plan, ensuring they allocate sufficient time for coursework and assignments.

Proactive Communication: The ability to communicate effectively with instructors and peers is vital. This includes seeking help when needed and participating in discussions through digital platforms, which requires comfort with written communication as the primary means of interaction.

Independence and Self-Motivation: Online learners need to be self-motivated and disciplined to study and complete assignments on their own. They should have a

clear educational goal and the focus to achieve it, regardless of the absence of direct supervision.

Technical Skills and Preparedness: Navigating online learning platforms and utilizing various digital tools are essential skills for online students. This includes basic computer operations, internet navigation, and the use of software relevant to their courses.

Adequate Study Environment: A quiet, dedicated space for studying can significantly enhance focus and productivity, making it easier for students to engage with their coursework effectively.

Adaptability to Online Learning: Embracing the online learning model and recognizing its value as a legitimate and effective way to gain education is important. Students should be open to sharing and learning from the experiences of others in a virtual setting (University of Illinois Springfield).

These characteristics underscore the multifaceted approach required for success in online learning, emphasizing the need for self-reliance, effective communication, and adaptability.

C. Personal Learning Environment

A Personal Learning Environment (PLE) in the context of engineering, specifically within the realm of predictive maintenance, refers to a tailored educational framework that allows individuals to control and manage their own learning experiences. This environment encompasses various tools, resources, and networks that learners select based on their personal learning objectives, styles, and needs. In predictive maintenance, a PLE might integrate a blend of technical resources, software tools, online communities, and practical experiences to foster a comprehensive understanding and skill set in this advanced engineering domain.

Components of a PLE for Predictive Maintenance:

Technical Resources and Content

This includes access to specialized journals, eBooks, and websites offering the latest research, case studies, and trends in predictive maintenance and related technologies such as IoT, machine learning, and artificial intelligence. For example, resources like the "International Journal of Predictive Maintenance" or platforms such as "ResearchGate" allow engineers to stay updated with cutting-edge findings.

Online Learning Platforms

Platforms like Coursera, edX, and Udemy offer courses tailored to predictive maintenance, covering topics from the fundamentals of machinery diagnostics to advanced data analysis techniques. These platforms cater to diverse learning preferences with a mix of video lectures, interactive quizzes, and hands-on projects.

Software Tools

A PLE for predictive maintenance would include software tools and simulations used in the field, such as MATLAB for data analysis, or specialized predictive maintenance platforms like IBM's Maximo. Gaining hands-on experience with these tools can be crucial for understanding their application in real-world scenarios.

Communities and Networks

Online forums and professional networks (e.g., LinkedIn groups dedicated to predictive maintenance) serve as valuable components of a PLE by enabling knowledge exchange, mentorship, and collaboration with peers and experts in the field.

Practical Experience

Incorporating real-life projects, internships, or collaboration with industry partners can provide practical experience, which is essential for applying theoretical knowledge to solve actual engineering problems in predictive maintenance.

Self-Reflection Tools

Tools such as learning diaries or blogs where learners can reflect on their learning process, document progress, and articulate challenges and achievements. This reflective practice enhances learning by making the learner more aware of their understanding and areas needing improvement.

Implementing a PLE in Predictive Maintenance

Creating a PLE involves identifying personal learning goals within predictive maintenance, selecting resources and tools that align with these objectives, and engaging with communities and experiences that will enrich the learning journey. It requires an ongoing process of evaluation and adaptation to ensure that the learning environment remains relevant to the learner's evolving needs and the advancements in the predictive maintenance field. A PLE empowers engineers and technicians to develop a deep, personalized understanding of predictive maintenance, enabling them to effectively address the unique challenges presented by machinery and equipment in various industries.

By leveraging a PLE, individuals can cultivate a skill set that not only includes technical expertise but also fosters innovation, critical thinking, and continuous professional development in the dynamic landscape of engineering maintenance.

Case Study 1: Predictive Maintenance in Urban Mass Transit Systems

The case study by Yuan et al. (2014) titled "Construction and Market Application Analysis of the Rail Transit Predictive Maintenance Management System" presented at the CICTP 2014 conference focuses on the development and application of a predictive maintenance management system specifically designed for rail transit systems. This study highlights the importance of predictive maintenance in ensuring the safety, efficiency, and sustainability of multimodal transportation systems, particularly within the context of rail transit.

Key Highlights of the Study:

System Construction: The case study outlines the construction of a predictive maintenance management system that integrates various technologies and methodologies, including data analytics, machine learning, and sensor technology, to monitor the condition of rail transit infrastructure and rolling stock in real time. The system is designed to predict potential failures or maintenance needs before they lead to operational disruptions.

Market Application: The authors analyse the application of this predictive maintenance system in the real-world market, focusing on its implementation in rail transit networks. They discuss the system's impact on improving operational reliability and reducing maintenance costs by transitioning from a traditional reactive maintenance approach to a proactive, data-driven strategy.

Challenges and Solutions: The study also addresses the challenges faced during the development and implementation of the predictive maintenance system, such as data collection, analysis, and the integration of the system into existing rail transit operations. Solutions and strategies to overcome these challenges are discussed, emphasizing the role of technology and innovation in enhancing maintenance management practices.

Benefits and Implications: The case study highlights the significant benefits of implementing a predictive maintenance management system in rail transit, including improved safety standards, enhanced operational efficiency, and reduced environmental impact through more sustainable maintenance practices. The authors also discuss the broader implications of their findings for the transportation industry, suggesting that predictive maintenance can play a crucial role in the development of safe, smart, and sustainable multimodal transportation systems.

Future Directions: Finally, the study suggests areas for future research and development, such as the integration of more advanced predictive analytics

techniques, the exploration of new sensor technologies, and the assessment of the system's scalability and adaptability to different types of rail transit systems and networks.

This case study provides valuable insights into the potential of predictive maintenance systems to revolutionize maintenance management in the rail transit sector, contributing to the advancement of transportation engineering and the promotion of more efficient and sustainable transportation solutions.

Case Study 2: Enhancing Construction Equipment Reliability

The study by Mohandes et al. (2023) titled "Towards enhancement in reliability and safety of construction projects: Developing a hybrid multi-dimensional fuzzy-based approach," published in the Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management journal, delves into the critical issue of improving reliability and safety in construction projects. This comprehensive research proposes a novel approach that integrates multi-dimensional analysis with fuzzy logic to address the complexity and uncertainty inherent in construction project management.

Overview of the Study:

Objective: The primary aim of the research is to enhance the reliability and safety of construction projects by developing a hybrid approach that combines the robustness of multi-dimensional analysis with the flexibility of fuzzy logic. This approach is designed to better manage the uncertainties and risks associated with construction projects, leading to improved outcomes in terms of safety and project reliability.

Methodology: The authors employ a multi-dimensional analysis to identify and categorize the various factors that influence the reliability and safety of construction projects. They then apply fuzzy logic techniques to model the uncertainty and vagueness associated with these factors. The hybrid approach allows for a more nuanced and accurate assessment of risks and their impacts on project outcomes.

Findings: The study presents a detailed analysis of the hybrid multi-dimensional fuzzy-based approach and its application to real-world construction projects. The findings demonstrate that this approach significantly enhances the ability of project managers to identify, assess, and mitigate risks, leading to safer and more reliable construction processes.

Implications: The research highlights the potential of combining fuzzy logic with multi-dimensional analysis to improve decision-making in construction project management. The authors argue that this hybrid approach can be a valuable tool

for construction professionals seeking to navigate the complexities of project execution while ensuring high standards of safety and reliability.

Future Directions: Mohandes et al. (2023) suggest areas for further research, including the exploration of advanced computational techniques for refining the fuzzy-based models and the application of their approach to a broader range of construction project types. They emphasize the importance of continued innovation in methodologies for risk assessment and management in the construction industry.

This study contributes to the field of construction management by offering a novel and effective approach to enhancing the safety and reliability of construction projects. By leveraging the strengths of fuzzy logic and multi-dimensional analysis, the research provides valuable insights and tools for construction professionals aiming to improve project outcomes amidst the challenges of uncertainty and risk.

Case Study 3: Predictive Maintenance for Bridge Health Monitoring

The study by Jin et al. (2019), titled "Predictive analytics of in-service bridge structural performance from SHM (Structural Health Monitoring) data mining perspective: a case study," published in Shock and Vibration, focuses on the application of predictive analytics and data mining techniques to assess the structural performance of in-service bridges. This research underscores the potential of SHM data in forecasting and enhancing bridge safety and reliability through advanced analytical methods.

Overview of the Study:

Objective: The primary goal of this research is to demonstrate how predictive analytics, when applied to data derived from structural health monitoring (SHM) systems, can significantly contribute to understanding and forecasting the structural performance of bridges. This approach aims to facilitate timely maintenance and intervention strategies, ultimately improving the lifespan and safety of such critical infrastructure.

Methodology: Jin et al. (2019) employ data mining techniques to analyse the vast amounts of SHM data collected from sensors installed on a specific bridge. The study meticulously processes and interprets this data to identify patterns, anomalies, and trends that may indicate potential structural issues or the need for maintenance actions.

Case Study: The research presents a detailed case study of an in-service bridge equipped with SHM systems, providing a real-world application of their proposed predictive analytics approach. The case study illustrates the process of data

collection, analysis, and the subsequent interpretation of results to assess the bridge's structural health.

Findings: The findings reveal that predictive analytics can effectively utilize SHM data to predict potential structural problems before they become critical. The study highlights the advantages of this proactive approach in preventing catastrophic failures, extending the service life of bridges, and optimizing maintenance resources.

Implications: This research demonstrates the significant implications of integrating predictive analytics with SHM data for bridge maintenance and safety. It suggests a shift towards data-driven decision-making in civil engineering and infrastructure management, emphasizing the importance of technological innovation in ensuring the longevity and reliability of bridges.

Future Directions: The authors suggest further research into refining data mining algorithms and exploring the integration of machine learning techniques to enhance the predictive capabilities of SHM systems. They advocate for the broader adoption of such advanced analytics in civil engineering practices to ensure the structural integrity of bridges and other critical infrastructures.

This study contributes to the evolving field of civil engineering by showcasing how the intersection of SHM data and predictive analytics can revolutionize the maintenance and monitoring of bridge infrastructures. By leveraging data mining techniques, the research provides valuable insights into the proactive management of bridge health, paving the way for safer and more efficient infrastructure management practices.

D. Student Typology

The concept of learner typology in the context of engineering, especially in predictive maintenance, is not directly addressed by a specific typology or educational theory that categorizes learners based on their preferred sensory modalities or learning strategies (such as the VARK model for visual, auditory, read/write, and kinesthetic learners). However, understanding and applying learning preferences can indeed play a crucial role in effectively training engineers and technicians in predictive maintenance, which increasingly relies on data-driven methodologies, such as machine learning and artificial intelligence. The VARK model, developed by Fleming & Mills (1992), categorizes learners into four main types based on their preferred sensory modalities for learning: Visual, Aural, Read/Write, and Kinesthetic. Each of these learning preferences suggests different strategies that can enhance an individual's learning experience.

1. Visual Learners

Prefer using visual aids such as charts, maps, and diagrams to understand information. For example, a visual learner might benefit from using mind maps to outline a project or study topic to better visualize the relationships between concepts.

Figure 61

Concept maps example developed within PreMETS

2. Aural Learners

Learn best through listening. This can include lectures, group discussions, podcasts, and any other auditory form of learning. An example of catering to aural learners could involve incorporating more oral presentations or discussions into the curriculum, allowing these learners to process and understand information more effectively.

Figure 62

Common aural learners' channels

3. Read/Write Learners

Prefer learning through written words. This could involve reading textbooks, taking extensive notes, or synthesizing information from various written sources. For read/write learners, strategies like summarizing articles or creating written reports can be particularly beneficial.

4. Kinesthetic Learners

Learn best through hands-on experiences, such as physical activities, experiments, and using tangible objects. For instance, a kinesthetic learner might grasp a concept more quickly if they can participate in a lab experiment or build a model related to the topic of study.

Figure 63

The VARK Model

Note. From *The VARK Modalities*, by Vark Learn, (n.d.)

The VARK model, developed by Fleming and Mills in 1992, categorizes learners into four main types based on their preferred sensory modalities for learning: Visual, Aural, Read/Write, and Kinesthetic. Each of these learning preferences suggests different strategies that can enhance an individual's learning experience.

Visual Learners: Prefer using visual aids such as charts, maps, and diagrams to understand information. For example, a visual learner might benefit from using mind maps to outline a project or study topic to better visualize the relationships between concepts.

Aural Learners: Learn best through listening. This can include lectures, group discussions, podcasts, and any other auditory form of learning. An example of catering to aural learners could involve incorporating more oral presentations or discussions into the curriculum, allowing these learners to process and understand information more effectively.

Read/Write Learners: Prefer learning through written words. This could involve reading textbooks, taking extensive notes, or synthesizing information from various written sources. For read/write learners, strategies like summarizing articles or creating written reports can be particularly beneficial.

Kinesthetic Learners: Learn best through hands-on experiences, such as physical activities, experiments, and using tangible objects. For instance, a kinesthetic learner might grasp a concept more quickly if they can participate in a lab experiment or build a model related to the topic of study.

The model also acknowledges that many learners are multimodal, meaning they do not have a single preference but rather a combination of two or more learning styles. Educators are encouraged to incorporate a variety of teaching methods to address the diverse needs of their students.

For educators and students interested in implementing or adapting to the VARK learning preferences, it is recommended to start by taking the VARK questionnaire to identify one's preferred learning styles. Then, explore the tailored strategies provided for each learning preference to enhance the learning and teaching experience. For a detailed exploration of the VARK model and to take the VARK questionnaire, visit the official VARK website (VARK-learn.com). Additionally, for practical applications of the VARK model in teaching, Sphero provides activities tailored to each learning style, offering a hands-on approach to applying VARK principles in educational settings (Sphero.com). By understanding and applying the VARK model, educators can create more engaging and effective learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of their students, ultimately enhancing the overall learning experience.

Predictive maintenance (PM) in engineering is a proactive approach that uses data analysis tools and techniques to detect anomalies in equipment and predict equipment failures before they occur, thereby preventing downtime and saving costs. Training in predictive maintenance often involves a combination of theoretical learning, hands-on practice, and the use of technology, such as:

Data Analysis and Machine Learning: Understanding the principles of data science and machine learning algorithms is crucial for identifying patterns that predict equipment failure. This area might appeal more to read/write learners who thrive on processing written information and to visual learners through data visualization techniques.

Sensor Technology and IoT Devices: The practical aspects of installing, monitoring, and interpreting data from sensors on machinery require hands-on learning, benefiting kinesthetic learners who prefer direct interaction with their learning environment.

Software Tools for PdM: Utilizing specialized predictive maintenance software involves both visual navigation through user interfaces and understanding software functionalities through textual documentation, catering to both visual and read/write learners.

Case Studies and Simulations: Analysing real-world examples and engaging in simulated predictive maintenance scenarios can enhance learning for all types, particularly for aural learners through discussions and kinesthetic learners through simulations.

Incorporating learning preferences into the training for predictive maintenance in engineering involves a multifaceted approach, blending theory, practical experience, and technology. While specific examples of learner typologies applied directly to predictive maintenance training programs are not readily documented in public sources, it is possible to extrapolate how different learning strategies might be implemented in real-world contexts based on the general principles of educational psychology and technical training.

Data Analysis Workshops for Predictive Maintenance

Organizations often conduct workshops that focus on data analysis techniques crucial for predictive maintenance. For instance, a workshop hosted by a leading engineering institution might cover statistical methods, machine learning algorithms, and their application in predictive maintenance, catering to read/write learners with comprehensive manuals and visual learners through data visualization sessions.

Online Courses on IoT for Predictive Maintenance

Online learning platforms like Coursera or edX offer courses on Internet of Things (IoT) technologies applied in predictive maintenance. These courses can include video lectures for auditory and visual learners, interactive labs for kinesthetic learners, and extensive reading materials for read/write learners.

Predictive Maintenance Software Training

Software vendors often provide training on predictive maintenance software solutions, which include hands-on training sessions for kinesthetic learners, detailed user manuals and online help resources for read/write learners, and tutorial videos for visual and auditory learners.

Professional Seminars with Case Studies

Professional associations or industry groups may host seminars where experts discuss case studies of successful predictive maintenance implementations. These seminars can engage auditory learners through the presentation, read/write learners through distributed case study documents, and visual learners through slides and charts.

E. Student Profiles

Visual learners

Visual learners in science and engineering disciplines excel when concepts and data are presented in a visual format. This preference aligns with the intrinsic nature of these fields, which often rely on diagrams, schematics, and visual simulations to represent complex systems and processes. Visual learning strategies in these contexts include the use of detailed illustrations to depict scientific phenomena or engineering mechanisms, employing software for modelling and simulation to visually demonstrate theoretical principles in action, and incorporating visual data representation techniques such as graphs and charts for analysing experimental data. The visual approach not only aids in the comprehension of abstract concepts but also enhances the ability to solve problems by allowing learners to see the relationships between different components of a system.

Implementing visual learning strategies effectively can significantly enhance the learning experience for visual learners. Here are detailed approaches with real-world examples to illustrate how visual learners can optimize their study habits:

Request Visual Materials: Prior to attending a webinar on digital marketing strategies, a participant might request slides or visual outlines from the presenter. Platforms like Zoom or WebEx often facilitate sharing these materials beforehand, enhancing the attendee's ability to grasp complex topics like SEO or content marketing through visual aids.

Use Visual Aids: Websites like Coursera or Khan Academy offer courses rich in visual aids. For instance, a course on Coursera about data science might use graphs, charts, and infographics extensively to explain statistical methods, making abstract concepts more tangible.

Watch Video Content: YouTube channels such as CrashCourse or TED-Ed provide educational videos that combine visual and auditory information, making them highly effective for visual learners. A video on CrashCourse about the human digestive system, complete with animations, helps students visualize and understand the process more clearly.

Mind Maps and Diagrams: Tools like MindMeister or Lucidchart allow users to create their own mind maps or diagrams online. A student studying for a history exam could use MindMeister to create a timeline of events, visually connecting causes and effects in a historical period.

Mindful Highlighting: Using apps like GoodReader for PDFs or Kindle's highlight feature for eBooks, learners can highlight text in multiple colours. A student might use yellow for key terms, blue for definitions, and pink for examples, visually categorizing information for efficient review.

Take Visual Notes: Visual note-taking apps like OneNote or Notability support combining sketches, diagrams, and typed notes. A student attending a lecture on environmental science could draw the water cycle while annotating it with typed notes, creating a more comprehensive and visually engaging set of notes.

Explore Interactive Simulations: The PhET Interactive Simulations project at the University of Colorado Boulder provides free interactive math and science simulations. A visual learner could use these simulations to explore concepts like the greenhouse effect, seeing the impact of different gases on temperature, thus gaining a deeper understanding through visual interaction.

Implementing these strategies allows visual learners to leverage their strengths, making learning more engaging and effective. Whether through advanced digital tools or simple methods like highlighting, visual learners have a myriad of options to enhance their educational experience.

Aural learners

Aural learners in scientific and engineering disciplines thrive in educational environments that emphasize auditory stimuli for learning and comprehension. These learners excel through listening to explanations, engaging in verbal interactions, and utilizing auditory content to grasp complex subjects. Their learning is significantly enhanced by environments where information is conveyed through speech, such as detailed lectures on scientific theories or engineering principles, discussions that facilitate the auditory exploration of concepts, and the use of audio recordings which allow for the repetition and reinforcement of material. Additionally, podcasts and other educational audio resources provide an effective medium for aural learners, offering access to a wide array of topics from recent advancements in technology to in-depth analyses of scientific phenomena.

In scientific and engineering contexts, incorporating auditory learning techniques can lead to a more profound understanding of material, as it complements the often visual and quantitative nature of these fields with the rich, descriptive, and narrative qualities of auditory information.

Implementing aural learner strategies and real-world examples of how aural learners can maximize their study effectiveness:

Participate in Group Discussions: Joining study groups where discussions on course materials are encouraged can significantly benefit aural learners. Platforms like Discord or Slack have dedicated channels for educational purposes where students can engage in real-time discussions on various topics.

Listen to Lectures and Podcasts: Platforms such as iTunes U and Spotify offer a wide range of educational podcasts and lectures. An aural learner might listen to a podcast series on philosophy or a set of recorded lectures from a university course while commuting or during downtime.

Use Audiobooks and Recorded Lectures: Many textbooks and literary works are available in audiobook format through services like Audible or LibriVox, providing aural learners with the opportunity to 'read' through listening. Additionally, platforms like Coursera or edX often provide recorded lectures for their online courses, allowing students to listen to course content repeatedly.

Engage in Oral Presentations: Tools like Zoom or Google Meet enable learners to engage in virtual presentations, facilitating a dynamic learning environment where aural learners can both listen to presentations and verbalize their thoughts and questions.

Utilize Mnemonic Devices: Creating rhymes, songs, or acronyms to memorize information can be particularly effective for aural learners. For instance, using a simple tune to remember the periodic table elements or creating a catchy acronym to recall the order of operations in math (PEMDAS).

Record and Review Notes Orally: Using voice recording apps on smartphones or computers, aural learners can record their own summaries of study materials or notes and listen to them later as a review method. This technique transforms written information into an auditory learning experience.

Participate in Debates and Oral Examinations: Engaging in classroom debates or preparing for oral examinations can reinforce learning through verbal expression and active listening. This method can be particularly effective in subjects like history or ethics, where discussions often provoke deeper understanding.

By leveraging these strategies, aural learners can effectively navigate their educational journey, making use of auditory content to enhance comprehension and retention of information. Whether through digital platforms offering podcasts and audiobooks or engaging in interactive oral activities, aural learners have numerous tools at their disposal to support their preferred learning style.

Read/write learners

Read/write learners in scientific and engineering contexts benefit from a structured approach to learning that emphasizes textual information. These learners find strength in the detailed exploration of concepts through reading and writing, making extensive use of scientific journals, textbooks, and online resources that present information in a textual format. The process of writing reports, documenting experiments, and synthesizing research findings into written form plays to the strengths of read/write learners. This learning style supports the development of critical thinking and analytical skills, as it encourages learners to engage deeply with textual content, analyse data, and articulate their understanding and conclusions in a clear and precise manner.

Implementing read/write learner strategies into lifelong learning can be done using the following:

Engage in Extensive Note-Taking: Read/write learners can benefit from apps like Evernote or Microsoft OneNote, which allow for organized note-taking and easy retrieval of information. These tools support their preference for written material and help them organize their thoughts and study materials efficiently.

Create Written Summaries: Summarizing articles, chapters, or lecture notes in their own words reinforces understanding and retention for read/write learners. Blogging platforms like WordPress or Medium can be excellent outlets for publishing these summaries, providing an opportunity to reflect on what they've learned.

Use Flashcards for Memorization: Digital flashcard apps like Anki or Quizlet support read/write learners by enabling them to create custom flashcards with textual cues and answers. This method aids in memorizing facts, vocabulary, or concepts through active recall and spaced repetition.

Participate in Online Forums and Discussion Boards: Engaging in written discussions on platforms like Reddit or specific educational forums related to their field of study can enhance understanding and application of concepts through textual interaction with peers.

Read Widely and Diversely: Accessing a wide range of written materials, including eBooks, online journals, and databases like Google Scholar or JSTOR, can cater to

the read/write learner's preference for textual information and deepen their knowledge base.

Write to Learn: Writing essays, reports, or journal entries on topics of study not only reinforces learning but also improves writing skills. Tools like Grammarly or the Hemingway Editor can help refine their writing, making this process more effective and efficient.

Utilize Text-Based Study Guides and Resources: Websites that offer study guides, summaries, or textual explanations of concepts, such as SparkNotes or CliffsNotes, can provide read/write learners with valuable written resources to complement their study.

Kinesthetic learners

Kinesthetic learners in the realms of science and engineering thrive on hands-on experiences and direct engagement with the material world. This learning preference is particularly compatible with laboratory experiments, fieldwork, and prototyping projects common in these disciplines. Through building models, conducting experiments, and participating in workshops or maker spaces, kinesthetic learners gain a tangible understanding of theoretical concepts. The physical manipulation of materials and tools, combined with the real-time observation of experimental outcomes, reinforces learning and fosters an intuitive grasp of scientific principles and engineering practices. Engaging in such active learning experiences also encourages innovation and creativity, essential qualities in the development of new technologies and solutions to complex problems.

Kinesthetic learners' strategies involve hands-on activities and learn through experience. They understand and remember information better when they are physically involved in the learning process.

Participate in Lab Experiments: Science courses with lab components, such as chemistry or biology, are ideal for kinesthetic learners. Engaging in experiments allows them to understand scientific concepts by directly manipulating the materials.

Utilize Interactive Learning Tools: Tools like LEGO Mindstorms or Arduino kits for programming and robotics can provide kinesthetic learners with the hands-on experience they crave while learning coding and engineering principles.

Incorporate Physical Movement into Study: Strategies such as pacing while reviewing flashcards or using a treadmill desk while listening to lectures can help kinesthetic learners maintain focus and absorb information.

Engage in Role-Playing or Simulations: Participating in role-playing games or simulations related to their field of study, such as mock trials for law students or medical simulations for nursing students, allows kinesthetic learners to experience and apply concepts in a dynamic way.

Build Models or Use Manipulatives: Constructing models or using physical objects to represent concepts, such as building a model of the solar system or using manipulatives to solve math problems, can enhance understanding for kinesthetic learners.

Work on Practical Projects: Engaging in projects that require creating something tangible, such as designing a website, crafting a piece of art, or setting up a business plan, allows kinesthetic learners to apply what they've learned in a practical context.

Use Gesture-Based Learning Technology: Technologies that incorporate gesture or touch, like interactive whiteboards or virtual reality (VR) learning experiences, can be highly effective for kinesthetic learners by immersing them in the learning activity.

F. Pedagogical framework

The Pedagogical Framework of the booklet focuses on outlining an educational strategy that enhances the teaching and learning of predictive maintenance, particularly within the construction and transportation sectors. This framework is designed to blend both traditional and modern instructional methodologies to create a holistic and dynamic learning environment. The goal is to equip learners with general knowledge necessary to develop the skills in predictive maintenance, which are increasingly vital due to the technological advancements and the critical need for efficiency and sustainability in these industries.

Pedagogical frameworks are essential for structuring effective teaching and learning strategies in specialized fields such as predictive maintenance. While there might not be specific frameworks exclusively dedicated to predictive maintenance due to its niche and technical nature, various educational frameworks can be adapted to enhance learning in this area.

1. Constructivist Learning Theory

Emphasizes learning through experience and reflection. In predictive maintenance education, this could involve students engaging in hands-on activities like analysing machine performance data, conducting vibration analysis, and using diagnostic tools in a lab setting. Reflecting on these experiences helps solidify theoretical concepts in real-world contexts.

An example provided by Bada, S. O., & Olusegun, S. (2015) titled "Constructivism Learning Theory: A Paradigm for Teaching and Learning," published in the Journal of Research & Method in Education, delves into the constructivism learning theory and its implications for educational practice. Constructivism is a learning theory that posits learners construct their own understanding and knowledge of the world, through experiencing things and reflecting on those experiences. This approach to learning emphasizes the active role of learners in constructing knowledge as opposed to passively receiving information.

Key Highlights of the Paper:

Foundations of Constructivism: The paper outlines the foundational principles of constructivism, emphasizing that knowledge is constructed by learners as they attempt to make sense of their experiences. It contrasts constructivism with traditional, teacher-centred approaches to education, where knowledge is seen as a set of facts to be transmitted from teacher to student.

Learner-Centred Approach: Bada and Olusegun highlight the learner-centred nature of constructivism, where learners are seen as active participants in their learning process. This approach encourages students to use their current knowledge base to discover new truths, concepts, and strategies.

Role of the Teacher: The paper discusses the transformed role of the teacher in a constructivist learning environment. Teachers are facilitators of learning rather than mere providers of knowledge. They create situations that lead the students to question, investigate, and discover new information for themselves.

Collaborative Learning: The authors emphasize the importance of social interaction and collaboration in the constructivist classroom. Learning is viewed as a social activity, and knowledge is constructed through discussion, collaboration, and interaction with peers.

Learning Strategies: The paper explores various constructivist learning strategies, such as problem-based learning, inquiry-based learning, and discovery learning. These strategies are designed to engage learners actively, encourage exploration and investigation, and foster a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Implications for Teaching and Learning: Bada and Olusegun discuss the implications of constructivism for teaching and learning practices. They suggest that educational institutions should embrace constructivist principles by designing curricula and learning environments that support active learning, critical thinking, and collaboration among students.

Challenges: The paper also acknowledges the challenges of implementing constructivist approaches in traditional education systems. These include the need

for significant changes in teacher training, curriculum design, and assessment methods to accommodate the constructivist paradigm.

2. Technology-Enhanced Learning (TEL)

Incorporates digital tools and resources to facilitate learning. For predictive maintenance, this could include the use of simulation software to model wear and tear on machinery, virtual reality (VR) environments for immersive training on equipment inspection, or online platforms for collaborative problem-solving exercises.

Another example provided by Trepule, E., Tereseviciene, M., & Rutkiene, A. (2015), entitled "Didactic Approach of Introducing Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL) Curriculum in Higher Education," published in *Procedia - Social and Behavioural Sciences*, likely explores the methodologies and pedagogical strategies for integrating TEL into higher education curricula. The paper discusses a didactic approach, which refers to the art and science of teaching, for incorporating Technology Enhanced Learning into higher education curricula. This involves using technology as a tool to improve teaching and learning processes, making education more accessible, interactive, and effective.

Key Themes:

Curriculum Design: How to strategically design or modify curricula to include TEL components, ensuring that technology use aligns with educational goals and learning outcomes.

Pedagogical Strategies: Discussion on pedagogical methods that are most effective when integrating technology into teaching, such as flipped classrooms, blended learning, or project-based learning with a technology component.

Faculty Training: The importance of training educators to effectively use technology in their teaching, including professional development opportunities and resources to build technological pedagogical content knowledge.

Student Engagement and Learning Outcomes: Examination of how TEL impacts student engagement, motivation, and ultimately learning outcomes, based on empirical evidence or case studies.

Challenges and Solutions: Identifying common barriers to TEL integration in higher education and proposing solutions or best practices to overcome these challenges.

3. Flipped Classroom Model

Involves students learning new content at home through videos or readings and then applying that knowledge in class through practical exercises. For predictive maintenance, learners could watch instructional videos on failure modes and

effects analysis (FMEA) techniques at home, then apply these methods in classroom workshops to assess real or simulated equipment.

The article by Al-Samarraie, H., Shamsuddin, A., & Alzahrani, A. I. (2020), titled "A Flipped Classroom Model in Higher Education: A Review of the Evidence Across Disciplines," published in *Educational Technology Research and Development*, provides a comprehensive analysis of the flipped classroom model within the context of higher education across various disciplines.

Objective: This paper aims to evaluate the effectiveness of the flipped classroom model in higher education by reviewing empirical evidence from studies conducted across different academic disciplines. The flipped classroom model reverses the traditional learning environment by delivering instructional content, often online, outside of the classroom, and moving activities, including those that may have traditionally been considered homework, into the classroom.

Key Themes Explored:

Implementation of the Flipped Classroom: The article discusses various approaches to implementing the flipped classroom model, including the use of online lectures, interactive activities, and collaborative learning tasks that students engage with before attending in-person sessions.

Impact on Student Learning Outcomes: The review examines how the flipped classroom model affects student engagement, comprehension, and academic performance compared to more traditional lecture-based approaches.

Faculty Perspectives and Challenges: An exploration of faculty experiences with the flipped classroom model, including the benefits and challenges of adopting this pedagogical approach, are included, covering aspects such as the development of online materials, restructuring of classroom activities, and assessment of student learning.

Technological Tools and Resources: The paper details the specific technologies and online platforms that facilitate the flipped classroom model, assessing their role in enhancing teaching and learning experiences.

Cross-Disciplinary Evidence: Given the focus across disciplines, the review highlights disciplinary differences in the application and outcomes of the flipped classroom model, suggesting best practices tailored to various fields of study.

Significance: By systematically reviewing evidence from multiple disciplines, this article contributes valuable insights into the flipped classroom model's potential to enhance learning experiences in higher education. It provides a foundation for educators and policymakers to make informed decisions about adopting and optimizing flipped classroom strategies to meet diverse learning needs.

4. Problem-Based Learning (PBL)

Centres on learners solving a real-world problem. This approach can be particularly effective in predictive maintenance training by presenting students with a scenario involving equipment showing signs of potential failure. Students would work in teams to analyse data, propose diagnostic tests, and develop maintenance strategies.

An example provided by Noordin, M. K., Nasir, A. N., Ali, D. F., & Nordin, M. S. (2011) entitled "Problem-based Learning (PBL) and Project-based Learning (PjBL) in Engineering Education: A Comparison," presented at the Proceedings of the IETEC Conference, explores the educational strategies of Problem-based Learning (PBL) and Project-based Learning (PjBL) within the context of engineering education.

Overview and Potential Contributions:

Objective: The main aim of this paper is comparing and contrasting the effectiveness and implementation of PBL and PjBL as pedagogical approaches in engineering education. Both methods are learner-centred and aim to develop critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and applied knowledge, but they do so through slightly different means and with different emphases.

Problem-based Learning (PBL):

Description: PBL is an instructional method where students learn through facilitated problem solving. In PBL, students are presented with a problem, and, through research and collaboration, they work towards a solution. This approach encourages learning in context, development of soft skills, and self-directed learning strategies.

Application in Engineering: PBL in engineering might involve students tackling real-world engineering problems (e.g., designing a sustainable water filtration system), requiring them to apply theoretical knowledge to practical scenarios.

Project-based Learning (PjBL):

Description: PjBL is a dynamic classroom approach where students acquire deeper knowledge through active exploration of real-world challenges and projects over an extended period. PjBL focuses on the completion of a project that culminates in a final product or presentation.

Application in Engineering: In engineering, PjBL could involve students undertaking a semester-long project to design, build, and test a prototype (e.g., a solar-powered vehicle), applying engineering principles and teamwork.

Key Themes Explored:

Implementation Challenges and Strategies: The paper discusses how to effectively implement PBL and PjBL in engineering curricula, including structuring problems

or projects, facilitating student collaboration, and integrating theoretical knowledge with practical application.

Impact on Student Outcomes: It examines the impact of PBL and PjBL on student learning outcomes, such as increased engagement, improved problem-solving abilities, and enhanced understanding of engineering concepts.

Comparative Analysis: A critical comparison between PBL and PjBL, highlighting the strengths, weaknesses, and situational advantages of each method in the context of engineering education.

5. Competency-Based Education (CBE)

Focuses on students achieving specific competencies rather than passing exams. In predictive maintenance education, competencies might include the ability to interpret vibration analysis data, perform thermal imaging inspections, or design a predictive maintenance schedule. Progress is measured through demonstrations of skill mastery rather than traditional testing.

An example by Wyne, M. F., Zhang, L., & Farahani, A. (2021) entitled "A Review of Competency-Based Education (CBE)" presented at the 2021 International e-Engineering Education Services Conference and published by IEEE, delves into Competency-Based Education (CBE) as an educational approach that focuses on acquiring and demonstrating specific skills and competencies rather than traditional time-based learning.

Key Aspects Likely Covered in the Paper:

Overview of CBE: The paper presents an introduction to Competency-Based Education, outlining its principles and distinguishing features. CBE is an approach where learning is focused on achieving specific learner outcomes or competencies defined by the educational program or industry standards. This method emphasizes mastery of skills and knowledge over seat time or credit hours.

Historical Context and Evolution: A review of the historical development of CBE is done, tracing its origins and how it has evolved to meet the changing needs of learners and employers in a dynamic global economy. This section explores the shift towards more flexible, learner-centered models in education, driven by the demand for practical, applicable skills in the workforce.

Implementation Strategies: The authors discuss various strategies for implementing CBE in educational institutions, including curriculum design, assessment methods, and the integration of technology, including examples of e-Engineering platforms and tools that support CBE by allowing for personalized learning paths, competency tracking, and digital badges or certifications.

Benefits and Challenges: The paper highlights the benefits of CBE, such as increased flexibility for learners, alignment with industry needs, and the potential for more efficient and effective learning processes. It also addresses challenges related to CBE implementation, including institutional resistance, the need for robust assessment mechanisms, and ensuring the quality and rigor of competency assessments.

Future Directions: The conclusion speculates on the future of CBE in higher education and professional training, considering trends such as digital transformation, the increasing value of lifelong learning, and the potential for CBE to address equity and access issues in education.

6. Collaborative Learning

Encourages learning through group interaction. This framework can be applied to predictive maintenance by having students collaborate on projects that require collecting and analysing maintenance data, sharing findings, and developing maintenance plans based on collective analysis.

The article by Ralston, P. S., Tretter, T. R., & Brown, M. K. (2017) titled "Implementing Collaborative Learning Across the Engineering Curriculum," published in the Journal of the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning, investigates the integration of collaborative learning strategies within the engineering education curriculum.

Overview and Potential Contributions:

Objective: The primary aim of this research is to explore the implementation of collaborative learning techniques in engineering education and to assess their impact on student learning outcomes, engagement, and retention. Collaborative learning, which involves students working together to solve problems, complete tasks, or understand concepts, is recognized for its potential to enhance critical thinking, communication, and teamwork skills—competencies that are vital in engineering practice.

Methodological Approach: The paper details a mixed-methods research design, combining quantitative analysis of student performance data with qualitative feedback from students and instructors. It describes the specific collaborative learning activities introduced, such as group projects, peer-led discussions, or cooperative problem-solving exercises, and the contexts in which they were implemented across various engineering courses.

Findings:

Enhanced Student Engagement and Learning Outcomes: The study reports improvements in student engagement and understanding of engineering concepts as a result of collaborative learning practices.

Development of Soft Skills: It highlights the role of collaborative learning in fostering essential soft skills, including teamwork, communication, and problem-solving abilities, among engineering students.

Challenges and Barriers: The article discusses challenges encountered in implementing collaborative learning, such as resistance from students accustomed to traditional learning methods or logistical issues in organizing group work.

Implications for Engineering Education: The authors conclude with recommendations for effectively integrating collaborative learning into the engineering curriculum, suggesting strategies for overcoming identified challenges and maximizing the benefits of this pedagogical approach. They advocate for institutional support, professional development for instructors, and curriculum redesign to accommodate collaborative learning activities.

Future Directions: The paper suggests areas for further research, such as long-term impacts of collaborative learning on career success, strategies for assessing collaborative skills, or exploring technology's role in facilitating collaborative learning.

7. Experiential Learning

Focuses on learning through direct experience. For predictive maintenance, this could mean internships with companies that specialize in predictive maintenance services, where students gain firsthand experience with the technologies and strategies used in the field.

The article by Gadola, M., & Chindamo, D. (2019) titled "Experiential Learning in Engineering Education: The Role of Student Design Competitions and a Case Study," published in the International Journal of Mechanical Engineering Education, delves into the significance of experiential learning through student design competitions within the field of engineering education.

Overview and Potential Contributions:

Objective: The study aims to explore the impact of experiential learning, specifically through the participation in student design competitions, on the educational outcomes of engineering students. Experiential learning, as a pedagogical approach, emphasizes learning through doing and reflecting on those experiences.

Experiential Learning in Engineering Education: The paper discusses the theoretical framework of experiential learning and its relevance to engineering education. It highlights the importance of providing students with real-world,

practical experiences that complement traditional classroom learning, thereby preparing them for professional engineering challenges.

Role of Student Design Competitions: The authors examine how student design competitions serve as a platform for experiential learning, allowing students to apply theoretical knowledge to design, build, and test prototypes in a competitive environment. These competitions might include events such as Formula SAE, Baja SAE, Solar Car Challenge, or similar engineering contests.

Findings:

Skill Development: The study finds that participation in design competitions enhances a wide range of skills, including technical proficiency, innovation, teamwork, and communication.

Learning Outcomes: It reports that improved understanding of engineering principles, increased student motivation and engagement, and a deeper appreciation for the interdisciplinary nature of engineering projects is beneficial for a successful career.

Challenges and Recommendations: The article discuss logistical, financial, and educational challenges faced by students and educators in facilitating participation in design competitions.

Implications for Engineering Education: The authors conclude with a discussion on the broader implications of experiential learning through design competitions for engineering education, suggesting that such activities are critical for preparing students for the complexities of real-world engineering tasks.

Blending traditional and modern instructional methodologies offers a comprehensive approach to teaching predictive maintenance, ensuring learners gain the necessary knowledge and skills to navigate the complexities of modern infrastructure.

Example: Predictive Maintenance Training Program for Wind Turbine Technicians

The paper by Çınar, Z. M., Abdussalam Nuhu, A., Zeeshan, Q., Korhan, O., Asmael, M., & Safaei, B. (2020) titled "Machine Learning in Predictive Maintenance Towards Sustainable Smart Manufacturing in Industry 4.0," published in Sustainability, explores the integration of machine learning techniques in predictive maintenance as a pathway to achieving sustainable smart manufacturing within the context of Industry 4.0. While the paper itself is centred on the application of machine learning for predictive maintenance, the underlying pedagogical framework can be inferred from its approach to disseminating knowledge and fostering skills relevant to contemporary manufacturing practices.

Contributions to Pedagogical Framework:

Interdisciplinary Learning: The paper emphasizes the importance of an interdisciplinary approach, blending principles from machine learning, engineering, and sustainability. This suggests a pedagogical framework that encourages learners to integrate knowledge across disciplines, promoting a holistic understanding of how technology impacts manufacturing sustainability.

Problem-Based Learning: By focusing on predictive maintenance, which involves identifying potential issues before they lead to machine failure, the paper implicitly advocates for a problem-based learning framework. This approach engages learners in solving real-world problems using machine learning algorithms, fostering critical thinking and practical application of theoretical knowledge.

Skill Development in Advanced Technologies: The paper highlights the necessity of developing proficiency in machine learning algorithms and data analytics tools. The pedagogical framework, therefore, includes hands-on training in these technologies, enabling students to gain practical skills that are directly applicable to Industry 4.0 environments.

Integration of Sustainability: By linking predictive maintenance with sustainable manufacturing, the paper guides a pedagogical approach that incorporates sustainability as a core component of engineering education. Learners are encouraged to consider the environmental and economic impacts of manufacturing processes and how technology can be used to mitigate negative outcomes.

Collaborative Learning: Although not explicitly stated, the research collaboration among authors from diverse backgrounds suggests a pedagogical framework that values collaborative learning. This approach fosters teamwork and communication skills, as learners work together on projects that apply machine learning to predictive maintenance challenges.

Continuous Learning and Adaptation: The rapidly evolving nature of Industry 4.0 technologies implies a pedagogical framework that emphasizes continuous learning and the ability to adapt to new tools and methodologies. This approach prepares learners for lifelong learning, ensuring they can keep pace with technological advancements in smart manufacturing. While the case study primarily addresses the technical aspects of applying machine learning in predictive maintenance for sustainable manufacturing, the pedagogical implications highlight the importance of interdisciplinary learning, problem-solving, hands-on skill development, sustainability integration, collaborative projects, and continuous adaptation to new technologies. These elements form the basis of a pedagogical framework suited to preparing students and professionals for the challenges and opportunities of Industry 4.0.

Effective training programs blend traditional and modern methodologies by starting with a strong theoretical foundation through lectures and textbooks, followed by hands-on workshops that develop basic maintenance skills. It then incorporates modern techniques like online learning for advanced topics, VR for practical skills development, and collaborative projects for real-world application. This holistic approach ensures that learners not only understand the underlying principles of wind turbine operation and maintenance but are also proficient in using advanced technologies and data-driven strategies for predictive maintenance. By combining these methodologies, the program prepares technicians to excel in the rapidly evolving field of wind energy, where technological advancements and the need for efficiency and sustainability are driving the adoption of predictive maintenance practices.

G. Active Learning

Active learning strategies are transformative in the context of eLearning, fundamentally shifting the focus from passive absorption to active engagement and participation. This approach not only enriches the learning experience but also aligns with the dynamic and interactive nature of digital education platforms.

Encouraging Critical Thinking and Problem-Solving

In 1985 De Bono presented the method of the Six Thinking Hats, a wonderful example of meta-skills in action. Six metaphorical hats symbolize six distinct perspectives on an issue, guiding you on "how to think" rather than dictating "what to think." Adopting these diverse mindsets sequentially fosters more effective collaborative thinking within a team when defining the scopes of an issue or thinking about innovative ideas and solutions. While the order of the hats is customizable, pre-determining a sequence is generally advantageous.

Edward de Bono's Six Thinking Hats, introduced in 1985, represents a powerful method for enhancing group discussion and individual thinking. It's a tool for meta-cognition, guiding users in adopting different perspectives towards problem-solving and creative thinking. The method categorizes thoughts under six coloured hats, each representing a specific direction or type of thinking, thus encouraging a structured and comprehensive exploration of issues or ideas. Here's a brief overview of what each hat symbolizes:

White Hat: Focuses on data and information. Wearing this hat, individuals concentrate on available data, what information is needed, and how to obtain it.

Red Hat: Signifies feelings, hunches, and intuition. Under this hat, emotional responses and reactions to the problem or situation are explored without justification.

Black Hat: Represents caution and critical judgement. It involves looking at the cons of decisions, spotting potential problems, and assessing risks.

Yellow Hat: Symbolizes optimism and the exploration of benefits. It focuses on the value and advantages of ideas, looking for feasibility and exploring positive outcomes.

Green Hat: Denotes creativity and new ideas. This is the hat of innovation, under which brainstorming occurs, and new solutions and alternatives are generated.

Blue Hat: Is used for managing the thinking process. It oversees and organizes the use of the other hats, setting objectives, summaries, and conclusions.

Figure 64

Edward de Bono's Six Thinking Hats

Note. From *Six Thinking Hats*, by De Bono, (2024)

Using the Six Thinking Hats in a sequential or predetermined order helps structure thinking processes, making meetings and collaborative efforts more productive. It ensures that all aspects of a problem are considered, from factual analysis and emotional responses to critical judgement, positive viewpoints, creative solutions, and process control. The Six Thinking Hats method exemplifies a structured approach to thinking that enhances communication and problem-solving in groups, making it a valuable tool in education, business, and beyond. By adopting these diverse mindsets, teams can navigate complex issues more effectively, fostering an environment conducive to innovation and comprehensive decision-making.

e-Learning environments can incorporate simulations and case studies that require learners to apply critical thinking and problem-solving skills. By navigating through complex scenarios that mimic real-life challenges, students develop a deeper understanding of the subject matter.

Figure 65

VARK Model of learners

Note. From *The VARK Modalities*, by Vark Learn, (n.d.)

Virtual labs and simulation software (e.g., Labster, PhET Interactive Simulations) that allow learners to experiment and solve problems in a risk-free, virtual environment offer good technology examples. Group projects and peer review sessions in eLearning settings encourage collaboration among learners. Working together on assignments or projects fosters a sense of community and enhances learning through diverse perspectives. Collaborative platforms like Google Workspace and Microsoft Teams enable learners to work together in real-time, sharing documents, data, and feedback seamlessly. eLearning can include project-based learning where students apply what they have learned to create something tangible, integrating knowledge with practical skills. Digital maker spaces and coding platforms (e.g., Scratch, Tinkercad) provide the tools for learners to apply theoretical knowledge in creating digital products or prototypes. Reflection journals and blogs within eLearning courses allow students to reflect on what they have learned, how they have applied the knowledge, and what they plan to do next. This reflective practice deepens learning and personal growth. E-portfolios (e.g., Mahara, Portfolium) and blogging platforms (e.g., WordPress, Blogger) offer spaces for learners to document their learning journeys, reflect on their experiences, and showcase their work.

By leveraging digital technologies to implement active learning strategies, eLearning transcends traditional boundaries, offering a more engaging, effective, and personalized educational experience. This approach not only equips learners with the necessary knowledge and skills but also prepares them for the complexities of the modern world by fostering critical thinking, collaboration, and creativity. eLearning activities can be designed to develop soft skills such as leadership, communication, and digital literacy, alongside encouraging creative expression through multimedia projects. Digital storytelling tools (e.g., Adobe

Spark, Canva) and video editing software (e.g., iMovie, Filmora) allow learners to express their understanding and creativity in diverse formats.

Self- Assessment

In the context of predictive maintenance within the engineering field, engaging in active learning and self-assessment is particularly crucial due to the rapidly evolving nature of technologies and methodologies involved. Predictive maintenance, which relies on data analysis, machine learning, and condition monitoring to predict equipment failures before they occur, requires engineers to continuously update their skills and knowledge. Here's how learners can effectively self-assess their competencies in this specialized area, using a competency model with clear behavioural indicators.

Understanding the Competency Model in Predictive Maintenance

1. Technical Competencies

Begin with a clear understanding of the technical competencies required in predictive maintenance. This might include knowledge of sensor technologies, data analytics, machine learning algorithms, and condition monitoring techniques. Behavioural indicators for these competencies could involve the ability to accurately interpret data from monitoring devices, apply algorithms to predict potential failures, and implement maintenance strategies that prevent downtime.

Figure 66

The KWL Chart Topics

Topic: _____		
What I Know	What I Want to Know	What I Learned

The **KWL Chart** is an effective instructional strategy that helps learners actively engage with new material by organizing what they already Know, what they Want to know, and what they have Learnt. This method promotes metacognition—thinking about one's own thinking processes—and aids in the integration of new knowledge with existing cognitive structures.

Using a KWL Chart:

Know (K):

Purpose: To activate prior knowledge and set the stage for new learning.

Action: Write down everything you already know about the subject at hand. This could include facts, concepts, experiences, or any relevant information.

Benefit: Identifying what you already know helps in making connections with new information, facilitating easier assimilation and retention.

Want to know (W):

Purpose: To set learning objectives and focus the learning process.

Action: List questions or areas of interest that you wish to explore or understand better. These should relate to gaps in your knowledge or curiosity about the topic.

Benefit: Articulating what you want to learn helps to direct your study efforts and keeps you motivated and engaged with the material.

Learnt (L):

Purpose: To reflect on and consolidate the learning experience.

Action: After the learning activity, document the new information, insights, and understandings you have gained. Also, revisit the "Want to know" column to see if your questions have been answered.

Benefit: This step allows you to assess your learning progress, integrate new knowledge with what you already knew, and identify any remaining gaps in understanding.

Example Application in Predictive Maintenance:

K (Know): You might start with a basic understanding of maintenance strategies and some familiarity with terms like IoT and machine learning.

W (Want to know): You may wish to learn specifically how machine learning algorithms can predict equipment failure or what data is most critical for effective predictive maintenance.

L (Learnt): After completing a course or project on predictive maintenance, you could note down your new understanding of predictive algorithms, key performance indicators for maintenance success, and perhaps how to implement a predictive maintenance program in a real-world scenario.

Tips for Using a KWL Chart:

Be Specific: The more specific you are in each column, the more effectively you can guide your learning process.

Review and Update: Regularly review and update your KWL Chart, especially the "Learnt" section, as your understanding evolves.

Use It as a Study Guide: The completed chart can serve as a personalized study guide for review or further exploration.

The KWL Chart not only structures the learning experience but also encourages a deeper engagement with the material, making it a valuable tool for learners across various fields,

2. Reflective Practice for Self-Assessment

Keep a detailed record of all practical experiences related to predictive maintenance, such as specific projects you've worked on, problems you've solved, and maintenance strategies you've implemented.

Figure 67

KWL Chart: Step 1

STEP 1 Reflect on your strengths and weaknesses	Observe your daily life and note down any encounters and decisions which you make. How did these small decisions lead you to success? Is there anything which you could have done better to improve or change the outcome?
STEP 2 Take action on your weaknesses	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Participate in class discussions and propose learning activities involving reflective moments where strengths are showcased and personal preferences become evident.
STEP 3 Build upon your strengths	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Seek feedback from parents, teachers, or peers to identify areas of improvement in your skill set
STEP 4 Review, refine and repeat	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Practice regular activities that promote reflection,, to enhance self-awareness and performance

Regularly compare your documented experiences against the course or job role's objectives and the competency model.

Figure 68

KWL Chart: Step 2

STEP 1 Reflect on your strengths and weaknesses	<p>A common error is attempting to tackle all weaknesses simultaneously, which proves ineffective for most. A more effective approach is to select a few key areas to focus on at a given time, particularly those that might impede your success. Concentrate on a manageable number, perhaps just a few.</p> <p>While trying to grow and change habits remember that:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Transforming habits takes time, and results may not be immediate. 2. When addressing weaknesses, set specific targets for yourself. Upon reaching these targets, take the opportunity to celebrate your achievements. 3. Get some guidance from your parents, teachers or a trusted friend to monitor your progress effectively
STEP 2 Take action on your weaknesses	
STEP 3 Build upon your strengths	
STEP 4 Review, refine and repeat	

This helps identify areas where you meet or exceed expectations and areas requiring further development.

Figure 69

KWL Chart: Step 3

STEP 1 Reflect on your strengths and weaknesses	<p>Certain tasks are areas where you excel compared to those around you. When others recognize your strengths, they are likely to seek your assistance in those specific areas. Not only do your strengths and talents enhance your own value, but they also benefit others. Similarly, don't hesitate to seek support from others, particularly in areas where you may be less proficient.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Consider how you can apply your strengths in novel and varied ways; 2. Identify complementary skills that can be cultivated to optimize your strengths further; 3. Uncover new strengths that may emerge over time; 4. Address your weaknesses (STEP 2).
STEP 2 Take action on your weaknesses	
STEP 3 Build upon your strengths	
STEP 4 Review, refine and repeat	

3. Seeking Feedback

Engage with peers and seek mentorship from experienced professionals in predictive maintenance. Their insights can provide external validation of your self-assessment and highlight aspects you might have overlooked.

Figure 70

KWL Chart: Step 4

STEP 1 Reflect on your strengths and weaknesses	<p>Effectively utilizing reflection and self-evaluation involves taking notes, either through typing or drawing, to track your progress. This practice is beneficial after completing activities, finishing tests, or concluding study sessions, providing a clearer understanding of yourself and potential follow-up actions. Self-evaluation is an ongoing, cyclical process that continues throughout your lifetime.</p> <p>When comparing your current self to your past self, if certain efforts yield unsatisfactory results, consider refining your approach putting in place the following actions:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Explore alternative ways to address weaknesses and develop strengths in areas that can compensate for persistent weaknesses; 2. Identify what you want to learn further and take the initiative to acquire new skills.
STEP 2 Take action on your weaknesses	
STEP 3 Build upon your strengths	
STEP 4 Review, refine and repeat	

Align your self-assessment with industry standards and best practices in predictive maintenance. This ensures your competencies remain relevant and applicable to real-world scenarios.

A Skills Map is an invaluable tool for personal and professional development, offering a structured way to visualize and manage your competencies and areas for improvement. By categorizing and assessing your skills, you gain insights into your professional profile, helping you to make informed decisions about your career path, education, and development opportunities.

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Figure 71

How to create a skills map

Creating a Skills Map

Identify Skills and Competencies:

Technical Skills: List specific technical abilities relevant to your field, such as proficiency in certain software (e.g., CAD for engineers, Python for data scientists), specialized knowledge (e.g., machine learning algorithms), or technical certifications.

Soft Skills: Include interpersonal and transferable skills like communication, leadership, teamwork, problem-solving, and adaptability.

Assess Proficiency Levels:

Rating System: Develop a rating system to evaluate your proficiency in each skill. This could be a scale (e.g., beginner, intermediate, advanced), numerical ratings, or descriptions of competency levels.

Self-Assessment: Honestly assess your current level of proficiency in each skill. Consider recent feedback, accomplishments, or instances where you've effectively demonstrated these skills.

Visualization:

Skills Map Layout: Arrange the skills on a two-dimensional chart or map, with axes representing different dimensions (e.g., technical vs. soft skills, current proficiency vs. importance for career goals).

Proximity to Poles: Place each skill near the pole or axis that represents its category or your proficiency level. Skills you wish to develop further could be placed towards the "areas for improvement" section.

Using a Skills Map for Development

Identify Gaps: The Skills Map will help you visually identify areas where your skills are strong and where there are gaps that may require development.

Set Goals: Use the insights gained from the Skills Map to set specific, measurable goals for skill improvement. This might involve seeking additional training, taking on new projects, or pursuing certifications.

Track Progress: Regularly update your Skills Map to reflect any new skills acquired or improvements in existing skills. This can help track your development over time and adjust your goals as necessary.

Career Planning: Leverage your Skills Map to guide decisions about your career path. It can help you identify roles that match your strengths or areas where additional skills could open up new opportunities.

Example: Predictive Maintenance Engineer

Technical Skills: Proficiency in predictive analytics software, experience with IoT devices for condition monitoring, knowledge of machine learning for predictive models.

Soft Skills: Strong communication for explaining technical concepts to non-technical stakeholders, leadership in project management, teamwork in collaborative problem-solving.

Assessment: Rate each skill based on current proficiency and importance to your role or career aspirations, identifying both strengths and areas for development.

A Skills Map is a dynamic, personal tool that requires honesty in self-assessment and willingness to seek feedback and growth opportunities. By regularly revisiting and updating your Skills Map, you can strategically manage your professional development, aligning your skills and competencies with your career goals and the evolving demands of the workplace.

Bloom's framework

The Bloom's Taxonomy framework is often used as an evaluation tool in education to assess the depth and complexity of students' learning outcomes. This taxonomy classifies educational objectives into cognitive levels that progress from simpler to more complex mental activities. Bloom's Taxonomy can also be utilized as a self-assessment tool, allowing individuals to evaluate their own learning and cognitive development across different levels.

In the following pages it is illustrated how you can practically use Bloom's Taxonomy to guide your self-assessment through self-reflective questions.

Figure 72

Bloom's Taxonomy

Note. From *Taxonomy of Educational Objectives: The Classification of Educational Goals*, by Bloom, (1956)

Peer assessment is a process in which individuals evaluate the performance, contributions, or skills of their peers within a group or team.

Figure 73

Peer assessment steps

Note. By Moowcode, (2024)

It is a valuable method for gaining multiple perspectives on an individual's work or behaviour and can be applied in various settings, including education, workplaces, and collaborative projects.

- Peer assessment allows individuals to receive feedback from their peers, providing a more well-rounded and **objective view of their performance**.
- Students can learn from both giving and receiving constructive feedback, enhancing their understanding of subject matter and improving their own work
- Peer assessment is a form of **360-degree feedback**, incorporating insights from various perspectives within the same level or team. This holistic approach can lead to more comprehensive evaluations.

360° Feedback

360-degree **feedback reviews** collect insights from multiple perspectives, creating a more holistic assessment and establishing a continuous feedback loop by periodically revisiting the 360-degree feedback. At that point personalized **growing plans** are to be developed based on the feedback outlining specific goals and actions for improvement.

Figure 74

360-degree feedback reviews

Note. From *360-degree feedback and leadership development*, by Atwater & Waldman, 1998

Training in those specific gaps should address the identified development areas, ensuring that the training is targeted, relevant, and aligned with the individual's goals. The reached goals should determine various stages, roles, and opportunities within an individual's **career path**.

Figure 75

Example of career path

Note. From *360-degree feedback and leadership development*, by Atwater & Waldman, 1998

Johari Window Model

The Johari window Model is a tool used to develop self-awareness and mutual understanding.

Figure 76

The Johari Window Model

Note. From The Johari Window: a graphic model of interpersonal awareness, by Luft & Ingham (1955)

The window is divided into four parts:

1. Open or Free Area: What is known to oneself and others, such as work ethics and behaviours. Receiving feedback reveals blind spots and leads to learning new things about oneself, fostering trust in others.
2. Facade or Hidden Area: Represents the vulnerable part of oneself that remains private, including feelings and ambitions. It becomes known through self-disclosure but requires mutual trust.
3. Blind Spot: What others see but the individual does not recognize. For example, one may think they are a confident leader, but others may notice signs of nervousness.
4. Unknown Area: Represents potentials and talents unknown to oneself and others, often emerging during onboarding with new hires.

4. Utilising Technology

Use digital platforms to create e-portfolios that showcase your projects, skills, and learning progress in predictive maintenance. This not only aids in self-assessment but also in demonstrating your competencies to potential employers or collaborators. Interactive content like quizzes, branching scenarios, and gamified learning modules in eLearning courses actively engage learners, making the learning process enjoyable and more effective. Take advantage of online courses and certifications in predictive maintenance and related technologies. Many of these programs offer assessments and projects that can serve as benchmarks for your competencies. Gamification platforms (e.g., Kahoot!, Quizizz) and interactive courseware (e.g., Articulate Storyline, Adobe Captivate) enrich the eLearning experience with engaging, interactive content.

By actively engaging in this structured self-assessment process, individuals in the predictive maintenance engineering field can foster a deeper understanding of their own skills and knowledge, identify areas for improvement, and chart a path for continuous professional development. This reflective practice is fundamental to staying abreast of technological advancements and maintaining the high level of expertise required in the dynamic field of predictive maintenance.

H. Conclusions

By embracing the strategies outlined in this booklet, educators and learners alike can navigate the challenges of predictive maintenance education, leveraging technology and innovative pedagogical frameworks to cultivate a skilled, adaptable workforce ready to contribute to the future of smart manufacturing and sustainable infrastructure maintenance. This booklet has systematically explored the multifaceted approach required to effectively integrate predictive maintenance within engineering education, touching upon critical aspects that contribute to a robust learning experience. Through a detailed examination of the Learning Environment, Personal Learning Environment, Student Typology, Student Type Profiles, Pedagogical Framework, and Active Learning strategies, we have laid a foundation for educators and learners to navigate the complexities of predictive maintenance with greater confidence and competence.

We emphasized the importance of creating a conducive learning environment that supports engagement and facilitates the practical application of predictive maintenance concepts. This involves equipping learning spaces with the necessary tools and technologies that mirror real-world scenarios engineers are likely to encounter. The booklet highlighted the significance of personalizing the learning journey, allowing learners to tailor their educational experiences to fit their unique needs, interests, and career goals. By leveraging digital tools and resources, learners can construct a Personal Learning Environment that fosters autonomy and encourages self-directed learning. Understanding the diverse learning preferences and needs is crucial for effective teaching. We discussed how recognizing different student typologies and creating detailed student type profiles can help educators design instructional strategies that cater to varied learning styles, thereby enhancing the learning experience for all students.

The adoption of a comprehensive pedagogical framework that integrates both traditional and innovative teaching methodologies ensures a holistic learning experience. This framework supports the delivery of predictive maintenance education by balancing theoretical knowledge with practical application, promoting deeper understanding and skill acquisition. Active learning strategies stand at the core of engaging students in the learning process. By involving students in activities that demand critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaborative efforts, we can ensure that the learning of predictive maintenance transcends traditional lecture-based teaching, making education more dynamic and impactful. The booklet serves as a comprehensive guide aimed at enhancing the learning and application of predictive maintenance within the realms of engineering education, particularly focusing on active learning strategies, competency models, and the use of innovative tools like KWL Charts and Skills Maps. Through detailed exploration of these methodologies, the booklet not only addresses the technical competencies required in predictive maintenance but also emphasizes the critical soft skills necessary for success in this field. The integration of active learning strategies, including problem-based and project-based learning,

underscores the importance of engaging learners in hands-on, practical experiences that mirror real-world challenges. These approaches encourage critical thinking, collaboration, and the practical application of theoretical knowledge, which are essential in navigating the complexities of predictive maintenance. Furthermore, the booklet highlights the role of competency models in providing clear, measurable objectives for skill development. By aligning learning outcomes with industry demands, learners can better prepare for the evolving landscape of engineering professions, ensuring their skills remain relevant and competitive. The incorporation of self-assessment tools like KWL Charts and Skills Maps empowers learners to take an active role in their educational journey. These tools facilitate a deeper understanding of one's strengths and areas for improvement, fostering a culture of continuous learning and self-improvement. They also offer a structured framework for reflecting on the learning process, setting goals, and tracking progress over time.

Ultimately, the booklet advocates for a holistic approach to engineering education, one that blends traditional knowledge acquisition with modern, active learning techniques and self-assessment strategies. This approach not only enhances the efficacy of predictive maintenance training but also prepares learners to meet the demands of the industry with confidence and expertise.

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PreMETS

PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

An alliance for boosting the European Innovation in Predictive Maintenance through entrepreneurial cooperation, education, and training

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PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

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WebQuests for modules:

WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6

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PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

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WN1: Holistic PM competences
- WebQuest

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Introduction

This quest aims to empower students to explore the holistic approach of Predictive Maintenance. In this WebQuest, students will delve into the realm of industrial machinery, exploring the significance of PM, selecting appropriate machinery systems, sensors, and methods for calculating Remaining Useful Life (RUL). The goal is also to provide the proper understanding of the challenges and solutions associated with maintaining and optimising IT infrastructure through predictive maintenance strategies.

Task

Application of the knowledge gained through the module's material is the main task of this assessment. Similar case studies can be found on the Internet. Additionally, critical thinking is crucial for the completion of the task.

The main scope is to select suitable sensors and a RUL calculation method for a specific machinery system. Explaining the reasons behind the selections made are required. Access to any historical or statistical data is also needed. Consequently, students will gain the basic understanding of the problems that PM Engineers face during the development of a PDM schedule. Another requirement is to investigate and analyse the challenges and solutions related to predictive maintenance in the following areas:

- Time Management System
- Reporting Models
- Structural Assessment Methods
- Forecasting Systems
- Remote Infrastructure Management

Challenges:

D. Time Management System (Module 1 Holistic PM competences Page 28)

Resource Allocation and Scheduling: Investigate how time management systems are utilised in predictive maintenance to optimise resource allocation and scheduling of maintenance tasks. Explore challenges such as balancing reactive maintenance with planned maintenance schedules.

Integration with Maintenance Workflows: Explore how time management systems integrate with existing maintenance workflows and software platforms. Analyse challenges in ensuring seamless communication and coordination among maintenance teams.

E. Reporting Models (Module 1 Holistic PM competences Page 36)

Data Visualization and Interpretation: Research reporting models used in predictive maintenance to visualise and interpret data collected from sensors and monitoring systems. Analyse challenges in presenting complex data in an understandable format for decision-makers.

Real-Time Reporting and Alerts: Explore the implementation of real-time reporting and alerting systems in predictive maintenance. Investigate challenges in ensuring timely notifications of potential equipment failures or maintenance requirements.

F. Structural Assessment Methods (Module 1 Holistic PM competences Page 41)

Predictive Analytics for Asset Health: Investigate the use of predictive analytics in assessing the health and condition of IT infrastructure assets. Analyse challenges in accurately predicting asset failures and determining maintenance priorities.

Integration of Sensor Data and IoT Devices: Explore how structural assessment methods leverage sensor data and IoT devices to monitor the condition of infrastructure components in real-time. Analyse challenges in managing and analysing large volumes of sensor data.

G. Forecasting Systems (Module 1 Holistic PM competences Page 52)

Predictive Modelling for Maintenance Needs: Research forecasting systems used to predict future maintenance needs based on historical data and predictive analytics. Analyse challenges in developing accurate predictive models for different types of IT infrastructure.

Integration with Inventory Management: Explore how forecasting systems integrate with inventory management systems to ensure the availability of spare parts and resources for maintenance activities. Analyse challenges in optimising inventory levels while minimising downtime.

H. Remote Infrastructure Management Module 1 Holistic PM competences (Module 1 Holistic PM competences Page 60)

Remote Monitoring and Diagnostics: Investigate remote monitoring and diagnostics solutions used in predictive maintenance to monitor infrastructure health from a distance. Analyse challenges in ensuring the reliability and accuracy of remote diagnostic tools.

Security and Data Privacy: Explore security and data privacy challenges associated with remote infrastructure management, particularly in accessing and transmitting sensitive maintenance data over networks. Analyse strategies for mitigating cybersecurity risks.

For the completion of the Web Quest students can refer primarily to the material available from the booklet and the rest of the educational content, but here are also some additional links to assist with the task:

- <https://limblecmms.com/blog/predictive-maintenance-examples/>
- <https://limblecmms.com/blog/predictive-maintenance-analytics/>
- <https://www.embedded.com/choosing-the-most-suitable-predictive-maintenance-sensor/>
- <https://www.cio.com/article/188922/predictive-analytics-4-success-stories.html>
- <https://de.adastragr.com/en/articles/predictive-maintenance-true-success-story/>
- <https://www.plantservices.com/predictive-maintenance/predictive-maintenance/article/11288555/push-the-needle-how-6-companies-are-achieving-predictive-maintenance-success>
- <https://www.iberdrola.com/innovation/predictive-maintenance>
- <https://trello.com/>
- <https://blog.asana.com/>
- <https://public.tableau.com/app/discover>
- <https://support.google.com/analytics/?hl=en#topic=14090456>
- <https://owasp.org/>
- <https://www.gartner.com/en>
- <https://www.forrester.com/bold>
- <https://blogs.cisco.com/>
- <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/blog/>

Process

Step 1:

Following the steps below is recommended for the completion of the task:

Select Industry

- This WebQuest represents a case study. Choose an industry of your interest that heavily relies on machinery.
- Consider industries like manufacturing, energy production, transportation, or any other sector where machinery systems play a critical role.
- Maintenance demands vary on each industry. Different maintenance requirements apply on vessels and shore-based plants, considering stock availability and spare parts supply.

- Accessibility to available information will assist you in the selection of suitable industry.

Select specific Machinery System

- Identify a specific machinery system within the chosen industry.
- Consider factors such as the criticality of the system, maintenance required and frequency of breakdowns.
- Explain your selection in a few words.

Brief description about the reasons to implement Predictive Maintenance

- Explain the reasons why implementing Predictive Maintenance (PDM) is beneficial for the selected machinery system.
- Research and discuss advantages. Make a simple comparison with traditional maintenance methodologies.
- Include examples or case studies where PDM has been successfully implemented in similar contexts (if available).

Select suitable Sensor(s) and RUL Calculation Method

- Based on the chosen machinery system, select one or more suitable sensors for monitoring requested parameters.
- Additionally, choose a method for calculating the Remaining Useful Life (RUL) of the machinery system.
- Justify your choices with relevant literature, industry standards and critical thinking.

Find Historical and Statistical Data

- Search for historical and statistical data related to the maintenance intervals or frequency of breakdowns on the chosen machinery system.
- Look for information such as past maintenance records, failure rates, performance trends and Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEM) recommendations.
- Analyse the available data to gain insights into the behaviour and reliability of the system.
- Discuss how this data assists in the development of a predictive maintenance strategy.

Step 2:

- Research: Participants research their assigned challenges using a variety of sources, including the provided document, external links, books, articles, and online resources.
- Analysis: After gathering information, participants analyse the challenges to identify key issues, potential solutions, and implications for predictive maintenance in IT infrastructure management.
- Documentation: Participants document their findings, analyses, and proposed solutions. This documentation can take various forms, such as written reports, presentations, infographics, or multimedia content, depending on the preferences and requirements of the WebQuest.
- Reflection: Participants will reflect on their learnings, insights or uncertainties, encouraging critical thinking and exploration of connections between different challenges.

By following these steps, participants will engage in a structured and collaborative exploration of predictive maintenance challenges in IT infrastructure management, gaining valuable insights and fostering critical thinking skills along the way.

Evaluation

Evaluation Criteria:

- Clarity and Presentation: Information should be presented in a clear, organised, and engaging manner.
- Depth of Analysis: Participants should demonstrate a deep understanding of the chosen manufacturing process and its environmental implications through thorough research and analysis. Cross-reference between available booklet and found material is allowed and totally recommended.
- Critical Thinking: Participants are expected to exhibit critical thinking in the selection of sensing technologies and RUL calculation method.
- Logical Flow and Cohesion: There should be a logical flow in the participant's approach, ensuring that each step builds upon the previous one. The narrative should be cohesive.
- In-depth Research: Participants should have conducted in-depth research to support their findings, drawing from reputable sources and databases.
- Understanding of Concepts: Participants demonstrated a clear understanding of the concepts related to the assigned challenge.

Participants could articulate key theories, principles, and implications relevant to the challenge.

- **Documentation Quality:** Participants' documentation (e.g., report, presentation) was well-structured, organized, and clear. Participants effectively communicated key findings, insights, and recommendations related to the assigned challenge.
- **Application of Solutions:** Participants proposed feasible and effective solutions to address the identified challenge. Participants' solutions were innovative, practical, and aligned with best practices and industry standards.
- **Critical Reflection:** Participants critically reflected on my learning experience, identifying insights gained and areas for improvement. Participants demonstrated self-awareness, open-mindedness, and a willingness to learn and grow.
- **Creativity and Innovation:** Participants demonstrated creativity and innovation in approaching the challenge and proposing solutions. Participants explored original and unconventional ideas, contributing to the richness of the discussion and analysis.
- **Overall Impact:** The WebQuest had a positive impact on participants' learning and development. Participants feel inspired to further explore the topic and apply the knowledge and skills gained.

Conclusion

Participating in this WebQuest allows participants to delve into the complexities of predictive maintenance in IT infrastructure management. Through thorough research, critical analysis, participants can gain valuable insights into the challenges and solutions associated with time management systems, reporting models, structural assessment methods, forecasting systems, and remote infrastructure management. It demonstrates the holistic approach of Predictive Maintenance development scheme for a specific machinery system. Students are allowed to choose an industry of their interest and explore the required tasks to implement a Predictive Maintenance method. This experience has not only deepened participants' understanding of predictive maintenance concepts but has also honed my research, analysis, and communication skills. By engaging with real-world challenges and proposing practical solutions, I feel more confident in my ability to address complex issues in IT infrastructure management effectively. Overall, this task not only equips students with practical skills in developing PDM, but also provides a good understanding of sensing technologies and their

applicability. In conclusion, the completion of this task provides a comprehensive understanding of the principles of Predictive Maintenance.

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PREDICTIVE MAINTENANCE EDUCATION & TRAINING SYSTEM

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WN2: Digital skills competences for PM
- WebQuest

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Introduction

In this webquest, we investigate the dynamic realm of Industry 4.0, where cutting-edge technologies are revolutionizing industrial processes. Explore the integration of Predictive Maintenance (PM) techniques with Internet of Things (IoT) devices, promising heightened operational efficiency and ushering in an era of intelligent and proactive machinery management.

Task

Your task is to select a specific category of machinery within an industrial setting and immerse yourself in the domain of Predictive Maintenance. Explore the PM methodologies relevant to the chosen machinery and examine how IoT devices can be strategically utilized for inspection and data collection.

Process

1. Selecting Machinery Type:

- ✓ Choose a specific type of machinery relevant to your industrial context. It could be a manufacturing equipment, a conveyor system, or any other machinery critical to operations.

2. Exploring PM Techniques:

- ✓ Research and identify three Predictive Maintenance techniques suitable for the chosen machinery.
- ✓ Provide a brief description of each technique, emphasizing its significance in ensuring optimal machinery performance.

3. Inspecting Machinery through IoT Devices:

- ✓ Investigate how IoT devices can be integrated to inspect and monitor the chosen machinery.
- ✓ Identify three specific IoT devices capable of collecting relevant data for Predictive Maintenance purposes.

4. Implementation plan and monitoring of chosen PM Technique

- ✓ Create a draft of an implementation plan and timeline (Gantt chart) to install equipment or utilise the chosen PM technique.
- ✓ Brainstorm and integrate communication standards and tools during the small project implementation phase.

5. Simulation or Case Study:

- ✓ Engage in a simulation or review a case study where PM techniques and IoT devices were successfully employed for the chosen machinery.
- ✓ Analyze the outcomes and highlight the effectiveness of this integration in preventing downtime and optimizing maintenance efforts.

Evaluation

Content Relevance:

- Machinery Selection: The chosen machinery should be pertinent to the industrial setting and align with the scope of PM techniques and IoT integration.
- PM Techniques: The identified PM techniques should be well-suited for the selected machinery, showcasing a deep understanding of maintenance strategies.
- IoT Integration: The exploration of IoT devices should demonstrate a clear connection to the inspection and data collection needs of the machinery.

Evaluation Criteria:

- Clarity and Presentation: Information should be presented in a clear, organized, and engaging manner. Visuals, if used, should be helpful in understanding the content.
- Depth of Analysis: Participants should showcase a profound understanding of PM techniques and IoT integration, drawing connections between theory and practical application.
- Logical Flow and Cohesion: Ensure a logical flow in your exploration, allowing each step to build upon the previous one. The narrative should be cohesive.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this webquest has unveiled the dynamic fusion of Predictive Maintenance techniques and Internet of Things devices, showcasing their pivotal role in shaping the future of industrial machinery management. By selecting a specific machinery type, exploring PM techniques, and understanding how IoT devices can revolutionize inspection processes, participants have gained invaluable insights into the symbiotic relationship between intelligent maintenance strategies and cutting-edge technology.

The integration of PM techniques and IoT not only promises to enhance the reliability and longevity of machinery but also provides a proactive approach to maintenance, preventing unexpected downtimes and optimizing resource utilization. As industries embrace the era of Industry 4.0, this webquest serves as a stepping stone for participants to grasp the practical implications of these advancements in their specific industrial contexts.

Through this exploration, participants are not only equipped with knowledge about the latest trends in machinery management but are also encouraged to utilise project management and collaboration skills, envisioning the broader implications of Industry 4.0 in fostering a more efficient, sustainable, and technologically-driven industrial landscape.

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WN3: Green skills competences for PM
- WebQuest

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Introduction

The Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) framework is highlighted as a crucial tool for assessing companies' approaches to managing sustainability issues, emphasizing the absence of a universal ESG reporting standard and the pivotal role of quality departments in achieving ESG objectives. Measuring and reporting greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, particularly the challenges associated with Scope 3 emissions in manufacturing, is crucial to achieving Net Zero goals. Additionally, the evaluation and reduction of the impact of human activities on the environment are explored, emphasizing the role of environment-oriented software tools, such as life cycle assessment software.

This WebQuest is designed for participants to explore the principles of sustainability, environmental responsibility, and energy efficiency in manufacturing processes. Based on the training content received, their task will be to follow the steps outlined below to gain insights into the resource consumption elements, carbon footprint, and potential energy efficiency interventions for a chosen manufacturing process.

Task

Your task is to select a manufacturing process of your choice. It could be related to the production of a specific product or within a particular industry. Next, investigate and identify the key resource consumption elements within the chosen manufacturing process. Consider raw materials, energy inputs, and any other resources involved. Utilize Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology to calculate the carbon dioxide (CO₂) and greenhouse gas (GHG) impact of the selected manufacturing process. Consider the entire life cycle, from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal. After analysing this, research and identify potential energy efficiency interventions for the chosen manufacturing process. Look for technologies, practices, or innovations that can reduce resource consumption and environmental impact. Apply Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) to evaluate the environmental impact of the proposed energy efficiency interventions. Consider how these interventions may affect resource consumption, CO₂ emissions, and overall sustainability.

After doing these analyses compare the results obtained from the initial LCA of the manufacturing process and the LCA after incorporating the proposed energy efficiency interventions. Analyse the changes in resource consumption, CO₂ emissions, and GHG impact. Based on your findings, make recommendations for

sustainable improvements by creating a PPT presentation showcasing the results found.

Primarily refer to the materials available from this content, but here are also some additional links to assist with the task:

<https://www.sme.org>

<https://www.openlca.org/use-cases/#education>

https://stat.unido.org/?_ga=2.2768949.420349183.1701442992-2022726063.1701442992

<https://www.msci.com/our-solutions/indexes/climate-indexes>

<https://unfccc.int/climate-action/climate-neutral-now/measure-your-emissions>

Process

The process consists of several steps:

- 1: Choose a Manufacturing Process
- 2: Identify Resource Consumption Elements
- 3: Apply Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) for CO₂ and GHG Impact
- 4: Research Potential Energy Efficiency Interventions
- 5: Apply LCA on Proposed Interventions
- 6: Compare Results and Make Recommendations

Evaluation

Content Relevance:

- Process Selection: The chosen manufacturing process should align with the scope and purpose of the WebQuest.
- Identification of Resource Consumption Elements: The identified resource consumption elements must be crucial for understanding the environmental impact of the chosen manufacturing process.
- Application of LCA for CO₂ and GHG Impact: The application of Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) should effectively contribute to assessing the carbon footprint and greenhouse gas impact of the manufacturing process.

- **Research on Potential Energy Efficiency Interventions:** The researched energy efficiency interventions must be appropriate and directly related to mitigating environmental impact in the selected manufacturing process.
- **Application of LCA on Proposed Interventions:** The application of LCA on proposed interventions should provide meaningful insights into the potential environmental improvements.
- **Comparison of Results and Recommendations:** The comparison of results and subsequent recommendations should align with the overarching goal of enhancing sustainability in the manufacturing process.

Evaluation Criteria:

- **Clarity and Presentation:** Information should be presented in a clear, organized, and engaging manner. Visuals, if used, should be helpful in understanding the content.
- **Depth of Analysis:** Participants should demonstrate a deep understanding of the chosen manufacturing process and its environmental implications through thorough research and analysis.
- **Critical Thinking and Creativity:** Participants are expected to exhibit critical thinking and creativity in proposing and evaluating potential energy efficiency interventions.
- **Logical Flow and Cohesion:** There should be a logical flow in the participant's approach, ensuring that each step builds upon the previous one. The narrative should be cohesive.
- **In-depth Research:** Participants should have conducted in-depth research to support their findings, drawing from reputable sources and databases.
- **Insightful Recommendations:** Recommendations provided by participants should be well-founded and insightful, demonstrating a keen understanding of sustainability principles.

Conclusion

By exploring the life cycle of chosen manufacturing process and evaluating potential energy efficiency interventions, participants will have gained valuable insights into sustainability practices. Their recommendations will contribute to promoting environmentally responsible manufacturing practices.

Participants were assessed based on the quality and relevance of their content, adhering to the evaluation criteria. Emphasis was placed on the depth of

understanding, critical thinking, and the ability to communicate findings effectively.

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WN4: Resilience Competences for PM
- WebQuest

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Introduction

Welcome to the "Exploring Resilience in Predictive Maintenance" Webquest! In this quest, you will delve into the critical concept of resilience in maintenance operations, focusing on predictive maintenance techniques. Through a series of interactive activities and research tasks, you will gain a comprehensive understanding of how resilience principles can ensure the longevity, safety, and efficiency of industrial and transport equipment.

Task

Task: Understanding Resilience in Predictive Maintenance

Objective: Define the concept of resilience in the context of predictive maintenance and its importance in industrial operations. Find real-life examples of risks and create examples of how to mitigate them.

Process

1. Read the provided booklet on resilience in predictive maintenance.
2. Summarize the key components of resilience in maintenance operations.
3. Identify at least three examples of potential risks or issues that refer to Resilience in Predictive Maintenance. Ideally, those examples are taken from your real-world work environment.
4. For each of these examples, use one of the tools from chapter C of the Booklet and explain how this tool can help to contribute to the effectiveness of predictive maintenance and foster resilience.
5. mitigate the risks identified in the former point.
6. Visualize your work as an infographic. You may use any tool or software of your choice. Examples include www.canva.com, www.genial.ly, MS Power Point, etc.

Examples:

Example of Risk: Equipment Failure Due to Lack of Timely Maintenance

Selected Tool: Failure Mode and Effects Analysis (FMEA)

Explanation: FMEA helps in systematically evaluating potential failure modes of equipment, their effects, and causes. By conducting FMEA on critical assets, maintenance teams can prioritize maintenance tasks, allocate resources efficiently, and anticipate potential failures, thus reducing the likelihood of equipment failure and enhancing resilience.

Example of Risk: Inaccurate Predictive Maintenance Data Leading to Unplanned Downtime

Selected Tool: Root Cause Analysis (RCA)

Explanation: RCA helps in identifying the root causes of issues such as data inaccuracies. By systematically analyzing the causes of data inaccuracies, maintenance teams can implement corrective actions to improve data quality, enhance the reliability of predictive maintenance models, and minimize unplanned downtime, thereby strengthening resilience.

Example of Risk: Disruption of Supply Chain for Critical Spare Parts

Selected Tool: Supply Chain Risk Management (SCRM)

Explanation: SCRM enables organizations to identify, assess, and mitigate risks within their supply chains. By applying SCRM principles, maintenance teams can diversify suppliers, maintain strategic inventories of critical spare parts, and establish alternative sourcing options, thus reducing the vulnerability to supply chain disruptions and enhancing resilience in obtaining necessary parts for maintenance activities.

Evaluation

Your task will be evaluated based on:

Understanding of Resilience in Predictive Maintenance: The clarity and depth of the explanation of resilience concepts and their application in maintenance operations.

Identification of Risks: The relevance and realism of the identified risks, considering their potential impact on maintenance operations.

Selection and Explanation of Tools: The appropriateness of the selected tools from the provided booklet and the clarity of their explanations in addressing the identified risks.

Integration of Real-world Examples: The incorporation of real-world examples or experiences to illustrate the identified risks and proposed solutions, demonstrating practical understanding.

Overall Coherence and Structure: The overall coherence, structure, and flow of the presentation, ensuring that the analysis and solutions are logically connected and well-developed.

Conclusion

By engaging in this task, you have gained valuable insights into the importance of resilience in maintenance operations and how it contributes to the effectiveness of predictive maintenance techniques. Keep exploring and applying these principles to enhance maintenance practices and ensure the reliability and efficiency of industrial equipment.

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WN5: Innovation and Entrepreneurship
Competences for PM
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Introduction

Welcome to the WebQuest on Predictive Maintenance and Innovation! In this digital age, the fusion of predictive maintenance with cutting-edge technologies like AI, IoT, and digital twins is revolutionizing industries. This WebQuest will explore how innovation and entrepreneurship play pivotal roles in harnessing the power of predictive maintenance to ensure operational efficiency and sustainability across various sectors.

Task

Your mission is to develop a proposal for a predictive maintenance project that incorporates innovative technologies and entrepreneurial strategies. Your proposal should:

1. Identify a specific industry or sector where predictive maintenance can be applied.
2. Outline how innovative technologies (e.g., AI, IoT) can be utilized in your chosen sector for predictive maintenance.
3. Describe the entrepreneurial competences needed to implement and sustain the project.
4. Propose a marketing and branding strategy for your predictive maintenance solution.

Process

1. **Research:** Begin by exploring the concepts of predictive maintenance, focusing on its definition, importance, and the role of technological advancements.
2. **Innovation Exploration:** Investigate how AI, IoT, and digital twins are used in predictive maintenance. Select one technology to focus on for your project.
3. **Entrepreneurial Skills:** Identify the key entrepreneurial competences necessary for the successful implementation of a predictive maintenance project. Consider skills like opportunity recognition, risk management, and resource mobilization.
4. **Marketing Strategy:** Develop a basic marketing and branding strategy for your project. Consider your target audience and how you will communicate the benefits of your predictive maintenance solution.
5. **Collaboration:** Discuss your ideas with peers or mentors to refine your proposal.

Evaluation

Your project proposal will be evaluated based on:

- **Innovation:** How effectively does your project utilize innovative technologies in predictive maintenance?
- **Entrepreneurial Competence:** How well have you identified and planned to develop the necessary entrepreneurial skills?
- **Feasibility:** Is your marketing and branding strategy realistic and tailored to your target audience?
- **Clarity and Creativity:** How clear, organized, and creative is your proposal?

Conclusion

Reflect on how predictive maintenance, powered by innovation and entrepreneurship, can transform industries. Consider the potential impact of your project on operational efficiency, cost savings, and sustainability.

References

Dodge, B. (1995). Some Thoughts About WebQuests. San Diego State University.

March, T. (2003). The Learning Power of WebQuests, Educational Leadership.

Industry 4.0 and Predictive Maintenance Reports and Articles (Specific articles and reports from reputable sources like IEEE Xplore, McKinsey & Company, Deloitte Insights, etc.)

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WN6: Relearning How to Learn in a digital environment
- WebQuest

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A. Introduction

This WebQuest aims to empower students to explore tailored approaches to enhancing learning environments. Students will delve into the significance of various learning environments, select appropriate strategies, and understand methods for optimising educational settings. Additionally, they will investigate challenges and solutions associated with creating and improving these environments.

Tasks:

- Research the evolution of learning environments.
- Compare traditional and modern learning settings.
- Discuss the impact of technology on learning spaces.

WebQuest Resources:

- Classroom Design Strategies - Edutopia. (2023). The Science of Classroom Design. Retrieved from Edutopia; Edutopia. (2015). A Place for Learning: The Physical Environment of Classrooms. Retrieved from Edutopia
- Virtual Learning Best Practices - EdSurge. (2020). The Guide to Remote Teaching and Learning. Retrieved from EdSurge
- Hybrid Learning Models - TeachThought. (2018). Blended & Flipped Learning Primer. Retrieved from TeachThought
- Inclusive Education Resources - CAST. (2021). Universal Design for Learning (UDL). Retrieved from CAST
- Educational Technology Tools - Common Sense Education. (2022). Best EdTech Tools for the Classroom. Retrieved from Common Sense Education
- Learn about machine learning applications by watching "[Predictive Maintenance: Unsupervised and Supervised Machine Learning](#)" and "[Predictive Maintenance with MATLAB - A Prognostics Case Study](#)".
- Explore the use of deep learning in predictive maintenance through "[Predictive Maintenance Using Deep Learning](#)".
- Understand the basics of digital twins from "[What is a Digital Twin?](#)" and delve deeper into their application in predictive maintenance with "[Predictive Digital Twins: From physics-based modelling to scientific machine learning](#)".
- Watch "[#IOTSWC23 Digital Twins and IoT Integrating the Physical and Virtual Worlds](#)" to see how IoT technologies enhance predictive maintenance.

These references provide valuable insights and practical advice on designing effective and engaging learning environments, both physical and virtual. They cover a wide range of topics including classroom layout, virtual learning best

practices, hybrid models, inclusive education strategies, and the integration of educational technology.

B. Task

The task involves applying knowledge gained through the module's materials. And similar case studies that can be found on the Internet.

Scope:

- Select and analyse different types of learning environments.
- Justify the reasons for implementing specific learning environment strategies.
- Access historical or statistical data.
- Investigate and analyse challenges and solutions in areas such as Physical Spaces, Virtual Learning, Hybrid Models, Inclusive Environments, and Technological Integration.

C. Process

Step 1: Environment and Strategy Selection

Select Environment: Choose a type of learning environment. Consider physical classrooms, virtual learning spaces, hybrid models, etc. Maintenance and resource demands vary per environment, considering accessibility and technological support.

Select Specific Strategy: Identify a specific strategy within the chosen environment. Consider factors such as student engagement, accessibility, and resource availability. Briefly explain your selection.

Implement Learning Environment Strategies: Explain the benefits of implementing specific strategies. Compare with traditional learning methods. Include examples or case studies where strategies have been successfully implemented.

Select Tools and Resources: Choose suitable tools and resources for the selected strategy. Justify choices with relevant literature and educational standards.

Find Historical and Statistical Data: Search for data related to the effectiveness of learning environments. Analyse available data to understand the impact on

student learning and engagement. Discuss how this data aids in developing effective learning strategies.

Step 2: Research and Analysis

Research: Utilise various sources, including provided documents, external links, books, articles, and online resources.

Analysis: Identify key issues, potential solutions, and implications for learning environments.

Documentation: Document findings, analyses, and proposed solutions in various formats such as reports, presentations, or infographics.

Reflection: Reflect on learnings and insights, encouraging critical thinking and exploration of connections between different challenges.

Research Areas:

- **Physical Spaces:** Optimise classroom layout and resource allocation.
- **Virtual Learning:** Enhance engagement and accessibility in online learning environments.
- **Hybrid Models:** Integrate physical and virtual learning seamlessly.
- **Inclusive Environments:** Create learning spaces that accommodate diverse needs.
- **Technological Integration:** Implement and manage educational technologies effectively.

D. Evaluation

Evaluation Criteria:

1. Information should be presented in a clear, organised, and engaging manner.
2. Demonstrate a deep understanding of the chosen environment and its implications through thorough research and analysis.
3. Exhibit critical thinking in the selection of strategies and tools.
4. Ensure a logical flow in your approach, building upon each step coherently.

5. Conduct in-depth research to support findings, drawing from reputable sources and databases.
6. Clearly articulate key theories, principles, and implications relevant to the challenge.
7. Structure and organise documentation effectively, communicating key findings and recommendations clearly.
8. Propose feasible and effective solutions, aligned with best practices and educational standards.
9. Reflect critically on the learning experience, identifying insights gained and areas for improvement.
10. Demonstrate creativity and innovation in approaching the challenge and proposing solutions.

E. Conclusion

Participating in this WebQuest offers students an invaluable opportunity to explore the multifaceted nature of learning environments.

Through comprehensive research and critical analysis, students will uncover the challenges and solutions inherent in optimising physical spaces, enhancing virtual learning, integrating hybrid models, fostering inclusive environments, and effectively utilising technology in education.

This experience aims not only to deepen students' understanding of these educational concepts but also to sharpen their research, analytical, and communication skills.

We are confident that this WebQuest will inspire a more profound appreciation of the intricacies involved in creating effective learning environments and equip students with the tools needed for innovative educational practices.

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- Interactive learner-persona based simulator as assessment tool**
- **Multiple choice questions for modules: WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6**

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Module WN1: Holistic PM competences

Question n°	Question
1	What is the role of sensing technologies in Predictive Maintenance?
2	How does Time Management System (TMS) enhance Predictive Maintenance?
3	Which maintenance strategy is characterized by the monitoring of mechanical conditions to prevent failures?
4	What is one key advantage of Predictive Maintenance over Reactive Maintenance?
5	What does the concept of Remaining Useful Life (RUL) signify in the context of Predictive Maintenance?
6	Which of the following best describes the application of sensing technologies in PDM?
7	What is the primary goal of a Time Management System (TMS) in the context of PDM?
8	What distinguishes Predictive Maintenance from Preventive Maintenance?
9	How do Reporting Models contribute to Predictive Maintenance?
10	What does the calculation of Remaining Useful Life (RUL) influence in Predictive Maintenance?
11	In the context of Industry 4.0, what role do smart sensors play in Predictive Maintenance?
12	Which of the following is a challenge associated with the implementation of predictive maintenance?
13	What is the impact of e-maintenance systems in the realm of PDM?
14	How do vibration sensors contribute to fault diagnosis in predictive maintenance?
15	What is one of the benefits of TPM (Total Productive Maintenance) as a part of maintenance strategies?
16	Which type of maintenance is traditionally seen as a cost driver in the production industry?
17	What does the "bathtub curve" in maintenance methodologies represent?
18	In Predictive Maintenance, what is the purpose of using machine learning algorithms in the context of RUL?
19	Which of these is a primary challenge in the integration of sensors for Predictive Maintenance within Industry 4.0?
20	What is the main advantage of using ultrasonic sensors in Predictive Maintenance?

21	How do decentralized smart industry systems contribute to Predictive Maintenance in Industry 4.0?
22	What is a key feature of e-maintenance systems in the context of Industry 4.0?
23	What is the impact of the Digital Twin concept on the development of a Time Management System (TMS) for Predictive Maintenance?
24	Why is continuous validation important in Predictive Maintenance systems?
25	What is the primary benefit of incorporating Machine Learning (ML) into Predictive Maintenance systems?
26	What are the key components of an effective reporting model for construction project management?
27	How can reporting models be adapted to ensure compliance with evolving safety regulations in the construction industry?
28	What are the most common non-destructive testing (NDT) methods used for structural assessment in construction?
29	How has the integration of BIM (Building Information Modeling) technology impacted structural assessment methods?
30	What role do forecasting systems play in the planning and execution of large-scale transportation projects?
31	Can you explain how remote infrastructure management systems contribute to the efficiency of transport logistics?
32	What are the challenges faced in implementing remote infrastructure management systems in existing transportation networks?
33	What are the benefits and drawbacks of using AI-based predictive maintenance in the construction and transport industries?
34	How has the COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the need for remote infrastructure management solutions in construction and transport sectors?

Module WN2: Digital skills competences for PM

Question n°	Question
1	Collection of temperature and pressure data catagorizes as:
2	Collection of data about physical location catagorizes as:
3	Sensor readings stored in the database is
4	XML documents are:
5	Video recordings are:
6	Data cleaning in the data transformation process involves:
7	Which of the following best defines a digital twin?
8	How are digital twins used in industrial manufacturing enterprises?
9	Benefits of virtual reality (VR) in maintenance include:
10	How are drones, robotics, and exoskeleton technology primarily utilized in maintenance tasks?
11	IoT devices use sensor to:
12	IoT devices use actuators to:
13	Predictive maintenance uses:
14	In the context of predictive maintenance, what technology is utilized to capture conditions of machines and equipment and enable intelligent actions through machine learning?
15	What is the primary goal of Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM)?
16	What role does Predictive Analytics play in Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM)?
17	How does Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM) differ from Predictive Maintenance (PM)?
18	What is a key element in Condition-Based Maintenance (CBM) that involves the establishment of a normal operating condition for each piece of equipment?
19	What is the primary purpose of Vibration Monitoring in predictive maintenance?
20	Which method in Visual Inspection involves using ultraviolet (UV) light to reveal fluorescent indications of issues such as leaks or contamination?
21	What is a limitation of ultrasonics in the context of predictive maintenance, as mentioned in the text?
22	Which of the following is a characteristic of Knowledge-Based Models in fault prediction for predictive maintenance?
23	What does the Data-Based Models approach in fault prediction primarily use to predict failures in the current state?
24	What is the primary function of Rule-Based Systems in predictive maintenance?

25	How does Knowledge Representation contribute to decision-making in predictive maintenance?
26	What is the primary objective of supervised learning in the context of machine learning?
27	What is the biggest challenge when implementing Machine Learning (ML) in Predictive Maintenance (PM) applications?
28	What is the purpose of Survival Models in the context of predictive maintenance?
29	What role does anomaly detection play in predictive maintenance, and what are the challenges associated with evaluating anomaly detection models?
30	What are some commonly used models for predicting remaining useful lifetime (RUL), and what metrics are used to evaluate the performance of regression models in predictive maintenance?
31	Predictive maintenance systems often operate in which type of networks?
32	Incorporating cybersecurity into predictive maintenance reaches what overall goal?
33	Which task is imperative in order to comply with security measures?
34	Which major cybersecurity tasks are included to be in line with regulatory compliances?
35	Regulatory compliance can be achieved in what manner?
36	What unique information does each blockchain transaction hold?
37	A block within the blockchain can be viewed as?
38	In terms of node structure, a blockchain can be viewed as?
39	Technology-wise, a blockchain is?
40	What are smart contracts?
41	Trello is a visual project management software that uses what kind of tools?
42	Which software is a computerized maintenance system?
43	Which software is an enterprise level asset management solution?

Module WN3: Green skills competences for PM

Question n°	Question
1	What does the Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) framework help investors assess?
2	What is the primary focus of ESG reporting?
3	What is the purpose of ESG compliance?
4	What do ESG metrics assess?
5	What does an ESG rating or score serve as?
6	What is greenwashing in the context of ESG reporting?
7	What is suggested as a top priority in Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) reports due to the urgency of climate change?
8	How can customers' willingness to pay for products with reduced GHG emissions be inferred?
9	What does Scope 2 of the Greenhouse Gas Protocol involve?
10	What poses the greatest challenge in terms of reliable and comparable measurement across different companies and over time?
11	What innovative method was introduced in a study by Razali et al. in 2015 to address the environmental challenge posed by the membrane fabrication process?
12	What is suggested as a potential solution for manufacturing companies grappling with measurement challenges in their GHG reporting frameworks?
13	What is the main objective of evaluating products, services, processes, and larger-scale endeavors across various environmental indicators?
14	What is the fundamental component of a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)?
15	What does the Tiered hybrid Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) method involve?
16	How does the Path Exchange (PXC) hybrid Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) method work?
17	What is one of the factors that impedes the widespread adoption of hybrid Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) methods?
18	Why is it recommended to adopt a consistent framework for classifying and defining hybrid Life Cycle Inventory (LCI) methods?
19	What is a significant challenge confronting present-day industries, considering the depletion of non-renewable resources and increasing environmental awareness?
20	What are additional incentives for industries to transition to environmentally friendly manufacturing solutions, beyond regulatory standards?

21	What is an example of an environment-oriented software tool mentioned in the text?
22	What role do evaluation and surveillance of energy and resource efficiency play in sustainable manufacturing practices?
23	What is the purpose of Resources Value Mapping mentioned in the text?
24	According to the text, how can energy efficiency be enhanced without compromising productivity in manufacturing?
25	What distinguishes technologies associated with renewable energy in terms of carbon emissions?
26	How are clean energy sources defined in the text?
27	What term is used to describe less polluting forms of energy, recognizing that no energy source is completely pristine?
28	What role did wind, solar, hydrothermal, hydrogen, and biomass-based energy systems play during the sudden onset of COVID-19?
29	What is the term used to describe the energy flexibility control of manufacturing systems in the context of variable renewable energy (VRE)?
30	What is a primary choice for renewable energy in manufacturing due to its versatility and substitution potential?

Module WN4: Resilience competences for PM

Question n°	Question
1	What does adaptability entail in the context of predictive maintenance?
2	Which skill is crucial for promptly diagnosing issues within transportation equipment or infrastructure?
3	What is the primary benefit of maintaining composure and focus under high-pressure situations in maintenance tasks?
4	Which skill involves evaluating potential risks associated with equipment failure or infrastructure issues?
5	What does resourcefulness entail in maintenance operations?
6	Which skill involves a meticulous approach to inspections and identifying even minor abnormalities?
7	What is essential for adhering to maintenance schedules and ensuring timely completion of tasks?
8	Which skill involves clear and concise communication with all stakeholders in the maintenance process?
9	What is crucial for staying updated with the latest technological advancements and industry best practices in maintenance?
10	Which skill involves adjusting to changing priorities or unexpected situations in maintenance tasks?
11	Which platform is known for its risk evaluation capabilities, particularly using the bowtie method?
12	What is essential for effective risk management in maintenance operations?
13	Which tool is specifically designed for process hazard analysis, including Hazard and Operability Study (HAZOP)?
14	What is crucial for developing effective mitigation strategies in maintenance operations?
15	What is a critical aspect of monitoring and reviewing mitigation strategies in maintenance operations?
16	What is a crucial aspect of developing mitigation strategies for high-priority risks?
17	In the context of staff training, what does "continuous learning" refer to?
18	What is the primary objective of stakeholder involvement in risk assessment?
19	What is a key benefit of using Microsoft Teams for stakeholder involvement?

20	How does structured documentation contribute to effective risk assessment?
21	What is the purpose of version control in documentation?
22	What is a key advantage of utilizing IoT devices for real-time monitoring in maintenance operations?
23	How does continuous training contribute to resilience in maintenance operations?
24	What is the primary purpose of regular review and improvement in maintenance processes?
25	How does effective documentation support resilience in maintenance operations?
26	What aspect of maintenance does Dude Solutions Maintenance Edge focus on?
27	What emerging technology is expected to play an increasingly important role in predictive maintenance?
28	Which strategy is recommended for organizations to meet future needs in predictive maintenance?
29	What will be a priority in predictive maintenance, requiring competence in environmentally friendly technologies?
30	Which technology will connect multiple devices and systems, generating massive amounts of data for predictive maintenance?

Module WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM

Question n°	Question
1	When did the concept of Predictive Maintenance emerge?
2	What distinguishes predictive maintenance from traditional maintenance approaches?
3	What is one major benefit of predictive maintenance over traditional maintenance?
4	What is a significant challenge in adopting predictive maintenance?
5	How does AI contribute to predictive maintenance?
6	What role does the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) play in predictive maintenance?
7	In predictive maintenance, what does machine learning primarily focus on?
8	What is an entrepreneurial mindset in the context of predictive maintenance?
9	What is adaptive thinking important for in predictive maintenance?
10	Which marketing approach is crucial for predictive maintenance services?
11	What is a key element of branding in predictive maintenance?
12	What is a primary target in marketing predictive maintenance solutions?
13	How does predictive maintenance contribute to sustainability?
14	What is a critical skill for market analysis in predictive maintenance?
15	What does SWOT analysis in predictive maintenance involve?
16	What is a benefit of leveraging IoT and data science in predictive maintenance?
17	What is an advantage of implementing predictive maintenance for businesses?
18	What is the main barrier of implementing predictive maintenance in companies?
19	TBM or time-based maintenance is called
20	What is the difference between preventive and predictive maintenance?
21	How many elements did W.Tiddens, T. Tinga and J. Braaksma proposed to support effective maintenance techniques (MT)-based decision-making?
22	What are the elements proposed by W.Tiddens, T. Tinga and J. Braaksma to support effective maintenance techniques (MT)-based decision-making?

23	The PReMMA model can help companies to:
24	Predictive Maintenance:
25	A creativity technique to create a free and open environment that encourages everyone's participation and makes it possible for all team members to share their knowledge and creativity is:
26	Contemporary tools and technologies:
27	A tool that can automate repetitive tasks, allowing for more innovative changes with the elimination of routine work is:
28	Predictive maintenance based on continuous and ongoing monitoring of machines:
29	There are benefits to implementing predictive maintenance systems:
30	The most effective approach to maintenance in pneumatics would be to use a strategy:
31	The benefits of introducing predictive maintenance include:
32	According to Deloitte, companies that have invested in predictive maintenance have seen cost reductions of:
33	In the field of marketing, comprehensive technology support provides:

Module WN6: Re-learning how to learn in a digital environment

Question n°	Question
1	What is a key aspect of online learning?
2	What is a characteristic feature of asynchronous online learning?
3	Which of the following is an example of asynchronous learning in the corporate sector?
4	What is one advantage of recorded sessions in asynchronous learning environments?
5	What is a key characteristic of Synchronous Online Learning (SOL)?
6	What is a key characteristic of a Personal Learning Environment (PLE) in the context of predictive maintenance?
7	Which component of a PLE for predictive maintenance provides opportunities for knowledge exchange, mentorship, and collaboration with peers and experts?
8	What is the VARK model primarily used for?
9	Which learning preference involves learning best through listening?
10	What does the VARK model suggest for visual learners to enhance their learning experience?
11	What is predictive maintenance (PM) in engineering primarily focused on?
12	How might a professional seminar on predictive maintenance engage auditory learners?
13	Which of the following visual learning strategies involves the use of detailed illustrations to depict scientific phenomena or engineering mechanisms?
14	What type of learner benefits from engaging in verbal interactions and listening to explanations to grasp complex subjects?
15	How can read/write learners reinforce their understanding and retention of study materials?
16	Which learning style involves hands-on experiences and direct engagement with the material world?
17	Which strategy can help kinesthetic learners maintain focus and absorb information?
18	What is the purpose of the Pedagogical Framework?
19	What is the primary emphasis of the Constructivist Learning Theory?
20	According to Bada and Olusegun, what is the role of teachers in a constructivist learning environment?

21	What is the primary focus of Technology-Enhanced Learning (TEL)?
22	What is the primary characteristic of the Flipped Classroom Model?
23	What is a key characteristic of Problem-Based Learning (PBL)?
24	What distinguishes Competency-Based Education (CBE) from traditional time-based learning?
25	What is a key benefit of implementing collaborative learning in engineering education, according to the research by Ralston, Tretter, and Brown (2017)?
26	Which of the following best describes the essence of experiential learning?
27	Which educational approach involves the use of Six Thinking Hats, a method introduced by Edward de Bono in 1985, to guide users in adopting different perspectives towards problem-solving and creative thinking?
28	Which learning strategy allows learners to actively engage with new material by organizing what they already know, what they want to know, and what they have learned?
29	Which model is used as a tool to develop self-awareness and mutual understanding by dividing information into four areas, including the open or free area, facade or hidden area, blind spot, and unknown area?
30	Which method involves individuals evaluating the performance, contributions, or skills of their peers within a group or team, offering a more holistic assessment and incorporating insights from various perspectives?

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Collection of demonstrative videos for modules:
WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6

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Module WN1: Holistic PM Competences

Video n°	Title	Video Link
1	Estimating Remaining Useful Life (RUL) Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Dd_4rbWYgI4
2	What is Predictive Maintenance?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mveN-1r7XiA
3	Identifying Condition Indicators Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pcXr8I2QvHw
4	Estimation of Remaining Useful Life: Very Short Explanation	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Z_F6bnK5iBY
5	Getting Started with Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RmVWKLbLq2Y
6	What is Predictive Maintenance ?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2V38jVkJQ0r4
7	Predictive Maintenance - An Approach to find the Remaining Useful Lifetime Insight Hub	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JVivCQ_IUtQ
8	Ultrasonic Testing	https://www.youtube.com/embed/UM6XKvXWVFA?feature=oembed
9	Magnetic Particle Inspection	https://www.youtube.com/embed/qpgcD5k1494?feature=oembed
10	Dye Penetrant Inspection	https://www.youtube.com/embed/xEK-c1pkTUI?feature=oembed
11	X-ray Inspection and Industrial Computed Tomography	https://www.youtube.com/embed/lcWjZbXiFkM?feature=oembed
12	Eddy Current Testing	https://www.youtube.com/embed/oriFJBYl6Hs?feature=oembed
13	Predictive Maintenance Best Practices Presented by Fluke	https://youtu.be/2tOeYGGaRNI?si=us6LFDlByNtGTNYa
14	Predictive Maintenance Explained	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2_oISDy6_U
15	Predictive Maintenance in Arctic Shipping	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AQKLZa7ZQIM
16	Predictive Maintenance in Aerospace Industry Turbofan Engine Machine Learning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RsMtVutAvY
17	Condition monitoring in centrifugal pumps: 3 fault detections [Case studies]	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sA3AjcRHCj8
18	An Introduction to Asset Management	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=JUmdVYQ-0Aw

19	Predictive Maintenance: Unsupervised and Supervised Machine Learning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AS0H43hMoWM
20	IoT based Predictive Maintenance Solution	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=uVpUlsMTszg
21	Moving from Reactive Maintenance to Predictive Maintenance with SAP's Intelligent Asset management	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=yUUFc0Tw7iE
22	Best Practices Webinar: 6 Steps to Effective Planning & Scheduling	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6_tOHHYEzak
23	Predictive Maintenance Using Deep Learning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=InMlOMcUzM4
24	Feature Extraction Using Diagnostic Feature Designer Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oDd7aEmRNpl

Module WN2: Digital skills competences for PM

Video n°	Title	Video Link
1	Predictive Maintenance Explained	https://youtu.be/2_o1SDy6_U?si=z3OxMZH30aeL5Bnu
2	The concept of predictive maintenance explained What The Tech?!	https://youtu.be/u0apbsPeDWM?si=t02_63CJO2oPlmOw
3	Industry 4.0: Predictive Maintenance with a Digital Twin	https://youtu.be/g7dDISUb6oo?si=LalIHssE-cNSbrcp
4	Drones – The Key to the Future of Predictive Maintenance of Powerline Assets	https://youtu.be/4gDwwabpKfU?si=MGUp_ehbMZRqqcMzT
5	Predictive Maintenance and Cybersecurity	https://youtu.be/qVK_gCnakpl?si=xNPVVLbXbe9vpdrs
6	Predictive Maintenance Using IoT (Internet of Things)	https://youtu.be/EXEd71jq3uE?si=vrBgvAxzPelDYX9S
7	Smart maintenance through AI and robotics	https://youtu.be/c9xOix-SsGY?si=Lv9AWlpk2ORHbTnt
8	Improving your Predictive Maintenance with Artificial Intelligence	https://youtu.be/O3YKaEAHW7g?si=943tcskp0EUEyUiK
9	Predictive Maintenance and More: How to Use Machine Learning Without Being a Data Scientist	https://youtu.be/zXcp2HvpJLE?si=Qsa1wl6q_S3oXOLp
10	Predictive Maintenance: Unsupervised and Supervised Machine Learning	https://youtu.be/ASOH43hMoWM?si=dP2K92c0vNqJM9Am
11	Predictive Maintenance & Monitoring using Machine Learning: Demo & Case study (Cloud Next '18)	https://youtu.be/4wneZDEB3VA?si=Ly32YZ1zA7kHljq
12	Identifying Condition Indicators Predictive Maintenance	https://youtu.be/pcXr8l2QvHw?si=97vxDDKbUbhrN3ir
13	What is predictive maintenance on electric motors - low power motors	https://youtu.be/cFIY6LligKY?si=vmm_vzHXdXrLZDhN
14	Smart Sensors for Predictive Maintenance	https://youtu.be/l3x8lqXYFI4?si=UbziSRfZs7siueLT
15	Vibration Analysis for beginners 1 (Predictive Maintenance and vibration explanation. How it works?)	https://youtu.be/BPMjYJ_HoWk?si=0k7Zw2Kqc5wsQKlp
16	Data Science Ethics in 6 Minutes	https://youtu.be/mA4gypAiRYU?si=k1y5LIV7GdQ822DB

17	Model-Based Design for Predictive Maintenance: Series Introduction	https://youtu.be/8k-cmf3uUyI?si=UpvzsCG1_QZ3xBAK
18	What is project management?	https://youtu.be/Jk-JwtScIIw?si=FmI92mj93IHZjvyE
19	Top 10 Project Management Tools 2023 Project Management Tools and Techniques Simplilearn	https://youtu.be/RmKIRxtBInA?si=GOUgRZi_vRgNJ_Kg
20	Project Implementation Plan: Project DPro (PMD Pro)	https://youtu.be/WIIbsmckuzU?si=jvj56PO2W-IRINHe
21	Predictive Maintenance Through Thermal Imaging Camera (Thermography for beginners)	https://youtu.be/bhpOxv0yin4?si=LQLHZ-RjwxQTK9I4
22	Ultrasonic Instrument for Reliability and Predictive Maintenance	https://youtu.be/Aqe0i7KA4Ac?si=prTAAk7SfH81ZIV-
23	Tribology – The Science of Friction and Lubrication	https://youtu.be/GvoqKkTI-2w?si=Dje2HF-Cv3wUshNI

Module WN3: Green skills competences for PM

Video n°	Title	Video Link
1	How can we green skills for a just transition? – ILO	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=MxIOeqOukCw
2	How to optimize marine maintenance? Webinar Wärtsilä	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jhPagN0dYoU
3	Operations and Maintenance in the Offshore Renewables Sector	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7jLRusOcljk
4	Should maritime industry have proactive safety alerting? Digital Ship webinar with Peter Broadhurst	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BXh97FOsb6Y
5	Maritime Skills Commission: Green Skills Forum	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-rttEZJfvIw
6	More effective maintenance planning to ensure compliance with rest hours	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=jKAL_FwC_fg
7	Pt. 4 - Maritime Shipping - Predictive Maintenance Stack Demo	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=lrUJm0wYV0
8	Vessel machinery predictive maintenance.	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0pjWov7SVzo
9	Predictive maintenance & AI in manufacturing	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9VHU SpqFtyA
10	Develop an Effective Predictive Maintenance Program - MaintenanceCon 2019	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KxOSjG94xp4
11	What is Predictive Maintenance? - Decoding Condition-Based Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6hhx-X8azoM
12	Inject some predictive maintenance to your engines	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8QLGy9OGkZk
13	Workiva, What is ESG?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EedXi7KTQNE
14	Constellation, Sustainability 101: ESG Reporting	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OT3gsCbCKdl
15	Plan A, ESG Fundamentals (Webinar by Plan A)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dK_YUGrCd3l
16	Corporate Finance Institute, Environmental, Social and Governance (ESG) Overview and Framework	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AkbGz3CYvqE

17	Bloomberg Quicktake, Getting to Zero Emissions in The Steel Industry	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qhBZl_wunTRM
18	Bill Gates, This tool will help us get to zero emissions	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2bXn2F58OsM
19	Karen Scrivener, A concrete idea to reduce CO2 emissions	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f9618uQlZmc
20	The Sustainability Speaker - Susanna Hasenoehrl, Corporate Carbon Footprint - Understanding Scope 1, 2 and 3 Greenhouse Gas (GHG) Emissions	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nWxly5ej25M
21	UNSW eLearning, Hybrid Life Cycle Assessment	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vCexmy69A-E
22	Parallel Project Training, Linear, Iterative and Hybrid lifecycles	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=r3xCtj-E0lc
23	Life Cycle Thinking & Environmental Management, Life cycle assessment (LCA) of hybrid car	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=X5YRJMXv6ZY
24	GetxInstitute, Selecting hybrid life cycle. A story understood with Agile Suitability Model	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=iDj--kaRqMU
25	United Nations ESCAP, Resource Efficiency & Sustainable Development	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kC3VTg-8f0s
26	International Resource Panel, How can Resource Efficiency contribute to the fight against climate change?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qQAX2lc3tGs
27	Emerson's Automation Technologies & Solutions, Making Resource Efficiency Strategic	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=C00Jrl4Zlpl
28	Hui Mien Lee, Driving resource efficiency through circular business model, TEDxDonauinselSalon	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=sIClPM3dnns
29	Vaitea Cowan, How Green Hydrogen Could End The Fossil Fuel Era, TED	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9OLxBvLvCoM
30	National Geographic, Renewable Energy 101	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=1kUE0BZtTRc
31	The Economist, Green energy: Which sources are the most sustainable?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ms--0d7Oh0s
32	Federico Rosei and Renzo Rosei, Can 100% renewable energy power the world?, Ted-Ed	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RnvCbquYeIM

Module WN4: Resilience competences for PM

Video n°	Title	Video Link
1	Introduction to Resilience in Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mveN-lr7XiA
2	Human Safety Systems in Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0Sc3VBsvFHW
3	Risk Assessment Tools for Proactive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=whbfvjg-y24
4	Structural Assessment in Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gYJoYUOjw2Q
5	Mitigation Strategies for Potential Failures	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=t0qbZGMuZgY
6	Forecasting Tools for Predictive Analysis	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LrGOTOdou2s
7	Efficient Recovery Planning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c2WRVclyFcq
8	Think Fast, Talk Smart: Communication Techniques	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HANw168huqA
9	Artificial Intelligence for Predictive Maintenance Case Study - Blair Fraser, Lakeside	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=c9fEnbNgn-E
10	Practical Machine Learning for Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9jPxWzrbLLI
11	Case Study: How a Large Brewery Uses Machine Learning for Preventive Maintenance (Cloud Next '18)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-D9Z2Ka9Q5E
12	NASA IoT - Different Ways to Model Predictive Maintenance and Engine Degradation	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4GBO2GNmEzk
13	Predictive Maintenance and More: How to Use Machine Learning Without Being a Data Scientist	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zXcp2HvpJLE
14	Predictive Maintenance Using Deep Learning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=InMIOMcUzM4
15	Predictive Maintenance with MATLAB A Prognostics Case Study	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9QUM5jtB0t4
16	An Animated Introduction to Vibration Analysis by Mobius Institute	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VjIxmze3GIE
17	ChatGPT for Data Science & Machine Learning: 5 Use Cases	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Bw7pAYv6iaM

18	TensorFlow, Deep Learning, and Modern Convolutional Neural Nets, Without a PhD (Cloud Next '18)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KC4201o83W0
19	Forecasting Stock Returns with TensorFlow, Cloud ML Engine, and Thomson Reuters	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VAkLSLuJCgc
20	Predictive Maintenance & Monitoring using Machine Learning: Demo & Case study (Cloud Next '18)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4wneZDEB3VA

Module WN5: Innovation & entrepreneurship competences for PM

Video n°	Title	Video Link
1	What is Predictive Maintenance (PM) - How to implement it	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A9VOMPROR48
2	Getting Started with Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RmVWKLbLq2Y
3	Predictive Maintenance 101: Transforming Your Factory Maintenance Strategy	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EXmcYJta70g
4	AI-Based Predictive Maintenance in 4 Steps	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=PngqgzJaSz8
5	Predictive maintenance solutions through advanced analytics	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YxCU3x-bJIA
6	Smart Data Analytics: BMW Group relies on intelligent use of production data	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SUlcf2U6pu4
7	AI for Predictive Maintenance seminar series	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=oAnNvbGTQFQ
8	Creative Thinking: How to Increase the Dots to Connect	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cYhgllTy4yY
9	Everyone Can Be Creative	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tTjETjGDFY
10	What is Creative Problem Solving (CPS) Process?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dtBBxCRIlnE
11	Effective Brainstorming	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=HRWt1rBG10o
12	OMRON Tech talks series: AI as new trend in Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=br6xBHb4YTc
13	Predictive Maintenance Explained	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2_o1SDy6__U
14	What is Predictive Maintenance? Explainer	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=94664TLwLqM
15	Fundamentals of Innovation	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-WQmMNG37tA
16	Introduction to Innovation Innovation and Entrepreneurship SkillUp	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=rLA-vVLNvws
17	What is Predictive Maintenance? - Decoding Condition-Based Maintenance	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6hhx-X8azoM

18	Branding Basics, Brand Strategy, Understanding Branding Fundamentals, Brand Marketing, Simplilearn	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LwrGSKnShmk
19	Learn Brand Strategy In 17 Minutes	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VrwBu8DYWkE
20	The Key to Finding a Profitable Market	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=LqC-oXjatmA
21	Understanding the Market and Identifying Opportunities	http://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GritZlyJoGO

Module WN6: Re-learning how to learn in a digital environment

Video n°	Title	Video Link
1	What is Predictive Maintenance?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=mveN-1r7XiA
2	Predictive Maintenance Explained	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2_o1SDy6_U
3	Predictive Maintenance: Unsupervised and Supervised Machine Learning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ASOH43hMoWM
4	Predictive Maintenance with MATLAB	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9QUM5jtB0t4
5	Predictive Maintenance Using Deep Learning	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=InMIOMcUzM4
6	Estimating Remaining Useful Life (RUL) Predictive Maintenance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Dd_4rbWYgl4
7	Predictive Maintenance with Machine Learning on AWS	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8V9OpBoiBCg
8	What is a Digital Twin?	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=cfbKR48nSyQ
9	Predictive Digital Twins: From physics-based modelling to scientific machine learning, by Prof. Willcox	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZuSx0pYAZ_I
10	Digital Twins and IoT Integrating the Physical and Virtual Worlds	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ZMMzTrPPTeY
11	Minds + Machines: Meet A Digital Twin	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2dCz3oL2rTw
12	Three Steps to Mastering Maintenance and Reliability	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=gnFlrk39TOg
13	Understanding Vibration and Resonance	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vLaFAKnaRJu
14	Webinar VOD An Introduction to Vibration Analysis	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TkExfl4Vm_4
15	Best Practices Webinar: 6 Steps to Effective Planning & Scheduling	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6_tOHHYEzak
16	Predictive Maintenance & Monitoring using Machine Learning: Demo & Case study (Cloud Next '18)	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=4wneZDEB3VA
17	Bloom's Framework	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=NjOa6l4GFJA

18	360 Feedback #1: Overview	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EPWmUdIXQMU
19	360 Feedback #2: Respondents	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0IP7dpU4w4k
20	360 Degree Feedback Process	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TJSwNaWEq5s

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**Funded by
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PreMETS

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Presentation slides for modules:
WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6

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Presentation slides containing educational material for modules WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6, can be found in the project repository using the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1A3j3gljNY0uGfW8QCN6wrNYTt9D5Yk3?usp=drive_link

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Videos of presentation slides with voice overlay for modules: WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6

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Videos of presentation slides with voice overlay, containing educational material for modules WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6, can be found in the project repository using the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1XE4L2QdB1wnNIVhHyEQclKHLvQJZr6uE?usp=drive_link

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Storyboards for modules:
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Storyboards containing educational material, outlining modules WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6, can be found in the project repository using the following link:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1A3j3gljNY0uGfW8QCN6wrNYTt9D5Yk3?usp=drive_link

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Language translations of educational material for modules:

WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6

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Educational material for modules WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6, in **Romanian** can be found in the project repository using the following link:
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1QxWXrrx2F_09eCMIBDP_C8pJePj-A222?usp=drive_link

Educational material for modules WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6, in **Greek** can be found in the project repository using the following link:
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1S_6-Tmx7myM2SGvglrJFUGSisS8i4qT-?usp=drive_link

Educational material for modules WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6, in **Italian** can be found in the project repository using the following link:
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1y33J0rlq3jUIJDSYttxYH76N2WM6aeH5?usp=drive_link

Educational material for modules WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6, in **German** can be found in the project repository using the following link:
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1pHbGX0e2ze2CdxA3Kt2a3N9zQB8Qc4QV?usp=drive_link

Educational material for modules WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6, in **Dutch** can be found in the project repository using the following link:
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1Rjx0oVq1ty62PbVJGrWgW5bqx2vCGiqw?usp=drive_link

Educational material for modules WN1, WN2, WN3, WN4, WN5, WN6, in **Serbian** can be found in the project repository using the following link:
https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1rCz9iWTW4cgNWFB49LpC_t1B9IylzZ46?usp=drive_link

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